

***Students' perceptions of the physical
and socio-physical environment in
their university campus learning
spaces: Associations with learning
and psychological outcomes***

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“The ideal library would not be one with all individual study rooms or all open areas but, instead, would contain a diversity of spaces that would meet the needs of introverts and extroverts, lone studiers and group studiers, browsers and day-long researchers ... It is a serious mistake to assume that all people have the same spatial needs”

The Ecology of Privacy

By Robert Sommer (1966)

Declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this thesis is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

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Candidate

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ABSTRACT

Over the last two decades there has been a substantial investment in the university estate across the United Kingdom. This investment has been accompanied by an increase in the use of ‘user-centred’ or ‘co-design’ approaches to learning space development and evaluation. Such approaches consider university students, the key user group of campus learning spaces, as ‘experts’ who should be consulted and involved in the design of new and evaluation of existing learning spaces. However, there is a scarcity of large-scale quantitative research on the associations between university students’ perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes, in their campus learning spaces. The few studies which have investigated this, suffer from psychometric and conceptual flaws. Overall, the research conducted in this thesis aimed to address these limitations, and in doing so contribute to knowledge.

A multiphase exploratory sequential mixed methods design was adopted, consisting of two qualitative studies (Studies 1 and 2) and a subsequent quantitative study (Study 3). Empirical data was collected from a single, multi-campus and multi-geographic, university in Scotland.

In Study 1, a thematic analysis of data from focus groups with students ($n = 15$) and instructors ($n = 20$) highlighted the importance of the physical and socio-physical environment in students’ learning space experiences. This included Spatial and Ergonomic (e.g., furniture arrangement and comfort), Acoustical (e.g., noise from people talking), Ambient (e.g., lighting, temperature, and window views), and Privacy characteristics (e.g., visual privacy). Linked to each of these characteristics was students’ (in)ability to choose suitable spaces or alternatives for their learning activities (Decisional Control). In addition, the thematic analysis highlighted a range of environmental consequences, including, Engagement in Learning Activities, Cognitive-Affective Consequences, and Quantity and Quality of Work produced when using campus spaces for learning and teaching activities. Drawing on the focus group findings, previous research, and relevant person-environment transaction theories, the “University Students’ Learning Space Experience (USLSE) Model” was developed to guide the subsequent empirical studies.

In Study 2, a qualitative systematic review identified 136 quantitative measurement instruments used in previous research to assess students’ perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces. However, only six instruments sufficiently addressed content validity, construct validity, and internal consistency reliability. Furthermore, a more nuanced

investigation of the six instruments demonstrated that (i) psychometric analyses and reporting were poor and (ii) conceptual/theoretical underpinnings were insufficient. To the best of the author's knowledge, Study 2 is the first systematic review of the quantitative instruments which measure students' learning space perceptions

In Study 3, a new questionnaire was developed to measure students' learning space experiences when using their academic library spaces for individual and collaborative learning activities, respectively. The so-called "University Students' Library Learning Space Experience (USLLSE) Questionnaire" was based on the USLSE Model. As such, content validity and conceptual underpinnings were superior to previous research. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) revealed that the two sections of the questionnaire, pertaining to individual learning activities ($N = 418$) and collaborative learning activities ($N = 307$), had good overall psychometric properties, including, construct validity and internal consistency reliability.

Additionally, the PLS-SEM results demonstrated significant associations between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment (Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical and Privacy Fit, Ambient Fit, and Decisional Control) and a range of learning and psychological outcomes, including, Academic Stress, Engagement, and Quantity and/or Quality of Work produced when using the academic library spaces for both individual and collaborative learning activities. Overall, the significant associations demonstrated that more positive perceptions of the environment were associated with better learning and psychological outcomes. To the best of the author's knowledge, Study 3 is the first to assess the relationships between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes in their academic library spaces.

The findings were discussed in relation to the research aims, previous empirical and theoretical works, methodological and practical implications, and proposals for future research, including, further development and applications of the USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire.

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List of Abbreviations

Adjusted R² (R²adj.)

Average variance extracted (AVE)

Confidence interval (CI)

Effect Size (f²)

Heterotrait Monotrait (HTMT)

Higher Education (HE)

Higher Education Institution (HEI)

Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA)

United Kingdom (UK)

United States (US)

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1. CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION TO THE THESIS

1.1. The Changing Nature of Higher Education Learning and Teaching

At the turn of the 21st century, Higher Education (HE) across the Western world entered an era of radical change (AUDE, 2015; Temple, 2007, 2008). In Europe and the United States (US) cuts in public investment have led many HE institutions (HEIs) to invest in innovative corporate branding strategies in an attempt to recruit both fee paying students and academics with successful records in research impact and funding attainment. In summary, HEIs have become competitors in a global market economy (AUDE et al., 2015; CABE, 2005; Edwards, 2013; Price et al., 2003; Wates Construction, 2012).

Alongside the commercialisation of HE, several societal and pedagogical trends, such as, widening participation, changing employer expectations, new information and communication technologies (ICTs), and empirical and theoretical developments in psychology and education have led to a 'paradigm shift' in beliefs about 'how' learning and teaching should occur (Beaten et al., 2010; Ananiadou & Claro, 2009; Harrison & Hutton, 2014; Johnson et al., 2014; King, 2015; Mullen, 2010).

The Robbins Report (Committee of Higher Education, 1963) commissioned by the British Government, for example, as well as the 1999 European widening participation agenda have led to an increase in the number and diversity of students enrolled in HE across the United Kingdom (UK). This includes students from non-traditional backgrounds, such as, deprived communities, Further Education (FE) colleges, and adult returners to education (Mullen, 2010). In addition, potential employers of graduate students now seek to recruit individuals who demonstrate not only strong academic aptitude but possess a range of highly sought-after skills and competencies. These include autonomy, team-working, collaboration, communication, confidence, creativity, critical thinking, and problem solving; these are believed necessary for students to become 'effective contributors' in the 21st century workforce (Ananiadou & Claro, 2009; King, 2015; Johnson et al., 2014). As Boys (2011) states:

Good education enables the ability to think critically and solve complex problems, preparing learners for the knowledge economy (p. 4).

Further, the continual development of ICTs and in particular mobile technologies, have allowed students to engage in learning activities ‘anytime’ and ‘anywhere’ (Beckers et al., 2016a; Harrison & Hutton, 2014). Finally, many HE scholars and leaders have emphasised the growing theoretical (e.g., Brown et al., 1989; Collins et al., 1991; Lave & Wenger, 1991; Piaget, 1977; Vygotsky, 1978) and empirical base (e.g., Beaten et al., 2010; Johnson et al., 2014) which highlights the value of ‘student-centred’ (e.g., collaborative learning) over traditional pedagogical practices (e.g., instructional-based lectures and seminars) for both academic attainment and the development of graduate skills. As summarised by Oblinger (2005):

Today, knowing includes critical thought, persuasive expressions, and the solution of complex ... and ... novel problems ... Learning research indicates that competence is developed in active, exploratory, and social settings. When participants are asked to think conceptually and critically, involving both peers and experts, learning is enriched ... Rather than telling students about a topic, engaging them in active learning and collaboration typically results in greater mastery and transferability (p. 15).

1.2. The Changing Nature of the Higher Education Estate

However, at the turn of the 21st century, scholars, estate managers, and HE leaders began to challenge the suitability of the existing HE estate as a means of facilitating wider institutional objectives. For instance, the buildings in many university campuses were designed in the 1960s and 1970s to accommodate an increasing student population and collection of library resources. Such buildings may lack the aesthetic appeal of ‘statement architecture’ found in the neo-gothic campus buildings of many ancient universities and ‘innovative’ new-build facilities (CABE, 2005; Edwards, 2013; Price et al., 2003; Scott-Webber, 2004; Temple, 2007, 2008; Strange & Banning, 2001, 2015).

Further, traditional classrooms designed for instructional learning, with an instructor podium at the front, rows of forward-facing desks, and a lack of circulation space were and remain prevalent in (i) many ancient university buildings and (ii) university buildings designed to accommodate the post-Robbin’s expansion (Temple, 2007, 2008). Likewise, academic library spaces were traditionally designed for ‘working alone’, reading, storing, and retrieving information (Bennett, 2009). It has been suggested that such spaces support and send messages to students and instructors about the value of traditional instructional pedagogies; however, such spaces may also constrain and devalue the importance of student-centred practices, such as, collaborative learning (Bennett, 2009; Blackmore, 2011; Edwards, 2013; Strange & Banning, 2001, 2015; Temple, 2007, 2008).

Given the discourse above, it is unsurprising that there has been a substantial investment in the HE estate over the last few decades. The Scottish Funding Council (SFC), for instance, invested £8 billion in Scottish HE estate-related projects between 2009 and 2019 (SFC, 2019). Many universities have now invested in spaces which are designed to support student-centred pedagogies, such as, 'active learning classrooms' and 'social learning spaces' (Beichner et al., 2014; Dori & Belcher, 2005; Whiteside et al., 2010). These 'next generation learning spaces' adopt a variety of designs but often include round group tables for collaborative learning (e.g., group discussions), flexible seating configurations for different types of learning, absent or centralised instructor podiums, increased circulation space, and collaborative resources such as shared group screens and whiteboards (Beichner et al., 2014; Bennett, 2009; Temple, 2007, 2008; Oblinger, 2006). Such investments and developments in HE physical learning spaces aim, in part, to address the wider societal and pedagogical changes outlined above (AUDE, 2015; Alexi Marmot Associates, 2012; Temple, 2007, 2008).

Alongside this investment and the so-called 'university building boom' (Burns, 2014; Dejevsky, 2016), several scholars, HE managers, and design consultancies have advocated 'user-centred' and 'co-design' approaches to learning space development and evaluation (Cleveland & Fisher, 2014; Glancy, 2007). Such approaches consider students and instructors, the key user group of university learning spaces, as 'experts' who should be involved and consulted in the design of new and evaluation of existing spaces. Indeed, it has been suggested that student involvement in the design process can lead to greater feelings of ownership over the learning space and thus the learning process (Alexi Marmot Associates, 2012).

Numerous researchers have, therefore, used a variety of methods to involve students in the design and evaluation process (Aronoff, 2016; Cleveland & Fisher, 2014; Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Lippincott, 2009; Somerville and Collins, 2008; Tevaniemi et al., 2015; Zhang & Maddison, 2016). Positive feedback is often considered as evidence of 'good' or 'successful design', while negative feedback is seen as an 'opportunity for improvement' (Cleveland & Fisher, 2014; Glancy, 2007). As stated by Cleveland and Fisher (2014):

Information can be collected and used to validate occupants' real needs, improve fit between occupants and their buildings ... support stakeholders in applying design skills more effectively ... improving user requirements (pp. 2-3).

1.3. Thesis Rationale and Aims

1.3.1. The physical environment: Associations with learning and psychological outcomes

An increasing body of inter-disciplinary literature on university buildings and learning spaces has provided support for claims about the benefits of ‘statement architecture’ and ‘next generation learning spaces’ for HEIs, students, and instructors. Some studies have linked HE facilities to corporate outcomes, such as, student and instructor recruitment and retention (CABE, 2005; Price et al., 2003). Furthermore, research by scholars across a range of disciplines (e.g., education, social sciences, and natural sciences) have demonstrated the predominantly positive impact of classrooms designed to facilitate active over traditional learning on students’ concept learning and course performance, students’ and instructors’ pedagogical practices, and students’ use of 21st century workplace skills (cf. Talbert & Mor-Avi, 2018).

In addition, since the establishment of environmental psychology in the 1960s, psychologists have studied the mutual transactions and relationships between university students and their physical (e.g., acoustics, lighting, temperature, and furniture arrangement) and socio-physical (e.g., crowding and privacy) environments. Such studies have addressed the impact of single environmental variables on a range of learning and psychological outcomes. This includes the effects of (i) lighting on cognitive task performance; (ii) acoustics on cognitive task completion rate and performance; and (iii) classroom window views of nature (versus a concrete wall) on students’ course satisfaction and performance (Alimohammadi & Ebrahimi, 2017; Belojević et al., 1992; Collins-Eiland et al., 1986; Gulian & Thomas, 1986; Maas et al., 1974).

Psychologists have also considered the impact of multiple environmental characteristics on students’ learning and psychological outcomes. This includes the effects of (i) open versus closed space and colour on cognitive task performance and perceptions of privacy; (ii) spatial and social density on students’ cognitive task performance¹; and (iii) acoustics, lighting, and temperature on students’ environmental perceptions, mood, and cognitive task performance (Marchand et al., 2014; Stone, 2001; Weldon et al., 1981).

¹ Spatial density refers to the size of a space, while social density refers to the number of people within a space (Weldon et al., 1981).

Other environmental psychologists have investigated the impact of an even wider range of environmental characteristics. The soft-classroom projects explored the effects of full classroom redesigns (e.g., softer lighting, furniture, and aesthetics) on participation in class discussion, course grades, and environmental perceptions (Sommer & Olsen, 1980; Wollin & Montagne, 1981; Wong et al., 1992). Finally, Scannell et al. (2016) highlighted the benefits of certain sound sources (e.g., people-related noise), soft furnishings, plants, and low density for students' environmental perceptions and 'acoustics-related well-being'. These studies emphasise the need to adopt a more holistic approach to understanding the impact of the physical and socio-physical environment in campus learning spaces on a wide range of learning and psychological outcomes.

1.3.2. Students' perceptions of the physical environment: Associations with learning and psychological outcomes

Of particular relevance to the present thesis, is a much smaller body of research that has demonstrated statistical associations between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces. Using a quantitative questionnaire approach to collect data from large samples of students, such studies have found positive associations between students' perceptions of physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics, affective impressions of the environment, cognitive task performance, course performance, and class and course evaluations (Castilla et al., 2017; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016). These positive associations between students' learning space perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes may be considered as supportive of 'user-centred' approaches to learning space design.

A strength of the research cited above is the collection of quantitative (i.e., numerical) data. First, the use of a quantitative questionnaire approach allows researchers to gather data from large samples. Compared with small samples, findings from large samples are more likely to be representative of the wider population (e.g., of students) from which the sample was drawn (cf. Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Thus, results from large samples are often easier to generalise to the wider population from which data was collected (Creswell, 2014; Morgan, 1998). Further, quantitative data is easily subjected to advanced statistical analyses which can investigate the presence and absence of relationships and the size of effects between variables (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011), such as, students' environmental perceptions and their learning and

psychological outcomes. Finally, quantitative research has traditionally been extremely valuable in informing real-world decision-making (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Following this logic, quantitative findings may be better received and utilised by stakeholders (e.g., designers, campus estates managers, and university managers) in the design of new and evaluation of existing learning spaces. As Doherty and Chen (2016) state:

Policy makers and funders are more likely to be persuaded about ... utility by the evidence of quantitative data, such as precise information on the prevalence and impacts of the issue (p. 326).

Previous quantitative studies on the associations between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and psychological and learning outcomes clearly have potential strengths. However, the research cited above (Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016) suffers from methodological and conceptual flaws.

First, the environmental characteristics and outcomes investigated appear to be selected on an ad hoc basis and therefore reflect the interests of researchers (e.g., class and course satisfaction). The relevance (i.e., content validity) of these constructs and their corresponding questionnaires to students' learning space experiences is, therefore, questionable (cf. Francis et al., 2016)². In support of this argument, students and instructors who participated in a range of qualitative studies have described the impact of environmental characteristics on students' engagement in different learning activities (e.g., individual and collaborative) and cognitive-affective outcomes such as frustration, annoyance, and relaxation within their campus learning spaces (cf. Granito & Santana, 2016; Hunter & Cox, 2014; Matthews et al., 2011; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017). Secondly, the constructs assessed in previous research and their corresponding questionnaires lack sufficient conceptual/theoretical underpinnings. As such, the ways in which researchers conceptualise students' environmental perceptions appear to be ad hoc in nature with no established theoretical basis. Deficiencies in each of these areas can hinder the validity and reliability of the conclusions drawn from subsequent inferential statistical analyses (Elf et al., 2016; Francis et al., 2016; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014).

² Content validity, discussed later in this thesis, is the extent to which a construct and measurement instrument (e.g., questionnaire items) are relevant to the concerns of the target population (Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink et al., 2010a, 2010b). One way of enhancing content validity in learning space research would involve consultations with the users of learning spaces to understand their concerns and incorporate this into subsequent research.

One potential reason for the limitations outlined above, is the inter-disciplinary nature of research and theorisation on the role of the physical and socio-physical environment in university campus learning spaces. This has led researchers to adopt a range of methodological approaches and theoretical frameworks which are common to disciplines such as library and information sciences, sociology, philosophy, education, educational psychology, architecture, and environmental psychology (Temple, 2007, 2008). Except for architecture and environmental psychology, none of these disciplines have a specific empirical or conceptual emphasis on person-environment transactions (Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007). Thus, in the Overview of the Empirical and Theoretical Literature (Chapter 2) the author is driven to consider two areas which, combined, may help to improve upon the limitations of previous research.

The first area reflects on best practice guidance in quantitative research design and questionnaire development. Specifically, scholars (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink, 2010a, 2010b) have highlighted the benefits of collecting 'rich' and 'detailed' qualitative data from members of the target population (i.e., students) and professionals involved in the phenomena of interest (e.g., instructors); this would allow researchers to identify issues which are relevant to the target population's experiences (e.g., students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes). These qualitative findings can then be used to inform the selection of relevant constructs and create questionnaires with high content validity in subsequent quantitative research (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink, 2010a, 2010b). In addition, such initial qualitative research is valuable for (i) the development of new conceptual/theoretical frameworks and (ii) understanding the utility or relevance of existing theories (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016). In short, drawing on the strengths of qualitative approaches and using qualitative findings to inform the design of subsequent quantitative research, would allow researchers to enhance content validity and conceptual underpinnings (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011).

Secondly, the author is driven to consider the relevance person-environment transaction theories (e.g., ecological, behaviour constraint, environmental stress, and person-environment congruence theories) to students' learning space experiences. Person-environment transaction theories are widely used in environmental psychology; that is, the study of mutual transactions and relationships

between people and their physical and socio-physical environments (Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007, 2014). None of the studies outlined above (Castilla et al., 2017; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016) seem to have adopted such perspectives as a basis for the conceptualisation of students' environmental perceptions nor to inform the design of questionnaires which measure students' perceptions. This is ironic since environmental psychology, by its very definition, focuses on person-environment transactions (cf. Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007, 2014). The utility of these perspectives in explaining university students' learning space experiences is considered in this thesis.

1.3.3. Thesis aims

Given recent investments in university learning spaces and efforts to involve students in the design process, it is evident that the limitations discussed must be overcome. The research conducted in this thesis will draw on the strengths of qualitative research and investigate the utility of person-environment transaction theories to inform subsequent quantitative research on the relationships between HE students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces. This will allow the author to address the methodological and conceptual limitations of previous research outlined in Subsection 1.3.2. By adopting this more robust approach, the research conducted in this thesis will make an original contribution to knowledge. The overall aims of this thesis are to:

1. Understand how HE students perceive (conceptualise) the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces;
2. Understand the relevance of different physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics and learning and psychological consequences to students' learning space experiences;
3. Develop a new and robust 'learning space experience' questionnaire to measure students' perceptions of the most relevant physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics in their campus learning spaces; and to
4. Explore how students' perceptions of relevant environmental characteristics are statistically associated with key learning and psychological outcomes.

These aims are addressed through:

1. A review of the literature to identify limitations with previous research, directions for subsequent research, and to serve as an empirical and theoretical base for the subsequent empirical chapters;

2. Qualitative research which aims to explore students' learning space experiences, including, the relevance of physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics and learning and psychological consequences in their campus learning spaces;
3. A systematic review of quantitative scales used in previous research to understand their utility in measuring students' perceptions of their learning environments; and
4. The use of the previous phases to develop a new and robust (i.e., psychometrically tested), 'learning space experience questionnaire'; and
5. The use of the new 'learning space experience questionnaire' to explore how students' perceptions of the relevant physical and socio-physical environment in a specific learning space, are statistically associated with key learning and psychological outcomes.

1.4. Terminological Clarification

As mentioned previously, the literature on university campus learning spaces is inter-disciplinary. As such, it is necessary to clarify key terms used throughout the thesis.

First, there is no agreed upon definition of 'learning spaces'. This is further complicated by the fact that researchers refer to 'social learning spaces', 'conceptual learning spaces', and 'technological learning spaces' (Granito & Santana, 2016; Temple, 2007, 2008). Further, since today's students can study 'anyhow', 'anytime', and 'anywhere', several scholars have proposed that any space can be reasonably considered as a learning space (Harrison & Hutton, 2014; King, 2015; Temple, 2007, 2008). The term 'learning spaces' in this thesis refers to any physical setting on the university campus, 'where' students participate in learning activities (e.g., campus library spaces, classrooms, social spaces, outdoor spaces, and cafeterias).

Secondly, there is limited agreement on the terminology that should be used to describe different types of learning spaces (e.g., informal learning spaces, social learning spaces, learning centres, information commons, learning commons, learning studios, active learning, and traditional /instructional classrooms) (Bennett, 2009; Temple, 2007, 2008; Scannell et al., 2016). Much of these terms are used interchangeably. It is beyond the scope of this thesis to define different types of learning spaces. The author will, therefore, clarify the use of such terms where necessary within the thesis.

Thirdly, this thesis is concerned with the physical and socio-physical environment within university campus learning spaces. The physical environment includes the spatial and ergonomic characteristics of a space, such as, physical density (size of a space), furniture arrangements, desk size, and furniture comfort (Castilla et al., 2017; Kim & de Dear, 2013; Weldon et al., 1981; Yang et al., 2013). Furthermore, the physical environment refers to ambient background variables, including, artificial and natural lighting, sound characteristics, view conditions (e.g., green spaces versus concrete wall), the presence of plants, and the use of colour within a space (Kim & de Dear, 2013; Yang et al., 2013). Where appropriate the thesis will also consider the importance of socio-physical characteristics within a space, such as, the actual number of people (social density), perceptions of the number of people (crowding), and control over input from and output to others (privacy) (Altman, 1975; Kupritz, 2000; Weldon et al., 1981). Thus, unless stated otherwise, the term 'environment' in this thesis will refer to the physical and socio-physical environment.

Fourthly, consistent with person-environment transaction theories (e.g., cf. Bell et al., 2001), the literature on learning spaces distinguishes between (i) the objective conditions or physical reality of a learning space and (ii) students' subjective perceptions of these conditions. Several researchers have, for instance, objectively measured environmental characteristics within learning spaces. This includes the sound level (decibels), illuminance (lux), temperature (Celsius), and the presence versus absence of environmental features (e.g., plants, soft furnishings, window views, and particular furniture arrangements) (Benfield et al., 2015; Brooks, 2012; Maas et al., 1974; Scannell et al., 2016).

Researchers have also sought to capture students' subjective perceptions and experiences of the environment. This includes assessments or ratings of environmental characteristics, for instance, descriptions or affective impressions (e.g., cold versus warm), preferences and perceived importance (e.g., important versus unimportant), satisfaction (e.g., satisfied versus dissatisfied), and congruence/incongruence (e.g., suitable versus unsuitable) (cf. Beckers et al., 2016a; Kim, 2016; Scannell et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2013). Furthermore, qualitative research on learning spaces has focused on students' subjective experiences. Analysis of learning space experiences has often sought to capture students' environmental preferences, the extent to which students believe these preferences are met by their learning spaces, the relevant characteristics of the environment to students' learning space experiences, and beliefs about the learning and psychological consequences of the environment (e.g., Granito & Santana, 2016; Hunter & Cox, 2014; Matthews et al., 2011; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017).

This thesis is concerned with students' perceptions and experiences of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces. That said, research on the objective conditions of the physical environment will be discussed where appropriate. To reiterate, this thesis aims to investigate the relationships between students' subjective perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces. By addressing the limitations of previous research in this area, this thesis will make an original contribution to knowledge.

1.5 Thesis Structure

In the Introduction, Chapter 1, the author set the scene by providing a contextualisation for the thesis, presenting the overall thesis aims, and providing a terminological clarification. To address the thesis aims, the literature review and methodology are presented in Chapters 2 and 3, respectively. This is followed by three empirical chapters (Chapters 4-6) and a General Discussion and Conclusions Chapter (Chapter 7).

In Chapter 2, the author presents an overview of the empirical and theoretical literature on the relationships between objective environmental conditions and students' learning and psychological outcomes. Then, quantitative research on the relationships between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes is evaluated to identify directions for future research; methodological limitations with this research drives the author to consider how a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches within the thesis may address these limitations. The review is also driven to consider the utility of person-environment transaction theories as a conceptual basis for the subsequent empirical research.

In Chapter 3, the author discusses his "Methodological Considerations and Reflections". The chapter begins by outlining the overall approach adopted in the thesis: mixed methods. The three empirical chapters are outlined, and the author reflects upon the mixed methods design which most closely aligns with his chosen approach. Then, the author reflects upon the considerations and research worldview which influenced this approach, the role of theory in the research, and how the challenges of mixed methods approaches are addressed. The chapter concludes with a brief description of ethical considerations and the sites from which data was collected.

In Chapters 4-6, the empirical studies are presented (Studies 1, 2, and 3, respectively). Each empirical chapter consists of chapter introductions, methods, findings, discussions, and conclusions.

Based on focus groups with students and instructors, the qualitative Study 1 (Chapter 4) addresses (i) how students conceptualise the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces; (ii) the relevant aspects of the environment to students' learning space experiences; (iii) students' and instructors' beliefs about the learning and psychological consequences of the environment; (iv) and the utility of person-environment transaction theories discussed in Chapter 2 in explaining students' learning space experiences. By addressing these aims, a model is developed to explain students' learning space experiences and serve as a conceptual basis for the subsequent empirical studies (Studies 2 and 3).

Chapter 5 (Study 2) presents a qualitative systematic review of the quantitative measurement instruments used in previous research to measure students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces. The author presents the findings of a psychometric evaluation based on best practice guidance for content validity, construct validity, and internal consistency reliability assessment. Then the author presents a conceptual evaluation based on learning space experience model developed in Study 1.

In Chapter 6, the author presents the development of a new university students' learning space experience questionnaire which is based on the model from Study 1. The construct validity (convergent and discriminant) and internal consistency reliability of the constructs in the model and questionnaire are assessed. Based on the model predictions (Study 1), the relationships between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes in a specific campus learning space are explored.

Chapter 7 presents the General Discussion and Conclusions. The author reflects upon the findings of the thesis in relation to each of the research aims. Following this, the author addresses the original contribution to empirical and theoretical knowledge, methodological and practical implications, directions for future research, and concludes the thesis.

2. CHAPTER TWO

OVERVIEW OF THE EMPIRICAL AND THEORETICAL LITERATURE

2.1. Chapter Introduction

Using previous empirical and theoretical literature, this chapter will highlight the ways in which the physical and socio-physical environment are related to learning and psychological outcomes in university campus learning spaces. However, there is little quantitative research on the associations between HE students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes within their campus learning spaces. What few studies exist and are reviewed, have methodological and conceptual flaws. This is of major concern, given recent movements to involve students in the design of new and evaluation of existing campus learning spaces, and is the focus of this thesis. The aim of Chapter 2 is to highlight limitations in the existing research, serve as an empirical and theoretical base for the subsequent empirical studies, and propose directions for the subsequent empirical studies.

Given the lack of research on students' perceptions of the environment and associated outcomes in their campus learning spaces, the author integrates the wider literature on university learning spaces.³ The review begins with a discussion of research and theory which has addressed the impact of objective environmental conditions on a range of learning and psychological outcomes. Research and theory are discussed on the effects of design factors incorporated within active learning (relative to instructional) classrooms on course achievement, concept learning, engagement in student-centred versus instructional practices, demonstration of 21st century workplace skills, and environmental perceptions. Then, research and theory from environmental psychology are presented on the impact of environmental factors on a range of learning (e.g., course performance) and psychological outcomes (e.g., rate of completion and performance on cognitive tasks, course

³ A review of research literature on institutional environments beyond HE (e.g., schools and workplaces) is beyond the scope of this chapter. University students, school pupils, and employees may differ in terms of the activities for which they use learning spaces, the degree of autonomy over tasks and the environment, and therefore their requirements from and perceptions of the environment.

evaluations, and mood). It is argued that adopting a holistic approach which focuses on the impact of multiple than opposed to single environmental characteristics, represents a more ecologically valid approach to studying learning environments. Moreover, the argument that environmental characteristics may interact with non-environmental characteristics (e.g., students' and instructors' personal and situational characteristics) to aid or hinder learning is presented. It is proposed that this argument provides a justification for focusing on students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment.

Following this, the review narrows in focus to discuss research on students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces. Environmental perceptions are introduced, and research is summarised on the predictors of students' perceptions of the environment. Following this, research on the relationships between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes is evaluated. It is argued that this research has several limitations, including, insufficient content validity and conceptual underpinnings. This drives the review to demonstrate how a 'rich' and 'detailed' qualitative investigation as well as person-environment transaction theories may serve as a useful basis for more rigorous quantitative research on the associations between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes within their campus learning spaces. The review concludes with a summary of the empirical and theoretical literature reviewed, and directions for the subsequent chapters.

2.2. The Physical and Socio-Physical Environment in University Learning Spaces: Associations with Learning and Psychological outcomes

2.2.1. Overview

When reviewing the literature on the impact of the objective physical environmental conditions on learning and psychological outcomes, two growing areas of research become apparent. First, there is a body of literature on the effects of objective design characteristics and ICTs in different classroom spaces (active learning versus traditional) on learning and psychological outcomes. Secondly, there is a body of research and theory from environmental psychology, dating from the 1960s, which investigates the impact of single and multiple physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics (e.g., lighting, acoustics, temperature, density, and window views) on HE students' learning and psychological outcomes. The subsequent subsections evaluate each of these areas in turn.

2.2.2. Classroom design characteristics: Associations with pedagogical behaviours and learning

Research and theory have addressed the effects of design factors in different classroom spaces on the learning and teaching process. This growing area of research is based on the mutual relationship between pedagogy and space; that is, space impacts pedagogical practices and pedagogical practices, in turn, impact upon the design of space (Talbert and Mor-Avi, 2018). This research has largely been conducted in the Mid-Western and South-Eastern US and has compared the impact of active learning relative to traditional classrooms. As mentioned previously, traditional classrooms are predominantly designed for instructional learning and usually contain an instructor podium and presentation screen at the front, rows of forward-facing desks, and a lack of circulation space (Beichner, 2014; Bennett, 2009; Oblinger, 2006). In contrast active learning classrooms are designed to facilitate active learning and foster social connections. Such spaces typically include round group tables for collaborative learning, larger circulation space for students and instructors to move around the room, flexible seating configurations, absent or centralised instructor podiums, and collaborative resources (e.g., shared group screens and whiteboards) (Beichner, 2014; Bennett, 2009; Temple, 2007, 2008; Oblinger, 2006).

A series of projects and evaluations, for example, were conducted between 2003 and 2007 to assess the longitudinal impact of large-scale active learning relative to instructional classrooms on students' learning experiences. These included the Technology-Enabled Active Learning (TEAL) classroom at the University of Minnesota (Dori & Belcher, 2005; Dori et al., 2003) and Student-Centred Active learning Environment with Upside Down Pedagogies (SCALE-UP) project at North Carolina State University (Beichner et al., 2007). Findings demonstrated that students who learned in large-scale active learning, relative to instructional, classrooms displayed (i) significantly higher gains in conceptual understanding of science and mathematics concepts (Beichner et al., 2007; Dori & Belcher, 2005; Dori et al., 2003), (ii) increased collaboration (Dori & Belcher, 2005), (iii) improved attitudes towards learning physics (Beichner et al., 2007), (iv) increased problem solving (Beichner et al., 2007), and (v) greater success rates (Beichner et al., 2007).

However, the TEAL and SCALE-UP projects suffered from methodological limitations which hinder the validity and reliability of their findings. Course materials and new technologies were repeatedly

added throughout the projects, different assessment methods were used between the experimental and control groups, and different instructors taught the experimental and control classrooms (Beckers et al., 2016a). It is, therefore, difficult to determine whether the findings stemmed from the different classroom environments, assessment methods, or between groups instructor effects, e.g., differences in teaching philosophies (Beckers et al., 2016a; Brooks, 2011).

Nevertheless, several findings from the TEAL and SCALE-UP projects have been replicated in more recent investigations involving both small-scale (45 student capacity) and large-scale (117 student capacity) active learning classrooms, at the University of Minnesota. In one such study, after controlling for a range of confounding variables⁴, Whiteside et al. (2010) found that students who took an undergraduate biology course in a large active learning classroom performed significantly better (by an average of 29.8 grade points) than was expected based on their American College Test (ACT) scores for entry to university. In contrast, students who learned in the classroom designed for instructional learning performed as expected based on their ACT scores. At the same institution, Brooks (2011) replicated these findings in a small-scale active learning and instructional classrooms, with post-secondary teaching and learning (biology) students. According to Brooks (2011), the findings “strongly suggests that ... learning environments, independent of all other factors, have a significant impact on student learning” (p. 719).

Observational findings at the same institution, have provided insight into the mechanisms through which classroom design influences course achievement. For instance, Whiteside et al. (2010) found that the instructor spent significantly less time consulting with groups of students, more time lecturing (instructing), and more time standing at the podium when delivering the same course in an instructional relative to active learning classroom. Students in the instructional classroom spent significantly less time engaging in group discussion than their peers in the active learning classroom.

In a similar study, the instructor attempted to hold his teaching approach constant between the active learning and instructional classrooms (Brooks, 2012). Nevertheless, findings demonstrated that he was significantly less likely to lecture and stand at the instructor podium, significantly more likely to circulate the room, and significantly more likely to consult with individual students and

⁴ Instructor style, time of day, course materials, and assignments were held constant (Whiteside et al., 2010).

groups of students, when using the active learning relative to instructional classroom (Brooks, 2012). Students who used the active learning classroom were significantly more likely to engage in student-to-instructor and student-to-student discussions than their peers in the instructional classroom. Contrary to expectations, high and moderate on-task student behaviour occurred significantly more often in the instructional classroom, while there were no significant differences for low on-task student behaviour between the two classrooms (Brooks, 2012).

The findings presented above imply that the design of active learning relative to instructional classrooms are more likely to encourage student-centred pedagogic practices, including, more discussion, consultation, and less instructional learning. These increased student-centred pedagogic practices, in turn, are assumed to lead to improvements in course performance (Brooks, 2012). However, more recent studies have challenged these assumptions (Lasry et al., 2014; Sawers et al., 2016). For example, several of the studies presented above (Brooks, 2011, 2012; Whiteside et al., 2010) used same instructor across both the traditional and active learning classrooms to control for differences in pedagogical approach. If the instructor had a more student-centred than opposed to instructional pedagogical philosophy, then they may be more inclined to engage in student-centred over instructional pedagogical practices, when the environment is designed in such a way that supports this opportunity (e.g., active learning classroom with enhanced circulation spaces, round desks for collaborative learning, and centralised or absent instructor podiums).

To address these limitations, Lasry et al. (2014) investigated whether instructors' pedagogical philosophies and practices interacted with design factors in active learning compared with instructional classrooms, to influence students' understanding of introductory calculus-based mechanics concepts. Students who took classes in the active learning classroom and had instructors with student-centred philosophies and practices, displayed the highest gains in concept learning. Meanwhile, those students who took classes in the active learning classroom but had instructors with traditional (instructional) pedagogical philosophies and practices, displayed the lowest gains in concept learning (Lasry et al., 2016). Further, students in the instructional classroom with low prior knowledge performed significantly better at the end of term than their peers with low prior knowledge in the active learning classroom. These findings suggest that the effects of the classroom design may interact with personal characteristics and behaviours of students and instructors (e.g., prior subject knowledge, pedagogical philosophies, and pedagogical behaviours) to influence learning (Lasry et al., 2014).

Similarly, Sawers et al. (2016) found that instructors with more student-centred pedagogical philosophies reported that their students were more engaged, than instructors who held more instructional philosophies. However, this effect was only present in an active learning classroom and not in the instructional classroom. Mediation analyses revealed that instructors with more student-centred pedagogical philosophies engaged in significantly more student-centred practices, which in turn, was associated with significantly higher instructor reports of student engagement.⁵ Again, this effect was only present in the active learning classroom. It is possible that these findings are a methodological artefact⁶. Nevertheless, it is also plausible that instructors with more student-centred philosophies are better placed to utilise the active learning as opposed to instructional environment because it is better aligned with their learning and teaching philosophies (Sawers et al., 2016).

Other findings pertain to students' perceptions of their physical environment. For example, several studies have shown that students who use active learning classrooms typically perceive significantly greater fit between the classroom environment and their learning experience (e.g., room-course fit) than those who use an instructional classroom (cf. Baepler et al., 2014; Brooks & Solheim, 2014; Whiteside et al., 2010). However, it is unclear whether these perceptions are a function of interactions between the environment, instructors' pedagogical beliefs and behaviours, and/or students' prior knowledge (cf. Lasry et al., 2014; Sawers et al., 2016).

There are, however, several limitations to the studies presented in this section. First, the generalisability of the findings is hindered by the use of typically small samples of students, instructors, and HEIs (Talbert & Mor-Avi, 2018). Indeed, three of the studies were conducted at the same US institution (Brooks, 2011, 2012; Whiteside et al., 2010), while only one of the studies presented in this subsection was conducted out with the US (Lasry et al., 2014). Secondly, except for

⁵ Mediation or indirect effects occur when the relationship between two variables is explained by a third variable (Hair et al., 2017; Hayes, 2018). For mediation to occur, the predictor variable must significantly predict the mediator variable, the mediator should significantly predict the outcome variable, and there must be a significant indirect effect through the mediator (Hair et al., 2017; Hayes, 2018).

⁶ Instructors with more student-centred pedagogical philosophies and who engage in more student-centred pedagogical practices may be more inclined to self-report their students as engaged.

observational research (e.g., Brooks, 2012; Whiteside et al., 2010), insights into the specific design characteristics which contribute to learning outcomes are speculative.

Thirdly, there is limited information on the validity and reliability of the questionnaires and observation schedules adopted in these studies. For example, it is unknown whether these measurement instruments were developed based on consultations with a sample of students and instructors who used the experimental and control classrooms, to ensure sufficient content validity. This may explain the unexpected findings of Brooks (2012): that students in instructional relative to active learning classrooms displayed significantly higher on-task behaviours. In support of this conclusion, Brooks (2012) notes that the operational definition of on-task behaviours in their observation schedule was “derived from a model of on-task behaviour familiar to traditional classroom settings” (para 26).

Fourthly, only Lasry et al. (2014) and Sawers et al. (2016) considered the importance of interactions between environmental and non-environmental factors, such as, the role of students’ prior subject knowledge and instructors’ pedagogical beliefs and behaviours. Finally, it is worth noting that there is an absence of research which have adopted similar quasi-experimental designs to investigate out-of-class learning spaces, such as, academic library and social learning spaces. A potential explanation for this latter issue is the greater difficulty in controlling for extraneous variables when investigating spaces used for students’ self-directed learning out with class (Alexi Marmot Associates, 2012; Temple, 2007, 2008).

Limitations notwithstanding, the studies discussed in this subsection have several strengths. For example, compared with experimental research, the use of real-world learning spaces, classroom sessions, and assessments has enhanced ecological validity⁷ (cf. Bell et al., 2001; Wilson & MacLean, 2012). Furthermore, use of a quasi-experimental design and controls for potential confounding variables allows the researchers to make strong causal claims about the impact of the physical environment on students and instructors (Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007). Overall, the findings presented in this subsection highlight that learning space design factors may interact with students’ and instructors’ personal characteristics (e.g., learning and teaching philosophies and prior

⁷ Ecological validity is the extent to which findings can be generalised to real world situations (Wilson & MacLean, 2012).

knowledge) to influence their pedagogical practices (student-centred versus instructional) and, in turn, learning (concept learning and course achievement). In other words, environmental factors may interact with non-environmental factors to aid or hinder learning (Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007).

2.2.3. Identifying environmental characteristics and their associations with learning and psychological Outcomes

In addition to the work presented in the previous section, there is a relatively large body of literature from environmental psychology (dating from the 1960s). This literature has sought to isolate and understand the effects of environmental variables on learning and psychological outcomes.

Examples of such physical and socio-physical environmental factors include the effects of lighting, acoustics, temperature, physical density (size of the space) and social density (number of people in the space), and window view conditions.

Maas et al. (1974), for instance, investigated the effects of full-spectrum lighting (closely replicating natural sunlight) and cool white fluorescent lighting (typically used in institutional settings) on 29 female students. Using a repeated measures design, students spent two days (four hours per day) under each condition in a classroom converted into a study room. Self-report findings revealed that participants were significantly less lively and more lethargic after studying under fluorescent lighting compared to full-spectrum lighting. Performance on two of three perceptual vision tasks (including reading and hand eye coordination) was significantly better under full-spectrum lighting. This suggested that students may experience significantly poorer reading ability and increased perceptual fatigue under fluorescent relative to full-spectrum lighting. However, the use of a repeated measures design makes it difficult to discern the effects of lighting from potential fatigue and practice effects (Field & Hole, 2013). Further, only female students participated in the study. Therefore, findings may not be applicable to a wider student population. Indeed, other single variable studies have noted gender differences in the effects of specific environmental variables, such as, noise level on students' cognitive task completion rate (Gulian & Thomas, 1986).

In addition, several studies have found evidence for the effects of noise on university students learning experiences as a function of: acoustical properties (e.g., white noise versus irrelevant speech, music versus television, and low versus high volume), person characteristics (e.g., gender,

noise sensitivity, personality traits, and perceived behavioural control), and task characteristics (e.g., task difficulty and instruction type) (cf. Belojević, et al., 1992; Collins-Eiland et al., 1986; Frankenhaeuser & Lundberg, 1977; Furnham & Strbac, 2002; Gulian & Thomas, 1986; Mehta et al., 2013; Salamé & Baddeley, 1987). In one such study, Collins-Eiland et al. (1986) randomly assigned students to two groups, exposure and non-exposure to conversational noise, while studying an essay using their 'normal study' methods. In a follow-up session, while exposed to noise, students with an internal locus of control outperformed those with an external locus of control on a free recall essay and short answer tests. Students with an external locus of control, however, outperformed those with an internal locus of control the non-exposure condition.⁸ The authors propose that students with an external locus of control are more likely to 'give up' under stressful conditions (noise), whereas those with an internal locus of control perceive the situation as a challenge or under their control (Collins-Eiland et al., 1986).

Other studies have used similar designs to Collins-Eiland et al. (1986) to identify personal and situational characteristics which make students more susceptible to the effects of noise. Such studies have found differences in (i) students' cognitive task performance as a function of perceived behavioural control⁹, noise type (irrelevant speech versus white noise), and the level of traffic noise (55 versus 75 dB) (Belojević et al., 1992; Salamé & Baddeley, 1987; Sherrod et al., 1977); (ii) students' creative performance as a function of noise level (low, moderate, and high) (Mehta et al., 2013); and (iii) students' rate of cognitive task completion as a function of gender differences (Gulian & Thomas, 1986).

In a more recent investigation, Benfield et al. (2015) investigated the effects of learning in two near-identical classrooms, one with a window view of nature and the other with a window view of a concrete retaining wall, on 567 introductory college students. Findings revealed that students in the classroom with a view of nature provided significantly more positive ratings of their course and had significantly higher end of term grades, than those with a view of a concrete wall. However, it ought to be borne in mind that students were not randomly allocated between the experimental and

⁸ Locus of control is a personality construct which reflects the degree to which one believes that they have control over the consequences of life events. Those with higher locus of control believe that they have a greater influence over events, while those with lower locus of control believe that the outcome of life events are a consequence of external factors beyond their control (Rotter, 1954).

⁹ Perceived behavioural control is an individual's belief about their ability to act upon/change an aspect of the environment, in this instance, switch off noise (Averill, 19737; Haghnia & Imani, 2016; Sherrod).

control classrooms. Therefore, the differences in course ratings and grades may have stemmed from pre-existing between group differences, such as, motivation and previous learning experience. Nevertheless, the findings are in line with a large body of research which points to the benefits of nature for attention restoration and stress reduction (Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007, 2014).

Several scholars have suggested that environmental factors seldom operate in isolation and typically combine to aid or hinder learning (e.g., Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007, 2014; Marchand et al., 2014). Thus, isolating the effects of multiple as opposed to single environmental variables is a more ecologically valid approach to understanding the learning and psychological consequences of the environment for university students (Marchand et al., 2014).

Adopting this more 'holistic' approach, Marchand et al. (2014) investigated the combined effects of acoustics, lighting, and temperature, set to one of two levels in an experimental classroom: (i) comfortable or (ii) just outside of the comfort zone. Students who participated in the comfortable conditions had significantly higher scores on a listening comprehension test compared to those in the normal listening condition, however, there were no differences on a reading task. Further, students in the comfortable condition self-reported significantly less negative affect (better mood), regardless of task. These findings suggest that the combination of extreme luminous, acoustical, and thermal conditions can lead to negative emotional states among university students. Furthermore, the findings imply that environmental characteristics may interact with learning activity-related characteristics (e.g., listening versus reading tasks) to influence performance.

Research by Scannell et al. (2016) also supports the holistic approach to understanding person-environment transactions. Scannell et al. investigated associations between multiple environmental characteristics and students' perceptions of the environment in informal learning spaces¹⁰. More positive perceptions of the acoustical environment were predicted by the presence of (i) background sound when the room was occupied; (ii) vegetation (e.g., plants); and (iii) soft materials (e.g., sofas) (Scannell et al., 2016). Further, high social density was a negative predictor of acoustical perceptions (Scannell et al., 2016). Reverberation time (echo), the presence of vegetation, and the presence of

¹⁰ Scannell et al. (2016) defined informal learning spaces as non-classroom campus spaces used for learning activities, including, computer work, discussion, and studying

soft materials positively predicted perceptions of the non-acoustical environment (temperature, air quality, lighting, and furniture comfort).

Perceived “Vitalising Consequences” (e.g., motivation, energy) of the acoustical environment were positively predicted by background sound when the room was occupied but were negatively predicted by background sound when the room was unoccupied and increased density. Finally, perceived “Restorative Consequences” (e.g., relaxation) of the acoustical environment were negatively predicted by (i) background sound when the room was unoccupied; (ii) increased density; but were (iii) positively predicted by reverberation time; and (iv) the presence of vegetation. (Scannell et al., 2016) Scannell et al. concluded that high background noise in unoccupied learning spaces (e.g., from ventilation systems) may be distracting. However, the authors propose that higher reverberation and background noise from others talking may promote conversational privacy (ability to hear or be heard by others) and, therefore, be more favourable when engaging in collaborative learning with peers. This conclusion suggests that the demands of learning activities (e.g., requirement for collaborative discussion) may interact with the conditions of the environment to influence learning space perceptions.

The findings that a combination of environmental characteristics may influence learning has long been recognised and is supported by early environmental psychology studies of soft classrooms (e.g., Sommer and Olsen, 1980; Wollin & Montagne, 1981; Wong et al., 1992). These studies investigated the effects of transforming barren and sterile traditional classrooms into more ‘welcoming’ spaces. In the ‘soft classroom’ project, for instance, Sommer and Olsen (1980) found that students who used a traditional 30-seat college classroom modified to include semi-circular and cushioned benches, adjustable lighting, and carpets, participated more in classroom discussion than those who used unmodified classrooms several years earlier. Further, instructors noted that the success of the ‘soft classroom’ was dependent on the fit between its physical characteristics and the learning and teaching activities which occurred within it (Sommer & Olsen, 1980). Despite substantial degradation, a post-occupancy evaluation of the ‘soft classroom’ conducted 17 years later revealed similar findings. The soft classroom resulted in significantly greater voluntary participation from students than control classrooms, though the difference between non-voluntary participation and student-to-student interaction was non-significant (Wong et al., 1992).

Several, potentially co-occurring, psychological processes have been proposed to explain the findings presented in this subsection. Such psychological processes are derived from models of cognitive load and physiological stress reduction which are used in environmental psychology (cf. Choi et al., 2014b; Ulrich, 1984). Models of cognitive load are based on the limited capacity of working memory to attend to the task at hand (Bell et al., 2001; Choi et al., 2014b; Gifford, 2007). These models suggest that environmental characteristics (e.g., acoustics, lighting, and temperature) may interact with non-environmental variables, including personal characteristics (e.g., locus of control, perceived control, personality) and situational variables (e.g., environmental and task conditions), to deplete students' limited attentional resources (Choi et al., 2014b; Marchand et al., 2014). This depletion of cognitive resources is manifested through reduced cognitive task performance, rate of completion, and increased negative affect (Choi et al., 2014b; Marchand et al., 2014). Related to this, several characteristics of the environment can be considered as 'restorative' (e.g., window views of nature) (Benfield et al., 2015; Gifford, 2007, 2014). Such restorative features do not require directed attention and therefore may restore students' attentional capacities and reduce physiological stress.

The studies presented in this subsection, however, have several limitations. Specifically, these limitations pertain to the generalisability and ecological validity of the findings. First, many of the experimental studies are hindered by relatively small samples of students (e.g., Collins-Eiland et al., 1986; Marchand et al., 2014; Maas et al., 1974); the extent to which the sample and findings are representative of and generalisable to a wider student population is, therefore, unclear. Secondly, most studies presented in this subsection have been conducted in US HEIs. As such, it is unclear whether the findings extend beyond these institutions. Thirdly, several studies presented in this subsection were conducted under laboratory conditions. Thus, the degree to which the environmental and (cognitive) task conditions represent environmental conditions and learning activities in real world settings is unclear (Stone, 2001). For example, when students use real-world learning spaces, they are typically exposed to a combination of environmental factors with a variety of characteristics (e.g., intensity, frequency, predictability, and controllability), engage in different learning activities (e.g., individual and collaborative) as opposed to cognitive tasks, and spend more time studying than students exposed to laboratory conditions (Stone, 2001).

Nevertheless, the studies presented in this subsection have several strengths. First, many of the studies adopt experimental or quasi-experimental designs, thus providing strong grounds for making

causal inferences (Field & Hole, 2013). Secondly, compared to work on active learning versus traditional classrooms, many of the studies presented in this subsection were able to isolate the effects of specific and multiple environmental variables on learning and psychological outcomes. Thirdly, overall findings from these studies have a strong conceptual basis in and provide support for person-environment transaction models, such as, cognitive load (Choi et al., 2014b). Finally, the studies highlight the importance of interactions between environmental and non-environmental variables, such as, personality, gender, perceived control, and learning tasks in influencing learning (e.g., Collins-Eiland et al., 1986; Gulian & Thomas, 1986; Marchand et al., 2014).

Overall, the findings provide further support for the conclusion of the previous subsection, that physical and socio-physical characteristics in university learning spaces may interact with students' and instructors' personal characteristics (e.g., personality traits, noise sensitivity, perceived control) and non-environmental situational characteristics (e.g., task type) to influence cognitive task performance and cognitive-affective outcomes (e.g., mood and course attitudes), and course performance.

2.2.4. Conclusions and summary

To summarise, the literature discussed in Subsections 2.2.2. and 2.2.3. is useful because it demonstrates the impact of single environmental characteristics as well as multiple environmental characteristics on a diverse range of learning and psychological outcomes. Further, several studies have also highlighted that the physical environment rarely operates in isolation. Rather environmental, personal, and situational characteristics may interact to aid or hinder learning and teaching (Gifford, 2007). This is important as it suggests that students may exhibit a diverse set of responses to the same environmental characteristics as a function of personal characteristics (e.g., personality, gender, perceived control, learning and teaching philosophies) and situational characteristics (e.g., environmental and learning task-related). This provides a justification for focusing on students' subjective perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and the associated learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces.

2.3. Students' Perceptions and Experiences of the Physical Environment in their University Campus Learning Spaces

2.3.1. Introduction to perception

As mentioned previously, this PhD is concerned with the statistical relationships between university students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces. While literature on this issue would seem to be scarce, it is necessary to review this work to identify limitations and directions for the subsequent empirical research conducted as part of this PhD.

This section begins with a contextualisation. Environmental perceptions are defined relative to the objective environmental conditions of a space; the need to study learning space perceptions is further justified; and the methodological approaches used to capture learning space perceptions are discussed. Following this, quantitative research on the associations between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces is evaluated. The methodological limitations of these studies then advance the review towards considering the potential value of conducting qualitative research to (i) understand students' learning space experiences, (ii) inform subsequent quantitative research, and (iii) in doing so improve upon the limitations of previous quantitative research. The section concludes by highlighting that future investigations would benefit from detailed qualitative research to inform subsequent quantitative research. The section conclusion also highlights the need to consider the utility of person-environment transaction theories as a conceptual basis for the subsequent research conducted in this thesis.

2.3.2. Contextualising perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment

To reiterate, scholars have differentiated between the physical reality or objective conditions of the environment and an individual's perceptions of that reality (Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007; Michelson, 1976; Orstad et al., 2016). Environmental perception is the process through which individuals acquire information about the physical and socio-physical environment around them; this information is acquired via their senses (feeling, hearing, seeing, smelling, and tasting) (Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007; Nasar, 2008; Zube, 1984). All person-environment transactions involve an element of environmental perception and, therefore, one cannot interact with their physical and socio-physical environment without being able to perceive it (Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007; Nasar,

2008). The term perception, as used in the present thesis, is concerned with students' cognitive representations of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces (cf. Bell et al., 2001).

Gifford (2007) proposes that environmental perceptions vary as a function of personal characteristics (e.g., environmental preferences) and situational characteristics (e.g., environmental conditions). This is in line with the research reviewed in Section 2.2., which demonstrates that students exhibit diverse responses to the same environmental variables as a function of personal and situational characteristics (Belojević et al., 1997; Collins-Eiland et al., 1986; Gulian & Thomas, 1986; Marchand et al., 2014; Sherrod et al., 1977). Several studies on the predictors of HE students' environmental perceptions are supportive of this conclusion. Such studies have highlighted statistically significant differences in students' perceptions of the environment in their campus learning spaces as a function of: furniture arrangements and the presence or absence of dividers (İmamoğlu & Gürel, 2016); expected GPA, study year, and gender (Yang et al., 2013); noise sensitivity (Belojević et al., 1997); personality traits, including, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience (Wilson & Cotgrove, 2016); and degree programme, including, Built Environment, Engineering, and Art and Design Disciplines (Wilson & Cotgrove, 2016).

In line with the wider literature on person-environment transactions, studies on learning spaces consider students' perceptions of the environment as unobserved psychological constructs. That is, subjective perceptions of the environment are not directly observable and therefore can only be investigated through indirect methods (Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007). Several quantitative and qualitative approaches have been used (alone or combined) to capture students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces.

Quantitative approaches involve the use of measurement instruments (e.g., questionnaires and diaries) to quantify or numerically represent a construct (Todd et al., 2004; Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Hine et al., 2016), such as, students' environmental perceptions. Such quantifications are typically used in subsequent inferential analyses, for instance, to identify the dimensions which compose students' environmental perceptions (e.g., acoustical, non-acoustical, spatial, and ambient), predictors of environmental perceptions, and/or the learning and psychological outcomes associated with students' environmental perceptions (e.g., Beckers et al.,

2016a; Belojević et al., 1992; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016; Scannell et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2013).

In contrast, qualitative approaches often involve the collection of rich and in-depth non-numerical data; examples include written or spoken words collected via open-ended surveys, interviews, and focus groups (Creswell, 2014; Sullivan et al., 2014; Todd et al., 2004). This data is typically analysed (e.g., thematically) to investigate students' subjective experiences of learning spaces; this helps to gain a 'user-centred' understanding of students' (i) requirements from the environment and (ii) beliefs about the learning and psychological consequences (i.e., impact) of the environment (e.g., cf. Granito & Santana, 2016; Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Melhuish, 2010; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017; Van Horne et al., 2014).¹¹

In the following subsection, quantitative and qualitative approaches are considered in turn. First, research is reviewed on the associations between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes. The review is then driven to consider the how future research in this area would benefit from a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches in order to address the limitations of previous work.

2.3.3. Students' perceptions of the environment: Associated learning and psychological outcomes

When reviewing this research, two trends become apparent. First, research has used quantitative questionnaires to investigate the relationship between students' perceptions of single environmental variables (noise and temperature) and performance-based outcomes, including, both cognitive task performance and course performance (Belojević et al., 1992; Hoque & Weil, 2016). For example, in an experimental study at Gothenburg University (Sweden), Belojević et al. (1992) investigated the relationship between students' self-reported perceptions of traffic noise and their cognitive task performance. Students who perceived traffic noise as more annoying performed significantly poorer on cognitive tasks than peers who perceived the noise as less annoying. Further, in a study of six classroom spaces at the University of Massachusetts, Hoque and Weil (2016) found a

¹¹ Instructors play a key role in students' experiences of classroom spaces and are, therefore, also often included to understand their own perspectives and create a clearer overall picture of students' learning space experiences (e.g., Granito & Santana, 2016).

significant relationship between students' self-reported thermal discomfort (temperature) and their grades. Specifically, higher perceived thermal discomfort was correlated with lower grades (Hoque & Weil, 2016).

However, Belojević et al. (1992) and Hoque and Weil's (2016) studies suffer from several limitations. The study by Belojević et al., for instance, was conducted under laboratory conditions and therefore the 'simulated experience' may not be representative of both students' learning space experiences (noise annoyance and performance on learning activities) within real world learning spaces (Field & Hole, 2013; Stone, 2001). In addition, both Belojević et al. and Hoque and Weil focused on the relationship between students' perceptions of single environmental characteristics in isolation (noise and thermal comfort). As mentioned previously, students are typically exposed to multiple environmental demands (e.g., acoustical, ambient, and spatial) in their campus learning spaces (Marchand et al., 2014).

The second research trend has adopted a more 'holistic' approach to investigating students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their classroom spaces, using quantitative questionnaires to measure students' perceptions of multiple environmental variables. Specifically, these studies have explored the relationships between environmental satisfaction, perceived impact of the environment, affective impressions of the environment, and/or class or course satisfaction (Castilla et al., 2017; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010).

In one such study, Hill and Epps (2010), found that students' satisfaction with seating (comfort, ability to find desirable seating location, amount of desk space for notes and tests, and arrangement), lighting (visual distractions, suitability of lighting for lectures, audio-visual presentations, and viewing presentation materials), hearing (ability to hear the professor and frequency of noise from outside the classroom), and general comfort within their classroom environments, were significantly and positively associated with their class satisfaction.

In another study of classroom spaces at the University of Minnesota, Choi et al. (2014a) found that students' satisfaction with temperature, acoustics, lighting, furnishings, aesthetics, vibrations, view conditions (ability to see presenter and presentation materials), and overall indoor environmental

quality, significantly predicted their 'perceived impact of indoor environmental quality on learning'. In addition, students' 'perceived impact of indoor environmental quality' mediated the relationship between their satisfaction with overall environmental quality and course satisfaction. The associations between different types of environmental perceptions (e.g., satisfaction with classroom features, overall classroom satisfaction, and perceived impact of the classroom environment on learning) are in line with the findings of Castilla et al. (2017). Castilla et al. found significant associations between students' 'perceived suitability' of classroom environmental characteristics (e.g., furniture arrangement, lighting, and ventilation) and their affective impressions of the physical classroom environment (e.g., as warm versus cold).

As mentioned in Chapter 1, there are advantages to adopting the quantitative questionnaire approach used above. First, quantitative questionnaires are quick and easy to administer to large groups of participants (e.g., students). The use of a quantitative questionnaire approach, therefore, allows researchers to gather data from large samples (Creswell, 2014; Wilson & MacLean, 2012). Indeed, in most of the studies presented above, the researchers were able to collect data from large samples of students, ranging from 257 to 918 participants (see Castilla et al., 2017; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016). Large as opposed to small samples, are more likely to be representative of the wider population (e.g., of students) from which the sample was drawn (cf. Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Thus, findings from large samples are often more generalisable to the wider population from which data was collected (Creswell, 2014; Morgan, 1998).

Secondly, because of its numerical nature, quantitative data can be easily subjected to statistical analyses to explore relationships between constructs (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011), such as, students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes. Finally, because of its inherent strengths, quantitative research has traditionally been extremely valuable in informing real-world decision-making (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Following this logic, quantitative findings may be better received and utilised by stakeholders (e.g., designers, campus estates managers, and university managers) in the design of new and evaluation of existing campus learning spaces. To reiterate, Doherty and Chen (2016) state that: "policy makers and funders are more likely to be persuaded about ... utility by the evidence of quantitative data, such as precise information on the prevalence and impacts of the issue" (p. 326).

While literature is scarce, it is evident that quantitative research on the associations between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes have several important strengths. However, the studies cited above (Belojević et al., 1992; Castilla et al., 2017; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016) also have significant methodological and conceptual flaws.

First, the environmental characteristics and outcomes investigated in the studies above seem to be selected by researchers on an ad hoc basis. As such, the relevance (i.e., content validity) of these constructs and their corresponding questionnaires to students' learning space experiences is questionable (cf. Francis et al., 2016). For instance, the relationships between students' perceptions of the environment and their course satisfaction may be of interest to both researchers and HEIs. However, students and instructors who have participated in previous qualitative research, often discuss their beliefs about the impact of the environment on cognitive-affective outcomes (e.g., annoyance, discomfort, and relaxation) and their engagement in learning activities (cf. Granito & Santana, 2016; Hunter & Cox, 2014; Matthews et al., 2011; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017). These qualitative findings challenge the relevance of the learning and psychological outcomes assessed in previous quantitative research to students' campus learning space experiences.

Secondly, the constructs assessed in the studies above and their corresponding questionnaires, lack sufficient conceptual/theoretical underpinnings. Only Hill and Epps (2010) included a theoretical statement pertaining to an established person-environment transaction theory (behaviour setting theory). However, the authors did not explicitly refer to the theory itself. Nor is it clear whether the theory was used to inform (i) their conceptualisation of students' learning space perceptions or (ii) the questionnaire used to assess these perceptions. As such, the way in which researchers (Belojević et al., 1992; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016) conceptualise students' environmental perceptions appears to be ad hoc in nature, with no established conceptual or theoretical basis. Indeed, in the research cited above conceptualisations of students' environmental perceptions appear to vary within and between studies, with no theoretical justification (e.g., perceived suitability, affective impressions, satisfaction, and perceived impact on learning).

Thirdly, the validity and reliability of the constructs representing students' holistic environmental perceptions and their corresponding multi-scale questionnaires are insufficiently addressed (i.e., Castilla et al., 2014b; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010). Specifically, where assessments of construct validity and reliability were conducted, analyses were implemented incorrectly, incomplete, poorly reported, lacked sufficient transparency, and/or validity and reliability were poor (e.g., Castilla et al., 2017). Poor validity and reliability may lead to researchers to incorrectly accept or reject the existence of significant relationships between variables (Elf et al., 2016; Francis et al., 2016; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014).¹²

Deficiencies in each of the three areas above may hinder the validity and reliability of the conclusions drawn from subsequent inferential analyses. To tackle the latter issues of construct validity and reliability, it is first necessary to consider how the former two issues, insufficient content validity and conceptual underpinnings, can be addressed.

In line with best practice guidance on research design and psychometric evaluation (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink, 2010a, 2010b), a particularly rigorous approach to enhancing the content validity of research in this area would involve conducting an in-depth qualitative study (e.g., data collected via interviews or focus groups) with members of the target population (i.e., students) and those with professional knowledge of the phenomena of interest (e.g., instructors). The resultant qualitative data on students' learning space experiences, could then allow researchers to identify from a 'user-centred' perspective, relevant (i) physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics and (ii) learning and psychological outcomes. In addition, when conceptualisations/theorisation of a phenomena are limited, qualitative findings are often useful in (i) generating new conceptual or theoretical frameworks and (ii) understanding the utility of existing conceptual or theoretical frameworks (Smith, 2018; Sullivan et al., 2014). Analysis of such qualitative data could be used to (i) inform the selection of relevant constructs, (ii) investigate the utility of existing theory, (iii) investigate the utility of questionnaires used in previous research, and (iv) inform the development of a new and more robust questionnaire. Such a study

¹² Construct validity is the extent to which a measurement instrument assesses the intended constructs (COSMIN, 2017; Francis et al., 2016; hair et al., 2017; Mokkink et al., 2010a, 2010b). Reliability is the degree to which participant scores are free from measurement error (COSMIN, 2016; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink et al., 2010a, 2010b; Nunnally & Berstein, 1994).

would have superior content validity and conceptual underpinnings, compared with previous quantitative research (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Francis et al., 2016).

In other words, to address the lack of content validity and conceptual limitations of previous quantitative research on students' environmental perceptions and the associated learning and psychological outcomes, future research may benefit from using a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches. The subsequent subsection will, therefore, review previous qualitative research to illustrate the benefits of using qualitative research as a basis for improving content validity in subsequent quantitative research.

2.3.4. Students' experiences of their campus learning spaces

In reviewing the literature on users' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces, a large body of qualitative research is available. Such data is typically collected from students and instructors via one or more methods, such as, interviews, focus groups, open-ended surveys, and photographic methods. While this qualitative data is often triangulated with basic quantitative data (e.g., observed or self-reported frequency counts of space use and behaviours), qualitative data on students' experiences of their learning spaces are particularly relevant to this section. This is because qualitative data provides a rich source of information as to how students experience their campus learning spaces, including, the relevance of physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics as well as their beliefs about the learning and psychological consequences of the environment (cf. Granito & Santana, 2016; Hunter & Cox, 2014; Melhuish, 2010; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017; Van Horne et al., 2014).

In one such study at Iowa State University, Rands and Gansemer-Topf (2017) conducted interviews and focus groups with students and instructors to capture their subjective experiences of an active learning classroom. Qualitative analysis revealed that flexibility and openness (ability to circulate the space) were perceived to be essential for creating a community of learners and encouraging engagement in learning activities. In addition, the configuration of the space was perceived as important for (i) the removal of student-instructor barriers, (ii) facilitating engagement in student-instructor interactions, (iii) creating a place where students felt that they were co-creating knowledge, and (iv) improving engagement in student-to-student and student-to-instructor interactions (Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017).

In study at a Midwestern US community college, Granito and Santana (2016) conducted focus groups with students and instructors. Their analysis of the qualitative data highlighted several environmental characteristics which users perceived as important for learning and teaching. Students and instructors noted that the presence of too many desks in small classrooms could lead to feelings of discomfort (e.g., claustrophobia), while the availability of wide circulation spaces could alleviate this discomfort (Granito & Santana, 2016). Other environmental factors which students highlighted as important were the size of the work surfaces, lighting (artificial and natural), temperature, acoustics, and technology. All students and instructors recognised how the furniture configuration could influence engagement or disengagement in interaction. In instructional classrooms, rowed seating was perceived to result in disengagement, feelings of alienation, and feelings of exclusion among students (Granito & Santana, 2016). Other negative consequences discussed by students and instructors included concentration deficits. Some instructors recognised the potential of individual differences in students' learning space experiences, suggesting that many students could ignore negative environmental conditions. Specifically, these instructors believed that negative environmental conditions could have a greater impact upon students who: are from non-traditional backgrounds, are underprepared, and/or have learning difficulties (Granito & Santana, 2016). For Granito and Santana's participants, the optimal environment would fully involve students in their learning activities, minimise distractions, reduce disengagement, and prevent alienation, feelings of discomfort and claustrophobia.

Matthews et al. (2011) conducted a series of observations, interviews and focus groups with students who used a science social learning centre for self-directed learning. Findings revealed that the students perceived their social learning centre as a place where they could develop a sense of belonging, as part of a science student and instructor community. Students believed that this sense of belonging was developed through the establishment of extended friendship networks with students in their own courses and students in other science degree programmes (Matthews et al., 2011). Related to this point, students viewed their social learning centre as somewhere where they could find peers who provided better ideas and clarification of difficult concepts than would an instructor (Matthews et al., 2011). Students cited that they were drawn to the space because of its comfortable furniture, open space, controllable temperature, location, large tables, and eating facilities. Students articulated that the presence of different 'zones' in the space allowed them to choose areas which were congruent with their needs, such as, open areas for socialising and eating

and closed areas with booths and meeting rooms for collaborative learning (Matthews et al., 2011). The use of this space brought students together to develop a shared sense of belonging and enhanced their engagement in social learning activities (Matthews et al., 2011). In summary, participants highlighted the relevance of several environmental features in (i) enhancing their ability to connect with peers, (ii) increasing their engagement in learning with peers, and (iii) encouraging them to use the social learning centre.

Finally, Hunter and Cox (2014) used (predominantly qualitative) questionnaires, observations, and follow-up interviews to understand students' out-of-class learning space experiences across three UK HE campuses. Several students perceived a 'calming and relaxing' versus a 'stressful' 'background atmosphere' as valuable to their learning experiences out with class. According to some students, negative aspects of the environment (e.g., poor lighting and excessive noise) could lead to concentration deficits, including, distraction and disengagement from learning activities.

Based on their qualitative findings, Hunter and Cox (2014) developed a "Model of Zengagement", whereby "Zen" represents a "relaxed frame of mind for studying" and "Gagement" is the degree to which students can absorb their background atmosphere. The model proposes that engagement in learning activities is enhanced for those who can absorb the background atmosphere, while those who cannot become disengaged. Students' personal zones or space (territories) are central to the model, and these can be increased or decreased by spreading out belongings or sitting in sheltered settings. Outside of the personal zone is the background atmosphere; students can zone in and out of the various environmental stimuli "to the degree that is optimum for stimulating their studies" (Hunter & Cox, p. 46). For instance, students can benefit from pleasant window views to draw on inspiration (i.e., they focus on stimuli which they find pleasant). However, stimuli which students cannot influence or control, such as distracting noise, can lead to an uncomfortable atmosphere. Finally, the model acknowledges variation in students' optimal atmospheres for learning; while the background atmosphere was energising and motivating for some students, it was 'too much' or 'overwhelming' and led to disengagement for others (Hunter and Cox, 2014). Like the qualitative findings discussed above, the students articulated a variety of environmental variables, engagement-related consequences, and cognitive-affective (e.g., discomfort, calming and relaxing, and stressful) consequences which were relevant to their learning space experiences.

However, the qualitative studies on university students' learning space experiences have several limitations. Due to the time constraints associated with data collection and in-depth analysis, qualitative data is typically collected from a small sample of users from the population of interest; this may hinder sample representativeness (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Thus, the extent to which qualitative findings and models (e.g., of 'ZenGagement') are generalisable to the wider population of students from which the sample was drawn, is questionable. Further, qualitative data is usually challenging to quantify, nor can it be used to assess statistical associations and determine the size of effects between variables (e.g., learning space perceptions and engagement-related and cognitive-affective outcomes) (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Johansson et al., 2003). As stated by Johansson et al. (2003), "qualitative research is valued for its relevance, but is considered lacking in scientific accuracy" (p. 10).

Nevertheless, qualitative approaches within learning space research can be beneficial. For instance, in line with 'user-centred' approaches to design mentioned previously, students and instructors who participated in the studies above were able to communicate their own subjective learning space experiences. They were able to articulate their own concerns directly to the researchers about specific environmental conditions and the impact that these conditions may have. Indeed, the use of such findings may be useful in informing the selection of variables and the creation of quantitative questionnaires with superior content validity. Such a follow-up quantitative study would also allow researchers to gather data from a larger and potentially more representative sample; this would allow researchers understand whether their qualitative findings (e.g., models) can be generalised to a wider population (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Todd et al., 2004).

Ideally, then, future research on students' environmental perceptions and the associated learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces would benefit from using a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches; this would help to overcome the weaknesses of using either approach alone (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Specifically, the analysis of in depth data from a qualitative phase could be used as a basis for a subsequent quantitative phase by (i) identifying variables which are relevant to students' learning space experiences, (ii) investigating the utility of existing theory in explaining students' learning space experiences, (iii) investigating the utility of the quantitative questionnaires used in previous research to assess students' environmental perceptions, and (iv) informing the development of a new questionnaire which measures students' learning space experiences. The constructs investigated in such a study and their

corresponding questionnaire, would have superior content validity and conceptual underpinnings, compared with previous quantitative research (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Francis et al., 2016).

2.3.5. Summary and conclusions

To conclude, Section 2.3. provided a contextualisation of, justified the focus on, and outlined the approaches used to capture students' learning space perceptions and experiences. Previous research on the statistical associations between students' perceptions of the environment and learning and psychological outcomes was reviewed. In summary, this research suffers from methodological and conceptual flaws, such as, poor content validity and insufficient conceptual underpinnings. The author highlighted how qualitative research with learning space users could be conducted to both identify constructs and create corresponding quantitative questionnaire subscales, which are relevant to students' learning space experiences. Such qualitative research would also allow researchers to understand the utility of existing theories in explaining students' learning space experiences and informing subsequent quantitative research design. Such an approach is in line with best practice guidance on research design, draws on the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative approaches, and would enhance the content validity and conceptual underpinnings of subsequent research conducted as part of this PhD. To sufficiently address the conceptual limitations of previous research, the review will now consider the value of person-environment transaction theories used in environmental psychology, in explaining students' learning space perceptions and the associated outcomes. While it is difficult to discern their utility at this stage, such theories may help to serve an empirical base which can be drawn upon for the subsequent empirical research.

2.4. Person-Environment Transaction Theories

2.4.1. Introduction to person-environment transaction theories

To reiterate, research on students' environmental perceptions and the associated learning and psychological outcomes have methodological and conceptual flaws. The constructs assessed in the previous studies and their corresponding questionnaires, lack sufficient conceptual/theoretical underpinnings. Only one quantitative study reviewed in the previous section (Hill & Epps, 2010) included a theoretical statement pertaining to an established person-environment transaction theory (behaviour setting theory). However, it is unclear whether the theory was used to inform (i)

Hill and Epp's (2010) conceptualisation of students' learning space perceptions or (ii) the questionnaire used to assess these perceptions. To summarise, in previous research (Belojević et al., 1992; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016), conceptualisations of students' environmental perceptions appear to be ad hoc in nature, with no established conceptual or theoretical basis. To address these limitations, the previous section highlighted the value of combining an in-depth qualitative study with a large-scale quantitative study to improve content validity. In addition, it was proposed that such a qualitative study would be useful in understanding the utility of existing theories. Thus, person-environment transaction theories are reviewed in this section. It is argued that such theories may be useful in informing the subsequent empirical research, though further (qualitative) research is first necessary to fully understand their utility and relevance.

Theories of person-environment transaction are predominantly used in the discipline of environmental psychology, that is, the study of mutual transactions between individuals and their physical and socio-physical environments (Gifford, 2007, 2014). Within environmental psychology, a number of these person-environment transaction theories have highlighted the role of environmental perception. These include behaviour setting theories (e.g., Barker, 1968) and affordance theories (e.g., Gibson, 1979), environmental control theories (Proshansky et al., 1970), environmental stress theory (Lazarus & Cohen, 1977); and person-environment fit theory (Michelson, 1976). However, there is no overarching theory within environmental psychology (Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007, 2014). Thus, the empirical studies conducted in this thesis will draw on several theoretical perspectives where appropriate. These theories are reviewed in the subsequent subsections.

2.4.2. Ecological theories

Ecological theories encompass a range of approaches which are concerned with environmental perception and behaviour as it occurs in real world settings (Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007; Heft, 2001). Two broad approaches to ecological perception are described and discussed below, behaviour setting theories and affordances (Barker & Wright, 1955; Barker, 1968; Costall, 1995; Gibson, 1966, 1979; Heft, 2001; Wicker, 1987).

Behaviour setting theories

Behaviour setting theorists (Barker & Wright, 1955; Barker, 1968) typically study human behaviour in its natural setting as opposed to under laboratory conditions. In his studies, Barker found that an individual's setting was a stronger driver of behaviour than their personal characteristics (e.g., personality traits) (Barker & Wright, 1955; Barker, 1968; Bell et al., 2001; Heft, 2001). Such synomorphy (i.e., congruence) within a setting, between a circumjacent (i.e., 'higher order') environmental structure and the behaviour of different individuals who occupy the setting, is referred to as a behaviour setting (Bell et al., 2001; Heft, 2001). Put simply, a behaviour setting is the physical and social contexts in which standing (i.e., socially accepted) behavioural patterns occur (Bell et al., 2001). As a higher order structure, a behaviour setting facilitates but also constrains the possibilities for action of its individual occupiers (Heft, 2001).

For Barker (1968), behaviour settings occur naturally due to the collective actions of groups of people; have beginnings and endpoints (temporal boundaries) that are generated and maintained by the setting, and understood by its occupiers; are perceivable and discriminable by occupants; exist independently of one's experience of them (i.e., are scientifically objective or real settings); and are interdependent with their occupants so that the actions of one individual are likely to influence the actions of others within the setting (Heft, 2001). Barker argued that behaviour settings are extra-individual and quasi-stable. Behaviour setting theorists propose a transactional or reciprocal relationship between the behaviour setting and its collective: behaviour settings are generated and maintained by congruence between the collective actions of individuals and the milieu of the environment, but also influence the behaviours of those who partake in them (Heft, 2001).

As an example, consider a university lecture. As with any other behaviour setting, it is a real/objective event, with a geographically and temporally bound location. The lecture occurred at the place and time because a required number of people (students and an instructor) gathered and essentially agreed to behave in a way which is congruent with consensual and shared rules. In addition, for the lecture to occur, a minimal set of materials (e.g., notebooks and lecture slides) and environmental characteristics are required (e.g., rowed seating and desks so that students can take notes). These components are the milieu of the behaviour setting and alongside other aspects of the milieu (students and the instructor) are the components to the setting as a whole. The circumjacent entity, the lecture, is generated by the relationships between and actions among its components. Reciprocally, individual behaviour is constrained by the rules of the setting and accordingly, students

and the instructor engage in the lecture activity. If a student should violate the rules of the lecture (e.g., by socialising, disrupting other students and the instructor), they may be ejected from the lecture. Behaviour settings do not determine behaviour per se, but constrain behaviour, allowing individuals to choose the behaviour possibilities that they engage in within the setting (Heft, 2001). The standing pattern of behaviour in a lecture classroom, for example, may include instructional activities, observation, sitting down and taking notes, asking questions, and answering questions.¹³

There are, however, several limitations to behaviour setting theories. For example, the overarching emphasis on group behaviour means that it is often difficult to understand individual differences, such as, variations in responses to (and perceptions of) the environment (cf. Bell et al., 2001; Heft, 2001). Some scholars, nevertheless, have attempted to modify behaviour setting theories to emphasise the role of individuals. Wicker (1987), for instance, purported that individuals form cognitive representations (e.g., cause maps) which contain knowledge about how different settings function. For Wicker, cause maps provide templates (e.g., of variables and relationships) which allow individuals to make sense of the environment. These cause maps stem from previous person-environment transactions; each person has multiple subjective environments represented within their cause maps. Cause maps reduce the inherent ambiguity and uncertainty in, allow individuals to make sense of, and allow people to selectively detect information in the environment (Heft, 2001; Wicker, 1984, 1987).

Behaviour setting theories have several advantages that are worth highlighting. For instance, the theories encourage environmental psychologists to study perceptions and behaviours in real world behaviour settings (Bell et al., 2001). Furthermore, behaviour setting theories advocate the consideration of the functionality or activities that one is using a space for. As Heft, (2001) states: “the functional nature of behavior settings and their psychological significance are the most significant theoretical contribution of Barker’s research programme” (p. 253).

Affordances and perceived affordances

In addition to behaviour setting theory, Gibson’s (1979) construct of affordances is key in ecological theorisation. Gibson (1979) defined environmental affordances as the functional properties of a

¹³ This example is adapted from Heft (2001).

space, that is, “what it offers the animal, what it provides or furnishes, either for good or ill” (p. 127). Gibson was critical of the traditional form-based (i.e., descriptive) approach to environmental perception, arguing that the perception of an object’s functional opportunities is a more ecologically valid approach to understanding environmental perception (Gibson, 1979; Heft, 1988, 2001). For Gibson, perception involves the individual recognising both environmental objects and the functional opportunities (action potentials) or limitations which are offered by these objects. In other words, environments and objects provide action potentials in relation to the individual’s behavioural potentials. Thus, functional properties depend on the relationship between the abilities of the individual perceiver and how effectively the object can support their abilities (Heft, 2001). For instance, an incline is only perceived to be climbable when the characteristics of the environment (e.g., step height) and the individual perceiver (e.g., leg length) are congruent (Warren, 1984). In relation to learning spaces, a classroom may only be perceived as appropriate for collaborative learning when environmental characteristics (e.g., round desks and large circulation spaces) are congruent with characteristics of the individual perceiver (e.g., their ability to communicate verbally, ability to move around the classroom, and pedagogical philosophies).

From Gibson’s (1966, 1979) perspective, meaning does not reside solely in the mind of the observer, but rather in the environment. For Gibson, individuals attend to the meanings of objects through previous experiences. The function of objects and environments can be instantly detected and are perceived in terms of what they allow an individual to do rather than their qualities. According to Gibson, affordances are invariant. Specifically, while the needs of the perceiver may change at any given moment, the perceivers’ perception of affordances do not change. In summary, for Gibson “affordances refer to the functional significances of environmental features ... are specified relative to some individual ... whereas form-based classifications are labels applied to environmental features independent of their relevance ... for an individual” (Heft, 1988, p. 48).

Some have criticised Gibson’s perspective for neglecting culturally bound aspects of perception and the invariant nature of affordances (i.e., the notion that affordances are static and do not change as a function of one’s goals), however, more recent interpretations of Gibson’s later work suggest that he acknowledged that environmental perception involved socio-culturally bound meaning (Costall, 1995). Specifically, Gibson believed that behaviour occurs within a socially and culturally bound setting and, therefore, the perceived meaning of environments and objects depends upon the community which one is a part of. According to Costall (1995), people within the surrounding

community introduce individuals to objects, explain the affordances of objects, and monitor (ensure and sanction against) their correct or incorrect use (Costall, 1995). Social discomfort, for example, may stem from the incorrect use of a learning space (e.g., using the library for social activities as opposed to learning activities). Thus, other people help us to create socially and culturally specific affordances of objects and extract these socio-culturally bound meaning from the environment (Costall, 1995; Heft, 2001). Indeed, this viewpoint is in line with the evidence presented in previous sections which highlight significant variability in students' responses to and perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces as a function of personal and situational characteristics (e.g., Beckers et al., 2016a, 2016b; Wilson & Cotgrove, 2016; Yang et al., 2013).

For Gibson (1979, 1984), the affordances of an environment do not cause behaviour, but offer possibilities for action to the perceiver. That is, the environment offers the perceiver a range of behaviour possibilities (affordances) and the perceiver has both agency and self-control over which behaviours are adopted. However, more recent perspectives on the theorisation of affordances and perceived affordances propose that while the environment may not cause behaviour, it does invite possibilities for action which then render certain behaviours more likely (Prieske et al., 2015; Withagen et al., 2012; Withagen & Wermeskerken, 2010). Accordingly, human beings are invited to and consequently behave automatically in a particular way, without necessarily deciding to do so. Indeed, this is in line with several studies on learning spaces which have found that active learning spaces and instructional learning spaces, dependent on the instructors' pedagogical philosophies, may invite congruent learning and teaching practices (Brooks, 2012; Lasry et al, 2014; Sawers et al., 2016). An active learning classroom may, for example, be more likely to invite student-centred behaviours than an instructional learning space (e.g., see Brooks, 2012), though this may interact with student and instructor characteristics (e.g., beliefs about how learning and teaching should occur) (Lasry et al., 2014; Sawers et al., 2016).

Evaluation and reflection on ecological theories

Ecological theories have several strengths. First, the perspectives are highly relevant to the settings/environments, objects within environments, and behaviours which are found in educational institutions (cf. Banning, 1993; Griffin, 1982; Strange & Banning, 2001, 2015). Secondly, behaviour settings and affordance theories bring the role of human (social) activities within a setting or environment (i.e., functionality of the environment) to the forefront in environmental perception

research and theorisation (Heft, 2001). Thirdly, while it has been argued that Gibson's theory neglected the dynamic nature of environmental perceptions, more recent interpretations of affordances by Costall (1995) have highlighted how Gibson recognised that perceptions of objects may vary as a function of one's social and cultural settings. This is in line with Barker's (1968) notion that behaviour settings are dynamic, varying over time and as a function of circumstances.

2.4.3. Control theories

Another set of theories which address environmental perceptions focus on the amount of control that one actually has (objective control) and that one thinks one has (perceived control) over the environment (Bell et al., 2001; Gatersleben & Griffin, 2016; Gifford, 2007). Generally, having greater control over the physical and socio-physical environment has better consequences for the individual (Gifford, 2007; Gatersleben & Griffin, 2016; Lee & Brand, 2005, 2010). The behaviour constraint model proposes that when people lose objective and/or perceived control over their environment, then they will react against the environment to try and regain control of the situation; this process is called psychological reactance (Bell et al., 2001; Proshansky et al., 1970). If repeated attempts to regain control fail, then learned helplessness may ensue, whereby people 'give up' attempting to regain control over the environment or engaging in a task within a particular environment, even in situations where objective control can be regained (Gifford, 2007; Proshansky et al., 1970). Central to behaviour constraint models is the proposal that objective control or loss of objective control is not strictly necessary. That is, an individual merely has to perceive that the environment is constraining their needs and that they cannot regain control for negative aftereffects to ensue (Bell et al., 2001; Proshansky et al., 1970). This has been evidenced in previous studies which have shown a lack of task engagement, negative affect-related consequences (including depression), and lowered cognitive task performance when exposed to uncontrollable environmental stressors in quasi-experimental and laboratory settings (Evans & Stecker, 2004; Sherrod et al., 1977).

Scholars have distinguished several different types of control. Cognitive control is the (in)ability to use information about a stressor (e.g., predictability) to make it seem less threatening or stressful (Averill, 1973; Bell et al., 2001; Haghnia & Imani, 2016). For instance, if students expect the library to be crowded and noisy, then the negative effects of crowding and noise may be reduced. Behavioural control is one's (in)ability to change an environmental characteristic to facilitate a particular behaviour or reduce stress (Averill, 1973; Haghnia & Imani, 2016). Examples include students rearranging the furniture within a library space to facilitate collaboration with their peers, using

earphones or closing a door to block out noise from other people talking, and putting on or removing a jumper when it is too cold or warm. Finally, decisional control is a person's (in)ability to choose spaces which best suit their needs, including, the ability to choose from a range of suitable alternatives (Averill, 1973; Gatersleben & Griffin, 2016; Haghnia & Imani, 2016). For example, a student may move from a space within the environment which does not meet their needs (e.g., too noisy) to a space which is more appropriate to their needs (e.g., silent).

The behaviour constraint model and control theories have several limitations. First, it is difficult to predict the consequences of situations when there is no need to infer a loss of perceived control (Bell et al., 2001). Secondly, behaviour constraint and control theories often emphasise individual environmental variables and in doing so neglect the whole setting (Bell et al., 2001). As mentioned previously, more 'holistic' approaches to learning space research propose that students are exposed to multiple physical and socio-physical environmental variables within their learning spaces, which may facilitate or hinder their learning (Marchand et al., 2014).

Nevertheless, a key strength of control theories is their ability to predict negative consequences which stem from a loss of control or perceived control (Bell et al., 2001). By way of example, the loss of perceived control may go some way to explain the behaviours of students who experience increased cognitive load and depleted attention in active learning classrooms (Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017; Whiteside et al., 2009). Specifically, some students (e.g., those with low prior knowledge and/or additional support needs) may perceive the increased stimulation within an active learning relative to an instructional classroom as overstimulating or constraining their ability to engage in student-centred learning activities (e.g., Lasry et al., 2014; Whiteside et al., 2009). It is possible that students in such situations feel that they are unable to regain control of the situation (e.g., through psychological reactance). Once repeated attempts to regain control have failed, such students, may experience 'learned helplessness' which can result in disengagement and reduced attendance (cf. Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017; Whiteside et al., 2009). Likewise, Sherrod et al. (1977) found that university students who believed that they had control over noise performed significantly better on a cognitive task than those who believed that they did not have control over the task.

Further, the recognition that the environment and perceptions of the environment vary as a function of environmental conditions, is in line with ecological theories and previous research on HE

learning spaces, which suggest that students' responses to the physical environment (e.g., environmental perceptions) may vary over time and as a function of circumstances (Barker & Wright, 1955; Barker, 1968; Beckers et al., 2016a, 2016b; Costall, 1995; Gibson, 1979; Yang et al., 2013).

2.4.4. Environmental stress theory

Lazarus and Cohen's (1977) environmental stress theory explicitly recognises the dynamic or temporal nature of the relationship between objective environmental stressors (environmental demands), appraisals of, and responses to stressors. Environmental stress theory proposes that the relationship between objective environmental demands (e.g., noise, temperature, lighting, crowding, and furniture arrangements) and the experience of stress and related outcomes, are mediated by an appraisal and coping process (Bell et al., 2001; Lazarus & Cohen, 1977). Cognitive appraisal involves a judgement or evaluative perception regarding the significance of the environmental stressor for the individual (Lazarus & Cohen, 1977). There are two types of appraisals: primary and secondary. During primary appraisal, one or more stressors are appraised as benign/irrelevant, challenging, threatening, and/or harmful.

Secondary appraisal occurs when individuals appraise their resources or abilities to cope with the stressor. Like environmental control, coping involves 'doing something about the stressor' to try and reduce or remove its impact (Bell et al., 2001; Lazarus & Cohen, 1977). Problem-focused coping may involve moving to a more suitable space, closing blinds, using earphones to drain out background noise, or reconfiguring furniture to enhance interaction with peers. Emotion-focused coping, on the other hand, might involve appraising a stressor as less threatening (Gatersleben & Griffin, 2016; Lazarus & Cohen, 1977). Negative primary appraisals (e.g., threat appraisals), negative (i.e., low) coping appraisals, and/or the inability to sufficiently cope with environmental stressors or demands can lead to negative consequences including stress and related outcomes, such as negative affect (Bell et al., 2001; Lazarus & Cohen, 1977). While primary appraisal does not necessarily precede secondary appraisal, Lazarus and Folkman (1984) suggest that the two constructs are interrelated.

Lazarus and Cohen (1977) note that environmental appraisals stem from complex interactions between the situation (e.g., nature of the stressor) and personal characteristics of the individual. This has led Bell et al. (2001) to challenge the concepts of primary and secondary appraisal, arguing that the conditions under which environmental stressors are perceived as, for example, threatening

or challenging are difficult to predict. Likewise, it is difficult to predict whether an environmental stressor or demand perceived as, for instance, challenging has positive or negative consequences for the individual.

Nevertheless, environmental stress theory has considerable strengths. First, as with perceptions of environmental control, differences in appraisal may help to explain why some people respond differently to the same environmental demands (Bell et al., 2001). Secondly, the explicit emphasis on the dynamic nature of environmental appraisals and their associated stress-related outcomes is in line with ecological theories, behaviour constraint theories, and differences in students' perceptions of and responses to environmental demands as a function of situational characteristics (see Subsections 2.2. and 2.3.).

2.4.5. Person-environment congruence

Finally, the theoretical construct of person-environment fit is of relevance to this thesis; that is the degree to which the environment is congruent with the needs of its users (Michelson, 1976). Michelson (1976) differentiates between the concept of experiential congruence and mental congruence. Experiential congruence is the degree to which different environments actually fit the needs of their users, while mental congruence is the extent to which individuals believe that an environment is congruent with their needs (Michelson, 1976). Of particular relevance to the present thesis is Michelson's concept of mental congruence. Michelson proposed that mental congruence is akin to a self-fulfilling prophecy. That is, if one believes that an environmental attribute (e.g., noise or room shape) is constraining their ability to engage in a particular activity, then they are unlikely to successfully engage in an activity (Michelson, 1976). For example, if a learner or instructor believes that a room is configured in such a way that constrains their abilities to engage in collaborative learning activities (e.g., too small for reconfiguration or fixed desks), then they are unlikely to engage in such activities; this may lead to different uses of the space, such as, engagement in traditional instructional activities instead.

Though Michelson was a sociologist, his distinction between experiential and perceived person-environment fit has several advantages. First, it is particularly relevant to each of the theories above, and thus may be seen as a meta-theory which encompasses each. For instance, a loss of perceived environmental control and/or perceptions of environmental demands as threatening may be

interpreted as representing poor person-environment fit. In addition, the notion of perceived fit as a self-fulfilling prophecy would certainly explain why negative perceptions of the physical environment might be associated with less positive outcomes. Secondly, in line with ecological theories, Michelson provides examples of perceived fit which pertain to the functionality of the physical environment. Finally, while Michelson (1976) proposed that person-environment fit and misfit can endure for lengthy periods of time, he recognised that person-environment fit can change over time and as a function of circumstances.

2.4.6. Overall theoretical evaluation and reflection

To reiterate, this thesis is concerned with the relationships between HE students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment, learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces. Previous research in this area is limited either by a lack of, or insufficient, conceptual underpinnings. Theories of person-environment transactions used in environmental psychology, however, may offer a useful conceptual base for the subsequent empirical chapters in this thesis. Within the theories reviewed, several key trends become apparent. First, each of the theories reviewed suggest or explicitly acknowledge that perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment are dynamic and vary over time and as a function of, for example, personal and situational characteristics.

Secondly, a number of theories highlighted the functional nature of environmental perceptions, with ecological theories suggesting that considering environmental perceptions in terms of the 'functional opportunities' which the environment offers its perceivers represents a more 'ecologically valid' or 'real world' approach to considering environmental perceptions, than traditional descriptive approaches (cf. Barker, 1968; Costall, 1995; Gibson, 1979; Heft, 2001; Michelson, 1976). Thirdly, all theories draw upon the notion of person-environment fit, the degree to which the environment meets one's needs.

However, it is worth noting that there are discrepancies between these theories in explaining individual's conceptualisations of their environments. This leads the author to question which conceptualisation or conceptualisations of environmental perceptions are most relevant to students' campus learning space experiences. Do students conceptualise the environment in their campus learning spaces as threatening, challenging, harmful, benign/irrelevant, congruent/incongruent, in a

dynamic manner, and/or in terms of its functional opportunities (e.g., cf. Barker, 1966; Gibson, 1978; Heft, 2001; Lazarus & Cohen, 1977; Michelson, 1976)? The utility of these theories is, therefore, difficult to discern. As such, in the initial instance, the research conducted as part of this PhD will draw upon each of these perspectives where appropriate to consider their utility as a basis for subsequent quantitative research on students' environmental perceptions in their campus learning spaces.

2.5. Chapter Conclusions and Thesis Aims

To conclude, Chapter 2 has demonstrated based upon previous illustrated how the physical and socio-physical environment in university campus learning spaces may be associated with a range of learning and psychological outcomes among students. First, the chapter highlighted that a large body of research has demonstrated the ways in which the objective conditions of the physical environment may interact with non-physical environmental factors (e.g., gender, personality, perceived control, and learning tasks) to influence a variety of outcomes. Such outcomes included course achievement, concept learning, engagement in student-centred versus instructional pedagogical practices, cognitive performance, course evaluations, students' mood, and environmental perceptions.

Several studies highlighted that considering the 'holistic' impact of the physical and socio-physical environment (i.e., considering the impact of multiple rather than single environmental characteristics) upon learning and psychological outcomes represents a more ecologically valid approach to understanding learning environment transactions. Further, the notion that students and instructors vary in their response to the same environmental characteristics as a function of personal and situational variables, provided a justification for focusing on students' learning space perceptions and experiences.

Following this, environmental perceptions were defined, and approaches used to capture environmental perceptions were outlined. This chapter moved on to evaluate quantitative research on the relationships between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces, learning and psychological outcomes. It was argued that while this quantitative research has significant strengths, what few studies have been conducted suffer from

methodological and conceptual flaws, including, poor content validity and insufficient conceptual underpinnings.

To address these limitations, the review outlined the value of underpinning future quantitative research with in-depth qualitative research (e.g., focus groups or interviews with learning space users). In line with best practice guidance on research design, this 'user-centred' approach would allow researchers to enhance the content validity of subsequent quantitative research. Specifically, the analysis of data from qualitative research could be used as a basis for subsequent quantitative research by (i) identifying variables which are relevant to students' learning space experiences, (ii) understanding the utility of the quantitative instruments used in previous research to measure students' environmental perceptions, and (iii) creating a questionnaire which measures these constructs. In addition, such qualitative research would serve as a useful basis for understanding the relevance of person-environment transaction theories in explaining students' learning space experiences.

The author reviewed a range of person-environment transaction theories used in environmental psychology. While there was no one overarching theory, several commonalities became apparent, including, an emphasis on the dynamic nature of environmental perceptions (i.e., changes over time and circumstances), the importance of the functionality of environmental perceptions (i.e., functional opportunities), and a focus on person-environment fit (i.e., congruence between the environment and users' needs). In sum, person-environment transaction theories may be useful in improving the conceptual limitations of previous quantitative research. Indeed, their utility will be investigated in the subsequent empirical chapters.

It is in addressing the limitations outlined above that this thesis makes an original contribution to knowledge. As it became clear through this review, a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches is necessary to address the overall aims of the thesis. The next Chapter (Chapter 3) will, therefore, outline the author's methodological reflections and considerations with regards to such an approach.

3. CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS AND REFLECTIONS

3.1. Chapter Introduction

This chapter is split into three parts. In part one (Section 3.2.), the author outlines the approach adopted in this thesis: mixed methods. The overall research aims of the thesis are reiterated, the mixed methods approach is defined, and then three empirical studies conducted as part of this PhD are outlined. Specifically, the author describes each study, explains how each study will contribute to the overall research aims, and discusses the links between the studies. The author briefly justifies why a mixed methods approach was adopted over a single quantitative or qualitative approach. Following this, the author outlines the different types of mixed methods research designs, before explaining which design most closely aligns with that adopted in this thesis. In part two of the chapter (Subsection 3.3.), the author reflects upon the considerations which influenced his chosen approach and his research worldview, pragmatism. The author then describes the role of theory in this research. The author then reflects upon the challenges of mixed methods research and how these were addressed. In part three, the chapter briefly outlines ethical considerations. Then, the author describes the data collection sites from which participants were recruited. The chapter concludes with a summary and brief outline of the subsequent chapters.

3.2. Overall approach

3.2.1. Background

To reiterate, this thesis is concerned with the relationships between university students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces. Chapters 1 (Introduction to the Thesis) and 2 (Overview of the Empirical Literature), suggested that previous research in this area is scarce and suffers from methodological and conceptual flaws.

The aim of this thesis was, therefore, to investigate the relationships between university students' environmental perceptions in their campus learning spaces and learning and psychological outcomes, using a more rigorous methodological approach than previous research. Specifically, the overall thesis aims were to:

1. Understand how HE students perceive (conceptualise) the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces;
2. Understand the relevance of different physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics and learning and psychological consequences to students' learning space experiences;
3. Develop a new and robust 'learning space experience' questionnaire to measure students' perceptions of the most relevant physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics in their campus learning spaces; and to
4. Explore how students' perceptions of relevant environmental characteristics are statistically associated with key learning and psychological outcomes.

These aims were addressed through three empirical chapters (Chapters 4-6) and a final discussion chapter (Chapter 7). In the final Discussion Chapter, the author discusses how each study addressed the overall research aims. The author describes, discusses the links between, and explains the overall thesis aims addressed by each study in the subsequent subsection.

3.2.2. Overview of the empirical studies

As indicated in Chapters 1 and 2, the present thesis used a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches. In other words, a mixed methods approach was adopted. While there is no universally accepted definition of mixed method approaches, the use of both qualitative and quantitative strands within a single research project, but not necessarily the one study, would seem to be a key defining aspect (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Johnson et al., 2007). Each strand (qualitative and quantitative) entails a set of common procedures, such as, developing research questions, data collection, data analysis and interpretation of results (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). In a review of definitions, Johnson et al. (2007) proposed that:

Mixed methods research is an intellectual and practical synthesis based on qualitative and quantitative research; it is the third methodological or research paradigm. It recognizes the importance of traditional quantitative and qualitative research but also offers a powerful third

paradigm choice that often will provide the most informative, complete, balanced, and useful results (p. 129).

The qualitative and quantitative studies conducted as part of this PhD are overviewed below.

Study 1 (Chapter 4) was a qualitative study with students and instructors at a Scottish, multi-campus and multi-geographic, university (described in subsection 3.3.). The study sought to address the first two thesis aims and inform the subsequent qualitative and quantitative empirical studies.

Specifically, Study 1 aimed to understand how students perceive the physical and socio-physical environment in their university campus learning spaces, identify the relevant environmental characteristics of these spaces for students' learning space experiences, identify relevant learning and psychological consequences of the environment for students' learning space experiences, and investigate the utility of person-environment transaction theories in explaining students' learning space experiences. Braun and Clarke's (2012) method of reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) was used to analyse data collected from focus groups with students and instructors. In addressing each of the aims, the author developed a thematic model which explains (i) how students perceive the environment in their campus learning spaces and (ii) the relationships between students' perceptions of the most relevant environmental characteristics and learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces. This thematic model was then used to inform the analysis of the subsequent qualitative study (Study 2) and design and interpretation of the subsequent quantitative study (Study 3).

Chapters 1 (Introduction to the Thesis) and 2 (Overview of the Empirical and Theoretical Research) served a valuable purpose in providing a broad contextualisation and an empirical and theoretical base for the subsequent empirical research in this thesis. However, to identify and more thoroughly review the quantitative measurement instruments used in previous research to assess students' environmental perceptions in their campus learning spaces, a more nuanced approach is required. Therefore, for Study 2 (Chapter 5), a systematic literature review was conducted. The review aimed to (i) identify the quantitative instruments used in previous research to capture students' perceptions of the environment in their campus learning spaces and (ii) assess the suitability of these instruments in terms of their psychometric properties (reliability and validity), conceptual underpinnings, and item content. To assess the suitability of existing instruments, the review evaluated their (i) psychometric properties using best practice guidance (Field et al., 2012; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink, 2010a, 2010b; Osborne, 2014; Osborne & Costello, 2005; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014); (ii) conceptual underpinnings using the thematic model developed in Study 1; and (iii) item

content using the thematic model from Study 1. By understanding how students' perceptions of the environment in their campus learning spaces have been conceptualised in previous quantitative research, Study 2 addressed the first overall thesis aim.

In Study 3, the development of a new quantitative 'learning space experience' questionnaire was described. This questionnaire measured university students' (i) perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and (ii) learning and psychological outcomes within a specific campus learning space. The constructs assessed by the questionnaire and questionnaire item content was informed by the thematic model developed in Study 1 (Chapter 4). The author presented and interpreted the psychometric evaluation of the instrument, including, construct validity (convergent and discriminant) and internal consistency reliability, using inferential statistical analyses. The author then presented and evaluated the relationships between the constructs proposed in the thematic model (Study 1). In other words, the relationships between students' perceptions of the environment and learning and psychological outcomes, in a specific campus learning space are explored using inferential analyses. As the thematic model was driven by instructors and students, previous research, and relevant person-environment transaction theories, the constructs assessed in Study 3 and their corresponding measurement instruments have superior content validity and conceptual underpinnings relative to previous research (Belojević et al., 1992; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016).

In addressing the psychometric properties of the questionnaire, Study 3 considered whether the conceptualisation of students' environmental perceptions described in the thematic model from Study 1 could be measured in a reliable and valid manner and generalised to a wider student population (thesis Aim 1). In the development of a new and robust learning space experience questionnaire, Study 3 addressed the third overall aim of the thesis. Finally, by exploring the relationships between students' perceptions of the environment and their learning and psychological outcomes, Study 3 addressed both the second and fourth aims of the thesis.

Research design and data collection for Studies 1 (focus groups) and 2 (systematic review) were conducted at the same time. However, data analysis and interpretation for Study 1 was conducted prior to data analysis and interpretation for Study 2. This allowed the thematic model developed in

Study 1 to inform, in part, the data analysis in Study 2. Research design, data collection, and data analysis for Study 3 were conducted after studies 1 and 2.

It is worth noting that the use of a single quantitative or qualitative approach were also considered. However, by using a solely quantitative approach, the research conducted within this thesis would have suffered from the same limitations as previous quantitative research. Specifically, environmental characteristics and learning and psychological outcomes would be chosen based on previous research alone. The relevance of those constructs, their corresponding measurement instruments, and person-environment transaction theories to students' learning space experiences would, therefore, be questionable. In contrast, a solely qualitative approach would have sacrificed data collection from a larger and more representative sample; the generalisability of findings; the ability to explore statistical relations between environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes; and, therefore, the potential practical utility of the findings. As such, a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches (i.e., mixed methods) were used in this thesis. In the subsequent section, the author outlines the most common mixed methods designs in order to identify the design which most closely aligns with the research conducted in this thesis.

3.2.3. A reflection on mixed methods designs

There are four main mixed methods designs: (i) convergent or triangulation designs, (ii) explanatory sequential designs, (iii) exploratory sequential designs, and (iv) multiphase designs (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Doyle et al., 2016; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016). In this subsection, each design is described and evaluated.

The convergent design is often used to acquire complementary data of different types (i.e., qualitative and quantitative) on the same research phenomena (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Doyle et al., 2016; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016). If implemented well, researchers can address the same research question, while drawing on the relative strengths and offsetting the weaknesses of using a qualitative or quantitative approach alone (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Researchers have therefore utilised the design to compare, contrast and/or synthesise qualitative and quantitative results in an attempt to validate and corroborate findings or gain a more complete understanding of phenomena (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Doyle et al., 2016; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016).

The explanatory sequential design begins with an initial quantitative strand; specific quantitative results are then followed up with a subsequent qualitative phase which aims to explain specific aspects of earlier results with more detail (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Doyle et al., 2016; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016). The explanatory sequential design is therefore useful in terms of providing follow-up explanations on specific quantitative results, for example, significant findings, non-significant findings, and outlying participants (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Doyle et al., 2016; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016).

However, both the convergent and explanatory sequential designs are only useful when the researchers: (i) know which predictor and outcome variables are of relevance for the preliminary quantitative study, (ii) have an established pre-existing conceptual framework on which to base the design the preliminary quantitative study, and/or (iii) have access to existing tools which can appropriately investigate the conceptual model (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Doyle et al., 2016; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016). As a result, these approaches alone are not best suited to addressing the thesis aims and the primary considerations of the author.

The exploratory sequential design addresses the issues with convergent and explanatory sequential designs by starting with a qualitative phase which aims to explore the phenomena of interest (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Doyle et al., 2016; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016). The qualitative findings can then be utilised to inform a subsequent quantitative approach by identifying relevant variables for inclusion in subsequent quantitative research, aiding in the development of an appropriate conceptual framework, and/or informing the design of measurement instruments (e.g., questionnaires) which (i) measure relevant variables and (ii) can be used to investigate the predictions proposed by the new conceptual framework using data collected from a larger sample and statistical analyses (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Doyle et al., 2016; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016).

Finally, in a multiphase design, the researchers adopt multiple concurrent (i.e., simultaneous) and/or sequential strands (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). In concurrent strands, studies are conducted simultaneously (i.e., at the same time), compared to sequentially (one after the other). The multiphase design is advantageous because researchers can draw on the combined strengths of convergent, explanatory sequential, and/or exploratory sequential designs (Creswell & Plano Clark,

2011). However, it is often difficult for researchers and participants to find the time required to adopt multiphase mixed methods designs, compared to convergent and sequential designs (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011).

As mentioned in the previous subsection, to address the aims of the thesis, research design and data collection for qualitative Studies 1 and 2 were conducted simultaneously. However, the analysis and interpretation of data from qualitative Study 1 was conducted prior to the analysis and interpretation of data for qualitative Study 2. This allowed the author to use the findings from Study 1 (i.e., thematic model) to partially inform the analysis and interpretation of data from Study 2. Once Studies 1 and 2 were completed, the findings from Study 1 (thematic model) were also used to inform Study 3. Finally, the findings from each phase were considered in light of the overall research aims. This design is, therefore, most closely aligned with a multiphase exploratory sequential design.

Following guidance from Creswell and Plano Clark (2011), in the subsequent subsection, the author reflects upon his own considerations and research worldview which led to the mixed methods approach and design adopted within the thesis.

3.3. Author's reflections

3.3.1. Author's research worldview

According to best practice guidance on research design, the selection of a research approach (e.g., quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods) should reflect the researcher's philosophical views about the nature of reality and knowledge, that is, the researcher's worldview. A researcher's worldview is based on their basic assumptions about ontology (the nature of reality), epistemology (the nature of knowledge), and methodology (the ways of discovering knowledge) (Creswell, 2014; Guba & Lincoln, 2005; Lincoln et al., 2011). It is noted by several scholars that researchers should reflect upon the influence of their worldviews on their research practice when designing a research study (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2003).

When reflecting upon previous research on students' learning space perceptions and experiences, three main considerations drove the author's selection of a mixed methods research approach and design:

- First, the author wanted to develop practical implications which could inform the HE learning space development and evaluation processes;
- Secondly, the author wanted to adopt a research approach which would best address the aims of the PhD; and
- Thirdly, the author wanted to adopt a research approach which would best tackle the limitations of previous quantitative research on students' environmental perceptions and the associated learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces.

The author believed that the strengths of a large-scale quantitative questionnaire approach would help to address the first consideration regarding 'practical implications'. This included the ability to collect data from a large and representative sample, generalise findings to a wider population, conduct statistical analyses to draw conclusions about the relationships between variables, and collect data which could be of value in informing real-world decision-making (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). However, to address the latter two considerations, the author believed that it would be necessary to use a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches, whereby the 'data rich' qualitative research informed the design of the subsequent quantitative research (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). In summary, the author firmly believed that a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches was the most effective means by which to address the considerations above.

A range of research worldviews were considered to identify an approach which best aligned with the author's considerations and reflections above. One approach would have involved adopting a single worldview, such as, post-positivism. Post-positivism is based on a critical realist ontology (Guba & Lincoln, 2005). A post-positivist researcher's assumptions about the nature of knowledge are founded on cause-and-effect relationships, reductionism (i.e., focusing on specific variables of interest), observations and measurement of 'reduced' variables, and theory testing and refinement (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Post-positivists recognise that researchers may influence their interpretations of phenomena, and therefore attempt to control such biases (Guba & Lincoln, 2005). Some scholars have positioned post-positivism as a 'single stance' worldview which aligns with mixed methods approaches (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). However, the post-positivist emphasis on cause-and-effect relations, reductionism, measurement, and experimental control, have led to questions about its suitability for underpinning research which adopts qualitative approaches to underpin subsequent quantitative approaches (Kurki, 2006).

Another stance involves combining two or more research worldviews within a single research study or project (Greene, 2007). For example, the dialectical stance proposes that researchers combine post-positivism with social constructionism; that is, the qualitative strand of a mixed methods study or project should be underpinned by social constructionism while the quantitative strand should be founded upon post-positivism. Unlike post-positivism, the constructionist paradigm is typically aligned with qualitative approaches and proposes that reality and knowledge are socially constructed by individuals; therefore, there may be as many tangible realities as there are individuals constructing those realities (Sullivan et al., 2014).

For social constructionists, reality and knowledge are constructed individually and collectively by the personal histories, interactions, and experiences of individuals (e.g., participants and researchers) (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Sullivan et al., 2014). However, the dialectical stance has been criticised for advocating the combination of two radically opposing or 'incompatible' paradigms (post-positivism and constructionism) within the same research project (Greene, 2007).

An alternative single paradigm approach which addresses this 'incompatibility' issue, is the pragmatic approach (Creswell, 2014; Greene, 2007). While traditional research paradigms (e.g., positivism, post-positivism, and social constructionism) are based on a researcher's beliefs about ontology and epistemology, a pragmatic approach does not make any assumptions about the nature of reality and knowledge (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Morgan, 2007, 2014). Rather, pragmatists are concerned with the end point of the research, that is, choosing the research approach (qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods) which best address the research aims and/or best solve real world problems (Morgan, 2014; Shannon-Baker, 2016). Based on the primary considerations of the author, the worldview adopted in this thesis is aligned with pragmatism.

There were several justifications for adopting the pragmatic approach as a research worldview. As discussed, pragmatists are concerned with the end point of a research study or project; therefore, the pragmatic approach proposes that researchers should choose the research approach (e.g., qualitative and/or quantitative) and corresponding methods (e.g., data collection techniques) which best address the aims of the research (Greene, 2007; Morgan, 2007, 2014; Shannon-Baker, 2016). The emphasis on solving real world problems addressed the author's considerations about

communicating practical implications. Further, the flexibility and freedom inherent in the pragmatic approach complimented the author's considerations about adopting a research approach which best addresses the aims of the thesis and tackles the limitations of previous quantitative research, i.e., a mixed methods approach.

3.3.2. Reflecting on the role of theory

In the previous subsection, the type of mixed methods design adopted and thus the ordering of the qualitative and quantitative phases were addressed. In addition to these issues, several scholars have proposed that mixed methods researchers should consider the extent to which theories drive their research design (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016).

Such theories can either be (i) specific to a particular field of academic inquiry such as social sciences or (ii) broader such as transformative and/or emancipatory theories on gender, race, or age (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Theories can be used deductively (e.g., testing and validating), inductively (e.g., exploring or generating emergent theories or patterns), or both. In addition, Creswell (2014) proposed that a theory may be used as an overarching framework. For instance, mixed methods researchers may present a theory, model, and/or conceptual framework in their literature review in order to inform the research questions and hypotheses of the different strands of the mixed methods study.

As mentioned in the Chapter 2, while there is no overarching framework which explains person-environment transaction theories, there are several commonalities between these theories. To reiterate, in the subsequent empirical chapters, the author will draw on a range of person-environment transaction theories where appropriate, including, Michelson's (1970) person-environment fit theory, Lazarus' and Cohen's (1977) environmental stress theory, ecological theories (Barker, 1968; Gibson, 1968, 1979; Heft, 2001), and control theories (Proshansky et al., 1970). The utility of these theories in informing the subsequent stages of the research will be considered in Study 1.

3.3.3. Addressing the challenges of a mixed methods approach

Despite the advantages of the mixed methods approach, there are several challenges which should be reflected upon. First, the mixed methods approach requires a significant investment in time for

successful implementation, such as, developing separate research questions, collecting different data types, adopting different analytical and interpretative processes, and mixing the qualitative and quantitative strands (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016). Similarly, researchers should, at the very least, be acquainted with both qualitative and quantitative data collection and analytical techniques (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016). Therefore, researchers should consider whether there is sufficient expertise to design, collect, and analyse both qualitative and quantitative data (Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2016).

Despite the increased demands of mixed methods over single method approaches, the mixing of qualitative and quantitative approaches within the timeframe of this PhD seemed feasible, since both the author and his supervisory team had experience with qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches. Further, while Study 1 informed the analyses of Study 2 and 3, data for Studies 1 and 2 was collected concurrently so that the thesis could be conducted within the maximum period of registration for the PhD (data collection within three years and write-up within four years).

In addition to the challenges of time and expertise, the viability of combining qualitative and quantitative approaches has also been challenged. This challenge is based on the fundamental differences in the assumptions underlying each approach and the notion that mixing qualitative and quantitative approaches can offset the inherent strengths and weaknesses of either approach alone. Specifically, Sandelowski (2012) argues that qualitative and quantitative approaches do not have inherent strengths and weaknesses and thus one must clearly define which strengths and weaknesses will be offset.

Reflecting upon Sandelowski's (2012) challenge, in the case of this thesis, the qualitative strand allowed for the collection and analysis of data about students' subjective experiences of their campus learning spaces as well as the collection and analysis of data about the measurement instruments used in previous studies to capture students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces. However, the use of small and potentially unrepresentative samples, would have limited the generalisability of the conclusions drawn from the qualitative research; further, the inherent challenges in quantifying qualitative data would have made it difficult to investigate statistical associations among variables (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). On the other hand, Study 3 (quantitative) allowed for a wider exploration of

students' experiences within a specific type of learning space, using data collected from a larger and more representative sample, which was more generalisable to a wider population, and that could be subjected to statistical analyses. By combining the inherent strengths of each approach, the author was therefore able to offset their inherent weaknesses (see Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Plano Clark & Ivankova, 2011).

3.4. Data collection

3.4.1. Ethical considerations

All data for Studies 1 (qualitative focus groups) and 3 (quantitative questionnaire) were collected, used, stored, and analysed in accordance with the British Psychological Society (BPS) Code of Ethics (BPS, 2014, 2018). In addition, papers retrieved for Study 2 (qualitative systematic review) were stored in compliance with GDPR. Ethical approval from Studies 1 and 3 were obtained from the School of Media, Culture and Society Ethics Committee, at the author's institution, The University of the West of Scotland (UWS). Participants for Studies 1 and 3 were recruited from Campuses A, B, C and/or D at a Scottish, multi-campus and multi-geographic, HEI. To ensure anonymity, the HEI will subsequently be referred to as the "target university". A brief description of each campus is presented in the subsequent subsection. Specific ethical considerations are outlined in the methods sections of the corresponding empirical chapters.

3.4.2. Data collection sites

Campus A is the main and largest campus at the target university. It contains a variety of buildings. The eldest building dates to the 1890s. The campus underwent significant expansion following the publication of the British Government's Robbins report in the 1960s, and these buildings now comprise the majority of the campus estate. The campus library and learning centre were opened in the late 1990s. In recent years, the campus underwent several refurbishments costing approximately £15 million. Approximately eight classroom spaces were converted into active learning classrooms, with collaborative discussion desks, shared group screens, and different zones which are designed to facilitate transitions between small group discussion, full class discussion, and instructional activities. The library and learning centre were also redesigned to incorporate additional spaces which support social activities, collaborative learning, and individual study. A new one-stop hub for all student services was integrated into the social learning centre, and the main entrance and atrium were redesigned to host events and support social activities. Despite the investment in social and social

learning spaces, at the time of data collection for Studies 1 and 3, most learning spaces (classroom and out-of-class spaces) were designed for individual learning activities.

Campus B is situated in a coastal town. Its original facilities were replaced with a new, purpose-built, campus in 2011 which cost approximately £80 million. All learning, teaching, and office spaces are in the one building. The campus has several specialist facilities, such as, media and broadcasting spaces (e.g., for students in journalism and creative disciplines). In addition, the campus multi-functional library and resource centre won an architectural award for its impact upon the academic community. At the time of Studies 1 and 3, the campus library contained a floor dedicated to silent study, a floor dedicated to collaborative study, and private group study rooms.

Campus C was originally founded in 1972 as a college of technology. Its main building was an eight-storey tower block, dating back to the early 1970s. The main building contained a small campus library as well as classroom spaces. By default, most classroom spaces were setup for traditional instructional learning. Campus C's most modern building was constructed in approximately 2001 and contained a number of lecture and tutorial rooms as well as specialist skills laboratories for nursing students. In 2016, a single 'classroom of the future' was setup in the main building; the room contained a small variety of collaborative furniture arrangements which were used for scheduled learning activities, unscheduled learning activities, and to provide feedback on furniture suitability for the transition to Campus D.

In 2018, students and instructors from Campus C transitioned to Campus D. Three parallel office blocks were renovated, in part, to create ultra-modern and technology-enhanced learning spaces. Most spaces, including, different classroom types, social spaces, canteens, and the campus library are open plan in nature in an attempt to foster student-centred learning and the skills required for the 21st century workplace. The campus library contains both an individual and group study zone with furniture which is designed to enhance students' needs (e.g., soundproofed study carrels for silent individual learning and collaborative study desks with shared group screens). Key to the campus, is an inbuilt flexibility which allows students and instructors to choose different spaces for scheduled and unscheduled learning, depending on their needs.

As noted in Subsection 3.2.2., focus group data for qualitative Study 1 was collected between March 2017 and November 2017. Thus, qualitative data was collected from students and instructors who were predominantly based in Campuses A, B, and C. Quantitative data for Study 3 was collected between May 2019 and June 2019. As the users of Campus C transitioned to Campus D in September 2018, quantitative data was collected from students at Campuses A, B, and D.

3.5. Chapter Conclusions

Chapter 3 outlined the mixed methods approach adopted within this thesis. This included a description of the three empirical studies, the links between these studies, and how each study addressed the overall thesis aims. In addition, the author justified why a mixed methods approach was conducted over a solely quantitative or qualitative approach. The chapter moved on to reflect upon the type of mixed methods designs and highlighted the design which most closely aligns with the approach adopted within this thesis: a multiphase exploratory sequential design. The author then described his own considerations (the desire to develop practical implications and address the limitations of previous research), research worldview (pragmatism), and theoretical reflections which underpinned this mixed methods approach. The chapter moved on to consider the potential challenges which are faced when conducting mixed methods research, and how the author and research team addressed these challenges. The chapter finished by briefly outlining ethical considerations and describing the data collection sites from which participants were recruited in Studies 1 and 3.

The subsequent empirical chapters will present each of the empirical studies in turn: Study 1 (qualitative focus groups) will be presented in Chapter 4, Study 2 (qualitative systematic review) will be presented in Chapter 5, and Study 3 (quantitative questionnaire) will be presented in Chapter 6. This will be followed by a final Discussion and Conclusions chapter (Chapter 7) which unites the findings from each study to address the research questions.

4. CHAPTER FOUR

STUDY 1. UNDERSTANDING STUDENTS' EXPERIENCES OF THE PHYSICAL AND SOCIO-PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENT IN THEIR CAMPUS LEARNING AND TEACHING SPACES

4.1. Chapter Introduction

Previous quantitative research on the associations between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces is scarce. What little research has been conducted suffers from methodological and conceptual flaws.

First, it appears that researchers have selected environmental characteristics and outcomes that reflect their own interests and those of HEIs (e.g., course performance, class evaluations, and course evaluations). It is therefore unclear as to whether these environmental characteristics and outcomes are relevant to students' learning space experiences. This hinders the content validity of the constructs assessed (environmental perceptions and outcomes) and their corresponding measurement instruments. Secondly, both the constructs assessed in previous research and their corresponding measurement instruments are limited by a lack of established conceptual underpinnings. Researchers therefore appear to conceptualise environmental perceptions in an inconsistent and ad hoc manner (e.g., affective impressions, satisfaction with the environment, and/or perceived suitability of the environment). Such deficiencies may hinder the validity and reliability of the conclusions drawn from inferential statistical analyses using these instruments (Elf et al., 2016; Francis et al., 2016; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014).

To address such research limitations, several scholars have highlighted the value of the exploratory sequential mixed methods design (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Researchers who adopt this approach begin with a detailed qualitative study to explore the experiences of the

phenomena of interest with a smaller subsample from the 'target population' (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Francis et al., 2016). The resultant qualitative data can be used to inform the constructs assessed, conceptual underpinnings, and measurement instruments used or developed in a subsequent quantitative study (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). By ensuring the relevance of the constructs assessed, their conceptual underpinnings (e.g., person-environment transaction theories), and corresponding measurement instruments, the content validity and conceptual underpinnings of the subsequent quantitative research can be enhanced (Francis et al., 2016).

In addition to consulting the target population in order to enhance content validity, other scholars have recommended collecting qualitative data from 'content experts' or 'professionals', that is, experts who are involved in and have professional knowledge regarding the phenomena of interest (Francis et al., 2016). In the context of students' learning space experiences, HE instructors (i.e., academics who are involved in learning and teaching) may be viewed as content experts or professionals. Instructors both use campus learning and teaching spaces and are professionals who play a key role in students' learning and learning space experiences.

Indeed, previous research suggests that when suitable spaces are available for self-directed learning out with class, students play a major role in choosing both the type of learning activities that they engage in and the spaces which they use for those activities (Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Matthews et al., 2011). However, it may be the case that instructors play a greater role than students in determining both the types of space used, and learning and teaching activities adopted, in scheduled classes. This claim is supported by research which highlights that instructors often determine how learning and teaching spaces are used by themselves and their students for class activities, as a consequence of their learning and teaching philosophies (Lasry et al., 2014; Sawers et al., 2016). Given the variety of pedagogical approaches and spaces available for learning and teaching in HE, instructors' perspectives should not be disregarded when trying to understand the relevance of the physical and socio-physical environment to students' learning and teaching space experiences.

Based on best practice guidance on research approaches and design (e.g., Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011), it is argued that qualitative data collected from the perspectives of both students and instructors would enhance the understanding of students' experiences of learning and teaching

spaces. Specifically, this would provide insight into the (i) environmental characteristics of relevance to students' learning space experiences, (ii) learning and psychological consequences of relevance to students' learning space experiences, and (iii) relevance of person-environment transaction theories (cf. Chapter 2) to students' learning space experiences. The findings from such a qualitative study can then be used in subsequent studies to (i) assess the suitability of the instruments used in previous research to measure students' learning space perceptions and (ii) develop a new questionnaire (with high content validity and strong conceptual underpinnings) which measures students' learning space experiences.

Following the logic outlined above, the present study sought to address the first and second aims of this thesis. Overall, Study 1 aimed to understand students' learning space experiences, based on focus group data from both students and instructors at the target university. The analysis and interpretation of this data is guided by students' and instructors' subjective experiences and compared with previous research and person-environment transaction theories discussed in Chapter 2. Overall, Study 1 aimed to understand HE students' experiences of their learning and teaching spaces on their university campus and provide a framework for the subsequent empirical research conducted within this thesis. Specifically, Study 1 aimed to:

1. Understand how students perceive the physical and socio-physical environment in their university campus learning spaces;
2. Identify the relevant environmental characteristics of these spaces for students' learning space experiences;
3. Identify relevant learning and psychological consequences of the environment with respect to students' campus learning space experiences; and
4. Investigate the relevance of person-environment transaction theories in explaining students' learning space experiences.

4.2. Methods

4.2.1. Design

To address the research aims, qualitative data was collected via focus groups with students and instructors who were based at the target university. The data was analysed using Braun and Clarke's (2006, 2012, 2017) method of Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA). This section begins by providing a justification for the use of focus groups. Then, sample size considerations and characteristics are

presented along with a summary of ethical considerations. The data collection materials and procedure are then presented before concluding the section with a justification for the chosen approach to analysis, RTA, and an explanation of the analytical procedure.

4.2.2. Data collection methods

The use of focus groups

A focus group is a data collection method, typically defined as a small group interview, with between four and 10 participants (Berg, 2004; Krueger & Casey, 2014; Morgan, 1998; Sullivan et al., 2014). Focus group participants typically engage in a focused discussion on a particular topic, as guided by a moderator (Anderson, 1990; Berg, 2004; Denscombe, 2007). The aim of focus groups is to capture the dynamics between the participants, including, shared and unshared experiences (Kitzinger, 1994; Seamon & Gill, 2016; Sullivan et al., 2014). This could include, for example, perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and perceived consequences of the environment in campus learning and teaching spaces. In addition, the researcher can capture participants' conversations, largely devoid of their own participation; this empowers the participants and minimises researcher dominance (Seamon & Gill, 2016).

In the present study, the moderator provided initial examples of what constituted environmental characteristics. Nevertheless, the empowerment of the participants was deemed extremely pertinent, given that the present study aimed to understand the relevance of those factors to different campus user groups.

The rejected alternatives

An open-ended, qualitative, questionnaire was considered. However, this would not have offered the researcher sufficient flexibility to follow up on areas of interest in the participants' responses. Indeed, other researchers have noted ambiguous responses to open-ended survey questions about learning space experiences (Montgomery, 2013; Vaska et al., 2009). Individual interviews with students and instructors were also considered. However, the author had dual PhD and instructor (Associate Lecturer) roles and believed that students may, therefore, feel inhibited in a one-to-one situation. Similarly, the author believed that instructors may also feel inhibited in a one-to-one situation with a student. Consequently, students and instructors may have avoided sharing negative experiences with the physical and socio-physical characteristics of learning and teaching spaces. In

contrast, focus group situations are “generally characterised by dynamism and energy as people respond to the contribution of others” (Cameron, 2000, p. 84).

4.2.3. Participants

There is wide disagreement about the ideal number of participants for focus groups. Morgan (1988) proposes between six and eight participants, while Sullivan et al. (2014) suggest between six and 10. Furthermore, Krueger and Casey (2014) note that small focus groups with four to six participants are “becoming increasingly popular because the smaller groups are easier to recruit and host and are more comfortable for participants” (p. 67). Nevertheless, there appears to be general agreement that focus groups should be large enough to promote discussion but small enough for each participant to voice their experience(s) (Morgan, 1998; Krueger & Casey, 2014). Additionally, Krueger and Casey (2014) note that if the aim of the discussion is to understand particularly complex issues, fewer participants should be recruited per focus group.

Considering the practicalities of sample size and the complexity of learning space transactions, in the current study, between four and six participants were recruited per focus group. Three focus groups were conducted with students ($N = 15$) and four with instructors ($N = 20$) at the target university. Participants had experience engaging with one or more of three campuses at the target university: Campus A, B, and/or C. The participants represented a range of disciplinary areas. Contextual information for each participant, including, degree programme, year of study, and/or job role are presented in Tables A1 and A2 (Appendix A). Students were considered eligible if they were full- or part-time undergraduate or postgraduate students based at Campus A, B, and/or Campus C. Instructors were considered eligible if they were full- or part-time members of staff at Campus A, B, and/or C.

Student and instructor focus groups were conducted separately. This allowed the researcher to minimise the potential impact of power dynamics and hierarchical positioning of participants in the groups (i.e., students versus instructors) which may have inhibited or altered discussion of experiences on either side (UK Data Service, 2017). Furthermore, students and instructors are not a homogenous group. Indeed, several scholars purport that focus group participants should be relatively homogenous to allow for sufficient expression of both common and uncommon experiences, and contrasting opinions (Krueger & Casey, 2014).

Participants were recruited via convenience sampling and snowballing (Braun & Clarke, 2013). The project was advertised on social media (Facebook and Twitter) and via posters in the relevant campus libraries, social spaces, cafeterias and canteens, and corridors. Miniature posters were distributed by the author to students in lectures and to instructors at campus development events. Most of the students were recruited via social media and e-mail. Willing students shared their university e-mail addresses when the author attended their lectures. Most instructors heard about the study through word of mouth, including, from other participants.

4.2.4. Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was granted by the School of Media, Culture and Society Ethics Committee at the authors' institution. Most participants were e-mailed Participant Information Sheets in advance of the focus groups, which contained contact details for the author, lead supervisor, and Chair of the School Ethics Committee. All participants were asked to read printed copies of the Participant Information Sheets and sign Consent Forms, prior to the commencement of the respective focus group. Participants were informed that the identities of all other focus group participants should remain anonymous and were given the opportunity to ask questions. Once written and verbal consent was achieved, the author announced the starting of the audio-recording. All participants were provided with a Debriefing Sheet at the end of the focus group and given the opportunity to ask further questions. Participant Information Sheets, Consent Forms, and Debriefing sheets for both students and instructors are accessible in Appendix B.

4.2.5. Data collection materials and procedure

Each focus group followed a semi-structured format, focusing on a range of campus spaces and behaviours, facilitated via prompts. This semi-structured design allowed for flexibility when guiding the participants' discussions (Willig, 2013). At the beginning of each focus group, participants were asked to identify the spaces which were most important to them, the best and worst environmental attributes of those spaces, and to share these issues with the rest of the group. Participants were provided with campus maps and/or post-it-notes to aid with this task. Maps were only provided to

participants at Campuses A and C because maps of Campus B were not sufficiently detailed for participants to identify specific spaces.¹⁴

Participants were encouraged to discuss issues in a normal conversational manner with the researcher guiding the conversation, when necessary, to enhance the validity of the data (Warr, 2005). Questions pertaining to learning spaces adopted the following formats:

1. Could you describe the activities that you use these types of spaces for (including, silent study, group study, lecture rooms, seminar or tutorial rooms, practical classrooms, social spaces, corridors, outdoor spaces, entrance spaces, and other)?
2. What activities do you use the space for and why?
3. How do these activities differ compared to other spaces/activities?
4. What are the best and worst features of the spaces that you use for these activities?
5. If there was anything you could change about the spaces you use for these activities what would it be and why?

Three final questions addressed (i) the ways in which the campus physical environment was important to the participants, (ii) whether there was anything they would change about the campus as a whole and why, and (iii) whether there was anything that participants wanted to cover that was not addressed in the discussions. Additional questions aimed to provide prompts for participants when necessary. These included: “Could you expand upon X please?”, “What do you mean by X?”, and “Why was X important to you?” The full focus group schedule is available in Appendix C.

All focus groups took place between March 2017 and November 2017 and were moderated by the author, who had previous experience conducting focus groups with students. Thus, the author was able to minimise group dominance by single individuals and encourage all participants to contribute to discussions (Kruger & Casey, 2014; Merton, 1967; Seamon & Gill, 2014). All focus groups were audio-recorded using two Olympus Dictaphones and transcribed by the author in verbatim. Identifiers were anonymised in the transcription process, including, students’ naming instructors, instructors’ naming colleagues, students’ and instructors’ references to course modules, and

¹⁴ As campuses A and C contained more buildings than Campus B, the maps were more detailed, and illustrated each building. The maps for Campus B were far less detailed as they contained only one single building.

institutional identifiers (e.g., campus building names and locations). All participants were given pseudonyms.

4.2.6. Analytical procedure and decisions

Reflexive thematic analysis

The focus group transcripts were analysed using Braun and Clarke's (2006, 2012, 2017) RTA. RTA is a qualitative data analysis method which seeks to identify meaningful patterns in a qualitative dataset (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2012, 2017). Patterns are identified by the researcher through a six step, iterative and cyclical, process which entails: data familiarisation, generating initial codes, searching for themes, defining and naming themes, and producing a qualitative report (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2012, 2017).

Three considerations influenced the author's choice of RTA. First, RTA was flexible enough to align with the pragmatic research paradigm and the focus group data collection method. Secondly, the authors' varied knowledge on the discipline and the a priori review of the literature, brought inherent subjectivities (e.g., pre-conceived empirical and theoretical ideas). For instance, a literature review was conducted to serve as an empirical and theoretical base for the PhD research, prior to the commencement of this study. As such, the author believed that it was not possible to remove such preconceptions. Related to this, RTA places greater value on researcher subjectivity than the rejected alternatives (Braun & Clarke, 2012, 2020). Thirdly, the method allowed for a sufficient depth of analysis in order to explore learning space experiences, understand the value of theories of person-environment transactions, and compare students' and instructors' discussions.

Before outlining the analytical procedure, it is necessary to define the analytical terminology. In RTA, codes refer to the initial labels given to chunks of the data, while themes refer to meaningful and coherent data patterns that are centralised around a particular concept (Braun & Clarke, 2012, 2017; Braun et al., 2016). Braun and Clarke (2012, 2017) propose that codes and themes can be developed using inductive and deductive orientations. For Braun and Clarke, induction and deduction are opposites on a continuum. Inductive data coding and thematic development are driven by the data to a greater extent, as opposed to extant empirical or theoretical works. However, Braun and Clarke (2012, 2019) note that inductive orientation is seldom purely driven by data. In particular, the researcher's interpretation is always influenced, for example, by their cultural, empirical, and

theoretical backgrounds (Braun & Clarke, 2012, 2019). In contrast, deductive orientation is to a greater extent based on the author's existing knowledge and perspectives and is, therefore, driven to a greater extent by theory and empirical research (Braun & Clarke, 2012, 2017; Braun et al., 2016). In this study, the author created preliminary codes using a largely, though not purely, inductive process (i.e., with limited guidance from the extant literature). A more deductive approach was then used by the author to construct (i.e., search, review, define, and name) themes, drawing on extant empirical and theoretical works. In line with Braun and Clarke, themes did not emerge from the data. Instead, themes expressed the researchers' interpretation of the participants' experiences.

Further distinctions are made between semantic and latent levels of coding and thematising. Semantic codes and themes are developed at a descriptive level, while latent levels of coding and thematising refer to the development of codes and themes at a more conceptual level (Braun & Clarke, 2012). In the present study, initial notes and coding (steps 1-2 below) were conducted at a more semantic/descriptive level, while the search for, refinement, and defining of themes, was conducted at a more latent/conceptual level.

As per Braun and Clarke (2006, 2012, 2017), the author, first, familiarised himself with the data through immersion in the dataset. This immersive stage entailed listening and re-listening to the focus group audio-recordings, transcribing the data in colloquial language, and taking initial notes. During this first step, the author reflected on the dataset; noted points of interest, and highlighted connections between different participants and areas of the dataset (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2012, 2017). Secondly, the author developed a set of coherent codes (i.e., labels) which were systematically applied across the datasets.

Thirdly, the author searched the codes and corresponding data to create 'prototype' or 'candidate' primary themes and subthemes (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2012, 2017). Similar codes and their corresponding data were collated into meaningful clusters which reflected different aspects of the data. At this stage, initial primary and subthemes were compared to the extant literature to provide further clarity.

Fourthly, the author reviewed the themes in relation to the coded extracts and focus group dataset, separated existing subthemes where appropriated, and then collated the themes into a thematic map which considered the connections between primary themes and subthemes themes. Fifthly, the specific nature of both the primary and subthemes were clearly defined, then both primary and subthemes were given corresponding names/labels.

Sixthly, the themes were written in various reports and presentations (e.g., for supervisory meetings, MPhil to PhD Transfer Event Assessment, and two conference presentations). Compelling extracts were selected and related to the research questions, theoretical literature, and empirical literature. This served as a final stage of analysis to assess the themes both at an individual level and in relation to the final dataset (Braun & Clarke, 2012). In line with best practice (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2012, 2017), the analysis was iterative and cyclical, with the researcher moving between stages in a non-linear manner. The refinement and grouping of codes and themes were led by the author, alongside frequent consultation with the research team. Stages one to five were conducted using NVIVO 12, a software package for qualitative data analysis software. Example student and instructor transcripts are accessible in Appendix D. To illustrate the process of theme development, examples of initial notes, corresponding codes, subthemes, and primary themes are accessible in Table E1 (Appendix E).

The credibility of the themes was assessed through the preparation of written documents, presentations to and discussions with the author's supervisory team. In addition, the author's MPhil to PhD Transfer Event Assessment provided him the opportunity to produce a written report that was assessed by a psychologist external to the supervisory team. This additionally provided the author with an early opportunity to present and discuss the thematic findings with a wider academic audience as well as members of the wider university community (e.g., undergraduate students, postgraduate students, and academic library managers). Moreover, the author presented and discussed the analysis with a wider academic community at the target university's Learning, Teaching, and Research Conference. Finally, the author presented and discussed the themes with both environmental psychologists and architects at an international conference for people-environment transaction studies. Documents and presentations are available from the author upon request.

The rejected alternatives

The author considered numerous alternative qualitative approaches to, and methods, of analysis. These included three forms of qualitative content analysis (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005), coding reliability thematic analysis (e.g., Boyatzis, 1998), codebook (e.g., template) thematic analysis (Brooks et al., 2015), grounded theory (Charmaz, 2006; Glaser & Strauss, 1967), and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) (Smith et al., 2013). It is beyond the scope of this chapter to describe each of the approaches and methods. In summary, content analytic methods were rejected as they would not have allowed participants to adequately express their concerns (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). Coding reliability and codebook thematic analysis placed too great an emphasis on objectivity over subjectivity (e.g., cf. Braun & Clarke, 2020). Grounded theory and IPA offered little scope for deduction over induction, and interpretative phenomenological analysis places greater emphasis on homogeneity of participants and the individual experience as opposed to the collective group (Smith et al., 2013).

4.3. Findings

4.3.1. Overview of findings

This section presents findings from the RTA of students' and instructors' focus group data. Overall, this study aimed to understand students' experiences of the learning and teaching spaces in their university campus.

Students' learning space experiences could be considered with regard to two main types of activities and spaces. Specifically, students and instructors discussed both learning spaces which were used for scheduled classes and learning spaces that were used for self-directed learning out with the class. Learning activities within class could be considered as either individual (e.g., attending to lecture instruction) or collaborative (e.g., student-instructor interaction, full class discussion, and small group discussions). Learning activities out with scheduled classes could also be considered as individual (e.g., working alone) or collaborative (e.g., working in small groups on a shared activity or working in small groups on a separate activity).

Interestingly, when asked to identify the spaces which were most important to them on campus, students predominantly identified spaces that were used for out-of-class activities, including campus library spaces, social spaces, and specialist facilities (e.g., radio stations). Overall, the findings

address two major aspects of the learning space experience in relation to individual and collaborative learning activities, (i) perceptions and (ii) consequences, of the environment.

The first primary theme, *The Ideal versus Experienced Environment*, addressed how students and instructors perceive or conceptualise the environment in their campus learning spaces. Specifically, the theme reflects students’ perceptions of the degree of fit between their needs from the environment for a particular learning activity (ideal or optimal environment) and the demands of the environment within the space(s) which they use for that activity. The second primary theme was *Learning and Psychological Consequences* of the environment. This theme addressed students’ and instructors’ beliefs about the learning and psychological consequences of the environment with respect to their learning activities. Primary themes and their corresponding subthemes are presented in Table 1.

Primary and subthemes were interpreted as relative to one another. For example, perceptions of privacy characteristics were interrelated with acoustical, ambient, and spatial characteristics. Similarly, perceptions of the acoustical environment were sometimes seen to be a consequence of the spatial environment. Likewise, engagement in learning activities was discussed as a consequence of the environment.

Table 1.

Summary of primary themes and their corresponding subthemes

Primary themes	Subthemes
(1) The Ideal versus Experienced Environment	(a) Spatial and Ergonomic Fit
	(b) Acoustical Fit
	(c) Ambient Fit
	(d) Privacy Fit
	(e) Choice (Decisional Control)
(2) Learning and Psychological Consequences	(a) Engagement in Learning Activities
	(b) Cognitive-Affective Consequences
	(c) Quantity and Quality of Work

In the following subsections, Primary Theme 1 is introduced, followed by its five corresponding subthemes. Then, Primary Theme 2 is introduced, followed by its three corresponding subthemes. For each of the subthemes, the student perspective is presented, followed by the instructor perspective, to gain a more complete understanding of the student experience. After the two primary themes and their corresponding subthemes have been presented, the key differences between the students' and instructors' perspectives are discussed.

4.3.2. Primary Theme 1. The Ideal versus Experienced Environment

Overview

Underlying students' and instructors' discussions of the environment in their campus learning and teaching spaces, was the notion of congruence versus incongruence between the (i) students' needs for a particular learning activity and (ii) the demands of the environment. Students' and instructors' learning space perceptions can, therefore, be conceptualised as perceptions of fit or misfit between their needs and the demands of the environment. Following this logic and at a more interpretative level, students' and instructors' perceptions reflect the degree of fit between (i) the environment of the learning space that is used for a particular learning activity and (ii) the ideal or optimal environment for the same learning activity. While it was not intended to understand how instructors perceive the environment, their perspectives also support this interpretation.

Primary Theme 1 consisted of five subthemes representing ideal versus experienced conditions. These are outlined in Table 2, alongside corresponding codes and descriptions. Each subtheme is elaborated in the subsequent subsections.

Table 2.*Primary Theme 1: The Ideal versus Experienced Environment*

Subtheme	Corresponding codes
1a. Perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit	<p>Perceptions of spatial density (space size) and social density (number of users), furniture arrangement and seating position, desk size, and furniture comfort.</p> <p>Interrelated with Acoustical Fit and Privacy Fit (e.g., presence or absence of partitions which promote minimise input from and output to others).</p>
1b. Perceptions of Acoustical Fit	<p>Perceptions of acoustical characteristics: people-related and non-people-related acoustical inputs, including, noise from other people talking, noise from equipment (e.g., radio and ventilation systems), and noise the noise level/volume.</p>
1c. Perceptions of Ambient Fit	<p>Perceptions of temperature and air quality/ventilation, and lighting (natural and artificial). Also addressed aesthetics or attractiveness of space, including, the colours used and access to window views.</p>
1d. Perceptions of Privacy Fit	<p>Perceptions of privacy fit addressed input and output to other people, including, interruptions, visual distractions, being watched by others, and speech privacy (disturbing others), and the need for isolation versus being surrounded by others. Also included architectural privacy (e.g., opaque and non-opaque partitions) which could increase or decrease input from and/or output to others.</p> <p>Interrelated with spatial fit (e.g., barriers which enhance privacy) and acoustical fit (e.g., noise/acoustical input from others)</p>
1e. Perceptions of Choice (Decisional Control)	<p>Ability to choose suitable (e.g., preferred space) or alternative suitable spaces when preferred space does not meet needs.</p> <p>Closely intertwined with Subthemes 1a-1d. Ability to choose suitable spaces dependent on the space meeting requirements for spatial and ergonomic, acoustical, ambient, and privacy fit.</p>

Subtheme 1a. Perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit

Subtheme 1a addressed perceptions of fit between the requirements of different learning activities and the important spatial and ergonomic characteristics of the environment. The participants discussed several Spatial and Ergonomic characteristics that were relevant to their learning space experiences. These included furniture arrangements and seating position, spatial density (space size) and social density (number of users in a space), furniture comfort, and to a lesser degree the size of work surfaces (e.g., for spreading resources and/or writing).

The importance of furniture arrangements to students' learning space experiences was evident in the students' focus groups. Below, Ross explained how the furniture arrangement within large lecture rooms (tiered or inclined from front to back versus flat) can aid or hinder students' ability to view the instructors' presentation materials, a key requirement for instructional activities:

Ross: The raked ones aren't so bad but ... at the minute we're in ... in a big, high capacity ... GT [general teaching] room on the top floor and ... you could probably fit 200 in there ... it's a large room, it's got two projectors, but ... it's not raked ... So you've got the same number of people that you would normally have in like a theatre styled lecture theatre but you can't see the screen because ... you know am [I'm] six foot two and a [I] can't see it when a sit at the back ... that's problematic a [I] think.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

In Ross' experience, non-tiered (flat) furniture arrangements in classrooms are incongruent with the requirements of lecture theatres, specifically, his and other students' need to view the instructors' presentation materials. Nevertheless, Ross suggested that this experience of incongruence between students' needs for instructional learning and the classroom furniture arrangement is not static; instead, this congruence/incongruence changes from one term to the next as a function of the furniture arrangement within the specific classroom space that is used (flat versus tiered).

Students also highlighted the importance of using spaces where the furniture is arranged to facilitate small group learning activities when using campus learning spaces for more 'collaborative' activities. Kayla discussed the ways in which the furniture arrangement (e.g., round tables versus rows) could aid or hinder learning in small groups:

Kayla: I like the rooms in the D block, they're great for group work ... they're smaller, the tables are more compact, so you've got more tables rather than a table, a row full of 20 or something like that. You've got maybe five or six and you can do more group work like that. It's better.

(Student

, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

Kayla explained the ease of interacting in small groups when using the active learning classrooms, where the furniture is designed or arranged (e.g., small round desks) to be congruent with group discussions. Kayla compared this congruence with the incongruence between ‘traditional/instructional’ classrooms with straight row furniture arrangements and group learning activities. According to Kayla, such straight row arrangements can place constraints on the ability of group members to interact. It can be inferred from the students’ perspective that the ideal furniture arrangement for small group learning would allow students to gather around, face other group members, and verbally interact with ease.

Other spatial issues which were interrelated with furniture arrangements pertained to density, including, interactions between spatial density (size of space) and social density (number of people in a space). For instance:

Jill: The lecturer is usually, usually having a discussion with the class ... so everybody’s kinda [kind of] trying to have their own wee like bit in to see how they’re getting on with their reflective reports and stuff ... we decided that putting it [the desks and chairs] in a kinda [kind of] square and having the lecturer sitting right at the end and everybody else is round about her is gonna [going to] be the most effective way for her to hear and see everybody talking but again it was really small and it was really cramped ... [I] just find it unpleasant ... am [I’m] just dead claustrophobic ... and as Cara said [referring to an earlier discussion], it might not affect her learning ‘cause she’s not always bothered about the room sizes or whatever but then there is some people that are really claustrophobic like maself [myself] and a [I] just like, you just can’t help it.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

Above, Jill described an experience in which the lack of sufficient classroom space relative to the number of students in the class was incongruent with and, therefore, constrained students’ and instructors’ ability to reconfigure the classroom to comfortably facilitate class discussions (collaborative learning). Interestingly, Jill noted how physical and spatial density may be less important to other students (Cara: see above).

Other issues raised by the students which pertained to subtheme 1a, albeit to a lesser extent, included ergonomic fit (i.e., furniture comfort) and the size of desks within learning spaces. Of the students who commented on the importance of furniture comfort, comfortable furniture was valued, while uncomfortable furniture was perceived negatively (e.g., “The chairs are rock hard” and “you end up back to the one place where you’ve got comfortable seating”, Students, Campus A, Focus Group 1). In a pertinent example, Ross emphasised the importance of furniture comfort within classrooms designed for lecture instruction:

Ross: Yeah there's no left-handed ones in Campus B ... I'm left-handed so I have to have two seats to myself which means av [I've] got nae [no] pals ... that's like an actually serious annoying thing ... that's in all lecture theatres, there's no left-handed ones in any ... it sounds like a really minor picky thing but imagine you just couldn't use a table. Like it's really really annoying.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

Here, Ross described how the lack of chairs with left-handed swivel desks were incongruent with his ability to comfortably engage in the lecture activities (e.g., take notes). While Ross highlighted that he can 'cope' with such incongruence between his ergonomic needs for lecture activities and the classroom furniture, his comments emphasise the frustration and the potential alienation that he suffers when doing so.

In another example, Susan briefly described the importance of having sufficient workspace (desk size) for learning activities, specifically in relation to the group learning spaces in her campus library:

Susan: I like the group rooms ... you have like a kinda [kind of] big table as well for all of your scripts.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

In this short excerpt, Susan emphasised the congruence between the requirements of group learning and the size of the work surface, allows her to sufficiently organise her learning materials.

Turning to the instructor perspective, the importance of furniture arrangements in relation to students' learning space experiences was evident. In the excerpt below, Cal emphasised how the furniture arrangement in classrooms used for large group instructional activities (tiered versus flat) can facilitate or impede students' ability to view the instructors' presentation materials:

Cal: We've got as a say like modules with hundreds on it ... it's awkward with the number because ... Albus Hall's [lecture room] is one as well where ... they've [students] each got an individual desk to sit on, it's not an inclination up ... but it's a massive big room and a [I] don't know how people at the back can see the screen.

(Instructor, Campus C, Focus Group 7)

Above, Cal expressed his confusion at the flat furniture arrangement in one of the main lecture classrooms in Campus B. For Cal, the flat floor and non-tiered arrangement is incongruent and interferes with a key requirement of lecture activities, students' ability to visualise the instructors' presentation materials.

Additionally, instructors emphasised the importance of furniture arranged to facilitate interaction when using classroom learning spaces for collaborative activities (e.g., full class discussion and small

group learning). Below, Don explained that straight row furniture arrangements can hinder class discussion:

Don: Well I think it comes back to what I was saying. You probably don't then use Powerpoint facilities, I mean you're usually not doing a presentation, so you want a discussion more in the realms so it's often more to do with the layout of the room really to encourage the students to interact rather than having the desk layout in rows so that's ... one of the big problems.

(Instructor, Campus A, Focus Group 4)

Specifically, Don emphasised the incongruence between the requirements of class discussion (interaction among students and instructors) and straight row classrooms. This is mirrored in an extract from Jodie who compared the ways in which round tables versus straight rows can aid or hinder small group interaction within class:

Jodie: The furniture plays a massive role and emmm that's one of the reasons why a [I] like the active learning studio 'cause it's not setup in the way that some of the other labs emmm upstairs are where, you know, it's very linear? ... you're kinda [kind of] looking behind the massive Mac screens to see people's faces? ... You know the layout of the room, this kind of conference table [in the focus group room] in itself can sometimes be really useful for generating discussion.

(Instructor, Campus B, Focus Group 6)

In the excerpts above, it can be inferred that both class discussion (Don) and small group discussion (Jodie) require furniture arrangements which allow 'interactors' to visually engage with one another. Jodie acknowledged the ease of interaction in classrooms with round desks which allow students and instructors to visually engage with one another (e.g., active learning classroom and focus group room), as opposed to straight row furniture arrangements with obstacles which obscure visual engagement ("massive ... screens"). Interestingly, it is clear from Jodie's comment that this experience congruence/incongruence is not static and changes as a function of the classroom space that she is using, for example, the "active learning studio" where the furniture is intentionally arranged to facilitate collaborative learning.

Interrelated spatial issues which were discussed by instructors included the ways in which both physical and social density could interact to aid or hinder students' and instructors' ability to rearrange the classroom furniture in such a way that suits collaborative learning activities:

Ann: The biggest challenge we have with any space that we get ... is ... we do like group work, so we want the students to break up into small groups but part of me knows if you've got 30 students [then] there's capacity for 30 desks, 30 chairs and 30 students, and it doesn't give an awful lot a [of] flexibility to kinda [kind of] move round about ... because of the nature of some of the work that we're trying to do ... it can be a bit of a challenge.

(Instructor, Campus B, Focus Group 6)

Above, Ann highlighted how she and her students are often assigned to classrooms which lack sufficient space relative to the number of students. For Ann, this is incongruent with the requirements of small group learning, specifically her ability to circulate between and consult each individual group of students. While Ann highlights that she attempts to ‘cope’ with such discrepancies by asking students to “breakout” of the classroom, this too is often incongruent with her approach to group learning because it is difficult to engage with those groups of students who are no longer confined to the classroom.

Other issues raised by the instructors in relation to Subtheme 2b, albeit to a lesser extent, pertained to ergonomics (furniture comfort) and desk size. As an expert in ergonomic matters (physiotherapist), Cal explained:

Cal: I don’t think any lecture theatre’s comfortable for students to sit in. You know, ergonomically it’s no [not] the best sort of layout for your back for a start? As a physiotherapist saying that, it’s no [not] the best ergonomic situation to be in eh hh the way they make people sit.

(Instructor, Campus C, Focus Group 7)

In Cal’s professional opinion, the lack of comfortable seating is incongruent with the requirements of instructional activities (e.g., sitting for one-to-two hours while writing notes, listening to the instructor, and viewing presentation materials). In another example, Mike briefly commented on the importance of having sufficient desk space for lecture activities:

Mike: Well they’ve had me teaching in M Block at the bottom of the Wetherspoon Building which is a bl**dy awful lecture room cause there’s nowhere for the students to write basically. Even with the refurb it’s like a tiny cramped little space.

(Instructor, Campus A, Focus Group 4)

Above, Mike highlighted how the incongruence between students’ needs for instructional activities (the ability to take notes) are incongruent with the environment (size of work surface).

Subtheme 1b. Perceptions of Acoustical Fit

Subtheme 1b focused on perceptions of fit between the requirements of learning activities and important acoustical characteristics of the environment in the campus spaces that were used for those activities. Acoustical input was viewed by the participants as either desirable (i.e., wanted or congruent with learning activities) or undesirable (i.e., unwanted or incongruent with learning activities).

Students discussed several important characteristics of the acoustical environment, including, both people-related and non-people-related acoustical input. Specifically, these acoustical inputs were noise from other people talking and noise from nearby equipment (e.g., ventilation, radio systems, and music videos). Linked to both people- and non-people-related inputs, was the noise level or volume within the space.

Several students articulated the importance of minimal irrelevant acoustical input (e.g., peer conversations or noise from the corridor) when using campus learning and teaching spaces for instructional learning activities:

Kim: I had my lecture on Tuesday and there were people ... whispering on one side but everyone could hear it apart from Lewis [instructor] so like it got to the stage where people were shouting at them to like be quiet and stuff cause it was our revision before this exam and like ... Lewis couldn't hear it cause he's down there ... he couldn't do anything and so people missed half the lecture ... he had no idea and ... it was like our last exam lecture ...

Ivor: We had that problem with our exam preparation on Monday ... people were talking whilst

Jill: The lecturer was talkin' [talking]

Ivor: The lecturer was talking and it's got to be one of thee most annoying things 'cause you do, you just get so distracted.

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

For the students above, it is evident that lecture instructional activities require minimal irrelevant acoustical input because this can interfere with learning and teaching dynamics, i.e., students' ability to hear relevant acoustical input from the instructor. However, these requirements are incongruent with Jill, Ivor, and Kim's experiences of two separate lectures earlier in the same week. Interestingly, the intertwining of spatial and acoustical perceptions is evident, whereby instructors are unable to hear and therefore act upon acoustical distractions because of the size of the space, the arrangement of the space, and their position within the space (Kim: "Lewis couldn't hear it 'cause he's down there ... he had no idea").¹⁵

This intertwining is mirrored in a later reflection, during which Kim suggested that the ideal furniture arrangement for lecture instructional activities would enhance the visibility and audibility of all students, so that the instructor can identify 'acoustically disruptive' students. In such a space, the

¹⁵ Undesirable acoustical input during lecture activities was described by some students as a result of spatial configurations which did not facilitate visual and audio contact between the instructor and all learners.

room may be wider and shorter than in traditional lecture theatres, have a gentler incline, and the furniture could be arranged in semi-circular rows which 'curve around' the instructor:

Kim: A lot of people at different unis, like they have more circle shape so it's not as high and people are more getting like the same like view so they can all see and they can hear the lecturer but it also means that it's, like people are less likely to talk because the like the lecturer can see them more, can hear them more, what they're saying so I feel like that would take away some of the problems.

(Student, Campuses A and C, Focus Group 2)

Several students also articulated the importance of minimal acoustical input when using campus learning spaces for self-directed individual learning activities out with class. Some final (fourth) year undergraduate students, for instance, discussed the benefits of using the 'silent zones' in their campus libraries for self-directed individual learning activities:

Amy: You can concentrate ... That's one of the best floors I think in the sense that it is silent. It's quiet and people do respect that... there's a seat upstairs [at the main entrance atrium] and people don't know about it but it's so super-quiet.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

And:

Kate: I think we'll be using them [silent/independent study spaces] more because we're going into 4th year ...

Ross: If you just want to be left alone, like they're really harsh about it down there. They [library staff] really don't let you annoy people, which is great.

(Students, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

For these students, the silent zones of their campus libraries were perceived as congruent with the requirements for individual learning out with class, specifically, the need for little or minimal acoustical input. The comment that Kate and Ross intend to make more frequent use of the silent study zones as they progress into the final year of their degree programme, suggests that their needs from and perceptions of the environment will change as a function of their academic progression. This suggests that requirements for learning activities and therefore the demands that students place on the acoustical environment are variable, as opposed to static, for the same students over time and change as a function of circumstances (e.g., year group).

In contrast, several second-year undergraduate students articulated the opposite requirement. For these students, the ideal acoustical environment for self-directed individual learning activities offered a balance between too much and too little acoustical inputs (sound level):

Ian: I can't do silent because I can't study ... I just don't like that silent atmosphere.

Emily: I can do both. I do like the silent and a wee bit of hussle bussle.

Ian: I need a [an] atmosphere.

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

Fortunately, for Ian and Emily, the hub social and learning space on Campus A is congruent with their requirements for self-directed, individual, learning. However, excerpts from Jill and Scott highlighted that their balance between too much and too little acoustical inputs can, on occasion, be difficult to find:

Jill: Am [I'm] not like a fussy person. Like am [I'm] not pernickety. A [I] understand people like talk and have group discussions or whatever but it was like last week and there was a group up the stairs that was sitting behind emmm maself [myself] and Marita emmm and they were just so loud because they were laughing and like pure "who-ha-ing" like constant... A [I] don't want to be in like a pure isolated little corner just doing ma [my] own wee work and bein' [being] told to "shoosh". Emmm so a [I] do like background noise like Kim said as well. It's just a [I] don't like people screaming and going crazy.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

And:

Scott: A lot of people do tend to treat it as a social area, fair enough. But emmm if you play your music and start talking about makeup and various places then you know? Fair enough people talk but you know, sometimes it's too loud? So maybe they could tone it down a bit. And then when you do ask them to quieten down they look at you like you've got two heads.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

For Jill and Scott, the congruence between the acoustical requirements of their individual learning activities and the demands of the acoustical environment varies over time (e.g., "last week" and "sometimes it's too loud").

Other sources of important acoustical input discussed by students included undesirable noise from equipment when using campus spaces for out-of-class learning activities:

Scott: E Labs are the same. There's ones you can go in and you can hear the fan moving

Amy: The fan's annoying.

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

And:

Jason: A lot of folk won't agree with me on this one but ... the comm [radio] ... can be a tad [a bit] too loud

Emily: Yeh it's a tad too loud ...

Karen: If you're there for more than an hour then you've heard ... the same songs like a million times ... and that really annoys me ... it's horrible ... and it's the same ones like every day and if I'm sitting in

there it's driving me insane but then at least it's better than sitting at the main entrance because all that music's really depressing.

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

Above, Scott, Amy, Jason, Emily, and Karen explained how noise from non-people-related sources (equipment, such as, ventilation and music from the radio) is incongruent with their ability to sufficiently engage in learning activities.

From the instructors' perspective, acoustical characteristics pertained to noise from other people (e.g., talking) and the background noise level within a learning space. Several instructors articulated the importance of minimal irrelevant acoustical input (e.g., peer conversations and noise from the corridor) when using campus learning spaces for lecture instructional activities. For instance:

Dan: Because a [of] ... the classical style of lecture there are a lot of people in the theatre and there's a dynamics going on all over the place we can't control so ... students are disrupted by local conversations all over the place so if there's a smaller number in a room where you can see everyone and it's more brightly lit, a [I] find that easier emmm if a [I] can see people on their phone you know a [I] can check with them.

(Instructor, Campus B, Focus Group 6)

In the example above, for Dan, lecture instruction requires minimal irrelevant acoustical input because this can interfere with students' ability to hear relevant acoustical input from the instructor (himself). However, these requirements can be incongruent with Dan's experience of campus lecture theatres. Interestingly, the intertwining of environmental characteristics (acoustical, socio-spatial, and ambient) is evident, whereby Dan notes that smaller class sizes and brighter lighting would allow him to identify and manage acoustically disruptive students.

Similarly, Ted highlighted the difficulties of noise from people in the corridors caused by his attempts to cope with poor classroom ventilation. Such irrelevant acoustical input was important, even when engaging in collaborative learning activities:

Ted: Ventilation's a problem. If you open the door then noise becomes a problem because there's comings and goings, people shouting down the corridor and things like that.

(Instructor, Campus C, Focus Group 7)

Ted's comment suggests that incongruence between the learning activity and the thermal environment, may lead him to open the classroom door for ventilation. This can introduce undesirable acoustical input from people in the corridor and create further incongruence between the environment of the classroom and the requirements of learning and teaching (minimal irrelevant acoustical input). An intertwining between perceptions of the acoustical and thermal environment is

evident.

Moreover, several instructors highlighted the importance of background noise levels in the campus library 'silent zones' to students' learning space experiences:

Mike: It's too noisy

Gina: It is noisy

Lindsay: Av [I've] heard students complain that there's not a quiet bit in the library

Mike: Well there is but it's still noisy, it's a designated quiet area but it's still noisy

Don: It's not as good as it used to be for studying. I mean the way that it's been reconfigured with the hub [below] does make it noisy.

(Instructors, Campus A, Focus Group 4)

From the perspectives of these instructors and their students, self-directed individual learning spaces require minimal acoustical input. Ironically, according to the perspectives of the instructors above and those of their students, the 'silent zone' in the Campus A library was incongruent with this requirement.

Subtheme 1c. Perceptions of Ambient Fit

Subtheme 1c addressed the congruence between the requirements of learning activities and important ambient characteristics of the campus spaces used for those learning activities. These additional ambient characteristics included temperature and air quality (including ventilation), lighting intensity (lighting in general, artificial lighting, and natural lighting), and aesthetic variables such as the use of colour within the spaces and window views to outside spaces.¹⁶

From the students' perspective, the importance of the thermal comfort and ventilation/air quality was clear:

Kayla: I think it [the hub social and learning space] can be cold but it's not too bad ... I think the library's always cold, I don't like that ...

Emily: The library though ... I don't really study you know if I'm going to go and read over notes and stuff like that ... because it's too cold.

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

¹⁶ Acoustical variables may also be considered as ambient environmental characteristics but because of the emphasis on different aspects of the acoustical environment (sound level, people-related and non-people-related sounds), subthemes on acoustical and ambient fit were presented separately.

In the excerpt above, for instance, Kayla and Emily highlighted that learning activities out with class require what they perceive to be a comfortable temperature. However, Kayla noted that the hub social learning space which she and Emily use most often for out-of-class study activities can occasionally ('can be') be incongruent with her thermal preferences. This suggests that there are variations in Kayla's perceptions of the thermal environment, within the same space, over time. Likewise, the importance of the thermal environment is emphasised by Emily's explicit acknowledgement of her attempts to avoid campus spaces where she perceives the thermal environment as incongruent with her requirements for learning.

Interestingly, other students in the same focus group described the opposite thermal sensation ("too cold" versus "too warm") in the Campus A library space:

Amy: But to me it's [the library] too warm, it's not too cold for me.

Ian: The library is warm.

Amy: Especially because I stay mostly on the third floor and it gets so warm in there, and it's good because ... compared to other buildings there's a lot of natural light but ... I think it's really warm.

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

This discrepancy is suggestive of variation in participants' experiences and perceptions of the same spaces. However, it is worth noting that Amy, unlike Emily, is willing to continue using the library space despite the thermal discomfort that she experiences. While the qualitative nature of this study limits the conclusions that can be drawn, these findings suggest that Amy may have placed less importance on the thermal environment and greater demands on environmental characteristics which she perceives to be more important for learning (e.g., natural lighting). Thus, Amy may prefer to utilise spaces which are more congruent with her need for natural light, even if they are incongruent with her thermal preferences. Alternatively, it is plausible that while Amy perceived the learning space to be "too warm", the temperature was not extreme enough to render the space unsuitable for her learning.

The importance of a comfortable temperature was mirrored in students' discussions of classroom spaces:

Emily: G220 [lecture theatre] ... It's probably the best because I cannot study comfortably if I'm cold and generally every single room I have been in is cold. It's always cold. Emmm and that's the most, that's the warmest for me.

Karen: G Block's always really warm.

Emily: There's no draft.

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

It is inferred from the discussions above, that the ideal thermal environment for learning is one that students perceive to be comfortable with sufficient ventilation.

Leading on from the thermal environment are perceptions of congruence and incongruence between the luminous (lighting) environment and learning activities. Across all student focus groups, participants highlighted the importance of having sufficient natural light and less artificial light. A combination of 'too much' artificial lighting and 'too little' natural lighting was perceived negatively by the students:

Susan: The ones upstairs have windows ... so they're much better than this one. This one is particularly a bad one ...

Ross: Did you pick this on purpose as an example?

Researcher: ... is there anything that you ... would change about the campus as a whole?

Susan: More windows

Sarah: ... Definitely more windows and less of this artificial light.

(Students, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

And:

Amy: But there is no windows. I hate the fact that there's no windows. It feels like you're in a pub ... with no natural lighting. And there's all these artificial lights and they just give you a headache, then make me tired and sleepy. Even in here, you know? Like, wow!

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

The excerpts above suggest that learning activities require a balance between too much artificial lighting and too little natural lighting. However, this is incongruent with students' experiences. Indeed, Amy's comparison of the largest lecture classroom on Campus A to "a pub" suggests that she perceives the space as unfit for learning and teaching, due to the lack of natural over artificial lighting.

Aesthetic features of the environment were also considered by some students to be important and included window views to outside spaces and the use of colour within the learning space:

Ross: Emmm you know if you were to sit in a [class]room like this ... which is ... windowless and fairly clinical-like, an unpleasant room like this ... you don't want to linger and you don't want to spend a lot of time working in there. Whereas if ... you get a bit of natural light ... there are birds that come in and it's quite pleasant. And they did, a couple of years ago they cleaned it out and put new plants in

and it's quite a nice wee area to look at [secret garden] ... it convinces you to stay and learn [laughs] rather than go home.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

And:

Susan: I prefer upstairs ones [classrooms] than down here. I just feel like when you're further up and you can see outside and you can see like the woods and the – or the river or whichever side of the building you're on

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

And:

Karen: The microbiology labs are amazing aren't they?

Ian: ... that level is better compared to the chemistry labs ... the bottom labs are more colourful ...

Emily: all the windows are on one side

Ian: it opens up the room. There are all the windows, The chemistry labs and the biomed labs are ...

Karen: very plain

Ian: old looking labs

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

And:

Amy: But it's good like, you could have an extra window but at least like they've done the new colours like in this room so it's quite a nice environment. I think it looks like a happy place, you know? All the colours?

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

It is clear from the excerpts above that for several students, learning requires or can be enhanced by 'pleasant' (attractive) spaces, with window views to outside and bright colours. Yet, it is clear that the spaces used by students vary in terms of 'aesthetic congruence'. Interestingly, Amy noted an intertwining of 'colour' and 'window views'; this suggests that in her experience, the absence of one aesthetic feature may be offset or mitigated by the presence of another.

Turning to the instructors' perspective, the importance of the thermal environment in relation to students' learning space experiences became apparent. By way of illustration:

Kay: You can't, you can open the window, a don't know, in the Clements Building if you open the window it creates like a wind tunnel rather than ... some ventilation and you feel like there's nothing you can really do to control it.

Cal: ... The environment is not productive for learning because people were sitting sweating and always needing drinks. People, you can see them sort'a [sort of] always drifting off. Whether it's just me boring them a [I] don't know but a [I] put it down to more the heat.

(Instructors, Campus C, Focus Group 7)

And:

Don: The worst from my point of view is the internal rooms where you've maybe got a two hour lecture on the inside of of the block, no windows so the students are, well you've got to leave the door open to get air and then of course you get the noise from the corridors and the students fall asleep because they can't get any air and it's so stuffy because they're just desperate and there's no natural light. Those rooms are awful to teach in for a long period.

(Instructor, Campus A, Focus Group 4)

In the excerpts above, several instructors suggested that learning activities require a comfortable temperature. However, their experience is often incongruent with these requirements, and they are 'forced' to use spaces which are 'too warm' and have insufficient 'ventilation' for learning activities. Interestingly, the interrelations between temperature, ventilation, air quality, acoustics, and illumination are evident, whereby increasing ventilation may reduce the temperature to a more comfortable level (opening a window), reduce the amount of natural lighting (closing the blinds), or introduce undesirable acoustical input from others (opening the door).

Leading on from the thermal environment, across all the instructor focus groups, the importance of artificial and natural light was clear. Too much light and too little light were perceived negatively:

Evan: I think none of them are very well lit actually in the university. I think that's maybe a bit of a problem. My experience ... when I first came to this campus I just felt like ... that was the issue with like rooms that ... don't have any like natural light in them ... and it doesn't give you a very nice sense actually, artificial lights.

R: So what problems do you think that might create?

Evan: It ... maybe feels a bit kinda that you're contained actually ... when you go into the Collins Building reception ... some the [newly refurbished] rooms there, it feels light, it feels open, it feels happy.

(Instructors, Campus A, Focus Group 5)

Evan highlighted how a 'positive' learning space requires sufficient natural lighting. While his experiences of classrooms on Campus A are often incongruent with these requirements for learning, Evan noted how several of the new 'refurbished' spaces alleviate this issue. This suggests that Evan and his students' experiences of the ambient environment, vary as a function of the learning space that they are using.

Interestingly, Ted highlighted the intertwining between different ambient environmental characteristics:

Ted: Heating, lighting, and ventilation in this building. It almost always conspires against what you're planning to do with students. Almost always ... I find that wherever I'm timetabled, it's the side where

the sun's shining in and then a canny [I cannot] get the blinds to work and then the heat in the room really heats up and sometimes the windows work ... if you open the door then noise becomes a problem because there's comings and goings in the corridor and things like that.

(Instructor, Campus C, Focus Group 7)

For Ted, learning and teaching activities require an optimal thermal and luminous environment with minimal acoustical input. Yet, this is incongruent with Ted's typical experience, whereby the ambient characteristics combine to create an overall ambient environment which is incongruent with learning and teaching activities. Noticeably, Ted highlighted that the ambient environment "almost always conspires against" learning and teaching, which implies that occasionally, the learning and teaching spaces meet his needs. This is in line with earlier notions that learning space perceptions vary over time and circumstances, for example, as a function of changes to the environment or the use of different spaces.

To a lesser extent, other ambient environmental characteristics which were discussed in the instructor focus groups included window views to outside and the use of colour (i.e., the attractiveness) of the learning space:

Jodie: Maybe furniture again just exactly what you said, the arrangement of the furniture obviously, but you know brightly coloured furniture? ... A [I] remember seeing they [those] improvements ... in the active learning centre in Campus A and they just Ikea-fied the place and you know it can just be a simple thing that makes a big difference.

(Instructor, Campus B, Focus Group 6)

And:

Patrick: A [I] like rooms with windows ... it's the freedom isn't it? The idea that, they [the students] can look out the window if they want.

(Instructor, Campus A, Focus Group 5)

And:

Leanne: You know A've [I've] just noticed this room has no windows but it has a glass door and this is a nice room

Patrick: That's something isn't it?

Leanne: A [I] think it's because it's a fresh new [painted], newly done up room, it's for me, maybe it's more to do with the state of the room ...

Evan: Décor's poor in general isn't it?

(Instructors, Campus A, Focus Group 5)

It is clear from the excerpts above that, for several instructors, learning and teaching requires or could be enhanced by 'pleasant' (attractive) spaces with window views to outside and bright colours. In addition, the spaces used by the instructors vary in terms of congruence. While Patrick highlighted

the importance of window views for learning, in a later discussion, he and Leanne noted the interrelationships between the use of colour and window views. This suggests that they believe the presence of one ambient feature (e.g., bright colours) may mitigate against the absence of another (e.g., windows views).

Subtheme 1d. Perceptions of Privacy Fit

Subtheme 1d addressed perceptions of fit between learning activities and important aspects of privacy.

Students' privacy concerns reflected both input from and output to others. Specifically, their concerns reflected students' requirements to be isolated from versus surrounded by others. Discussions by students addressed several aspects of privacy, suggesting these are important to their learning space experiences.

This included people-related noise for both classroom and out-of-class activities (acoustical privacy). It is worth noting the overlap between perceptions of the acoustical and privacy fit. Specifically, isolation includes the need to isolate oneself from other people talking. However, since privacy addressed the other types of input and output described below (e.g., visual privacy), privacy was considered as a separate theme. Other types of privacy discussed by students focused specifically on out-of-class learning activities and included seeing other people moving, being observed by others (observational privacy), the ability to speak without disturbing others (speech privacy), and interruptions from learning activities by others e.g., class peers (task privacy). Binding each of these together was architectural privacy (e.g., partitions, curtains, and fogged glass). Not all students however, preferred to be isolated from others, with some preferring to be surrounded by other people when engaging in out-of-class learning activities.

As highlighted in relation to Subtheme 1a, several students discussed the importance of minimal acoustical input from others when engaging in individual learning activities (i.e., acoustical privacy):

Kate: Well if someone's ... recording in the middle room [radio station] and someone walks in the door to go to the right hand room you can hear them coming through and talking and shouting and that can be like lecturers and stuff like that as well. So ... you need to stop your recording and go again.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

And:

Sarah: But a [I] would say because it is next to the atrium a lot of the noise sort of bleeds through into the quiet study area as well so that's not exactly ideal at busy times.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

Yet, Kate and Susan described experiences of learning spaces which were incongruent with their need for acoustical privacy. Here, the notion of architectural privacy is also evident in terms of poor soundproofing between the radio studio rooms, as well as between the library and atrium social space and canteen.

In relation to classroom spaces, acoustical privacy discussions concerned isolation of the class from the acoustical inputs of those who are not in the class. For instance:

Jill: and you don't want to ... [ask] "oh can you just leave that door open?" Because then you hear everybody

Ivor: everybody from other classes

Jill: out in the corridor and stuff

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

However, incongruent with the requirement for acoustical privacy, in Jill and Ivor's experience, a choice must be made between the need to ventilate uncomfortably warm classrooms, and the need to maintain acoustical privacy. Here, the interrelationships between ambient and socio-physical characteristics are clear: poor ventilation may lead to insufficient acoustical privacy.

From the students' perspectives, the importance of being able to speak without disturbing others (speech privacy) when engaging in collaborative learning out with class was also evident. Specifically, it could be inferred that the ideal learning space would allow students to converse without the 'worry' of disturbing others. For example:

Amy: It's not a quiet zone so you can talk ... and people ... expect it to be quite loud so that's good ... you CAN talk without disturbing anyone.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

And:

Jill: Every time ... [I'm] studying or doing an essay or something am [I'm] with another student so we do talk ... we will discuss ... but a [I] can't do that in the silent study area or else al [I'll] disrupt people that's working alone.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

And:

Ivor: If I'm doing something in a group ... I don't want to be interrupting other people that are there ... so I would rather just have access to other spaces that aren't seen as communal spaces as it were.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

For the participants above, group and peer learning required speech privacy. Amy, Jill, and Ivor described how the library group study zones (Amy and Jill) and empty classroom spaces (Ivor) are congruent with their need for speech privacy when engaging in group and peer learning. Jill compares this with the silent study spaces of her campus library. Jill chooses not to use such spaces because the expectation for silence and individual activities is incongruent with her need to engage in peer discussion.

In another example, for Ivor, self-directed individual learning out with class requires isolation from class peers:

Ivor: I don't find the uni [university] as useful for me when it comes to studying ... it's too noisy or it's too much going... if you've got someone coming in from your class [they] can be talking so I prefer to be away from anyone in the class that way I'll actually do it.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

However, this need is incongruent with Ivor's use of his campus learning spaces, where he has experienced interruptions from his learning activities by class peers, i.e., a lack of task privacy.

In addition to acoustical input from others, acoustical output to others, and interruptions, several students highlighted the relevance of visual privacy when studying out with the classroom environment. In the extract below, Susan and Sarah described the 'private' group study spaces in their campus library:

Susan: Only thing that is annoying about those rooms is that like when you're in the room and you can see people looking in on you ... 'What're you doing? Why is that like that?' It's just like you're sitting in there because people will be looking for a room so they'll like look on the door for the ... schedule bookings ... so they'll look in to see if anyone's in there so immediately you're sitting there, you're drawing your picture of a giraffe or whatever.

Sarah: And you can feel someone's eye on you.

Susan: And you can feel your eyes of this person being like 'I study nursing and you study – you're drawing a giraffe? I feel like this room is more important for me' ... and then they carry onto the next room and do the same to the next person and it's just that's what I was like maybe not having glass in the library.

(Students, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

Susan and Sarah explained that while the 'private' group rooms in their campus library are generally facilitative of their learning, the space is incongruent with their need for visual privacy. First, it is

clear that participants feel uncomfortable when being watched by others (output to others). Secondly, at a more interpretative level it appears that Susan and Sarah are distracted by those outside of the room (input from others). In a later discussion, these same participants emphasised how the incorporation of architectural or design features (e.g., “curtains” and “fogged glass”) may help to increase visual privacy.

Finally, several students across the Campus A focus groups highlighted the need to be surrounded by rather than isolated from others. To illustrate:

Ian: I think the best feature of the hub is that ... there’s a nice atmosphere you know? ... You see who’s coming in, going out, it’s always busy, it’s lively, as well as you know ... So I think that is the best feature over there ... the worst feature is, I think the library is very conjuncted over the two floors

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

In the excerpt above, Ian highlighted how the hub social space and social learning space is congruent with his need for input from others while studying. At a more interpretative level, the notion that the library is ‘conjunct’ implies that the presence of visual barriers (e.g., bookshelves) and separation of silent and group study zones, limits his desired level of stimulation from others.

Turning to the instructors’ perspective, instructors discussed the relevance of acoustical privacy in both classroom and library spaces as well as speech privacy (disturbing others) in library spaces. By way of illustration:

Don: The worst from my point of view is the internal rooms where you’ve maybe got a two-hour lecture on the inside of ... the block, no windows ... you’ve got to leave the door open to get air and then of course you get the noise from people shouting up and down the corridors

(Instructor, Campus A, Focus Group 4)

Don highlighted the need for acoustical privacy from those out with the classroom environment. However, incongruent with the requirement for acoustical privacy, in Don’s experience a choice must be made between the need to ventilate uncomfortably warm classrooms and the need to maintain acoustical privacy. Here, the interrelationships between ambient and socio-physical characteristics are clear. The ideal classroom space would include sufficient ventilation to minimise the need to choose between a comfortable thermal environment and acoustical privacy.

Furthermore, the importance of speech privacy was highlighted by the instructors who met students out with scheduled classes in the campus library spaces:

Sandra: I [a] occasionally use the bit where ... there's sort of seats and tables ... congregated and a [I] often see quite a lot of students there and al [I'll] occasionally use that to meet dissertation students ... it's quite a good space cause ... it feels like structured but not so much so that you can't have an open discussion. You don't get dirty looks from anyone like you would higher up in the library.

(Instructor, Campus A, Focus Group 5)

And:

Ted: I've been in there [the Campus C library] and I've had chats with groups of students but but ... I feel awkward ... because a feel like am making a noise that a shouldnae [shouldn't] [be making] because am [I'm] in a library so a [I] don't really like.

(Instructor, Campus C, Focus Group 7)

In the examples above it is apparent that these instructors require speech privacy when engaging in learning activities (dissertation meetings) with students out with the classroom. For Sandra, the group learning spaces in the Campus A library are congruent with these requirements. However, this is not mirrored in Ted's account, who felt that the Campus C library was incongruent with his need for speech privacy when meeting students. However, it is unclear whether instructors perceived speech privacy as important for students' learning space experiences out with class.

Subtheme 1e. Perceptions of Choice (Decisional Control)

As emphasised in previous subthemes, students strive to achieve the best possible level of fit between the environment and their needs. One of the processes by which fit may be regulated is through students' choice of learning activity congruent spaces (e.g., including their preferred spaces). This also includes the ability or inability to choose suitable alternative spaces, for example, when one desires to do so or when one's preferred space no longer meets their needs. This perception of one's ability to choose activity congruent spaces is closely interrelated with each of the previous subthemes, particularly for students' out-of-class learning experiences. That is, if one feels that they cannot choose a suitable space because it is too loud, too cold, and/or overcrowded, then they are likely to experience a loss of perceived choice.

From the student perspective, the importance of the ability to choose appropriate spaces was predominantly evident in discussions of learning activities out with the classroom environment. The ideal campus for many students would allow them to choose appropriate spaces for different learning activities. To illustrate:

Ross: The library ... a [I] think from an environmental point of view is quite good. There's a good mix of use-case spaces ... there's the group area ... the sort of sitting about waiting on people area ... the private rooms and then there's the whole floor for being quiet which is good.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

Ross highlighted how the Campus B library is congruent with his need to choose from a variety of settings which are suitable for different learning activities, including, a silent study zone for individual learning activities, an open group study area, and alternative spaces for group study (i.e., 'private' group study rooms).

When such choice of suitable spaces for learning activities out with class were constrained, this was largely a consequence of environmental issues. For instance:

Scott: Between the hours [of] ... 9 and 4 ... for example, forget it. See unless you're in the library for about 8 o'clock in the morning, half 8, you don't get a PC. Anytime between the hours of like 9 and 4, even down in E Labs [computer lab used for out-of-class learning] forget it. You need to do your work between 6 and 9. And it doesn't always suit me to do that either ... [I] wouldn't really want to be in late to be honest. But that's the only times you can get places to work ... the space that really annoys me at the moment is ... where the café used to be ... is basically sitting empty ... they could actually have cleared that out, put PCs in there right away and wired it up. Even if it was on a temporary basis until ... utilise the space.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

In this extract, Scott highlighted that learning activities required access to congruent settings. However, because of low spatial density and high social density, Scott explained how the campus is incongruent with his ability to choose congruent spaces. This is further emphasised by Scott's frustration regarding the poor utilisation of empty spaces which could be used to increase his choice of suitable spaces for individual learning activities. This constrained choice as a consequence of high social density and low social density was mirrored by Cara in relation to congruent spaces for group learning:

Cara: A [I] think more little ... booths and stuff as well would probably be more beneficial, you have to be there super early if you want to get a booth so you can count on one hand like how many there are

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

Ivor noted how the acoustical and socio-spatial environment could constrain his ability to choose suitable on campus spaces:

Ivor: I think I might be here more if there was ... more facilities for doing it. I mean we've been discussing this morning the main areas for actually doing this [studying] are either too full or noisy or something like that ... whereas if we did actually have more areas then I might actually come in ... if I knew that I could come in somewhere where there was a proper bit that I could actually get what I wanted from it whereas when I'm trying to study I'll usually go home because although there are distractions ... I can provide myself with better facilities than I can at the uni.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

In the excerpt above, Ivor highlighted that he requires access to spaces on campus which are congruent with his acoustical and socio-spatial needs for individual learning activities out with class (i.e., quiet spaces with low social density). However, this is incongruent with Ivor's on campus experience.

While Ivor explained that he was able to cope with the inability to choose campus learning spaces which meet his requirements for individual learning activities by studying at home, the home environment does not meet all students' needs. As such, some students noted that they are compelled to use spaces on campus which can be incongruent with the requirements of their learning activities, with no choice of suitable alternatives:

Emily: I've got kids and I don't like to study in the house and I need to study but I'm studying on the campus ... and that's why I'm here today with no lecture ... but unfortunately it is really cold and you are kind of only you end up back to the one place where you've got comfortable seating, you know the hub?

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

Emily noted that the ability to choose congruent spaces on campus was important because, due to her home responsibilities, she experiences difficulties studying at home. While Emily was able to choose a congruent space for learning activities (the hub social learning space), she is compelled to use this space and is unable to find alternative spaces when necessary due to a lack of comfortable furniture and thermal discomfort.

None of the students emphasised the ability or inability to choose congruent settings for class activities, suggesting that this lay predominantly with the instructors or campus services. Choice of seating positions for class activities, nevertheless, were highlighted by two students:

Jill: A good room would be to use D143 ... cause you've got desks at the side but then you've got seating area in the middle ... with like actual couches and ... where people can have discussions without trying to look over computers ... D143 or 134 would be a good example because we don't have the computers and plus the group screens where if you're working in a group you can see it but obviously a discussion in the middle of the classroom where there's actually seating ... and it's not claustrophobic.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

In Jill's experience, the ability to effectively transition between different learning activities within class, could be facilitated by classrooms which allowed students to move between zones which are designed to facilitate these different activities. For Jill, the active learning classrooms, with desks around the circumference of the room for small group activities and a central zone for full class

discussion, were congruent with the need to choose activity-appropriate settings. However, in contrast with out-of-class learning activities, it is unclear whether Jill was able to exercise this choice or whether this choice rested predominantly with the instructor.

Only Ross discussed the importance of choosing learning activity congruent seating positions within the classroom as a function of the physical environment:

Ross: Yeah there's no left-handed ones in Campus B ... I'm left-handed so I have to have two seats to myself which means av [I've] got nae [no] pals ... that's like an actually serious annoying thing ... that's in all lecture theatres, there's no left-handed ones in any ... it sounds like a really minor picky thing but imagine you just couldn't use a table. Like it's really really annoying.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

Beyond choosing a specific seating position within class, students' choice over appropriate spaces for class activities (e.g., choosing appropriate classrooms) appeared to be limited.

Instructors discussed the importance of being able to choose activity congruent settings. It can be inferred that this could help to regulate fit between environmental characteristics and the requirements of learning and teaching activities. For example, Josh highlighted the potential value of being able to choose alternative spaces (outdoor spaces) for scheduled classes/learning activities, without having to consult campus services:

Josh: But you're trailing chairs out and things [moving chairs into outdoor spaces for learning]. Ad [I'd] rather there were fixtures [fixed furnishings] for doing that. This is probably the most beautiful campus there is ... Don't worry that somebody else might have booked it or that you have to actually book it. Have open space just available for people to use when they want to use it.

(Instructor, Campus B, Focus Group 6)

However, this requirement is incongruent with Josh's experience of the campus as the lack of appropriate seating constrains his ability to choose alternative settings (outdoors spaces) for learning and teaching activities. Interestingly, the notion that the choice of spaces was typically constrained by 'room booking services' suggests that choice over appropriate settings rests with instructors and room booking services, with limited input from students.

Similarly, Dan discussed his decision to 'take his class' into the Campus A grounds:

Dan: We took a class out in Campus A ... out into the sunshine because the class[room] was pretty much freezing and it wasn't ... big enough ... we took them out into this nice grassy clear area and there were students complaining "a can't take this sun" and eh hh "am getting dizzy so can we go back in?" ... so it wasn't working.

(Instructor, Campus B, Focus Group 6)

Dan valued the ability to move class activities to what he perceived to be a more congruent space (outdoors) when the classroom space was less congruent with the requirements of the learning activities (too warm and too small). However, it was clear from the Dan's comment that this decision was largely within his control rather than his students. While Dan's comment illustrates how students were able to react against the negative effects of the outdoor environment, it is clear that they had to 'ask permission' from their instructor (Dan).

When instructor choice of appropriate spaces for class activities was constrained, several instructors suggested that this was often a consequence of campus services (room booking) rather than the physical or socio-physical environment per se:

Ann: So say you had twenty students but you knew you needed a space for 30, even if you ask for 30 what they'll then do is they go and check on banner ...

Josh: They'll OVERRULE you

Ann: They'll [say] "you've got 20 students you need a room for 20" and actually you want a bigger space but you can't get it

Josh: And we know what we – we're you know? Without stamping up and down and having a wee fit – we know what we need for our students.

(Instructors, Campus B, Focus Group 6)

And:

Evan: A [I] think a lot of staff are moving towards thinking differently about what they do in a lecture ... and in their module descriptor [formal description of classes for a particular subject module] it's still called a lecture and it's timetabled as a lecture but actually they're using a different pedagogy ... it's like a [I] wanna [want to] discuss with them ... you're trying to make the most of the space whereas actually you might want to think about the way we design module descriptors ... if that did feed into timetable systems ... then you probably would find that you wouldn't need as many lecture theatres.

(Instructor, Campus A, Focus Group 5)

In the excerpts above, the instructors highlighted the importance of being able to choose activity congruent settings for classroom learning activities. However, Ann and Josh emphasised how campus room booking services often constrain their abilities to choose congruent classrooms. Similarly, Evan noted that the mismatch between module descriptors (formal description of the classes) and those identifying the appropriate classrooms for the module's classes, constrains the ability to choose appropriate classroom spaces. Again, it is evident that choice lies with those who are responsible for organising classes, that is, instructors and campus room booking services.

Finally, several instructors discussed the choice of seating positions within different classroom spaces. For example:

Mike: There's a couple of rooms in D Block that do that I try to get because you can just throw them up there [instructor presentation] ... and then you can leave it and they can all be clustered round in their own little groups, still talking about that [the subject of the presentation] ... it allows for the continuation of activity in a smaller group.

(Instructor, Campus A, Focus Group 4)

For Mike to transition effectively between different learning activities, in this case lecture instruction and small group activities, multiple zones which suit both types of learning are required within the classroom. The active learning classrooms on Campus A allow him are congruent with this requirement and allowed Mike to choose suitable zones for his students to seamlessly flow between more individual activities (instruction) and more collaborative activities (group). Again, however, it is clear from Mike's comment that the decision to choose between activities and congruent zones is in his hands rather than his students.

It is worth noting that both students and instructors emphasised other ways of regulating the environment, specifically, acting upon environmental demands to try and change these. This included behaviours, such as, asking others to talk quietly or using earphones to mitigate against the effects of disruptive noise; switching lights on and off; opening and closing blinds; using a thermostat to control the temperature; opening and closing windows or doors to provide ventilation; and rearranging furniture within a space to suit learning activities. However, given the sheer number of behavioural options available to students, these were not included in the present analysis, nor the subsequent studies conducted as part of this PhD.

4.3.3. Primary Theme 2. Learning and Psychological Consequences

Overview

Primary Theme 2 concerned students' and instructors' beliefs about the positive and negative learning and psychological consequences of physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics, for students' learning space experiences. Positive learning and psychological consequences resulted from what students and instructors perceived as 'good fit' between their needs for a learning activity and the environment. In contrast, negative learning and psychological consequences occurred when students and instructors believed that the fit between their needs for a learning activity and the demands of the environment were poor.

This primary theme consisted of three subthemes representing the learning and psychological consequences of the physical and socio-physical environment: *Engagement in Learning Activities*, *Cognitive-Affective Consequences*, and *Quantity and Quality of Work* when using the campus learning spaces for learning activities. Summaries and descriptions of the codes for each subtheme are presented in Table 3.

Table 3.

Primary theme 2. Learning and psychological Consequences

Subtheme	Description
2a. Engagement in Learning Activities	Motivation to engage, involvement/engagement and disengagement, broken concentration, and distraction
2b. Cognitive-Affective Consequences	Stress relief, relaxation, relief, annoyance and frustration, comfort, and discomfort. Also evidenced by discussions of 'positive' and 'happy' spaces.
2c. Quantity and Quality of Work	Task quantity (productivity), task quality (creativity, performance)

Subtheme 2a. Engagement in Learning Activities

The most prominent subtheme was that of student's engagement in learning activities. This concerned two main issues: (i) students' involvement or motivation to involve themselves in a learning activity and (ii) students' ability to concentrate on a learning activity without distraction.

From the discussions, it was clear that students' involvement and motivation to involve themselves in learning activities was an important consequence of the physical and socio-physical environment in campus learning spaces:

Ross: Emmm you know if you were to sit in a room like this ehheh which is you know windowless and fairly clinical-like, an unpleasant room like this? Ehheh you would, you don't want to linger and you don't want to spend a lot of time working in there. Whereas if you're you know? You get a bit of natural light and you get, because there are birds that come in and it's quite pleasant. And they did, a couple of years ago they cleaned it out and put new plants in and it's quite a nice wee area to look at [secret garden] ... it convinces you to stay and learn [laughs] rather than go home.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

It is apparent from the excerpt above that for Ross to engage in self-directed individual learning, he requires a “pleasant environment” and “motivating” environment (with natural light and views). Indeed, for Ross, these requirements were congruent with the silent zones in the Campus B library. In contrast, the “windowless” focus group (class)room was perceived by Ross to be incongruent with such requirements.

In another example:

Cara: You see a [I] always feel really disengaged in that class cause it's so big that a genuinely just feel like a [I] get lost in it and a feel like ma [my] voice gets almost lost in it so a [I] always like feel really apprehensive to just shout out over a full room so a just wouldn't say anything ... a [I] just find it really hard to concentrate in a big room but ... it's just an example of how you learn differently ... so you'll obviously learn differently to me ... So you [to Jill] maybe prefer like a bigger room and a [I] prefer like a smaller room.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

It is evident that Cara requires a smaller classroom to confidently engage in class discussion. Unfortunately, Cara's experiences of an active learning classroom at Campus A were incongruent with such requirements. Specifically, Cara believed that the classroom was too large and therefore hindered her ability to engage in class discussion (i.e., collaborative learning activities). Interestingly, Cara recognised that there may be differences between her own spatial preferences and those of Jill.

Other examples pertained to students' ability to concentrate on learning activities. By way of illustration:

Jill: av [I've] really struggled tae [to] concentrate ... when am [I'm] too warm, a [I] pure fidget and am [I'm] pure gasping for like fresh air ... and you don't want to be rude and be like £oh can you just leave that door open?" because then you hear everybody

Ivor: everybody from other [classes]

Jill: out in the corridor and stuff.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

It is evident from Jill's comment that she requires a comfortable temperature to concentrate on classroom learning activities without becoming distracted. However, Jill revealed that the thermal environment in classrooms is often incongruent with her requirements. While asking the instructor to open the door may help to alleviate poor ventilation, Jill (and Ivor) believed this could lead to incongruence between the classroom learning activities and acoustical environment and in doing so cause further disengagement.

Amy, on the other hand, described more positive concentration-related consequences:

Amy: You can concentrate ... That's one of the best floors I think in the sense that it is silent. It's quiet and people do respect that.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

Amy believed that the congruence between the acoustical environment (noise level) and her needs for individual learning activities enhanced her ability to concentrate. As noted previously, Amy required minimal acoustical input when engaging in self-directed individual learning activities out with class. Reassuringly, the acoustical environment within the silent zone of Amy's campus library was congruent with her needs for minimal acoustical input, and thus enhanced her ability to concentrate on the task at hand.

It was clear from the instructors' perspective that students' involvement in and concentration on learning activities were perceived to be a key consequence of the physical and socio-physical environment. For example:

Christina: An example from Campus C so we [Christina and Sandra] taught a second year class where half the module in Trimester 1 but it was a classroom and we were doin' [doing] lectures but we could discuss with them, put them in groups, whatever, and we both said that that class ... spoke back to us, they weren't scared to ask us questions, they engaged, they gave us their opinions and then in Trimester 2 the room was the, one of the lecture theatres in the Almada Building so it was like rows [hand movement delineating straight rows] and we both commented separately saying

Sandra: it was a different class.

Christina: It was different before now ... they don't wanna [want to] speak.

(Instructors, Campus A, Focus Group 5)

In the discussion above, Christina and Sandra believed that when the spatial environment (e.g., furniture configuration and physical density) in classroom learning spaces is congruent with student-centred learning activities (e.g., instructors can circulate, students' face one another and their instructors), then students are more likely to participate in collaborative activities. However, when the spatial environment is incongruent with student-centred activities, then these same students become disengaged from such classroom interactions.

Furthermore, instructors emphasised engagement-related consequences pertaining to concentration and distraction. For instance:

Cal: the environment is not productive for learning because people were sitting sweating and always needing drinks. People, you can see them sort'a [sort of] always drifting off. Whether it's just me boring them a [I] don't know but a [I] put it down to more the heat ...

(Instructor, Campus C, Focus Group 7)

And:

Don: the students fall asleep because they can't get any air and it's so stuffy because they're just desperate and there's no natural light. Those rooms are awful to teach in for a long period.

(Instructor, Campus A, Focus Group 4)

In the excerpt above, it is evident that both Cal and Don perceived incongruence between the ambient environment (temperature) in classroom spaces and classroom learning activities to hinder students' ability to concentrate.

Subtheme 2b. Cognitive-Affective Consequences

Subtheme 2b was evidenced by participants' discussions around the positive and negative cognitive-affective consequences of the physical and socio-physical environment. It is evidenced, in part, by students' discussions of the positive cognitive-affective outcomes which seem to occur as a consequence of using spaces where the environment is congruent with their learning activities. For example:

Amy: You could have an extra window but at least like they've done the new colours like in this room so it's quite a nice environment. I think it looks like a happy place you know? All the colours ... If you have a nice window you can just like look out for two seconds and rest your eyes for [out-of-class spaces] ... we want windows. We definitely want windows.

(Student, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

In the example above, Amy highlighted the importance of (i) studying in an environment with bright (pleasant) colours and (ii) having access to window views. Interpretatively, this suggests that ambient environmental features (use of colour and window views) which are congruent with learning activities and described as "happy" and offering "rest", may invoke positive psychological consequences. Such consequences, for example, include happiness and relief or rest from learning activities. Similarly:

Ross: It's a good [the library], it's like a pleasant place to be 'cause it's got quite a lot of windows and you can see out into the wee secret garden in the quiet bit which is quite nice emmm because you can sit and watch birds which is quite fun.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

Again, the notion that pleasant ambient features (e.g., natural light and window views of nature) are suggested to have positive cognitive-affective consequences, such as invoking positive emotions (e.g., "which is quite nice" and "fun") when engaging in learning activities, is evident.

The theme of cognitive-affective outcomes is also evidenced by students' discussions of the negative cognitive-affective consequences which appear to stem from the use of spaces where the environment is incongruent with their learning activities. To illustrate:

Karen: There's never enough places to sit during the day because you've got one person sitting in a booth that can sit like maybe six people and stuff like ... that is really frustrating. Like the seating is good but you'll always get like one person sitting in a booth ... if you have something you do like ... between 12 and 2pm and you try to get a computer in the third floor like it will always be jam-packed with people and you can't actually find anywhere to sit and use a computer.

Scott: Yeh yeh and then you get annoyed.

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

In the example above, Karen and Scott highlighted that when the socio-spatial environment (social density) is incongruent with their needs for learning and there is lack of suitable alternative spaces, negative cognitive-affective consequences occur. This is evidenced by their explicit discussions of their feelings of 'frustration' and 'annoyance'.

This is mirrored in a discussion by Jill and Ivor:

Ivor: See when I grew up, you weren't allowed to talk.

Jill: Aye [yes] in a library point blank.

Ivor: If you talked in a library your Mum or you Dad would slap you across and say "shut up".

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 2)

In the example above, Jill and Ivor discussed the incongruence between the acoustical environment and their expectations or demands of the campus library spaces for their learning activities. Ivor and Jill highlighted not only their annoyance, but their confusion, at what they perceived to be a 'breach of the social conventions' within their library spaces (disruptive noise from other students talking).

Instructor perspectives also highlighted the importance of positive and negative cognitive-affective consequences which may arise from person-environment congruence and incongruence, respectively. For instance:

Patrick: A [I] like rooms with windows ... it's the freedom isn't it? The idea that, they [the students] can look out the window if they want.

(Instructor, Campus A, Focus Group 5)

In the example above, Patrick suggested that the presence (as opposed to absence) of window views may potentially have positive psychological consequences for students, in this case (i) increase their feelings of autonomy and (ii) act as a positive distraction from learning activities.

In another example:

Jodie: Sometimes people just feel more relaxed when there's like a couch for you.

(Instructor, Campus B, Focus Group 6)

Here, Jodie expressed her view that soft and comfortable informal furnishings could increase students' relaxation and comfort when engaging in learning activities, thereby enhancing their willingness to participate in collaborative learning activities.

In contrast, several instructors noted that environmental demands which are perceived as incongruent with learning activities could have negative cognitive-affective consequences for students. To illustrate:

Mike: It's too noisy.

Gina: It is noisy.

Lindsay: A've [I've] heard students complain that there's not a quiet bit in the library.

Mike: Well there is but it's still noisy, it's a designated quiet area but it's still noisy.

Don: it's not as good as it used to be for studying. I mean the way that it's been reconfigured with the hub does make it noisy.

(Instructors, Campus A, Focus Group 4)

In the excerpt above, the instructors' discussion suggests that incongruence between out-of-class learning activities and the acoustical environment in campus library spaces may lead to frustration and annoyance among students.

Subtheme 2c. Quantity and Quality of Work

Finally, Subtheme 2c concerned both the quantity and quality of output produced by students in their learning spaces.

From the students' perspectives, this was evidenced by discussions and comments about task productivity, performance on learning activities, and creativity when engaging in learning activities.

For example:

Scott: I've got a utility room at home and my mum set it all up so as I can study with the laptop and stuff but I still can't focus right in there so I usually end up in here anyway and it ...

Kayla: Yeah I prefer to study in the uni ... I'd rather study in the uni because I don't get as much done at home.

(Students, Campus A, Focus Group 1)

And:

Kate: A [I] think if you've got the space to sit quietly and there's like a nice kinda bit of scenery then you might get your work done a bit faster than when you

Sarah: I'm far more productive when I'm down there.

(Students, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

Scott and Kayla highlighted how being able to choose activity congruent settings (on campus) over incongruent settings (at home) can positively influence the amount of work that they complete when engaging in learning activities. Similarly, Kate and Sarah emphasise how their productivity increases when engaging in learning activities within campus spaces where their acoustical and ambient requirements are congruent with the environment (silent zone of Campus B library).

Other findings pertinent to this theme addressed the quality of work when engaging in study tasks, in learning spaces which were perceived as congruent or incongruent. Examples of quality focused on issues such as student creativity and quality of work produced. For instance:

Susan: Yeah so they're really nice and so there's a bit of natural light and that just, it's a space but it's kind of a creative space, there's no like boundaries.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

And:

Ross: People can freely come and go through the airlock doors ... it isn't really sound-proofed as a result of that and it does affect you from a student perspective, from a learning perspective, it does impede your capabilities. Because we have to do that work for assessment ... and my experience is that eh-h-h the students taking that degree don't do any radio work outside of the building because they think that they can do it in their own house ... but there's a marked drop in the quality of work generally coming out of it from when the students are working and when the studios are offline for six months.

(Student, Campus B, Focus Group 3)

Here, Susan emphasised that the presence of certain ambient features which are congruent with her learning activities (individual study) may enhance her creativity. Similarly, Ross discussed how the

privacy-related and acoustical environment (noise from others) can interfere with students' ability to produce work of a sufficient quality in out-of-class learning spaces (radio studios). Unfortunately, by extension, Ross believed that students who are forced to work from home suffer from performance decrements in their assignments as a longer-term after-effect.

While instructors' perspectives did not address the notion of quantity of work produced, instructors recognised how the physical environment may impact upon the quality of work produced by students. For example:

Jodie: Just what you were saying about the ability to just you know, identifying that it would be quite nice if we could just get out of this room and find? Like you know sometimes when you go around different spaces you kinda [kind of] think ... maybe more freshly about something.

(Instructor, Campus B, Focus Group 6)

In the excerpt above, Jodie believes that giving students the ability to 'breakout' of the 'formal' classroom environment can help to promote 'new ways of understanding' issues covered in class.

In another example:

Samuel: Tutorial rooms should be ... a space where students can be more creative. Initially a creative space because a tutorial is when you feel you have smaller numbers of students, and you can interact with them and again you need to be as acquainted as possible. If I am in a room and it's too warm or it's too cold, then how can I?

(Instructor, Campus A, Focus Group 5)

Samuel noted that creativity in class-based learning activities requires sufficient student-instructor interaction. However, high social density (too many students in the classroom) may limit creativity in learning activities.

4.3.4. Comparing students' and instructors' perspectives

Between groups comparisons are challenging with qualitative data. Nevertheless, comparing students' and instructors' perspectives provides some useful insights and directions for the subsequent empirical studies within the thesis.

Overall, there was considerable overlap between students' and instructors' perspectives, with students' and instructors' discussions contributing to the same primary and subthemes. Specifically,

there was substantial overlap between students' and instructors' discussions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Ambient Fit, Engagement in Learning Activities, and Cognitive-Affective Consequences.

There was also some overlap between students' and instructors' experiences of Acoustical Fit and consequences of the environment for the Quantity and Quality of Work produced. However, there were a few exceptions for these themes. First, both students and instructors discussed people-related noise and the noise level. However, only students' highlighted sources of noise that did not include other people, specifically, noise from equipment (e.g., radios and ventilation systems). In addition, only student participants noted situations in which higher noise levels could be beneficial for learning. One explanation is that these additional acoustical concerns are more relevant to students' learning space experience out with class. Secondly, both students and instructors discussed the relationships between the environment and work quality (e.g., performance, creativity, and new perspectives). However, only students discussed the potential impact of the environment on the quantity of work that they produced (productivity).

Thematic areas where there were more noticeable discrepancies pertained to both subthemes of Privacy Fit and Choice (Decisional Control). With regards to Privacy Fit, both students and instructors discussed concerns pertaining to speech privacy, acoustical privacy, and architectural privacy. However, only students highlighted the importance of task privacy (interruptions from learning tasks by their peers) and requirements for visual privacy (being observed by others and visual distractions from other people moving). Another issue raised by students in relation to out-of-class learning activities is the need to be surrounded by others.

Indeed, it is plausible that interruptions from learning activities by peers may be less likely to occur in class, under the observation of the instructor. Likewise, spaces out with the classroom are often designed to be open and visually accessible, with students engaging in separate individual and collaborative learning activities. As such, invasions of visual privacy may be more likely to occur in spaces where students are visually accessible and surrounded by a wider body of students. Likewise, when engaging in class activities, by the very nature of those activities, students are surrounded by others. In comparison, out with the classroom, students can choose spaces where they are isolated

from or surrounded by others. In short, certain components of privacy may be more relevant to students' learning space experiences out with class, where instructors have limited insight.

When reflecting upon the subtheme of choice, it was clear that students had greater ability to choose learning activity congruent settings when engaging in learning out with the classroom environment. When choice was constrained, from the students' perspective, this was largely a consequence of environmental issues (e.g., physical and social density, acoustics, privacy, temperature, and comfortable seating). However, beyond choosing a particular seating position within the classroom, students' ability to choose learning activity congruent spaces for scheduled class activities (i.e., classrooms) was unclear. When interpreting the instructors' perspectives, it was clear that instructors made the decision to transition between spaces, with limited input from students. When this transition was constrained, this was largely as a function of campus services (e.g., room booking), as opposed to environmental demands. In other words, it seemed to be the case that instructors and campus services drove and constrained the choice of settings that students used for class activities.

4.4. Discussion and Conclusions

4.4.1. Overview

In this section the findings are considered with respect to each of the study aims, previous research, and theory. This leads onto the development of a thematic model which aims to explain students' experiences of their campus learning and teaching spaces. The section finishes with the limitations and strengths of the study, chapter conclusions, and directions for the subsequent empirical chapters.

1. Understand how students perceive the physical and socio-physical environment in their university campus learning and teaching spaces;
2. Identify the relevant environmental characteristics of these spaces for students' learning space experiences;
3. Identify relevant learning and psychological consequences of the environment with respect to students' campus learning space experiences; and
4. Investigate the relevance of person-environment transaction theories in explaining students' learning space experiences.

4.4.2. Addressing the research aims

- *Aim 1. Understand how students perceive the physical and socio-physical environment in their university campus learning spaces*

As per Primary Theme 1, *The Ideal versus Expected Environment*, the findings suggest that when students use their campus spaces for learning and teaching activities, they predominantly perceive their physical environment with regards to (i) the degree of fit between their needs for a specific learning activity (functionality) and the demands of the environment and (ii) their ability to choose an activity appropriate setting or settings. Theoretical implications of these findings are discussed in relation to Aim 3.

- *Aim 2. Identify the relevant environmental characteristics of campus learning spaces for students' learning space experiences*

To varying degrees, students' and instructors' discussions centred around the following environmental characteristics: their need for Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, and Choice of appropriate settings. These are discussed, in turn, below.

Spatial and Ergonomic Characteristics

Students and instructors discussed the same spatial and ergonomic issues, including, physical and social density, furniture configuration and seating position, furniture comfort, and the size of work surfaces. Indeed, the importance of spatial attributes (e.g., furniture configurations and circulation space) for students' learning (e.g., engagement in different pedagogical behaviours, concept learning, and course performance) have been well documented (Brooks, 2011; Brooks, 2012; Talbert & Mor-Avi, 2018; Whiteside et al., 2010). Furthermore, these findings are in line with previous qualitative research in which students and instructors have highlighted the relevance of furniture arrangements and seating position, physical and social density, comfortable furniture, and sufficiently sized workspace (Granito & Santana, 2016; Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Hunter & Cox, 2014; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017; Van Horne et al., 2014).

Acoustical Characteristics

Acoustical issues which appeared to be relevant to the learning space experience from both students' and instructors' perspectives pertained to the background noise level and noise from other

people talking. In addition, several students, though not instructors, discussed the relevance of noise from equipment, including, radios and ventilation systems. Students, unlike instructors, also highlighted that background noise can be beneficial for learning. One reason for these discrepancies may be that noise from equipment and the benefits of noise may be more specific to out-of-class learning activities.

The importance of the acoustical environment has been recognised as important in previous experimental studies, including, the effects of background noise level and white noise versus conversational noise on students' creative and cognitive performance (Mehta et al., 2013; Marchand et al., 2014; Salamé & Baddeley, 1987). In previous qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods studies, students and instructors have highlighted the importance of the acoustical environment in allowing students to hear their instructors, hindering in class learning, and both hindering and enhancing learning out with scheduled classes (Granito & Santana, 2016; Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Hunter & Cox, 2014).

Ambient Characteristics

Other ambient variables which were identified in students' and instructors' discussions as relevant to the learning space experience were temperature and ventilation/air quality, natural and artificial lighting, the use of colour, and the presence of window views to outside spaces. These findings are in line with previous research which have found statistical associations between temperature, lighting, colour, window views, and learning and psychological outcomes (Benfield et al., 2001; Marchand et al., 2014; Maas et al., 1974; Stone, 2001). Furthermore, in several qualitative studies students and instructors have highlighted the importance of lighting, temperature and fresh air, views of outdoor spaces, and warm colours (Granito & Santana, 2016; Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Hunter & Cox, 2014).

Privacy Characteristics

Concerns about privacy were also pertinent to students' learning space experiences, particularly in relation to spaces used for out-of-class activities. For both students and instructors, privacy addressed the degree of isolation which one required in terms of input from and output to other people. Students' discussions reflected interruptions from learning activities by peers (task privacy), being observed by others (observational/visual privacy), distractions from seeing other people moving (visual privacy), and the need to be surrounded by others when engaging in self-directed

learning activities out with class. Both students and instructors discussed the relevance of speech privacy (disturbing others) in library spaces. Binding all these concerns together was the notion of architectural privacy (e.g., partitions, fogged glass, and curtains) which could aid or hinder one's ability to achieve their desired level of privacy.

Although fewer privacy issues were discussed by instructors compared to students, one should be cautious of assuming that the instructors did not perceive these additional issues as relevant to students' learning space experiences. Rather, it is likely that these issues were more pertinent to students' experiences in campus learning spaces used for out-of-class activities. Indeed, it seems logical that environmental privacy concerns are less relevant to scheduled activities in architecturally enclosed classroom contexts, where students and instructors gather as a collective with a common purpose (learning).

The need to be isolated from (and surrounded by) others when using university campus spaces for self-directed learning out with class, has been well documented. For example, several studies have found that some students preferred to study in spaces where they are surrounded by stimulation from others (e.g., seeing others moving and background conversational noise), while other students preferred to study in spaces where they are isolated from other's input, for out-of-class learning activities (Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Hunter & Cox, 2014; Sommer, 1966). Furthermore, both students' and instructors' discussions of privacy-related experiences are in line with Altman's (1975) definition of privacy as an input and output regulatory process whereby one attempts to regulate input from and output to other people to achieve the desired level of privacy.

Perceptions of Choice (Decisional Control)

The choice of appropriate learning spaces was emphasised by students and instructors, including the choice of activity congruent spaces and suitable alternatives. Students' ability to choose spaces for class activities seemed to be relatively limited compared to instructors and campus services.

Nevertheless, it seemed to be the case that students exhibited greater choice of congruent spaces for learning activities out with scheduled classes. When the ability to choose suitable spaces for out-of-class learning was constrained, this appeared to stem from environmental demands such as spatial and ergonomic, acoustical, ambient, and privacy misfit, rather than instructors and campus

services. In short, it appeared to be the case that students' ability to choose suitable learning spaces may be greater for out-of-class learning activities.

This theme is in line with previous research on users' perceptions of learning spaces which have found that students consciously choose learning spaces "based on what they consider most valuable for their learning activities" (Beckers et al., 2016b, p. 152). Further, these findings map onto the construct of decisional control, one's (in)ability to choose spaces and alternatives which best suit their needs (Averill, 1973; Gatersleben & Griffin, 2016; Haghnia & Imani, 2016). A lack of decisional control due to spatial and ergonomic, ambient, acoustical, and privacy issues can result in the use of incongruent spaces, which are not facilitative of learning.

At a more interpretive level, these findings are also in line with the construct of territoriality, that is, cognitions and behaviours exhibited due to perceived ownership of a space (Altman, 1975; Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007). Related to territoriality, students and instructors expressed that they had clear preferences for certain spaces or types of spaces. However, behaviours which aimed to mark territorial boundaries such as leaving books or bags on a chair or desk to claim one's space (cf. Kaya & Burges, 2007) were not articulated in any of the discussions.

- *Aim 3. Identify relevant learning and psychological consequences of the environment with respect to students' experiences of campus learning and teaching spaces*

Students and instructors discussed the impact of the physical and socio-physical environment on Engagement in Learning Activities, Cognitive-Affective Consequences, and the Quantity and Quality of Work produced when engaging in learning activities. These conversations suggest that such consequences are relevant to students' learning space experiences and are discussed, in turn, below.

Engagement in Learning Activities

Across the focus groups, it was clear that both students and instructors believed that the physical and socio-physical environment could impact upon students' ability to engage in a variety of individual and collaborative learning activities. This included the impact of the environment on students' involvement and their ability to concentrate on learning activities.

This is congruent with previous quantitative research which suggests that, for example, the design of classroom spaces (traditional versus active learning) can influence whether students engage in passive versus active and collaborative learning activities (Brooks, 2011, 2012; Whiteside et al., 2010). Quantitative and qualitative studies have also highlighted the benefits of learning in social learning spaces (as opposed to at home) for students' engagement in social learning activities (Matthews et al., 2009, 2011). Finally, the findings from our study compliment previous qualitative research findings in which students and instructors have articulated the impact of physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics on students' motivation and involvement, engagement in different types of learning activities, and ability to concentrate without distraction (Granito & Santana, 2016; Hunter & Cox, 2014; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017; Van Horne et al., 2014).

Cognitive-Affective Consequences

The relevance of positive and negative 'cognitive-affective' consequences of the environment, were evident from both students' and instructors' discussions. Positive consequences included feelings of happiness and positivity and the ability to relax and take stress relieving breaks. Negative consequences whilst using campus spaces for learning included feelings of frustration and annoyance. Indeed, these findings are in line with previous quantitative research which has highlighted the effects of objective environmental conditions on students' cognitive-affective outcomes, including, mood, environment-related well-being, and course evaluations (Benfield et al., 2015; Marchland et al., 2014; Scannel et al., 2016). Additionally, in prior qualitative research, students have highlighted the positive and negative psychological consequences of physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics in their learning spaces, including, happiness, relaxation and refreshment, and annoyance and frustration (Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Hunter & Cox, 2014).

Quantity and Quality of Work

Finally, the relevance of the quantity of work produced by students when engaging in learning activities on campus was discussed by students, while the quality of work produced (including creativity) was discussed by both students and instructors. Indeed, the effects of the physical and socio-physical environment on students' rate of completion on cognitive tasks, performance on cognitive and creative tasks, concept learning, and course performance are well documented in previous quantitative studies (Brooks, 2011, 2012; Gulian & Thomas, 1986; Marchand et al., 2014; Mehta et al., 2014; Whiteside et al., 2010). Likewise in previous qualitative studies, students and

instructors have highlighted how the physical environment can inspire students, improving the quality of their output (Hunter & Cox, 2014) and course performance (Granito & Santana, 2016).

- *Aim 4. Investigate the relevance of person-environment transaction theories in explaining students' learning space experiences*

In relation to the third aim, several issues pertaining to the person-environment transaction theories (discussed in Chapter 2), became apparent in students' and instructors' discussions. As mentioned previously, Primary Theme 1 (*The Ideal versus Expected Environment*) suggested that when students use their campus spaces for learning and teaching activities, they perceive the physical and socio-physical environment in terms of the degree of fit between their needs for their learning activity (i.e., individual or collaborative learning) and their experience (i.e., demands) of the environment. In addition, Primary Theme 1 also captured students' and instructors' discussions about the importance of choice, that is, the ability to choose learning activity appropriate spaces and suitable alternatives.

The notion of perceived fit is in line with Michelson's (1976) construct of mental congruence, the notion that people perceive the congruence between their needs and the demands of the environment. The idea that students perceive the functionality of their environment is in line with ecological theories and Michelson's mental congruence which propose that people perceive the environment in terms of its functions (e.g., individual and collaborative learning) (Barker, 1968; Costall, 1995; Gibson, 1979; Wicker, 1987). The conceptualisation of choice is in line with Averill's (1973) construct of Decisional Control, the ability to choose appropriate spaces and alternatives. Finally, in line with person-environment transaction theories, it became clear that students' environmental experiences are variable over time and change as a function of circumstances (Barker, 1968; Costall, 1995; Gibson, 1979; Lazarus & Cohen, 1977; Michelson, 1976; Proshansky et al., 1970; Wicker, 1987).

Both students and instructors stated that environmental characteristics may influence students' engagement, cognitive-affective outcomes, and the quantity and quality of work produced when engaging in learning activities. This is in line with Evans and Stecker's (2004) conclusion that perceived uncontrollable environmental demands in quasi-experimental and laboratory settings may have negative outcomes, including, lack of task engagement, negative cognitive-affective consequences (including depression), and lowered cognitive performance.

In the subsequent subsection, the findings and discussion of findings pertaining to Aims 1-4 are brought together. The relationships between the primary themes and subthemes are considered in a unified thematic model called the University Students' Learning Space Experience (USLSE) Model.

4.4.3. Developing a thematic model

The USLSE Model is depicted in Figure 1 and draws upon focus group data and themes relevant to both classroom and out-of-class spaces from students and instructors, including, *Perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit*, *Perceptions of Acoustical Fit*, and *Perceptions of Ambient Fit*. In addition, the model is driven by the discussion of the themes in relation to previous research and person-environment transaction theories. Given the importance of out-of-class spaces to the student participants, and the apparent greater applicability of subthemes such as *Perceptions of Privacy Fit* and *Perceptions of Decisional Control* in out-of-class spaces, the model is predominantly intended to capture students' experiences of out-of-class spaces.

As indicated in the focus group discussions and in line with person-environment transaction theories, students' learning space experiences are dynamic rather than static and vary over time and according to circumstances. This includes as a function of changes to the environment, different learning activities, as students progress from one year of study to the next, and personal preferences. Further, perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and consequences are concerned with the requirements of a particular learning activity and therefore can be interpreted as functional, in line with theories of mental congruence, behaviour settings, and affordances (Barker, 1968; Costal, 1995; Gibson, 1979; Michelson, 1976; Wicker, 1987).

To reiterate, underlying both students' and instructors' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces, was the degree of fit between the ideal and actual environment for a particular learning activity. In other words, perceptions of the environment in campus learning spaces, could be interpreted as perceptions of fit or congruence between the requirements of a learning activity and the demands of physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics. Specifically, a campus learning space would therefore be perceived as congruent with the learning activities if it met students' Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical, Ambient and Privacy needs. Furthermore, the model these distinguishes such 'fit constructs' from one's ability to choose

or access their preferred space(s) for a particular learning activity. This includes the ability to choose suitable alternatives (e.g., when one's preferred space is incongruent). Following this logic, the model distinguishes between Perceived Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control (choice). While Decisional Control can be viewed as a meta-construct or a type of Person-Environment Fit (like Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical, Ambient, and Privacy Fit), to distinguish it from other Fit constructs and in line with Averill (1973), it is referred to as Decisional Control.

The model recognises the interrelationships between the Person-Environment Fit Constructs. However, since Decisional Control is linked to all four Person-Environment Fit constructs (Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical, Ambient, and Privacy), these particular relationships are pertinent to the model. In other words, when students perceive an environment to be congruent with their requirements for a particular task (e.g., good Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical, Ambient, and Privacy Fit), then perceptions of the ability to choose a task congruent space or spaces should be high. Similarly, those who perceive the environment as incongruent with their requirements for a particular learning activity (poor fit), should perceive less controllability. This is in line with person-environment transaction theories which purport that primary appraisal (e.g., threat) is associated with a secondary appraisal process (of one's ability to cope with environmental demands) (Lazarus & Cohen, 1977). In short, variations in perceptions of Person-Environment Fit are linked to variations in perceptions of Decisional Control.

Negative perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in campus learning spaces, including, both Perceived Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control, should therefore lead to negative consequences, such as, negative Cognitive-Affective Consequences (e.g., increased stress), lowered Engagement in Learning Activities, and lowered Quantity and Quality of Work when using campus learning spaces for self-directed learning out with class. In contrast, positive perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment should be associated with more positive consequences. This is in line with previous research on learning space perceptions, other institutional environments, and person-environment transaction theories which propose that negative perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment are associated with negative outcomes. Michelson (1976), for example, proposes that person-environment fit is a self-fulfilling prophecy. That is, if one perceives that they cannot carry out a particular activity, then they are unlikely to successfully engage in said activity. Likewise, literature suggests that a loss of environmental control (including choice) is associated with negative consequences for task engagement, cognitive-affective

outcomes, cognitive task performance, and job performance (Evans & Stecker, 2004; Lee & Brand, 2005, 2010; Sherrod et al., 1977). The relationships within the model are likely to be bi-directional.

Figure 1.
The University Students' Learning Space Experience Model

4.4.4. Limitations and strengths

The first limitation concerns the instructor focus groups which were initially conducted to gain insight into both their own and students' experiences, though with less emphasis on the student perspective. Five of the instructors engaged in limited teaching, including, two Academic Skills Advisors, one Honorary Research Fellow, one Professor, and one instructor with a 70% research contract. Input on learning spaces from these instructors was, therefore, less than that from others. As such, instructor data was only able to supplement the student perspective. Nevertheless, instructors highlighted many of the same issues as students and discrepancies may be explained with regards to the specific types of learning spaces. Further, drawing on the perspectives of both groups painted a more comprehensive picture of students' learning space experiences. The similarities in findings and clear explanations for discrepancies (e.g., regarding privacy and decisional control) enhances the validity of the analysis and provides an interesting avenue for the subsequent research conducted in this thesis.

Secondly, while participants represented a range of disciplines, they did not represent all departments within the university. Specifically, students in education, students in engineering, and instructors in science disciplines did not participate in any focus groups. As mentioned previously, students across disciplines may have different experiences of their environments (Wilson & Cotgrove, 2016). Thus, the inclusion of participants from these disciplines may have allowed for a more representative data set and analysis, for example, highlighting further themes and refinements to the USLSE Model. That said, the participation of students and instructors with experiences of one or more of three campuses, allowed for the analysis and interpretation of experiences pertaining to different types of learning spaces.

Thirdly, given the variety of topics discussed in the focus groups, when sample sizes exceeded four participants it was often difficult to follow up on participants' responses. A more focused approach on a narrower range of spaces and activities may have helped to alleviate these issues. Nevertheless, the focus groups allowed participants to articulate both direct agreements as well as juxtapositions concerning their environmental experiences. Thus, the focus groups provided richer data on a variety of learning and teaching space experiences, which may not have been revealed through interviews or open-ended questionnaires.

A fourth limitation concerns what the author and others (e.g., Braun & Clarke, 2012, 2020) would argue is a strength of the study. Specifically, the author recognises that other researchers may view objectivity (e.g., through use of inter-rater reliability analyses) as superior to researcher subjectivity (e.g., Boyatzis, 1998). However, the author argued that researcher subjectivity should be both acknowledged and valued. That is, thematic analysis does not pretend to be neutral (Brule, 2020):

demonstrating coding reliability and the avoidance of 'bias' is illogical, incoherent and ultimately meaningless in a qualitative paradigm and in reflexive TA [thematic analysis], because meaning and knowledge are understood as situated and contextual, and researcher subjectivity is conceptualised as a resource for knowledge production, which inevitably sculpts the knowledge produced, rather than a must-be-contained threat to credibility (pp. 7-8).

To address this issue, the author explicitly acknowledged that the empirical and theoretical literature discussed in Chapter 2 would serve as an empirical and theoretical base for this study (Study 1) and the subsequent empirical chapters. A related strength also concerns the 'trustworthiness' of the analysis and interpretation. Specifically, the author provides a transparent account with regards to the process of theme development, the analytical process, draws upon relevant excerpts from students and instructors where appropriate, and both acknowledges and draws upon empirical and theoretical subjectivities.

Overall, this study has developed a model which explains students' learning space experiences based on the target population, professionals involved in learning and teaching, and relevant empirical and theoretical literature. As such, the constructs in this model have superior content validity and conceptual foundations than previous research. This model therefore serves as a useful conceptual basis for the future empirical studies in this thesis.

4.4.5. Chapter conclusions

The findings of the present study demonstrated (i) how students perceive the physical environment; (ii) relevant physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics to students' learning space experiences; (iii) relevant learning and psychological outcomes to students' learning space experiences; and (iv) the utility of person-environment transaction theories in explaining students' learning space experiences. By addressing these four aims, the USLSE Model was proposed to explain students' learning space experiences, with a particular focus on out-of-class learning activities. Driven by students and instructors, previous research, and person-environment transaction theories, the constructs in the USLSE Model have superior content validity and conceptual foundations when compared with previous research. As such, the USLSE Model serves as

a robust basis for investigating (i) the suitability of existing instruments and (ii) developing a new 'learning space experience questionnaire'. The subsequent empirical studies in Chapters 5 (Study 2) and 6 (Study 3) will address each of these issues, in turn, using the USLSE Model as a conceptual base.

5. CHAPTER FIVE

MEASURING STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS

ENVIRONMENTAL PERCEPTIONS IN

THEIR CAMPUS LEARNING SPACES: A

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF MEASUREMENT

INSTRUMENTS

5.1. Chapter Introduction

5.1.1. Background

As mentioned in Chapters One and Two, there is increasing empirical and theoretical interest in the extent to which the physical and socio-physical environment in university campus learning spaces supports or hinders students' requirements. Specifically, there is a relatively rich body of qualitative studies on university students' campus learning space experiences (e.g., Granito & Santana, 2016; Hunter & Cox, 2016; Matthews et al., 2011; Melhuish, 2010; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017).

Further, an increasing number of studies have adopted quantitative 'user-centred' approaches to investigate students' learning space perceptions. Much of this quantitative work has focused on the predictors of students' learning space perceptions, including, personal and situational characteristics (Beckers et al., 2016a, 2016b; Castilla et al., 2017; Wilson & Cotgrove, 2016; Yang et al., 2013).

However, as noted in Chapters 1 and 2, there is a scarcity of research on the associations between university students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning space. The few studies which have investigated this (Belojević et al., 1992; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016), suffer from several methodological and conceptual flaws.

First, as highlighted in Chapters 1 and 2, the constructs assessed in previous empirical work and therefore their corresponding measurement instruments, would seem to be hindered by a lack of content validity. Specifically, it is unclear whether the constructs assessed, and their corresponding measurement instruments are relevant to students' learning space experiences. Secondly, the constructs assessed, and their corresponding measurement instruments appear to be theoretically agnostic. Where authors have made 'theoretical claims' (e.g., Hill & Epps, 2010), it is unclear whether and how these theories underpin the constructs assessed and their corresponding measurement instruments. Finally, the construct validity and internal consistency reliability of the constructs measured, and their corresponding questionnaires is unclear. Specifically, where assessments of construct validity and internal consistency have been conducted (e.g., Castilla et al., 2017), there would seem to be a lack of transparency and/or incorrect implementation of psychometric analyses. Insufficiencies in each of these areas may hinder the validity and reliability of the conclusions drawn from subsequent inferential analyses using these instruments.

The study presented in this chapter therefore seeks to (i) identify the measurement instruments used in previous research to assess HE students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces; (ii) critically evaluate the suitability of these instruments in terms of their item psychometric properties; and (iii) assess their suitability based on the USLSE Model, developed in the previous chapter.

5.1.2. Approaches to measuring learning space perceptions

As discussed, research on university campus learning spaces is interdisciplinary. As such, approaches to capturing students' learning space perceptions and experiences are varied. Further, learning spaces on university campuses are also varied and the extent to which spaces meet learners' needs are therefore diverse (Alexi Marmot Associates, 2012; Temple, 2007, 2008).

One approach to investigating these issues, has been the development of quantitative self-report instruments (questionnaires, structured interviews, and diaries) which measure students' perceptions of the extent to which the physical and socio-physical environment in campus learning spaces meet their needs. Such measurement instruments often serve research purposes and/or are used to evaluate the success of a building (post-occupancy evaluations) (Cleveland & Fisher, 2014). Unlike qualitative methods (open-ended questionnaires, interviews, or focus groups), can be

distributed to larger and, therefore, more representative samples (cf. Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Findings are therefore more generalisable to the wider population from which the sample was drawn and data can be subjected to statistical analyses (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). For example, measurement instruments can be used to quantify the size of statistical effects, such as, associations between the physical learning environment, users' learning space perceptions, and learning and psychological outcomes (cf. Baepler et al., 2014; Castilla et al., 2017; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010).

However, several learning space scholars have cautioned against an overreliance on statistical associations between HE physical learning spaces and learning and psychological outcomes (Alexi Marmot Associates, 2006; Temple, 2007, 2008). In addition, caution should be drawn when interpreting differences within and between groups as a function of different learning space typologies (e.g., active learning versus traditional classrooms). For instance, it is often difficult to control for variables which may confound with within and between group differences in outcomes across learning spaces (Alexi Marmot Associates, 2012, Temple, 2007, Temple, 2008). Despite these cautions, to the best of this author's knowledge, there is no study which has aimed to address the suitability and limitations of the quantitative measurement instruments which were created to assess students' subjective perceptions of the environment in their campus learning spaces.

This is of concern, given the widespread creation and use of such instruments for both research purposes and post-occupancy evaluation (Cleveland & Fisher, 2014; Kim & Fisher, 2015). Specifically, no study has provided a systematic and critical account of (i) the psychometric properties (validity and reliability) of these instruments and (ii) the suitability of the item content and conceptual frameworks underpinning these instruments (if any).

There is therefore a need for a more nuanced and comprehensive review which both identifies and critically evaluates the measurement instruments used by previous research to assess students' environmental perceptions in their campus learning spaces. In order to evaluate the suitability of existing instruments in terms of their psychometric properties and conceptual underpinnings, it is necessary to reflect on each of these issues in turn.

5.1.3. Psychometric considerations

A critical evaluation with regards to the psychometric properties of the measurement instruments used in previous research requires a short introduction to the field of psychometrics. Psychometrics is a method for assessing the validity and reliability of psychological constructs, including, perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment (e.g., *Spatial and Ergonomic Fit*, *Acoustical Fit*, and *Privacy Fit*) and their corresponding measurement instruments (e.g., questionnaires). Psychometric measurement is based on participants' responses to a range of statements (e.g., questionnaire items), typically rated using Likert-scales, such as, agreement (e.g., agree [1] to disagree [5]) or frequency of occurrence (e.g., never [1] to always [7]) scales (Field et al., 2012; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). Researchers typically assume the existence of multiple (related or unrelated) psychological constructs or unobserved variables (e.g., perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and perceptions of Privacy Fit) which explain, in part, participants' response patterns to particular questionnaire items referred to as measured or observed variables (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). Statistical techniques such as factor analysis and measures of internal consistency reliability (e.g., Cronbach's α) are typically used to estimate the construct validity and reliability of the psychological constructs and their corresponding measurement instruments, based on participants' responses (data) (Field et al., 2012; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014).

With respect to validity and reliability, psychometric theory proposes that measurements obtained using instruments such as questionnaires can never be truly accurate and thus some degree of measurement error will always be present (Nunnally & Berstein, 1994; Wilson & MacLean, 2012; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). Nevertheless, the development and use of both valid and reliable self-report measures can help to minimise measurement error (Hine et al., 2016; Nunnally & Berstein, 1994). Data obtained from instruments with sound psychometric properties and conceptual underpinnings may lead to improved evidence-based decision making in learning space development. This may ultimately lead to learning spaces which better meet the varied requirements of their users, through more rigorous research practices. According to psychometric theory, three measurement properties should be addressed when constructing self-report instruments: (i) content validity, (ii) construct validity, and (iii) reliability (Francis et al., 2016; Hine et al., 2016; Nunnally & Berstein, 1994).

Several researchers and organisations have highlighted the importance of content validity (COSMIN, 2017; Field et al., 2012; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink et al., 2010a, 2010b). In fact, COSMIN (2017)

have argued that content validity is the most important of the three measurement properties. Content validity is the extent to which constructs and their corresponding measurement items (e.g., individual questions on a questionnaire), are relevant to participants' experiences of the phenomena; this also includes the extent to which measurement items represent the full content domain of a construct (COSMIN, 2017; Field et al., 2012; Francis et al., 2016; Hair et al., 2017; Mokkink et al., 2010a, 2010b). The relevance and content domain of an instrument can be investigated two main ways: (1) consultation with content experts and (2) reviews of the relevant literature (Francis et al., 2016).

Experts can include those with professional knowledge of the content domain as well as the members from the target population which will complete the instrument (Mokkink et al., 2010b). In the case of learning space research this may include professionals involved in the design (e.g., architects, environmental psychologists), professional use (e.g., instructors), and evaluation and management (e.g., HE and estate management) of HE learning spaces. Consultation may occur through the quantitative and/or qualitative data collected through focus groups, interviews, and feedback from pilot studies (Elf et al., 2016; Francis et al., 2016). Consultation can help to identify items and constructs which are relevant and irrelevant to the population of interest and particular settings as well as items which may be misinterpreted (Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink et al., 2010). Even when distributing questionnaires developed in previous research on a new population, it is useful to consider the relevance and interpretability of items to content experts (van Teijlingen & Hundley, 2001).

Construct validity is the extent to which a measurement instrument assesses the intended constructs (COSMIN, 2017; Francis et al., 2016; hair et al., 2017; Mokkink et al., 2010a, 2010b). Construct validity is typically assessed with regards to factorial validity, for example, using principal components analysis (PCA) and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) (Field et al., 2012; Hair et al., 2017; Kline, 2016; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). PCA and EFA are used to determine the number of dimensions which reflect or predict a psychological construct. PCA aims to identify the linear components of a set of measurement items in order to reduce the items into a smaller number of dimensions called composites; PCA assumes participant's responses on the measurement items represent or compose (predict) a composite variable (Field et al., 2012; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014; Osborne, 2014). EFA, on the other hand, aims to identify the extent to which correlations between participants' responses on measurement items are explained by one or more underlying

hypothetical latent variables (common factors); unlike composites in PCA, common factors are assumed to explain (predict) participants' responses on the questionnaire items (Field et al., 2012; Osborne, 2014; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014).

Both PCA and EFA are exploratory approaches, although it is often assumed that constructs are theoretical entities, and hence theory should be used in the item formation and PCA/EFA interpretation stages of scale development (see Field et al., 2012; Osborne, 2014; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). There are several steps and reporting practices that should be explicitly adhered to (Field et al., 2012; Osborne, 2014; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014).

Another stage of psychometric assessment requires an analysis of reliability, the degree to which participant scores are free from measurement error (COSMIN, 2016; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink et al., 2010a, 2010b; Nunnally & Berstein, 1994). In the context of the present study, internal consistency reliability was considered. Internal consistency is the degree of association between different segments (e.g., questionnaire items) in an instrument (Francis et al., 2016; Field et al., 2012). Representing precision at a specific time point, internal consistency assesses the degree to which items which are proposed to measure the same construct and are correlated (Francis et al., 2016; Nunnally & Berstein, 1994; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). Internal consistency reliability is typically assessed using Cronbach's α and/or Dillon-Goldstein's rho, whereby values between 0.70 and 0.95 are considered acceptable (Field et al., 2012; Hair et al., 2016). Values below 0.70 are indicative of low reliability, while values above 0.95 indicate item redundancy. Where possible, items which contribute to low reliability or redundancy should be removed to increase reliability, so long as item removal does not hinder content validity (Field et al., 2012; Francis et al., 2016; Nunnally & Berstein, 1994).

Table 4 presents a template of the steps and procedures commonly recommended for the use of existing scales on new target populations and the development of new scales. This includes procedures for the establishment of content validity, PCA and EFA (construct validity analyses), and internal consistency reliability (Field et al., 2012; Osborne, 2014; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). Best practice guidance advocates transparent reporting of each stage (e.g., APA, 2009; Field et al., 2012; Osborne, 2014; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). This template serves as useful criteria for evaluating the

psychometric properties of the instruments used in previous research to assess students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces.

Table 4.*Psychometric assessment template: Content validity, construct validity, and internal consistency reliability*

Psychometric properties	Guidance for content validity, construct validity, and internal consistency reliability assessment
Establishing content validity	Step 1. Established through consultation with content experts to identify relevant constructs and items: this includes members of the target population and professionals involved in the phenomena of interest. Such data may be collected, for instance, via focus groups, interviews, and/or pilot studies. Can also be established through a review of the relevant literature.
Construct validity assessment	<p>Step 2. Analysis is conducted on data collected from members of the target population using the measurement instrument.</p> <p>Step 3. Choose either PCA or EFA. If EFA is chosen, the EFA estimation/extraction technique (e.g., maximum likelihood estimation, principal axis factoring, alpha factoring, generalised [weighted] least squares) should be chosen and detailed ^a.</p> <p>Step 4. Factor rotation: constructs should be rotated using either orthogonal or oblique rotation methods to aid interpretation. Orthogonal rotation constrains constructs so that they are uncorrelated, oblique rotation allows constructs to correlate. Researchers should report the type of orthogonal or oblique rotation used and the percentage of variance explained by each factor or composite.</p> <p>Step 5. Factor selection: choose number of constructs to be selected based on factor selection techniques including Kaiser's (1960, 1970) eigen value criterion ^b, Cattell's (1966) scree plot interpretation ^c, Horn's (1965) parallel analysis ^d, Velicer's (1974) minimum average partial analysis. ^e Several factor extraction techniques have important limitations (e.g., over- or under-estimation, subjectivity). Specifically, Kaiser's criterion has been shown to be the least reliable factor extraction technique, while scree plot interpretation is most sensitive to researcher subjectivity (Osborne, 2014; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). Hence, all three should be used in combination. Theory should also be used to aid interpretation scale formation and factor selection (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014).</p> <p>Step 6. Assessment of loadings and cross-loadings. Typically, items should be retained if their loadings for the corresponding construct are > 0.3 and there are no cross-loadings. Cross-loadings are items which load > 0.4 on more than one construct and should generally be removed on an individual item basis. Other authors have proposed that there should be a minimum difference of 0.15 between the loadings for a primary construct and other constructs. N.b., PCA and EFA are iterative processes and should be re-run with the removal of each problematic item until an approximate simple structure is achieved (no problematic items e.g., with low loadings or high cross-loadings).</p> <p>Step 7. Once retained, factors should be named based on item content, previous empirical and theoretical works.</p>

Internal consistency reliability Step 8. Internal consistency reliability be assessed and reported (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014; Osborne & Costello, 2005; Osborne, 2014). Where possible, items which contribute to low reliability or redundancy should be removed to increase reliability, so long as item removal does not hinder content validity (Field et al., 2012; Francis et al., 2016; Nunnally & Berstein, 1994).

a. There are several types of EFA with different aims, assumptions, and underlying algorithms. For reasons beyond the scope of this review, the most commonly utilised and recommended are maximum likelihood estimation and principal axis factor analysis (Field et al., 2012; Osborne & Costello, 2005; Osborne, 2014).

b. Eigenvalues are the sum of the factor loadings squared, eigenvalues > 1.0 are indicative of large factor loadings. Kaiser's (1960, 1970) criterion proposes that the number of eigenvalues > 1.0 represents the number of factors that should be extracted.

c. Cattell's (1966) scree plot interpretation proposes that the number of eigenvalues plotted above the characteristic point of inflexion, represents the number of factors to be extracted.

d. Horn's (1965) parallel analysis: eigenvalues from the dataset prior to rotation are compared with those obtained from a randomly generated dataset with the same sample size; those which are larger than the corresponding values from the random dataset are retained (Osborne & Costello, 2014; Pallant, 2012).

e. Velicer's (1974) minimum average partial analysis: computes the average of the squared partial correlations once each component is partialled out. Once the minimum average squared partial correlation is found, the residual matrix resembles an identity matrix (where the correlations between items are equal to zero), no further components are extracted (Osborne & Costello, 2014).

5.1.4. Underpinning conceptualisations and item content

As discussed, it is important that measurement instruments are underpinned by both a relevant and robust conceptual framework. Theory can provide a coherent framework for understanding psychological constructs in person-environment transaction research (cf. Bell et al., 2001; Gifford, 2007), such as, students' environmental perceptions. In addition, the constructs assessed by measurement instruments and subjected to psychometric assessment are often assumed to represent theoretical entities (Nunnally & Berstein, 1994; Field et al., 2012; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). The USLSE Model proposed in the previous chapter (Study 1), offers a valuable template/framework which can be used to evaluate the conceptual suitability of the measurement instruments used in previous studies to assess students' physical and socio-physical environmental perceptions in their campus learning spaces.

The USLSE model consisted of two broad constructs which represent students' environmental perceptions in their campus learning spaces, and which are relevant to the review of measurement instruments. First, Person-Environment Fit refers to the perceived congruence between the requirements of a learning activity and the demands of the physical and socio-physical environment. This includes perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical, Ambient, and Privacy Fit. Secondly, perceptions of Decisional Control pertain to students' beliefs about their ability to access or choose settings which are congruent with their learning activities and the ability to access suitable alternatives (e.g., if the environment becomes to become 'too noisy'). Environmental perceptions are seen to be dynamic than opposed to static concepts. That is, students' environmental perceptions vary over time and as a function of circumstances. In addition, perceptions of the environment are viewed as functional rather than form-based, that is, students perceive the extent to which the environment meets their needs for a particular learning activity (function) (cf. Study 1, Subsection 4.4.3.).

Some aspects of the model may be more relevant to students' experiences in out-of-class spaces than classroom spaces (cf. Study 1), such as, certain aspects of Privacy and Decisional Control. Nevertheless, the model presents a useful framework for evaluating the conceptual utility of the instruments used in previous studies to measure students' environmental perceptions, in terms of their item content and underpinning conceptualisations.

Accordingly, a suitable measurement instrument should incorporate items which assess students' perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, and Decisional Control with respect the content derived from the USLSE Model, presented in Table 5. In addition, a suitable measurement instrument should assess the functionality of perceived Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control, that is, assess students' perceptions of (i) fit between their specific learning activities and the physical and socio-physical environment (ii) the ability to access learning activity congruent spaces. Finally, a suitable measurement instrument should address the dynamic nature of students' environmental perceptions by using items and rating scales which consider the frequency of fit and control over time, as opposed to considering fit and control as static constructs.

Table 5.

Thematic template of environmental perceptions: Constructs and item content

Theme/dimension	Proposed content
Spatial and Ergonomic Fit	Furniture arrangement
	Seating p
	Spatial density (size of space)
	Spatial density (size of space)
	Furniture comfort
	Work surface size
Acoustical Fit	Noise level
	Noise from people talking
	Noise from equipment
Ambient Fit	Temperature
	Air quality/ventilation
	Natural lighting
	Artificial lighting
	Use of colour
	Window views to outside spaces
Privacy Fit	Architectural privacy
	Interruptions
	Seeing other people moving
	Being observed by others

Decisional Control	Speech privacy (disturbing others) Ability to access suitable space Ability to access suitable alternatives
Functional nature of learning space perceptions	The instrument should assess learning space perceptions in relation to specific learning activities, such as, individual and collaborative learning (functions of space)
Dynamic nature of learning space perceptions	The instrument should assess the frequency of which Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control perceptions

5.1.5. Review aims

Researchers and practitioners should aim to select measurement instruments for research and/or evaluation purposes which have acceptable psychometric properties and are underpinned by relevant and robust conceptual and theoretical frameworks. That said, the psychometric and conceptual information which is required in order to (i) choose a suitable existing instrument, (ii) adapt an existing instrument to suit, or (iii) inform the development of a new instrument is widespread across many peer-reviewed (journal articles) and unpublished (e.g., conference presentations, dissertations, and theses). To the best of this author's knowledge, there is no single, summative paper which evaluates the suitability of existing instruments for research or in practice, nor the procedures that should be considered to ensure that the development of future instruments are psychometrically and conceptually sound. The present review therefore aims to:

1. Identify the self-report measurement instruments used in previous research to assess students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces; and
2. Critically evaluate the suitability and quality of these instruments with respect to their psychometric properties and conceptual underpinnings.

5.2. Methods

5.2.1. Design

Unlike previous reviews on the physical environment of higher education learning spaces, including that in Chapter 2, this review adopted a more nuanced and systematic process. To address the research aims, this review sought to identify, quality appraise, and synthesise as much of the empirical research as possible, which met pre-determined inclusion criteria (Higgins & Green, 2011). The use of a comprehensive process aims to enhance replicability and minimise publication and

selection biases (Higgins & Green, 2011). A flow chart of the search strategy and selection process is summarised in Figure 2. Data for all stages were managed in Endnote X8. A copy of the Endnote file is available upon request.

5.2.2. Search strategy

An initial scoping review identified six databases and a variety of keywords which could be used to comprehensively review the relevant literature. UWS library databases were searched, including, EbscoHost (Education Source; Library, Information Science, and Technology Abstracts; PsycArticles; Psychology and Behavioural Sciences Collection, SocIndex with Full Text); Sage Journals, Educational Resources and Information Centre, Science Direct, Web of Science, and ProQuest. Abstract searches were conducted in all databases as this returned more relevant results, except for Web of Science which lacked this functionality. In addition, all available articles from the Journal of Learning Spaces were downloaded and added to the database; the journal was identified in the initial scoping search, however, was not linked to UWS library databases. Search terms were entered into the databases based on the following Boolean logic string:

("University" OR "higher education" OR "college" OR "further education")

AND

("learning space*" OR "study space*" OR "classroom space*" OR "classroom design" OR "classroom redesign" OR "library space*" OR "green space*" OR "place attachment" OR "place identity")

OR

("classroom" AND "acoustics*" OR "air quality" OR "ceiling height" OR "crowding" OR "density" OR "humidity" OR "layout" OR "lighting" OR "noise*" OR "personal space" OR "physical environment" OR "privacy" OR "spatial organisation" OR "spatial organization" OR "temperature" OR "territoriality" OR "wall colour" OR "wall color" OR "window*")

Final searches were conducted between the 29th June 2017 and 11th July 2017. The broad use of search terms and databases aimed to ensure that a representative sample of studies were retrieved across a range of disciplines. Database searches identified 4701 papers and 56 papers were retrieved from the Journal of Learning Spaces ($N = 4757$).

5.2.3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Papers were removed using pre-determined inclusion and exclusion criteria across the following stages: (1) Removal of duplicates and patents, (2) abstract and title selection, (3) full text selection, and (4) quality appraisal. Following the removal of duplicates and patents, 2956 papers remained for the abstract and title screening stage. Criteria for inclusion and corresponding exclusion criteria (where appropriate) based on title and abstract screening is presented in Table 6.

Table 6.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria for abstract and title screening

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Relationship between HE and/or FE environment, psychological, and academic outcomes. This includes abstracts which described or investigated the relationship between HE and/or FE physical environments and behavioural (e.g., learning and teaching behaviours, learning space choices), cognitive and affective (e.g., learning space preferences and perceptions, attitudes, mood, well-being, stress, cognitive task performance), and academic outcomes (e.g., achievement).	Irrelevant topic or addressed the relationship between HE and/or FE environment, environmental outcomes (e.g., air quality, decibel levels), and physical health outcomes (e.g., asthma, allergies).
Sample consisted of students (typically developing) and/or instructors.	Sample did not consist of students who were typically and/or instructors. Examples include questionnaires or interviews completed by library managers, students with dyslexia, students with hearing difficulties only.
References of the following type: journal articles, research reports (published or unpublished), conference abstracts, dissertations/theses, anecdotal discussions (e.g., press releases, such as, descriptions of new learning spaces).	References of the following type: books, book chapters, guidebooks, book reviews, media interviews with experts.
Articles which addressed the flipped classroom, blended learning, virtual learning environment, augmented and virtual reality were only included if the title or abstract also referred to physical or socio-physical environmental attributes.	Articles which addressed the flipped classroom, blended learning, virtual learning environment, augmented and virtual reality were <u>not</u> included if the title or abstract also referred to physical or socio-physical environmental attributes.
Articles on the construction process, given that these may involve user consultations.	
If the abstract did not contain information to apply the inclusion/exclusion criteria at the title and abstract review stage, the papers were retained until further evidence for	

inclusion or exclusion was available at the full-text review stage.

Following abstract and title selection, 1034 papers remained for full-text screening. The full-text inclusion and exclusion stage was more focused in order to address the review aims. Criteria for inclusion and exclusion at the full-text stage is presented in Table 7.

Table 7.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria for full-text screening

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Utilise or develop a measurement instrument (e.g., quantitative questionnaire, diary, or structured interview schedule) which assessed HE or FE students' or instructors' preferences or subjective appraisals with regards to physical or socio-physical environmental factors in the spaces that they use for campus learning.	Did not meet the corresponding inclusion criteria. This includes articles which are irrelevant in topic, address different populations, or preferences for and perceptions of spaces not used for learning (e.g., place attachment to neighbourhood, perceptions of office spaces and University counselling rooms).
Papers had to utilise instruments which contained quantitative response options, including, nominal, dichotomous, ordinal, or continuous measurements pertaining to the issues above (preferences or subjective appraisals). Papers which included instruments with both quantitative and qualitative response options were included.	Papers which did not contain instruments with quantitative response options, such as, instruments with only open-ended/qualitative response options pertaining to the issues above (preferences or subjective appraisals).
Papers were required to clearly specify the target population as learners or instructors to merit inclusion.	Did not meet the corresponding inclusion criteria, including, target population consisting of library managers, members of the public living in the University neighbourhood).
Written in English language.	Papers which were not written in English language.

Following application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria, a further 898 papers were removed at the full-text screening stage. The 136 remaining papers were then subjected to data abstraction and quality appraisal.

10% of the papers at the title and abstract selection phase were chosen at random and split between three members of the author's supervisory team so that each supervisor reviewed a different sample of papers. Three percentage agreement and three Cohen's Kappa scores were calculated between the author and the three raters to examine inter-rater reliability. Percentage agreement ranged from 93%-95%. Kappa scores ranged from 0.81-0.85, indicative of near perfect reliability (cf. Landis & Koch, 1977).

5.2.4. Data abstraction and quality appraisal stages

The 136 papers which met the criteria for full-text inclusion were read in full and, if available, the following information was extracted: evidence of content validity, evidence of reliability, and evidence of construct validity. This data was extracted from all papers which met the criteria for full-text inclusion (see Table F1 in Appendix F, for extracted data).

The final inclusion and exclusion criteria were based on quality assessment of three commonly cited methodological steps which are key to successful quantitative instrument development (COSMIN, 2017; Francis et al., 2016; Hair et al., 2017; Mokkink et al., 2010a, 2010b; Nunnally & Berstein, 1994). Studies were included if they clearly stated any effort towards establishing all three methodological domains which are central to psychometric scale development and measurement theory: (i) content validity, (ii) construct validity, and (iii) internal consistency reliability. In addition, papers were required to include more than one subscale which addressed perceptions of the physical and/or socio-physical environment. For instance, if a questionnaire on library service quality met psychometric criteria for inclusion but only included one subscale with items pertaining to the physical and/or socio-physical environment (e.g., the others pertained to library services), then the questionnaire was not included.

While theoretical underpinnings are also important for validity, a scoping review of the literature suggested that few, if any, papers sufficiently used conceptual framework. Therefore, the presence or absence of sufficient conceptual underpinnings was not a quality criterion for inclusion. Definitions and requirements for each domain are presented in Table 8.

Table 8.*Description of methodological steps for psychometric scale development*

Methodological steps	Requirements
Content validity	<p>Content validity was evidenced by the use of <u>one or more</u> of the following three procedures proposed by Francis et al. (2016) to inform item content, regardless of the range of content coverage:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Item development informed by user input, for example, via pilot studies, focus groups, and interviews; 2. Expert input. Examples include input from environmental psychologists; architects; engineers; academic library, estate, and HE management; and 3. Informed by literature reviews, including, reviews of previous instruments.
Construct validity	<p>For the present study, construct validity required a consideration of factorial validity, for example, using principal components, exploratory and/or confirmatory factor analysis to demonstrate dimensionality (Field et al., 2012; Francis et al., 2016; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014), regardless of the quality of the solution.</p>
Minimum of two subscales addressing physical and or socio-physical environment	<p>Papers with a minimum of two subscales focusing on perceptions of physical or socio-physical environmental factors and/or physical or socio-physical environmental preferences.</p>
Reliability	<p>Assessment criteria for internal consistency reliability in the present review included analysis of internal consistency reliability, for example, using split-half test, Cronbach's α, and/or Dillon-Goldstein's Rho, regardless of the quality of the solution.</p>

When information regarding scale development procedures or psychometric properties was distributed across more than one reference, these were combined to provide a more complete account of reliability and validity considerations. Specifically, four studies which addressed thermal comfort (Faria & Souza, 2016; Hoque & Weil, 2016; Wang et al., 2016; Zaki et al., 2017) used the same ASHRAE thermal comfort scale. A second questionnaire which measured appraisals of active learning classrooms was utilised across two studies (Walker et al., 2011; Whiteside et al., 2010). However, both instruments were excluded at the quality assessment stage on the basis of poor psychometrics. Following the application of the quality appraisal criteria, only six papers were retained.

Figure 2.

Search and Selection Process

5.2.5. Data synthesis

All seven instruments and corresponding papers which met the quality criteria for inclusion were subjected to a hybrid inductive and deductive thematic template analysis (Brooks et al., 2015). The analysis was largely deductive and focused on the conceptualisation of the instruments, their item

content, underpinning conceptualisations, and the extent to which each addressed the three psychometric properties discussed in the previous subsection (content validity, construct validity and internal consistency reliability). The stages of coding are presented below:

1. Although all the included papers following the quality appraisal process addressed the three psychometric quality criteria for inclusion, the extent to which these were addressed for each instrument was analysed using deductive coding.
2. The item content (e.g., noise level, lighting, privacy, and furniture arrangement) were coded using an initial deductive approach, with the USLSE Model (Study 2) as a framework. Two additional codes were used to categorise items which did not address the constructs of interest identified in the previous chapter. "Other" was used to refer to other aspects of the physical and/or socio-physical environment that had not been identified in the previous study. Items which did not pertain to the physical and/or socio-physical environment, such as, those relating to library staff or ICT were coded as "irrelevant".
3. The item content for each questionnaire was then thematised deductively according to the constructs present in the USLSE Model, including, perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, and Decisional Control. Further, a deductive approach was applied to determine the extent to which key components of the person-environment transaction models and theoretical framework proposed in Study 1 (Chapter 4) could be discerned from each questionnaire.
4. Finally, an inductive approach was utilised to identify whether the authors used established theoretical frameworks to underpin each instrument, such as, Relph's place identity framework (Kim, 2016).

5.3. Findings

5.3.1. Overview of Section

In the following subsections, each of the six instruments will be described and evaluated in turn. The description and evaluation will address the general characteristics of the instruments (e.g., target environment, population, and country of origin), evaluation of their psychometric properties, item content coverage and conceptual underpinnings, and a more general evaluation.

5.3.2. Characteristics of the included instruments

All six instruments, which met quality appraisal criteria for inclusion, were questionnaires completed by higher education students. None of the questionnaires were completed by instructors. One instrument originated from Spain (Castilla et al., 2017), one from The Netherlands (Beckers et al. 2016a), one from Canada (Scannell et al., 2016), and two from the United States (Kaya & Burgess, 2007; Kim, 2016). While Yang et al. (2013) did not state the location of the institution from which students were sampled, the authors are affiliated with a U.S. higher education institution and design consultancy. One instrument assessed students' preferences for out-of-class learning spaces (Beckers et al., 2016a), three assessed students' perceptions of their classroom environments (Castilla et al., 2017; Kaya & Burgess, 2007; Yang et al., 2014), one focused on the importance of the academic library (Kim, 2016), and one assessed students' perceptions of informal learning spaces (Scannell et al., 2016). All instruments were used for research purposes as opposed to evaluation purposes.

Table 9 summarises the key characteristics of the six instruments.

Table 9.*General characteristics of the included instruments*

Authors and instrument availability	Country of origin	Aim of instrument	Target/sampled environment	Target/sampled population
Beckers et al. (2016a)	The Netherlands (HAN University of Applied Sciences)	Research purposes: identify associations between preferred social (socio-physical) environmental variables, importance placed on physical environmental variables, and type of learning space preferred (on and/or off-campus)	On and off-campus spaces used for out-of-class learning spaces	HE Students
Castilla et al. (2017)	Spain (two universities in the Valencia region)	Research purposes: identify affective responses and design elements of the physical classroom environment which are relevant to students. Identify relationships between affective impressions and perceptions of design elements.	30 classrooms in 11 different buildings “with ... different height classrooms, surface areas, location, layout, indoor environmental quality, finishes and type of teaching (classrooms for theory and practical lessons, laboratory work and work on projects)” (p. 74).	HE Students
Kim (2016)	U.S. (State University in the South-eastern region)	Research purposes: to identify the dimensions of academic library as place. Instrument aims to measure the importance of library as place dimensions.	University campus library	HE Students
Kaya & Burgess (2007)	U.S. (large public University in the Southeast region).	Research purposes: identify “which seats would be the easiest to claim and define as one’s own territory” across a range of classroom layouts. Determine whether degree of territoriality differs according to seating preference and gender.	Classroom	HE Students
Scannell et al. (2016)	Canada (large University)	Research purposes: explore associations between objective measures of acoustical environment, researcher ratings of non-acoustical environment, and perceived suitability of the acoustical and non-acoustical environment for learning, and well-being. Instrument aims to assess perceived suitability of acoustical and non-acoustical environment for learning, positive and negative psychological consequences of the acoustical environment.	Informal learning spaces, defined as “non-classroom indoor areas on campus where students engage in learning-related activities such as discussion, studying, or working on a computer” (p. 775). 23 informal learning spaces in 11 buildings.	HE Students
Yang et al. (2013)	Unclear, though authors based at U.S. HEI (University of Southern California) and a U.S.	Research purposes: investigate the association between personal characteristics, GPA, and perceptions of classroom attributes. Instrument aims to assess satisfaction with attributes	Six classrooms: two large auditoriums with seating capacities of 150 and 350 students, two high-tech distance education network classrooms, two discussion classrooms with different furniture arrangements.	HE Students

design consultancy (Arup Group).

of the physical classroom environment and perceived impact of classroom attributes on performance.

5.3.3. Psychometric evaluation

Overview

Although all six questionnaires addressed the three psychometric properties required for inclusion in this study, the extent to which they did so varied considerably. A summary of the psychometric evaluation for all six instruments is presented in Table 10.

Content validity

To recap, content validity in the present study was evidenced by questionnaires that were informed by user input (e.g., via pilot studies, focus groups, and/or interviews); input from experts or professionals (e.g., environmental psychologists, engineers, architects, university management, professionals involved in learning and teaching) and literature reviews (including reviews of previous instruments). None of the six instruments explicitly referred to content validity, nevertheless, all instruments addressed one or more of the criteria for content validity.

Two of the six instruments which met psychometric criteria for inclusion, those by Castilla et al. (2017) and Yang et al. (2013), were explicitly considered by all three criteria for content validity assessment. Castilla et al. developed an initial list of words and expressions which described perceptions of the physical classroom environment via preliminary interviews with students, journals, and professional magazines. The researchers compiled 160 expressions describing affective impressions of the physical environment and 84 describing design elements within the physical classroom environment. An affinity diagram technique, which involved the qualitative reduction of words into similar categories, was conducted in focus groups with instructors, students, architects, and engineering experts to reduce the expressions and inform questionnaire items (Castilla et al., 2017). Yang et al. adopted a more basic approach to assessing all three aspects of content validity, including, a review of the literature, and pilot tests of the questionnaire with students and 'education professionals' to minimise bias and reduce misinterpretation.

A further three of the instruments addressed two criteria for content validity assessment, including, those by Beckers et al. (2016a), Kaya and Burgess (2007), and Scannell et al. (2016). Beckers et al. informed item content based on a review of the literature and two pilot studies with students to assess clarity of items and response options. Kaya and Burgess conducted two focus groups, one with students and one with instructors to identify classroom layout attributes which then informed the questionnaire design. The questionnaire constructed by Scannell et al. was reviewed by both

“acoustics professionals” and a “psychologist”. Further Scannell et al. pilot tested the questionnaire with students who provided feedback on the range of response options and wording; this student feedback was then used to refine the questionnaire (Scannell et al., 2016).

Finally, one of the instruments which met quality appraisal criteria for inclusion explicitly addressed one criterion for content validity. Specifically, Kim (2016) conducted a “comprehensive” review of the literature on library as place to inform questionnaire items.

Construct validity

To recap, construct validity is the extent to which a measurement instrument assesses the intended constructs (COSMIN, 2017; Francis et al., 2016; hair et al., 2017; Mokkink et al., 2010a, 2010b). As with content validity, none of six the instruments explicitly referred to construct validity considerations. That said, Kaya and Burgess (2007), Kim (2016), and Yang et al. (2013) conducted PCAs, while EFAs were conducted by both Beckers et al. (2016a) and Scannell et al. (2016). Factor analyses were conducted by Castilla et al. (2017). However, it is not clear whether this was PCA or EFA and, if EFA, which specific type.

Of the two questionnaires which used EFA (Beckers et al., 2016a; Scannell et al., 2016), only Scannell et al. (2016) specified the type of EFA that was used, specifically, maximum likelihood estimation. Three of the six questionnaires, those by Kaya and Burgess (2007), Kim (2016), and Yang et al. (2013), used orthogonal (varimax) rotation. Two of the questionnaires used oblique (direct oblimin) rotation, including those by Beckers et al. (2016a) and Scannell et al. However, Castilla et al. (2017) provided no information on the rotation method used.

Of particular concern, however, were the factor extraction methods used to determine the number of factors to be extracted. Two of the studies, those by Castilla et al. (2017) and Yang et al. (2013) provided no information on the factor extraction techniques used. All other studies used only one factor extraction technique, either Kaiser’s (1960, 1970) criterion (Beckers et al., 2016a; Kaya & Burgess, 2007; Kim, 2016) or Cattell’s (1966) scree plot interpretation (Scannell et al., 2016). As mentioned previously, Kaiser’s technique has been shown to be the least reliable factor extraction technique (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). Interpretation of Cattell’s scree plot is hindered by researcher subjectivity; under certain conditions this can lead to an over- and/or under-estimation of the

number of factors that should be extracted and thus hinder the validity of subsequent inferential findings (Osborne, 2014; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). Of note, none of the studies used more robust techniques, such as, Horn's (1965) parallel analysis or Velicer's (1974) minimum average partial analysis. Therefore, any subsequent findings based on measurement by each of the instruments may be invalid due to the use of unreliable extraction methods and/or based on researcher misinterpretation.

Other limitations pertained to issues which hinder the construct validity of the instruments and subsequent inferential findings, including, the inclusion of items with loadings below the 0.32 recommended threshold (see Yang et al., 2013), cross loadings with non-primary factors above the 0.40 recommended threshold (see Castilla et al., 2017), and the use of less than two items per factor (see Beckers et al., 2016a; see Castilla et al., 2017).

Internal consistency reliability

The internal consistency reliability for all instruments was assessed using Cronbach's α . Three of the questionnaires, those by Kaya and Burgess (2007), Kim (2016), and Scannell et al. (2016), demonstrated α values between the 0.70 minimum and 0.95 maximum thresholds for each scale. However, one of the questionnaires (Yang et al., 2013), assessed internal consistency reliability for all subscales combined. As mentioned previously, where numerous subscales exist, Cronbach's α should be applied to each subscale separately to prevent inflated α values (Cronbach, 1951; Field et al., 2012; Nunnally & Berstein, 1994). Two of the questionnaires contained subscales with unacceptable α values below the minimum recommendations, including, scales pertaining to preferences for "Quiet, Closed Areas" for individual study (Beckers et al., 2016a), "Layout" (Beckers et al., 2016a), "Good Artificial Lighting" (Castilla et al., 2017), and "Humidity" (Castilla et al., 2017). One explanation for these scores may be the low number of items on the corresponding subscales (between one and two).

Summary

Each of the six papers were included in this review because they created questionnaires which addressed a minimum of one criterion for each of the following psychometric areas: (i) content validity, (ii) construct validity, and (iii) internal consistency reliability. However, a more nuanced analysis highlighted that the extent to which these areas were assessed varied between instruments. By way of illustration, only two of the measurement instruments considered all three criteria for

content validity. With regards to construct validity, none of the instruments referred to the use of robust factor extraction techniques, including, parallel and minimum average partial analyses. Several instruments contained low loading and/or cross-loading items. These issues may lead to invalid measurements and subsequently invalid inferential findings (Elf et al., 2016; Francis et al., 2016). Finally, internal consistency reliability was sufficient for only three of the instruments. For other instruments, internal consistency was either below the minimum recommended threshold of 0.70 or calculated improperly.

Table 10.

Psychometric evaluation

Instrument	Beckers et al. (2016a)	Castilla et al. (2017)	Kaya & Burgess (2007)	Kim (2016)	Scannell et al. (2016)	Yang et al. (2013)
Content validity considerations						
Constructs and item content informed by review of previous literature	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes
Constructs and item content informed through consultation with target population	Yes (two pilot studies with students)	Yes (focus groups with students)	Yes (focus groups with students)	Unclear	Yes (pilot study with graduate students who commented on wording and response option range)	Yes (students tested validity of the survey to minimise bias and misinterpretation)
Constructs and item content informed through consultation with professionals	Unclear	Yes (review of professional magazines; instructor focus groups also included architects)	Yes (focus groups with instructors)	Unclear	Yes (acoustics professionals and a psychologist)	Yes (education professionals tested the validity of the survey to minimise bias and misinterpretation)
Construct validity considerations						
PCA or EFA	EFA	Unclear (unspecified “factor analysis”)	PCA	PCA	EFA	PCA
Type if EFA used (e.g., maximum likelihood, principal)	Unclear	Unclear	NA	NA	Maximum likelihood estimation	NA
Rotation method: type of orthogonal (e.g., varimax) or oblique (e.g., direct oblimin)	Oblique (Direct Oblimin)	Unclear	Orthogonal (Varimax)	Orthogonal (Varimax)	Oblique (Direct Oblimin)	Orthogonal (Varimax)
Factor extraction method: Kaiser criterion (Eigenvalues > 1.0), scree	Kaiser criterion (Eigenvalues > 1.0)	Unclear	Kaiser criterion (Eigenvalues > 1.0)	Kaiser criterion (Eigenvalues > 1.0)	Scree plot interpretation only	Unclear

plot interpretation,
parallel analysis,
minimum average partial
analysis

Acceptable primary loadings > 0.32 recommended threshold	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No (one item – “daylight” – with loading of 0.23)
All cross-loadings with non-primary factors < 0.40 recommended threshold	Yes	No: cross loadings for “good design”, “good ventilation”, “well lit”, “oppressive”, and “intimate on the affective impressions subscales; “windows”, “equipment”, and “humidity conditions” on the design elements subscales > 0.40.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear
> 2 items per factor	No: Privacy/Retreat (2 items), Autonomy/Control (2 items), Layout (2 items), ICT Facilities (2 items)	No: Modern Design (2 items), “Good Daylight and Outward Facing (2 items), “Good Artificial Lighting (2 items), “Humidity” (1 item) on the Affective Impressions Scale	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes, for relevant physical and socio-physical factors, though technology has 2 items
Internal consistency reliability considerations						
Calculated per each subscale	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Cronbach’s α and/or composite reliability (Dillon-Goldstein’s Rho) between 0.70 and 0.95	Cronbach’s α for Layout, ICT Facilities; Interaction/Communication; Quiet, Closed Area for Individual Study < 0.70 recommended threshold. No assessment of composite reliability.	Cronbach’s α for Good Artificial Lighting and Humidity subscales < 0.70 recommended threshold. No assessment of composite reliability.	Yes, Cronbach’s α for both scales between 0.70 and 0.95 recommended thresholds No assessment of composite reliability.	Yes, Cronbach’s α for both scales between 0.70 and 0.95 recommended thresholds. No assessment of composite reliability.	Yes, Cronbach’s α per scale between 0.70 and 0.95 recommended thresholds. No assessment of composite reliability.	NA. Calculated on overall scale rather than subscales.

5.3.4. Conceptual and theoretical evaluation

To reiterate, based on the USLSE Model, a suitable questionnaire should (i) assess the degree of fit between the requirements of students' specific learning activities and the environmental characteristics within a learning space (perceived functionality) and (ii) dynamic nature of learning space perceptions (i.e., use a scale and/or items which measure frequency of environmental perceptions). In short, the questionnaire should consider the frequency with which the environment meets students' needs for a particular learning activity.

While some of the six questionnaires addressed the abovementioned elements, none of them did so consistently. In addition, none of the questionnaires referred to the person-environment transaction theories presented in Chapter 2. Overall, there was variation in the conceptual underpinnings, both within and between each of the questionnaires. There was no universal model underpinning the questionnaires, with most lacking explicit and strong conceptual frameworks. Conceptual considerations for each of the instruments are presented in Table 11 and discussed below.

Kim's (2016) questionnaire sought to measure the dimensions of library as place and, therefore, the item content was based a priori on Relph's (1976) multidimensional place identity framework and literature on library as place. Specifically, Relph's framework proposes a multidimensional experience of place. This entails the (i) physical setting which provides the possibilities for experience within a place, (ii) the place and identity that one has with the place, and (iii) the interactions that occur within the place which create common meanings and experiences (Kim, 2016; Relph, 1976). However, Kim's instrument measured the perceived importance of these dimensions to university students, rather than one's identity with or attachment to the academic library per se, nor the perceived frequency with which the environment met students' needs for a particular learning activity. Beyond operationalisation of variables, it was unclear how Relph's framework was linked to questionnaire development.

Beckers et al. (2016a) referred to several theoretical construct definitions and statements presented a priori. First, Beckers et al. referred to Altman's (1975) definition of privacy as a "dynamic process to control the desired levels of interaction, which varies according to individual differences and circumstances over time" (p. 244). Next, Beckers et al. further describe personal control, in relation to a definition by Appel-Meulenbroek et al. (2011), as the "degree of autonomy in deciding what to

do, where, and when” (Beckers et al., 2016a, p. 245). Finally, Becker’s et al. refer to Beard and Wilson’s (2006) Learning Combination Lock model which emphasises the importance of linking ‘where’ learning activities occur to ‘what’ learning activities occur. For Beckers et al. the ‘what’ entails both collaborative activities which require communication and individual activities which demand concentration. Taking these theoretical considerations, as well as previous operationalisation of social and physical environmental preferences on board, the authors propose a conceptual model. This conceptual model links students’ personal characteristics (age, gender, living situation, and study year), their social preferences (for privacy, interaction, and autonomy), and perceived importance of the physical environment (comfort, aesthetics, ICT facilities, and layout) to their learning space preferences for individual and collaborative study activities (“quiet, closed spaces” and “busy, open spaces”).

One strength of the questionnaire by Beckers et al. (2016a) is the integration of the functionality of the learning environment, that is, the assessment of preferred study spaces for ‘individual’ and ‘collaborative’ learning activities. However, untrue to the functional and dynamic nature of such desires and preferences, the authors fail to consider the functionality of physical and social dimensions of the environment in terms of students’ learning activities nor the frequency of participants’ desires. This is ironic, given that Beckers et al. state in their definition of privacy (based on Altman), that learning space desires and preferences are dynamic over time and vary with circumstances (e.g., as a function of learning activities) (Beckers et al., 2016a).

Further, Kaya and Burgess (2007) defined classroom territoriality in terms of Altman and Chemers (1980) as behavioural mechanisms used by students to create and maintain social contact with others using territorial markers. In addition, the authors note the feelings of insecurity and vulnerability which stem from invasion of a clearly delineated space. True to their construct definition, the authors include questionnaire items which address the need to claim a particular seat and engage in behavioural mechanisms which define one’s own space and consider their dynamic nature by investigating differences as a function of classroom furniture arrangements (rowed with individual chairs and tablet armchair arrangements, u-shaped, and cluster-shaped). The need to claim a space is somewhat akin to Averill’s (1973) construct of Decisional Control, the ability or inability to choose a suitable space for a learning activity or suitable alternatives. In addition, behavioural mechanisms (e.g., defining one’s space with books and bags) used to defend one’s territory is akin to the theoretical construct of behavioural control, the ability to control

environmental attributes through behavioural actions (Averill, 1973). However, the questionnaire does not consider the frequency with which spaces meet students' territorial needs, with which students express territorial behaviours, nor does it consistently assess the functional nature of learning space perceptions.¹⁷

Of concern, Castilla et al. (2017) included only a single 'theoretical statement' pertaining to Duncanson's (2003) notion that learning spaces communicate silent messages to students and post-hoc operational definitions of variables. Scannell et al. (2016) provide definitions of vitality and restoration following factor analysis of perceived frequency of positive and negative consequences of the acoustical environment. Yang et al. (2013) fail to refer to any theoretical frameworks, constructs, or statements. As mentioned previously, while underpinning theoretical frameworks were not a prerequisite for inclusion, a lack of theory can severely hinder the construct validity of questionnaires and subsequent inferential findings (Elf et al., 2016; Francis et al., 2016).

That said, despite the lack of explicit conceptual underpinnings, several components of person-environment transaction theories can be discerned from the item conceptualisation (phrasing and response options) from each of the six instruments. However, this was somewhat inconsistent within and between questionnaires.

Some questionnaires included items which required students to merely rate descriptions or affective impressions of environmental attributes, such as, the degree to which the environment is 'spacious', 'cosy', 'pleasant', 'intimate', and 'old' versus 'new' design (Castilla et al., 2017).¹⁸ Nevertheless, others assessed students' environmental preferences and desires, that is, their 'user needs' (Beckers et al., 2016a; Kim, 2016; Kaya & Burgess, 2007). Additionally, some questionnaires measured the interaction between environmental characteristics and users' needs, that is, perceptions of person-environment fit (Castilla et al., 2017; Scannell et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2013). These latter items ranged from being rather general to specific in nature. For example, some questionnaires included

¹⁷ Of note, by highlighting the breadth of mechanisms which one can adopt to exert behavioural control over the environment, these findings support the decision not to incorporate behavioural mechanisms into the present iteration of the USLSE Model (see Study 1).

¹⁸ As mentioned in Chapter 2, ecological psychologists argue that such form-based (descriptive) approaches to defining learning space perceptions have poor ecological validity compared with more 'functional' approaches (Barker, 1966; Gibson, 1979; Heft, 2001).

items which asked students to rate agreement with generally phrased statements such as “I think the following design elements in this classroom are appropriate [e.g., ‘furniture’]” (Castilla et al., 2017), “how well do these aspects of the environment [e.g., ‘people talking, moving’] interfere with or enhance your ability to use this space for your activities?” (Scannell et al., 2016), “satisfaction with the [e.g., Furniture] in this classroom” (Yang et al., 2013), or “rate the degree to which you believe the [e.g., Temperature] in this classroom impacts your performance” (Yang et al., 2013). While such questions do not consider the frequency nor the functionality of person-environment fit, they do reflect perceptions of the degree to which the environment meets students’ needs.

Some items and subscales did reflect concerns of functionality and frequency of person-environment fit for specific activities. By illustration, Beckers et al. (2016a) asked students to rate their preferences for “quiet, closed spaces” and “busy, open spaces” for individual and collaborative activities and Castilla et al. (2017) asked students to rate the degree to which the classroom environment “helps me to concentrate”. Finally, Scannell et al. (2016) included two (of four) subscales which asked students to rate the frequency of positive and negative consequences of the overall acoustical environment (e.g., “difficulty hearing” and “difficulty talking”). However, as mentioned earlier, specific considerations (e.g., for particular learning activities) were infrequent as well as inconsistent within and between questionnaires.

Table 11.

Constructs, dimensionality, and conceptual underpinnings

Instrument	Beckers et al. (2016a)	Castilla et al. (2017)	Kaya & Burgess (2007)	Kim (2016)	Scannell et al. (2016)	Yang et al. (2013)
Construct(s)	Socio-physical environmental preferences and perceived importance of the physical environment.	Affective impressions of the physical environment. Perception of the appropriateness of design elements.	Territoriality	Perception of library as place.	Perceived Suitability of the Acoustical and Non-Acoustical Environment for Learning Activities. Restorative and Vitalising Psychological Consequences (Environment-Related Well-Being) of the Acoustical Environment	Perceptions
Construct definition(s) and theories	Construct definitions provided only for privacy and autonomy/control. Altman's (1975) privacy definition: "dynamic process to control the desired level of interaction, which varies according to individual differences and circumstances over time" (Beckers et al., 2016a, p. 244). Definition of personal control from Appel-Meulenbroek et al. (2011): "degree of autonomy in deciding what to do, where, and when" (Beckers et al., 2016a, p. 245). A priori reference to the Learning combination lock	No a priori or post-hoc construct definition. A priori reference to Duncanson's (2003) notion that learnings places communicate silent messages to students to students, however, it is unclear whether and how this relates to questionnaire design.	Territoriality defined a priori in terms of Altman and Chemers (1980): "a behavioural mechanism that individuals utilise to establish and regulate social contact through territorial markers ... because territoriality allows one to effectively control social interaction, personas who possess a clearly delineated space feel secure about shared spaces and invulnerable intrusion by others" (Kaya & Burgess, 2006, p. 859).	Library as place based a priori on Relph's definition of place as "directly experience phenomena of the lived-world and hence ... full with meanings, with real objects, and with ongoing activities" (Relph, 1976, p. 143, cited in Kim, 2016, p., 510). Operationalisation based on Relph's (1975) place identity framework and asserts that attachments with significant places are "a deep human need". Clear link between framework and questionnaire items.	No a priori or post-hoc construct definition for Perceived Suitability of the Acoustical Environment for Learning nor Perceived Suitability of the Non-Acoustical Environment for Learning Defined restoration after factor analysis as "recovery of depleted cognitive resources ... or the improvement of negative affective states" (Scannell et al., 2016, p. 780) based on definitions by Kaplan and Kaplan (1987) and Ulrich (1993). Defined vitality after factor analysis as "an	None

	model (Beard and Wilson, 2006), however, it is unclear whether and how this informs questionnaire design.				activated state of positive psychological energy" (Scannell et al., 2016, p. 780) based on definitions by Ryan et al. (2010).	
Constructs/ Dimensions (sub- constructs/ sub- dimensions)	<p>Social Dimension represented by the following constructs: preferences for Privacy/Retreat (1a), Interaction/Communication (1b), and Autonomy/Control (1c).</p> <p>Physical dimension represented by the following constructs: perceived importance of Comfort (2a), Aesthetics (2b), ICT Facilities (2c), and Layout (2d).</p> <p>Learning space preferences for individual study: "Busy, Open Area" (3a) and "Quiet, Closed Area" (3b).</p> <p>Learning space preferences for collaborative study: "Busy, Open Area" and "Quiet, Closed Area" (not factor analysed)</p>	<p>Affective impressions represented by the following constructs: "Functionality and Layout" (1a), "Cosy and Pleasant" (1b), "It Helps Me to Concentrate and is Comfortable" (1c), "Modern Design" (1d), "Good Daylight and Outward Facing" (1e), "Good Artificial Lighting" (1f), "Humidity" (1g).</p> <p>Design Elements: "Finishes" (2a), "Personal Work Space" (2b), "Interior Environmental Conditions" (2c), "Relationship with the Outside" (2d).</p>	<p>Territoriality represented by the following constructs: needs with regards to (1a) "Claiming a Particular Seat" and "Defining One's Own Territory" (1b)</p>	<p>In line with Relph's (1975) multi-dimensional theory of place identity. Proposes three dimensions based on the physical setting of the place, the person, and acts within the space.</p> <p>Three constructs/dimensions resulting from PCA: "Information and Services" (1a), "Reading and Study" (1b), "Relaxation" (1c).</p>	<p>Frequency of "Restorative Psychological Consequences of the Acoustical Environment" (1a: Environment-Related Well-Being).</p> <p>Frequency of "Vitalising Psychological Consequences of the Acoustical Environment" (1b: Environment-Related Well-Being).</p> <p>"Perceived Suitability of the Acoustical Environment" (1e)</p> <p>"Perceived Suitability of the Non-Acoustical Environment" (1d).</p>	<p>Satisfaction with and perceived impact of environmental attributes, including, "Ambient Attributes" (1a), "Spatial Attributes" (1b), and "Technological Attributes" (1c).</p>
Assessed functional nature of environmental perceptions for individual and/or collaborative activities	Inconsistently between items	Inconsistently between items	Inconsistently between items	Inconsistently between items	Inconsistently between items	Inconsistently between items

Assessed dynamic nature of environmental perceptions (frequency of perceptions)	No	No	No	No	Only Vitalising Psychological Consequences and Restorative Psychological Consequences subscales	No
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Note. Content in brackets represents constructs (dimensions) and sub-constructs (sub-dimensions)

5.3.5. Item Content Evaluation

Overview

The number and scope of the items which assessed students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environments in their campus learning spaces, varied considerably across the six instruments. In addition, the construct dimensions associated with items varied between measures, as a function of the item content domains and factor analytic results.

For instance, in their questionnaire Scannell et al. (2016) used multiple items to assess the Perceived Suitability of both the Acoustical and Non-Acoustical Environments in informal learning spaces; these items assessed students' perceptions of different acoustical qualities (e.g., noise from "people talking, moving", intermittent noise", and "continuous noise") as well as perceptions of different non-acoustical environmental attributes (e.g., "Temperature", "Lighting", and "Comfort of Furniture"). Unsurprisingly, the results of their factor analysis revealed construct dimensions which the researchers named "Perceived Suitability of the Acoustical Environment" and the "Perceived Suitability of the Non-Acoustical Environment". Specifically, items pertaining to the acoustical environment had stronger loadings with the "Perceived Suitability of the Acoustical Environment" dimension and items pertaining to the non-acoustical environment had stronger loadings with the "Perceived Suitability of the Non-Acoustical Environment" dimension (Scannell et al., 2016).

In contrast, the questionnaire by Yang et al. (2013) included a single item on acoustical perceptions. The results of their factor analysis revealed that this item, alongside several other items pertaining to ambient attributes (e.g., lighting, temperature, air quality), loaded highly onto the same dimension. The authors therefore labelled this dimension, "Ambient Attributes" (Yang et al., 2013).

Given this variability, to impose some order and clarity to the analysis, item content is presented and discussed with respect to the codes and themes in the USLSE Model (see Table 5, Subsection 5.1.4). While not all studies explicitly used the conceptual language of the USLSE Model (e.g., Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, and Decisional Control), examples of items representing such constructs were identifiable from the item content domain across all six questionnaires. Item content which did not address these areas but pertained to perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment (e.g., overall perceptions of a space) is also discussed. A general evaluation of the item content/phrasing is presented throughout. An overview of the item

content in relation to factor analytic interpretation by the authors as well as the USLSE Model is presented in Table 12.

Perceptions of the Spatial and Ergonomic Environment

As mentioned previously, in Study 1, several Spatial and Ergonomic characteristics of the physical environment were identified as important to the student learning space experience, to varying degrees. These included perceptions of fit between spatial density (volume or size of the space), social density (crowding or number of users), the furniture arrangement and seating location, size of desks, furniture comfort within the space, and learning activities (Study 1). Five of the six questionnaires which were included in the present review, following quality appraisal, addressed perceptions of spatial characteristics. These included the questionnaires by Beckers et al. (2016a), Castilla et al. (2017), Scannell et al., (2013), and Yang et al. (2013). The extent to which the different spatial characteristics and number of items varied greatly between instruments.

First, two questionnaires, those by Beckers et al. (2016a) and Scannell et al. (2016), included items which measured students' perceptions of furniture comfort. Specifically, Beckers et al. assessed the perceived importance of "the comfort of the furniture" in learning spaces, while Scannell et al. assessed whether the "comfort of furniture" enhanced or interfered with students' current activities at the time of completing the questionnaire. Secondly, only one questionnaire, that by Castilla et al. (2017), assessed perceptions of physical density (size of the space); students were asked students to rate the extent to which they agree or disagree with the statement "In my opinion the classroom is spacious". Thirdly, only the questionnaire by Castilla et al. included an item pertaining to students' perceptions of desk size, asking students to rate the appropriateness of the "size of the working surface". Fourthly, Yang et al. (2013) and Castilla et al. (2017) assessed the arrangement of the space. Specifically, Yang et al. asked students to rate both their satisfaction with the room layout and the degree to which they believe the room layout impacted upon their "performance", while Castilla et al. included an item pertaining to the appropriateness of the "furniture arrangement". None of the six studies included following quality appraisal included questionnaires with items that addressed perceptions of social density (crowding) or seating location.

Overall, these findings are concerning given that a number of quantitative and qualitative studies have highlighted the negative learning-related consequences of high social density and task-

incongruent furniture arrangements, including, task performance deficits, lower concept learning, course performance gains and deficits, and engagement in learning activities (Becker et al., 1973; Brooks, 2012; Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Koneya, 1976; Levine et al., 1980; Scannell et al., 2016; Shernoff et al., 2017; Whiteside et al., 2010).

Further, three of the six questionnaires (by Beckers et al., 2016a; Castilla et al., 2017; Scannell et al., 2016) included items concerning Spatial and Ergonomic characteristics which were not reflected in the USLSE Model. These included the perceived importance of “a central location of learning settings in the building” and “transparency/unconfinedness of the learning environment” (Beckers et al., 2016a); affective impressions of the environment as “well laid out” and being “well positioned” (Castilla et al., 2017); and perceived appropriateness of “dimensions”, “location and access”, and “layout of installations” (Castilla et al., 2017). Despite this, many of these items are ambiguously phrased. By way of illustration, generally phrased items such as “dimensions”, “well laid out”, and “furniture” are insufficiently detailed compared to items such as “furniture comfort”, “furniture arrangement”, and “room layout”. In addition, item terminology such as “transparency/unconfinedness” may be difficult for participants to comprehend. As mentioned previously, ambiguously phrased questionnaire items may increase the risk of erroneous responses and in turn measurement error (Wilson & MacLean, 2012).

Perceptions of the Acoustical Environment

To reiterate, acoustical characteristics of the environment were identified as important in the USLSE Model. These included students’ perceptions of fit between their learning activities and characteristics of the acoustical environment within their learning spaces, including, noise from people talking, noise from equipment (e.g., radio and ventilation systems), and the background noise level (Study 1).

Only one of the questionnaires, by Castilla et al. (2017), included a single item on the appropriateness of the “noise level”, specifically within the classroom environment. Further, one questionnaire, by Scannell et al. (2016), included a single item pertaining to noise from other people talking and moving, asking participants to rate the degree to which “people talking, moving” interfered with or enhanced their present activities. Use of such ‘double-barrelled’ items (i.e., items that assess multiple issues and only allow for only a single answer) should be avoided to minimise

measurement error (Wilson & MacLean, 2012). None of the questionnaires included items which explicitly addressed noise from equipment such as fans or radio systems.

Three of the questionnaires, including those by Castilla et al. (2017), Scannell et al. (2016), and Yang et al. (2013), contained items which pertained to characteristics of the acoustical environment which were not reflected in the USLSE Model. The most frequent examples of this were the use of items which asked students to rate the overall acoustical environment in their learning spaces, including, the perceived consequences of the overall acoustical environment. Examples included the perceived appropriateness of “acoustical conditions” within classroom spaces (Castilla et al., 2017); the frequency of perceived consequences of the overall acoustical environment, such as, “annoyance”, “stress”, “conversational privacy”, and “difficulty hearing” (Scannell et al., 2016); and satisfaction with and perceived impact of “acoustics (the audio contact with the instructor and the ability to hear the presenter etc.)” on performance (Yang et al., 2013). To reiterate, the use of general (i.e., ambiguous) item content can lead to erroneous responses among participants and thus increased measurement error (Wilson & MacLean, 2012). It is worth noting that Scannell et al. (2016) included items which did not reflect the concerns of the participants in Study 1, including, the perceived suitability of “continuous noise”, “intermittent noise”, and “reverberation (echo)”.

Previous research has highlighted the role of the acoustical environment, including, the impact of different acoustical characteristics such as noise type (e.g., silent, white noise, conversation) on cognitive task performance; noise level or volume (low versus high) on cognitive task performance and mood; and background noise when the space is occupied, unoccupied, and reverberation time on perceived suitability of the environment for learning and environment-related well-being (Marchand et al., 2014; Salamé & Baddeley, 1987; Scannell et al., 2016).

Perceptions of the Ambient Environment

A third construct in the USLSE Model concerned students’ perceptions of Ambient Fit more broadly. This included perceptions of the following ambient environmental characteristics: thermal environment (temperature and air quality/ventilation), lighting (artificial and natural), and the attractiveness of a space (i.e., pleasant use of colour and window views to outside spaces) (Study 1).

Four of the six questionnaires (by Beckers et al., 2016a; Castilla et al., 2017; Scannell et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2013), assessed students' perceptions of temperature and three of the six questionnaires (by Castilla et al., 2017; Scannell et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2013) assessed air quality/ventilation. Two of the six questionnaires (Castilla et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2013) measured students' perceptions of artificial lighting and a further three assessed their perceptions of natural lighting (Beckers et al., 2016a; Castilla et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2013). Finally, one of the questionnaires, by Beckers et al. (2016a) assessed the attractiveness/aesthetics of the space in terms of colour. None of the questionnaires, however, specifically assessed the attractiveness of the space in terms of window views.

Three of the six questionnaires contained items relating to the aesthetic environment which were not considered in the USLSE Model. This included "the presence of plants" (Beckers et al., 2016a). However, other ambient characteristics assessed included generally phrased items concerning perceptions of overall lighting and perceptions of windows in general. Examples include the extent to which "lighting" enhances or interferes with students' activities (Castilla et al., 2017), affective impressions of the environment as "well lit" (Castilla et al., 2017) and the perceived appropriateness of "windows" (Castilla et al., 2017). As mentioned in previous subsections, general phraseology of questionnaire items can lead to ambiguity, thus erroneous responses, and in turn measurement error (Wilson & MacLean, 2012).

As mentioned in earlier chapters, quantitative research has highlighted the impact of ambient variables in University learning spaces, such as, the lighting levels on cognitive performance (Maas et al., 1974); lighting and temperature levels on cognitive performance and mood (Marchand et al., 2014); window views (presence of green space versus concrete wall) on students' course attitudes and performance (Benfield et al., 2015); and the presence versus absence of plants on students' perceptions of informal learning spaces (Scannell et al., 2016).

Perceptions of Privacy

A fourth construct in the USLSE Model concerned students' perceptions of Privacy Fit. This overlapped to a degree with perceptions of Acoustical and Spatial Fit and included perceptions of input and output from others, including, noise from other people talking, interruptions from other

people, seeing other people moving, being observed by other people, and speech privacy (disturbing others). Other examples included architectural privacy and the need to be surrounded by others.

Three of the questionnaires (Beckers et al., 2016a; Scannell et al., 2016) included items which assessed perceptions of privacy. Beckers et al. (2016a) assessed privacy preference using two questions that concerned output to others, including, “I find it unpleasant when others can see what I do” and “I find it unpleasant when others can hear what I say”. While a third item was concerned with architectural privacy and asked students to rate the importance of “transparency/unconfinedness of the learning environment” (Beckers et al., 2016a), the item was double-barrelled and used ambiguous terminology. Scannell et al. (2016) included an item pertaining to “conversational privacy (you can’t overhear others or be overheard by them)”, however, the item was double-barrelled in nature and asked participants to rate two separate experiences. Finally, Beckers et al. (2016a) included items pertaining to students’ need to be surrounded by others. Specifically, items addressed students’ preferences for interaction/communication, including, “I enjoy being with others”, “I enjoy working with others”, and “I go to school for company too”.

Perceptions of Decisional Control

A final construct identified in the USLSE Model reflected perceptions of the physical environment was Decisional Control. This referred to students’ ability to choose suitable space(s) for their learning activities, including, their preferred space and alternative spaces. Two questionnaires which were included following quality appraisal contained items which concerned Decisional Control, were those by Beckers et al. (2016a) and Kaya and Burgess (2007).

In line with the USLSE Model, Beckers et al. (2016a) included an item which referred to the perceived importance of being able to “decide for myself where I work on my study activities”. The questionnaire by Beckers et al. (2016a) also referred to the perceived importance of being able “to decide when to work on my study activities”. While this item clearly relates to decisional control, it is unclear whether the question addresses, for example, the opening hours of campus learning spaces than opposed to the physical or socio-physical environment.

In addition, while Kaya and Burgess (2007) assessed territorial cognitions, several of the items overlapped with Decisional Control, including the need to access one’s preferred seating location

and beliefs about the consequences of being unable to access one's preferred seating location. An example item pertaining to the need to access a particular seat within the classroom environment is "in larger classrooms there is more of a concern that someone will sit in the seat I am used to". Examples relating to the perceived consequences include "I get annoyed when I have to sit in a different seat" and "I get anxious during exams if I have to sit somewhere other than my usual seat". None of the questionnaires, however, included items which addressed students' perceptions of their ability to access alternative spaces, e.g., when their preferred space is incongruent with their learning activities (Study 1).

Other Physical and/or Socio-Physical Environmental Characteristics

Perceptions of environmental characteristics not included in the USLSE Model were addressed by four of the six questionnaires included following quality appraisal, including those by Beckers et al. (2016a), Castilla et al. (2016), Kaya and Burgess (2007), and Kim (2016). Item content pertains to three main areas: (i) preferences for and importance of different types of learning spaces, (ii) territorial cognitions and/or perceptions of behavioural control (iii) ambiguous item content.

With regards to preferences and perceived importance of different types of learning spaces, both Beckers et al. (2016a) and Kim (2016) included items which focused on preferences for and the perceived importance of different types of learning spaces. Examples include preference for engaging in individual study in a "catering area", "café", "entrance area", "corridor", "project room", and "personal cockpit" (Beckers et al., 2016a). Other examples include the perceived importance of "individual study space", "group study space", and "space for reading" (Kim, 2016). While such items provide insight into students' demands or requirements of their learning spaces, they do not provide insight into the extent to which the environment meets those requirements. As mentioned previously, a more ecologically valid approach to studying learning space perceptions is to measure the degree to which the environment meets students' requirements for a particular activity.

Finally, all six questionnaires included items with somewhat ambiguous content. This included items which asked students to rate their perceptions of the overall learning spaces, such as, "How well does the environment in general in this learning space interfere with or enhance your ability to use this space for your activities?" (Scannell et al., 2016); the perceived importance of "individual study spaces" and "group study spaces" (Kim, 2016); and the perceived appropriateness of "furniture",

“windows”, “cladding”, “flooring”, “doors”, and “ceilings” (Castilla et al., 2017). As mentioned previously, such ambiguous items may be subject to multiple different interpretations by students, leading to erroneous responding, and subsequently measurement error. For example, when reflecting on the environment in general, students may consider a wide range of environmental characteristics, depending on what is salient to them, for example, specific acoustical qualities, lighting, temperature, furniture arrangement, crowding, and/or window views.

Item content summary

An analysis of the item content for each of the questionnaires revealed that none of the six instruments sufficiently addressed the issues pertinent to the USLSE Model (Study 1). In addition, many of the questionnaires contained items pertaining to issues which were not discussed by students and instructors in Study 1. Some of these items had limitations (e.g., ambiguity, relevance, and/or respondent burden). Nevertheless, it may be worth drawing upon others for subsequent questionnaire development (e.g., specific acoustical and privacy-related characteristics like continuous noise, intermittent noise, reverberation, and the presence of plants).

Table 12.*Item content domains*

Instrument/Dimensions of the USLSE Model	Beckers et al. (2016a)	Castilla et al. (2017)	Kaya & Burgess (2007)	Kim (2016)	Scannell et al. (2016)	Yang et al. (2013)
Spatial density (i.e., volume or size of space)	No	"Spacious" (Dimension 1a)	No	No	No	No
Social density (i.e., number of users, crowding)	No	No	No	No	No	No
Furniture arrangement	No	"Furniture arrangement" (Dimension 2a)	No	No	No	"Satisfaction with the room layout" and "degree to which you believe the Room layout ... impacts your performance" (Dimension 1b).
Seating location	No	No	No	No	No	No
Desk size	"Size of the working surface" (Dimension 2a)	No	No	No	"Comfort of Furniture" (Dimension 1d)	No
Furniture comfort	"Comfort of the furniture" (Dimension 2a)	No	No	No		No
Other Spatial and Ergonomic Attributes	"A central location of learning settings in the building", "Transparency/unconfinedness of the learning environment" (Dimension 2d)	"Well laid out", well positioned" (Dimension 1a) "Dimensions", "location and access" (Dimension 2b) "Layout of installations" (Dimension 2b)	No	No		No
Acoustical Fit						
Noise from others talking	No	No	No	No	"People talking, moving" (Dimension 1c)	No
Noise from others moving	No	No	No	No	"People talking, moving" (Dimension 1c)	No

Noise from equipment (e.g., ventilation or radio systems)	No	No	No	No	No	No
Noise level (i.e., volume)	No	"Noise level" (Dimension 2b)	No	No	No	No
Other Acoustical Attributes	No	(Overall) "Acoustical conditions" (Dimension 2b)	No	No	"Continuous noise", "Intermittent noise", "Reverberation (echo)" (Dimension 1c) "Annoyance", "Stress", "Fatigue", "Difficulty hearing", "Difficulty talking" (Dimension 1a). "Relaxed", "energised", "productive" (Dimension 1b). "Distraction, broken conversation".(negative consequences of the acoustical environment, removed following factor analysis). "Conversational privacy (you can't overhear others or be overheard by them)" (Positive consequence of the acoustical environment, removed following factor analysis) "Temperature" (Dimension 1d)	"Satisfaction with the acoustics (the audio contact with instructor and the ability to hear the presenter, etc.)" and "degree to which you believe the Acoustics (the audio contact with instructor and the ability to hear presenter, etc.) ... impacts your performance" (Dimension 1a)
Temperature	"Temperature of the learning environment" (Dimension 2a)	"Good temperature" (Dimension 1c) "Thermal conditions" (Dimension 2d)	No	No	"Temperature" (Dimension 1d)	"Satisfaction with the temperature" and "degree to which you believe the temperature ... impacts your performance" (Dimension 1a)
Air quality or ventilation	No	"Good ventilation" (Dimension 1a)	No	No	"Air Quality" (Dimension 1d)	"Satisfaction with the Air Quality" and "degree to which you believe the air quality ... impacts your performance" (Dimension 1a)

								"Ventilation conditions" (Dimension 2d)	
Artificial lighting	No	"Good artificial lighting" (Dimension 1f)	No	No	No	No		"Satisfaction with the Artificial Lighting" and "degree to which you believe the Artificial Lighting ... impacts your performance" (Dimension 1a)	
		"Artificial lighting" (Dimension 2c)							
Natural lighting	"Presence of natural light" (Dimension 2a)	"Good daylight" (1e)	No	No	No	No		"Satisfaction with daylight" and "degree to which you believe the daylight ... impacts your performance" (Dimension 1a)	
		"Daylight" (Dimension 2c)							
		"Daylight" (2d)							
Use of colour	"Use of colour" (Dimension 2b)	No	No	No	No	No		No	
Window views	No	No	No	No	No	No		No	
Other Ambient Attributes	"Presence of plants" (Dimension 2b)	"Well lit" (Dimension 1f)	No	No	No	(Overall) "Lighting" (Dimension 1d)		No	
		"Decoration" (Dimension 2a)							
Privacy Fit									
Architectural privacy	"Transparency/ unconfinedness of the learning environment" (Dimension 1d)	No	No	No	No	No		No	
Interruptions	No	No	No	No	No	No		No	
Visual distractions	No	No	No	No	No	No		No	
Being observed by others	"I find it unpleasant when others can see what I do" (Dimension 1a)	No	No	No	No	No		No	
Speech privacy (disturbing others)	"I find it unpleasant when others can hear what I say" (Dimension 1a)	No	No	No	No	"Conversational privacy (you can't overhear others or be overheard by them)" (Positive consequence of the acoustical environment,		No	

					removed following factor analysis)	
Need to be surrounded by others	"I enjoy being with others", "I enjoy working with others", "I go to school for company too" (Dimension 1b)	No	"I like to be able to see the other students when I am in a class" (item dropped)	No	No	No
Other Privacy Attributes	No	No	"I worry about disturbing others when I am in class", "I like to be able to see the other students when I am in a class" (item dropped)	No	No	No
Decisional Control						
Ability to choose suitable space(s)/preferred spaces	"I think it is important to decide for myself where I work on my study activities" (Dimension 1c)	No	Claiming a Particular Seat: "I get annoyed when I have to sit in a different seat", "I like to get to class early to get the same seat each day", "I try not to sit in someone else's seat if I can help it", "In larger classrooms, there is more of a concern that someone will sit in the seat I am used to", "I get anxious during exams if I have to sit somewhere other than my usual seat".(Dimension 1a) "I would be more concerned with someone sitting in my seat in a large classroom rather than in a small classroom", "I prefer classes with assigned seating" (items dropped)	No	No	No
Ability to choose alternative space(s)	No	No	No	No		No
Other Attributes of Decisional Control	"I think it is important to decide for myself when I work on my study activities" (Dimension 1c)	No	No	No		No
Other environmental attributes. I.e., not Spatial	"Finish of floors" (Dimension 2b)	"Well organised", "good"	"I like to partition and define my own space in a class", "I	"Interior of the library building", "Individual study	No	"Satisfaction with the Visibility (ability to see blackboard, whiteboard, projector,

and Ergonomic,
Acoustical, Ambient,
Privacy, or Decisional
Control

Preference for individual study:
“catering area, “café”, “entrance
area”, “corridors” (Dimension 3a)

Preference for collaborative study:
“project room” and “personal
cockpit” (Dimension 3b)

equipment”,
“easy access”,
“oppressive”,
“good design”
(Dimension 1a)

“Cosy”,
“cheerful”,
“pleasant”, “safe”
(Dimension 1b)

“Helps me to
concentrate”,
“comfortable”,
“intimate”
(Dimension 1c)

“Old”, “new”
(Dimension 1d)

“Outward
facing/Exterior”
(Dimension 1e)

“Damp”,
“oppressive”
(Dimension 1g)

“Location and
access”
(Dimension 2a)

“Humidity
conditions”
(Dimension 2c)

“Cladding”,
“walls”, “ceiling”,
“doors”,
“flooring”
(Dimension 2a)

“Windows”
(Dimension 2d)

“Good furniture”
(Dimension 1a)

Furniture
(Dimension 2b)

have strong need for a clear
definition of my own space in
a class”, “I like to keep
“trespassers” and “intruders”
out of my own space in a
class” (Dimension 1b)

“I would ask someone to
move if they took the seat
which I usually like to sit”, “I
tend to sit in the same
general area in every class
(front, back, middle ...”,
“Compared to other
students, I bring more things
to class”.(items dropped)

space”, “Group study space”,
“Space for reading”
(Dimension 1b)

“Outdoor seating”, “Café”,
“Lounge”, “Exhibition space”
(Dimension 1c)

visual aids, etc.)”, and “degree to which
you believe the Visibility (ability to see
blackboard, whiteboard, projector,
visual aids, etc.) ... impacts your
performance”.(Dimension 1b)

Non-physical and/or socio-physical attributes	"Presence of desktop computers", "presence of printing facilities" (Dimension 2c)	"Equipment" (Dimension 2c)	No	"Books", "Reference and information services", "Circulation", "Library cultural events", "Instructions/ workshops", "Library staff", "Student workers", "Staff at =subsidiary facilities" (Dimension 1a) "Wireless connection".(Dimension 1b)	"Satisfaction with the Hardware (projector, computer, clicker, smart board, etc.)", "degree to which you believe the Hardware (projector, computer, clicker, smartboard, etc.) ... impact your performance", "satisfaction with the Software (Software installed on classroom computers, and the Internet)", and "degree to which you believe the Software (Software installed on classroom computers, and the Internet) ... impact your performance" (Dimension 1c)
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Note. Content in brackets represents the dimensions that the items belonged to as proposed by the corresponding authors following factor analysis.

5.4. Chapter Discussion and Conclusions

5.4.1. Summary of findings

The aims of the systematic review were to identify the measurement instruments used in previous research to assess students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces and to critically evaluate their suitability for the subsequent empirical chapter in this thesis. Measurement instruments were included for an in-depth review if they attempted to address at least one criterion from each of the following psychometric properties: (i) content validity, (iii) construct reliability, and (iv) internal consistency reliability.

136 instruments which measured students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces were identified, however, only six sufficiently addressed content validity, construct validity, and internal consistency reliability and were therefore included in the review. With regards to the instrument characteristics, all the six instruments sought to measure students' perceptions rather than instructors. Questionnaires originated from Spain, the Netherlands, Canada, and the US. None of the six questionnaires were developed in a UK HEI context. Half of the instruments were developed to assess perceptions of classroom spaces and the other half assessed perceptions of out-of-class spaces, including, informal learning spaces and library spaces.

In considering the psychometric issues, each of the six papers were included because they developed questionnaires which assessed content validity, construct validity, and internal consistency reliability. However, the extent to which the three psychometric properties were addressed for each instrument varied.

In summary, only two measurement instruments considered all three criteria for content validity: (i) user input (e.g., via pilot studies, focus groups, and/or interviews); (ii) input from experts or professionals (e.g., environmental psychologists, engineers, architects, university management, professionals involved in learning and teaching), and (iii) input from literature reviews. In relation to construct validity, each of the instruments failed to use robust factor extraction techniques (parallel and minimum average partial analyses) while several contained low loading and cross-loading items. As mentioned previously, such issues may lead to measurement invalidity and subsequently invalid inferential findings (Elf et al., 2016; Francis et al., 2016). Finally, internal consistency reliability

analyses for half of the instruments were insufficient. Specifically, subscales contained alpha values below the recommended minimum threshold and/or analyses were conducted at the overall scale level. This latter issue may lead to inflated alpha values (Cronbach, 1950).

None of the questionnaires contained sufficient conceptual underpinnings. Established theoretical frameworks and/or construct definitions, such as, Relph's (1976) place identity theory, Altman's (1975) definition of privacy, Appel-Meulenbroek et al.'s (2011) definition of personal control, Beard and Wilson's (2006) Learning Combination Lock Model, and Altman and Chemer's (1980) definition of territoriality were discussed a priori. However, it was unclear how these frameworks informed item content beyond the operationalisation of variables. In addition, assessment of the key components of the USLSE Model (Study 1), and person-environment transaction theories by extension, were infrequent and varied within and between instruments.

That said, some aspects of the USLSE Model were discernible from each of the questionnaires. For example, two subscales (of four) from one instrument (by Scannell et al., 2016) assessed the dynamic nature of students' learning space perceptions by including a frequency scale. Similarly, some instruments assessed functionality (e.g., suitability for specific learning activities), however, this was infrequent and varied between instruments. Decisional Control was assessed by only two instruments (Beckers et al., 2016a; Kaya & Burgess, 2007). As commented on, while underpinning theoretical frameworks were not a prerequisite for inclusion, a lack of theory can severely hinder the content and construct validity of questionnaires and subsequent inferential findings (Elf et al., 2016; Francis et al., 2016).

In addition, none of the questionnaires sufficiently addressed Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, or Decisional Control. Meanwhile, all six instruments contained item content which could be considered ambiguous. As discussed, ambiguous item content (e.g., double-barrelled items) may have multiple interpretations, lead to erroneous responding, and therefore increased measurement error (Wilson & MacLean, 2012). At a more pragmatic level, the inclusion of items with ambiguous content may increase respondent burden and therefore should be avoided in future studies to minimise participant dropout.

5.4.2. Limitations and strengths

As with similar reviews on institutional environments (e.g., Elf et al., 2016), the interdisciplinary nature of learning space research may have caused some limitations. This review was conducted from an environmental psychology perspective and as a result, researchers from other disciplines such as architecture or education may differ in their selection of search terms, databases, inclusion and quality appraisal criteria, and conceptual interpretations. Due to the diversity of keywords and publications, it is not possible for any review of this nature to capture all the relevant studies. Furthermore, several references were not accessible through our institutional repositories ($n = 62$). That said, our broad search strategy and focus on grey literature databases aimed to ensure that a representative sample of studies were retrieved across a range of disciplines with a variety of methodological and conceptual terminology. In addition, the search protocol was subject to discussion among a multidisciplinary research team, consisting of three researchers with a variety of psychology backgrounds, one researcher with an engineering background and experience in HE senior management, and two academic librarians in social science disciplines.

A further limitation relates to quality appraisal. It is worth highlighting that the author deemed existing standardised quality appraisal tools as insufficient for the purposes of the review. This may have led to an element of subjectivity. That said, quality appraisal criteria for inclusion and exclusion criteria were based on previous discussions of best practice pertaining to psychometric scale development procedures (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Francis et al., 2016; Field et al., 2012; Osborne, 2014; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014; Wilson & MacLean, 2012).

In addition, final requirements for inclusion were strict, focusing on an explicit adherence to psychometric scale development procedures. Ultimately, poor reporting quality may have stemmed from the requirements for publication (e.g., word count). That said, fully transparent scale development procedures and results are the most appropriate way to allow researchers and practitioners to best select the most appropriate instruments (Francis et al., 2016).

Finally, although the review followed systematic review procedure, inter-rater reliability was conducted on only 10% of abstracts and titles. That said, inter-rater reliability scores between the author and three members of his supervisory team were high ($\alpha > 0.80$). In addition, unlike most

previous reviews of learning space research, this review adopted far more explicit and rigorous methodological steps and had a narrower, more detailed, and critical focus.

5.4.3. Conclusions and directions for the subsequent empirical chapters

This systematic review identified 136 papers which used quantitative scales to measure students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in relation to their campus learning spaces. Only six questionnaires met quality appraisal criteria for inclusion. A more nuanced critical analysis of these instruments revealed several limitations, including, failures to sufficiently address content validity, limitations in construct validity and internal consistency analyses. Where theoretical underpinnings and constructs were discussed a priori, it was unclear how and whether these informed the design of the questionnaires utilised, beyond operationalisation of variables. Overall, the instruments lacked sufficient item content in relation to the USLSE Model. Bearing this in mind, several useful items pertaining specifically to the ambient and acoustical environment which were not addressed in the USLSE Model became apparent (Beckers et al., 2016a; Scannell et al., 2016). Overall, however, the findings are supportive of the conclusions from Chapter 2 and demonstrate the need for a new robust and psychometrically tested Learning Space Experience Questionnaire. This is addressed in the subsequent Chapter (Chapter 6, Study 3).

6. CHAPTER SIX

STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF THE PHYSICAL AND SOCIO-PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENT IN THEIR UNIVERSITY CAMPUS LEARNING SPACES: ASSOCIATED LEARNING AND PSYCHOLOGICAL OUTCOMES

6.1. Chapter Introduction

6.1.1. Background

Over six decades of empirical and theoretical works have highlighted relationships between the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes in university campus learning spaces (e.g., Becker et al., 1973; Brooks, 2011, 2012; Choi et al., 2014a; Marchand et al., 2014; Sommer, 1966; Sommer & Olsen, 1980; Wollin & Montagne, 1981). In addition, numerous scholars, HE managers, and design consultancies have called for an increase in student involvement in the process of evaluating new and designing existing campus learning spaces (Aronoff, 2016; Cleveland & Fisher, 2014; Glancy, 2007; Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Lippincott, 2009; Somerville and Collins, 2008). According to such works, student involvement in the design process can lead to greater feelings of ownership over the learning space and thus the learning process (Alexi Marmot Associates, 2012). Despite the latter assumption, studies on the relationships between students' perceptions of the physical environment and their learning and psychological outcomes are scarce. Of the little research which has investigated this, the focus is largely on classroom spaces. Furthermore, such research suffers from significant methodological and conceptual flaws, outlined below.

First, as highlighted in the introduction to the thesis, overview of the empirical literature, and systematic review (Chapter 1, 2, and 3 [Study 2], respectively), the constructs assessed in previous empirical work and their corresponding measurement instruments, are hindered by a lack of content validity. Specifically, it is unclear whether the environmental characteristics and learning and psychological outcomes assessed are relevant to students' learning space experiences. Secondly, the constructs and their corresponding measurement instruments are often theoretically agnostic. Where authors have made 'theoretical claims' (e.g., Hill & Epps, 2010), it is unclear whether and how these theories underpin the constructs assessed and their quantitative measurement instruments. Finally, the constructs and their corresponding instruments lack sufficient construct validity and reliability analyses. Where these have been conducted, analyses are implemented incorrectly, incomplete, poorly reported, lack sufficient transparency, and/or validity and reliability were poor. Insufficiencies in each of these areas may hinder the validity and reliability of the conclusions drawn from subsequent inferential analyses using these instruments. The reader is directed to Chapters 2 (Overview of the Empirical and Theoretical Literature) and 5 (Systematic Review) for a more detailed description and evaluation of this research.

Addressing the limitations of previous research is important because, if more positive perceptions of the environment are associated with learning and psychological benefits, this would support so-called 'user-centred' approach to learning space research, evaluation, and design. This study aims to address the issues outlined above by investigating a sample of students across three academic library spaces at a Scottish, multi-campus and multi-geographic, HEI.

There are three drivers for the decision to focus on academic library spaces. First, there is a lack of empirical evidence on the relationships between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes in out-of-class learning spaces relative to classroom spaces. This is somewhat ironic since HE learning should predominantly occur outside of the physical classroom environment (Scannell et al., 2016). Secondly, a preliminary qualitative study (Study 1) highlighted several environmental concerns which may be more applicable to students' experiences in out-of-class learning spaces. These concerns pertained to perceptions of Privacy Fit and Decisional Control. Thirdly, it became clear from the focus groups (Study 1) that students use a wide range of spaces for out-of-class learning activities, including, library silent and group spaces, social spaces, open-access classrooms (e.g., lecture and seminar rooms), and discipline-specific learning spaces (e.g., art studios

and radio stations). While such choice of spaces for out-of-class learning may be beneficial, there is a need to narrow the focus of the study in order to draw conclusions about specific campus areas. The campus multi-functional library and resource centres at the target university, provide a variety of spaces which may be used for both individual and collaborative learning activities.

The current study describes the psychometric development and assessment of a new measurement instrument (questionnaire) which assesses students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and the associated learning and psychological outcomes within their academic library learning spaces. The so-called University Students' Library Learning Space Experience (USLLSE) Questionnaire is based on the USLSE Model. The second aim of this study is to explore the statistical associations between students' environmental perceptions and their learning and psychological outcomes proposed in the USLSE Model. The model is driven by the focus group findings (Study 1, Chapter 4) and their discussion in relation to relevant research and theory discussed in Chapter 2.

6.1.2. The University Students' Learning Space Experience Model

According to the USLSE Model, environmental perceptions and associated outcomes are dynamic and therefore vary in frequency over time as a function of circumstances. This dynamic nature is in line with the person-environment transaction theories presented in Chapter 2. Further, the model considers the functionality of environmental perceptions and outcomes, in line with ecological and person-environment fit theories (e.g., Barker, 1968; Gibson, 1979; Costall, 1995; Michelson, 1976; Wicker, 1987). Thus, driven by the learning activities described in Study 1, perceptions and outcomes should be considered in relation to two types of activities: individual and collaborative learning.

Two environmental perception constructs are key to the Model. The first construct relates to students' perceptions of Person-Environment Fit. Based on Michelson's (1976) construct of mental congruence, Person-Environment Fit refers to a student's beliefs about the extent to which a learning space is congruent with (i.e., fits) their needs for a particular learning activity. Person-Environment Fit perceptions are defined by several sub-constructs which represent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical, Ambient, and Privacy Fit.

The second construct pertains to students' perceptions of Decisional Control. Perceived Decisional control within the model is defined based on the focus group analysis and the work of Averill (1973); it refers to one's beliefs about their ability to choose a suitable (e.g., preferred space) for their learning activities and the availability of suitable alternatives when, for example, one's preferred space is incongruent with their needs (Averill, 1973; Bell et al., 2001; Gatersleben & Griffin, 2016). While perceptions of Decisional Control can be interpreted as a meta-construct of Perceived Person-Environment Fit, to distinguish it from other constructs and in line with Averill (1973), it is referred to as Decisional Control.

The third set of constructs pertains to the Learning and Psychological Consequences of environments which are perceived to be congruent or incongruent with the requirements of students' learning activities. This includes Cognitive-Affective Outcomes (e.g., Stress), Engagement in Learning Activities, and Quantity and Quality of Work produced.

To recap, Michelson (1976) proposed that perceptions of Person-Environment Fit can be thought of as a self-fulfilling prophecy. Therefore, in the context of the USLSE Model, if a learner believes that the physical and/or socio-physical environment constrains their ability to perform an individual or collaborative learning activity, then they are less likely to engage in this activity. Following this logic, less frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit (i.e., more negative perceptions of fit) may lead to negative learning task-related outcomes, including, increased Academic Stress, decreased Engagement and increased Disengagement, and Quantity and Quality of work produced. Conversely, more frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit (i.e., more positive perceptions of fit) may lead to better learning and psychological outcomes.

As with Person-Environment Fit, based on the interpretation of the data from Study 1, the wider empirical literature on institutional (e.g., educational and workplace) environments, and person-environment transaction theories, less Decisional Control is generally seen to have negative consequences (Bell et al., 2001; Gatersleben & Griffin, 2016; Gifford, 2007; Lee & Brand, 2005, 2010; Proshansky et al., 1970). As stated by Sommer (1966) in his research on students' study space preferences, academic libraries should include a variety of spaces, from which different user groups can choose those which best meet their needs:

The ideal library would not be one with all individual study rooms or all open areas but, instead, would contain a diversity of spaces that would meet the needs of introverts and extroverts, lone studiers and group studiers, browsers and day-long researchers ... It is a serious mistake to assume that all people have the same spatial needs (p. 246).

It is therefore reasonable to assume that more frequent (i.e., positive) perceptions of Person-Environment Fit (Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical, Ambient and Privacy) and Decisional Control should result in better (i.e., more positive) outcomes with regards to learning activity-related outcomes in campus (e.g., library) learning spaces, including, reduced Affective Stress, increased Engagement, and increased Quantity and Quality of Work produced. While these relationships are likely to be bi-directional, for pragmatic reasons, this study is predominantly concerned with environmental perceptions as predictors of learning and psychological outcomes.

The model postulates that perceptions of Decisional Control are closely linked with perceptions of Person-Environment Fit. Following this logic, perceived Decisional Control may be improved through learning spaces which are perceived by students as having more frequent Person-Environment Fit. For instance, students with more frequent perceptions of Acoustical Fit should be able find/choose a space or spaces which are more congruent with their needs than students with less frequent perceptions of Acoustical Fit. Therefore, more frequent (i.e., positive) perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical, Ambient, and Privacy Fit should be associated with more frequent (i.e., positive) perceptions of Decisional Control. While this relationship is likely two way, in the present analysis Person-Environment Fit is explored as a predictor of Decisional Control. Again, this is underpinned by a pragmatic justification. Specifically, by understanding the predictors of Decisional Control, guidance can be provided to designers about the types of environmental (e.g., Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical, Ambient, and Privacy-related) considerations that need to be made when designing settings from which students can choose spaces which are most appropriate for their learning. Related to this, the mediation effects are also explored to determine whether the associations between students' perceptions of Person-Environment Fit, Cognitive-Affective Outcomes (Stress), Engagement, and Quality and Quantity of Work produced, can be explained by perceptions of Decisional Control when using the academic library spaces for individual and collaborative learning activities.¹⁹

¹⁹ To reiterate, mediation or indirect effects occur when the relationship between two variables is explained by a third variable (Hair et al., 2017; Hayes, 2018). For mediation to occur, the predictor variable must significantly predict the mediator variable, the mediator should significantly predict the outcome variable, and there must be a significant indirect effect through the mediator (Hair et al., 2017; Hayes, 2018). Full mediation

Predictions based on the University Students' Learning Space Experience Model are presented diagrammatically in Figure 3. The specific aims and hypotheses for Study 3 are presented in the following subsection.

Figure 3.

The University Students' Learning Space Experience Model (Predictions)

6.1.3. Aims and hypotheses

Based on the University Students' Learning Space Experience Model, Study 3 aims to:

1. Investigate the psychometric properties of the USLLSE Questionnaire developed to measure the sub-dimensions proposed in the USLSE Model when using the academic library for individual learning activities. In essence it seeks to explore whether students' learning space perceptions can be reduced into dimensions which represent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit (Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical, Ambient, and Privacy Fit) and Decisional Control when using the academic library for individual learning activities. Due to the exploratory nature of this aim and possible associations between perceptions of the

occurs when the predictor variable only predicts the outcome variable via the mediator (i.e., absence of a direct effect and presence of an indirect effect), while partial mediation occurs when there is a direct effect from the predictor to the outcome, as well as an indirect effect from the predictor to the outcome through the mediator (i.e., presence of both direct and indirect effects) (Hair et al., 2017; Hayes, 2018).

environmental characteristics which constitute each sub-dimension, the potential need to merge items for some of the person-environment fit items was recognised.

2. Statistically explore the associations proposed in the USLSE Model, including, the relationships between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes, when using the academic library for individual learning activities.
3. Investigate the psychometric properties of USLLSE Questionnaire developed to measure the sub-dimensions proposed in the USLSE Model when using the academic library for collaborative learning activities. Specifically, this study seeks explore whether students' learning space perceptions can be reduced into dimensions which represent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit (Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical, Ambient, and Privacy Fit) and Decisional Control when using the academic library for collaborative learning activities. Again, due to the exploratory nature of this aim and possible associations between perceptions of the environmental characteristics which constitute each sub-dimension, the potential need to merge items for some of the person-environment fit items was recognised.
4. Explore the associations proposed in the University Students' Learning Space Experience Model, including, the relationships between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes, when using the academic library for collaborative learning activities.

Specific hypotheses pertaining to the associations between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes are presented in Tables 13 and 14 for Aims 2 and 4, respectively.

Table 13.

Aim 2. Hypothesised relationships between environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes, when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities

Hypothesis	Prediction
Hypothesis 1.	More frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit will be associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control, when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities.
Hypothesis 2.	More frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control will be associated with less frequent Academic Stress, when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities.
Hypothesis 3.	More frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control will be associated with more frequent Engagement in Learning Activities, when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities.
Hypothesis 4.	More frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control will be associated with greater Quantity and Quality of Work, when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities.
Hypothesis 5.	More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control will mediate the relationships between more frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and less frequent Academic Stress, when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities.
Hypothesis 6.	More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control will mediate the relationships between more frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and more frequent Engagement in Learning Activities, when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities.
Hypothesis 7.	More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control will mediate the relationships between more frequent perceptions of Person-Environment fit and greater Quantity and Quality of Work, when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities.

Table 14.

Aim 4. Hypothesised relationships between environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes, when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities

Hypothesis	Prediction
Hypothesis 8.	More frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit will be associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control, when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities.
Hypothesis 9.	More frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control will be associated with less frequent Academic Stress, when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities.
Hypothesis 10.	More frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control will be associated with more frequent Engagement in Learning Activities, when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities.
Hypothesis 11.	More frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control will be associated with greater Quantity and Quality of Work, when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities.
Hypothesis 12.	More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control will mediate the relationships between more frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and less frequent Academic Stress, when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities.
Hypothesis 13.	More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control will mediate the relationships between more frequent perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and more frequent Engagement in Learning Activities, when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities.
Hypothesis 14.	More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control will mediate the relationships between more frequent perceptions of Person-Environment fit and greater Quantity and Quality of Work, when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities.

6.2. Methods

6.2.1. Study design and recruitment

The target population were students who used the academic library spaces at the following Campuses of a Scottish, multi-campus and multi-geographic, HEI: Campuses A, B, or D. Data was collected via an online questionnaire using the eSurvey website (now called SurveyHero) and convenience sampling. Ethical Approval was granted by the School of Media, Culture and Society Ethics Committee at the authors' institution (University of the West of Scotland).

6.2.2. The University Students' Learning Space Experience Questionnaire

Development of the questionnaire

The questionnaire was developed based on several considerations, including the overview of the empirical and theoretical literature (Chapter 2) and focus group findings from Study 1 (Chapter 4). That is, the questionnaire was based on the USLSE Model. The model highlighted the importance of different physical and socio-physical environmental factors in university learning spaces, including, perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, and Decisional Control.

The phrasing of anchor statements, item content, and response options were based on five considerations. First, it was necessary to have a broad range of item content which sufficiently assessed each of the sub-constructs above; this would help to ensure sufficient content validity. Secondly, there was a requirement to balance the sufficiency of item content with respondent burden to ensure as high a response rate as possible and minimise participant burden and dropout.

To address the first two considerations, each of the codes which informed the environmental perception environmental perception subthemes in Study 1 (focus groups) were used to create the questionnaire items. Therefore, the questionnaire items mapped onto perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, and Decisional Control. To further ensure sufficient content validity, the suitability of the questionnaire (content, phrasing, and clarity) was reviewed upon each draft by the author and his supervisory team. The supervisory team have substantive experience working in the HE sector and included an experienced Environmental Psychologist and Vice Principal (Academic). A small sample of postgraduate students ($N = 14$)

completed the questionnaire, 10 of whom provided feedback on the relevance and clarity of the content, including, the phrasing of (i) anchor statements, (ii) items, and (iii) response options. The author considered drawing on useful item content from the six instruments identified in Study 2, however, deemed that it was important to balance sufficiency of item content with respondent burden in an attempt to minimise participant dropout. Thus, item content from Study 2 was not used to inform the USLLSE Questionnaire.

Thirdly, it was important to consider the functionality of the academic library learning spaces for the students at the Scottish, multi-campus and multi-geographic, HEI under investigation. That is, it was necessary to consider each scale in terms of the learning activities that the students engaged in, or the function served by the library learning spaces. As such, the questionnaire included separate sections focusing on either experiences of individual or collaborative learning activities. This was driven by the USLSE Experience Model, i.e., the focus group data and its interpretation in light of previous research and person-environment transaction theories. Fourthly, it was important to assess the dynamic nature of person-environment transactions. Each scale, therefore, asked students to rate the frequency with which they experienced Person-Environment Fit/Misfit, Decisional Control, and Learning and Psychological outcomes.

Finally, it was necessary to measure the outcomes experienced when using the academic libraries for individual and collaborative learning activities, including, Cognitive-Affective Outcomes, Engagement in Learning Activities and Quantity and Quality of Work produced. Consequently, scales from previous research which have been psychometrically tested were adapted to suit the USLSE Model. Again, these considerations were driven by USLSE Model (Study 2).

Structure of the questionnaire

The questionnaire contained three sections in total. Section 1 contained demographic questions pertaining to age, gender, study year, and subject area. Section 2 related to the campus library (Campus A, B, or D) used most often for individual learning activities, while Section 3 referred to the campus library (A, B, or D) used most often for collaborative learning activities. Both Sections 2 and 3 contained contextual questions and Likert-scale items which measured latent constructs representing students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes.

Sections 2 and 3 began with a series of contextual questions regarding the academic library used most often for individual/collaborative study, the frequency with which said academic library was used, and the importance of the academic library for individual/collaborative learning activities. This was followed in both sections by a scale which sought to assess students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their academic libraries; items pertained to their perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, and Decisional Control. Finally, both sections contained three scales which sought to measure students' Cognitive-Affective outcomes (Academic Stress, including, Affective, Behavioural, and Cognitive Stress), Engagement in Learning Activities (Vigour and Dedication), and Quantity and Quality of Work produced.

To minimise measurement error, definitions for individual and collaborative learning activities in the context of the study were provided at the beginning of Sections 2 and 3, respectively. Section 2 began with the following statement "In this study we have defined INDIVIDUAL study as studying alone. Please answer the following questions by reflecting on the campus library that you use most often for INDIVIDUAL study." Section 3 began with the following statement: "In this study we have defined GROUP study as studying with three or more people. Please answer ALL of the questions from now on by reflecting on the campus library that you have used most often for GROUP study."

Measures

Perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment were assessed using 31-item and 34-item Likert-scales, for individual and collaborative learning, respectively. Scales for both individual and collaborative learning activities pertained to Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, and Decisional Control. Four items in the individual learning and six in the collaborative learning sections pertained to resource access (e.g., shared group screens, whiteboards, computers, and printers). To maintain a specific focus on the physical and socio-physical environment and reduce model complexity, these were not included in the analysis.

For both Sections 2 (individual) and 3 (collaborative), all items concerning Person-Environment Fit were anchored with the following statement: "How suitable is this campus library for INDIVIDUAL/GROUP study activities: Over the last academic year, have you ever experienced difficulties participating in INDIVIDUAL/GROUP study due to the following factors?" Example items include "Layout of furniture" and "Background sound/noise level". Items pertaining to Decisional

Control were anchored with “The following statements are about your ability to choose spaces which meet your needs for INDIVIDUAL/GROUP study. Please select the most appropriate response.” Example items include “In my university library the types of spaces that I want to use for INDIVIDUAL/GROUP study are available to me” and “In my university library, when required, I can choose from alternative spaces which are suitable for INDIVIDUAL/GROUP study”. Response options ranged from “Never” (0) to “Always” (4). Due to the nature of the phrasing, lower scores on the Person-Environment Fit variables represented more frequent (i.e., good) fit and high scores represented less frequent (i.e., poorer) fit; in contrast, lower scores on the Decisional Control subscale represented less frequent (i.e., lower Decisional Control) while higher scores represented more frequent (i.e., higher) Decisional Control.

Cognitive-Affective outcomes, when using the academic library spaces for both individual and collaborative learning activities, were assessed using an adapted version of the Lakaev Academic Stress Response Scale (LASRS; Lakaev, 2006, 2009), a measure which quantifies students’ stress responses across four domains: physiological, behavioural, cognitive, and affective stress. The USLLSE Questionnaire included the Affective Stress (i.e., emotional distress) and Behavioural Stress (i.e., concentration, distraction, and avoidance) subscales. Specific item content for both individual and collaborative study sections were identical. Response options ranged from “None of the time” (0) to “All of the time” (4), with low scores representing less frequent (i.e., reduced) experiences of Academic Stress. An example item is “My emotions stopped me from studying”.

Experiences of Engagement in Learning Activities, when using the academic library spaces for individual and collaborative learning activities, were assessed using adapted versions of the UTRECHT Work Engagement Scale for Students (Schaufeli et al., 2002) and the UTRECHT Collective Work Engagement Scale (Salanova et al., 2003). Both scales quantify three components of work engagement among university students: vigour, dedication, and absorption. The present study utilised adapted versions of the (Collective) Vigour and (Collective) Dedication subscales to assess self-reported Engagement in Learning Activities in the academic library. According to Schaufeli and Bakker (2002) “vigor is characterised by high levels of energy and mental resilience while working, the willingness to invest effort in one’s work, and persistence even in the face of difficulties” and “dedication refers to being strongly involved in one’s work and experiencing a sense of significance, enthusiasm, inspiration, pride, and challenge” (pp. 4-5). Response options for Vigour and Dedication for individual learning activities ranged from “Never” (0) to “Always” (6), while response options for

Collective Vigour and Collective Dedication ranged from “Never” (0) to “Most of the time” (4). Higher scores represented more frequent (i.e., higher) Engagement in Learning Activities. An example item is “When I was studying I felt mentally strong.”

Finally, the Quantity and Quality of Work produced by students when engaging in individual and collaborative learning activities in the academic libraries was assessed using an adapted version of Lee and Brand’s (2005, 2010) job performance scales. Item content for both individual and collaborative learning activities was altered slightly to reflect the collective nature of work produced when engaging in collaborative learning activities. Response options ranged from “Never” (0) to “Always” (4). Higher scores indicated higher Quantity and Quality of Work produced when engaging in individual and/or collaborative learning activities in the academic library. An example item is “I accomplished a great deal.”

Items for each of the outcome variables, were anchored with the following statement: “Over the last academic year, how often have you experienced the following, when engaging in INDIVIDUAL/GROUP study in your campus library?”

6.2.3. Participants

Participants were students from the same multi-campus Scottish University as those who participated in Study 1. Students were recruited from Campuses A, B, and D. At the time of data collection, there were approximately 8105 students enrolled at Campus A, 2495 at Campus B, and 4147, and at Campus D. The individual study section of the questionnaire (Section 2) was completed by 418 students (approximate response rate = 3%) and the collaborative study section of the questionnaire was completed by 310 (approximate response rate = 2%). 296 participants completed both individual and collaborative learning sections of the questionnaire. Participant ages for individual learning ranged from 18-58 years ($M = 30$ years, $Median = 28$ years) and 17-58 years ($M = 30$ years, $Median = 28$ years) for collaborative. Participant demographics are presented in Table 15.

Table 15.*Participant demographics*

Demographics	Individual learning activities	Collaborative learning activities
Gender		
Male	106	75
Female	312	235
Campus of study		
Campus A	228	170
Campus B	61	87
Campus D	129	53
Study year		
1 st year	68	54
2 nd year	84	64
3 rd year	102	82
4 th year	78	60
Postgraduate (including Masters, PhD, Doctorate)	86	50
Departmental Area		
Business and Enterprise	92	66
Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences	35	29
Education	43	35
Health and Life Sciences	119	86

Media, Cultural and Social Science Disciplines	127	94
Unclear	2	0
Total	418	310

6.2.4. Data collection procedure

Following ethical approval from the School of Media, Culture and Society Ethics Committee, at the author's institution and final amendments to the questionnaire, data were collected online between May 2019 and June 2019. Five e-mails were circulated on behalf of the author to all students at Campuses A, B, and D.

All data was collected and stored in accordance with the principles of the British Psychological Society. On the first page of the online questionnaire, participants were provided with and were asked to read a Participant Information Sheet. On the following page, participants were required to provide their consent, using the following response options "I consent to participating in this study" or "I do not consent to participating in this study". To minimise order effects, upon each circulation of the questionnaire, the author re-arranged Sections 2 (individual learning) and 3 (collaborative learning) as well as the item content within each subscale. After the participants had completed the relevant sections of the questionnaire, they were redirected to a Debriefing Sheet which reiterated the study aims, provided references for further reading, the contact details for the ethics committee chair and the university's student counselling service, and thanked them for their participation.

Participants who responded "Never" to the questions "how often have you used this campus library for INDIVIDUAL/COLLABORATIVE study over the last ACADEMIC YEAR?" were redirected to the subsequent section. Those who responded "Never" to both questions were redirected to the debriefing sheet. The full online questionnaire is available in Appendix G, including, the Participant Information Sheet, Consent Form, Questionnaire, and Debriefing Sheet. Participants were given the opportunity to withdraw from the study by closing the questionnaire before completion. All data was anonymous and stored on password protected and encrypted drives.

6.2.5. Data analysis decisions and procedure

Aims and hypotheses were explored using structural equation modelling (SEM). SEM assesses the relationships between unobserved (i.e., latent) constructs based on the measurement of observed variables or indicators (in this case, questionnaire items) (Hair et al., 2016; Kline, 2016). There are two main approaches: (i) covariance-based SEM (CB-SEM) and (ii) partial least squares SEM (PLS-SEM) (Hair et al., 2017; Kline, 2012). CB-SEM determines the degree of fit between a theoretical model and the covariance matrix that is present in the data (Hair et al., 2017; Kline, 2016). PLS-SEM, on the other hand, aims to maximise the explained and minimise the unexplained variance in the endogenous variables (Hair et al., 2017; Kline, 2016).

CB-SEM is well suited to the comparison and testing of theoretical models. However, PLS-SEM is better suited for studies which seek both to explore and assess a larger number of parameters, that is, relationships between variables (parameters) (Hair et al., 2017). PLS-SEM is widely used in marketing literature (Hair et al., 2017) and has recently been used in cross-sectional questionnaire studies that have been published in the *Journal of Environmental Psychology* (Duchi et al., 2020; Mancha & Yoder, 2015; Wan et al., 2017, 2020; Zhang et al., 2015, 2020). PLS-SEM requires substantially fewer participants relative to the number of parameters estimated, compared to CB-SEM. PLS-SEM is also well-suited to data analysis with non-normal distributions (Hair et al., 2017).

Considering sample size requirements for PLS-SEM, an a priori power calculation with G*Power 3.1. (Faul, Erdfelder, Lang, & Buchner, 2007) was conducted. In line with guidance from Hair et al. (2017) a linear multiple regression analysis was considered with a fixed model, R^2 deviation from zero, with four, five, and six predictors, respectively. Each of the proposed sub-constructs/sub-dimensions (Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control) were used as predictors, with power (1- β) set at 0.95 and $\alpha = 0.05$. It was indicated that $N = 124, 138, 146$ would be required to detect moderate effects ($f^2 = 0.15$) for four, five, and six predictors, respectively. Furthermore, $N = 59, 63, 67$ would be sufficient to detect large effects ($f^2 = 0.35$) for four, five, and six predictors, respectively.

In addition, following the criterion of 10 times the largest number of structural paths directed at a construct in the model, the minimum sample size required to detect a moderate effect was 40, 50, and 60, for four, five, and six predictors, respectively. Following Cohen's criteria for multiple regression for a statistical power of 80%, with $\alpha = 0.05$: $N = 113, 122, \text{ and } 130$ would be

necessary to detect an $R^2 = 0.1$ for four, five, and six predictors, respectively; $N = 41, 45,$ and 48 to detect an $R^2 = 0.25$ for four, five, and six predictors, respectively; $N = 18, 20$ and 21 for an $R^2 = 0.50$ for four, five, and six predictors, respectively; and $N = 11, 12,$ and 13 to detect an $R^2 = 0.75$ for four, five, and six predictors, respectively.

All analyses were conducted using RStudio (RStudio Team, 2019). Analyses were conducted separately for Sections Two and Three (individual and collaborative learning activities) of the questionnaire. Both sets of analyses followed the procedure described below.

Prior to conducting the inferential analyses and following best practice guidance for PLS-SEM (cf. Hair et al., 2017), assumptions of linearity (linear relationships between variables), univariate and multivariate normality (distribution of residuals), and aberrant responders (outliers) were assessed. A series of cross-tabulations were run on the questionnaire items for both individual and collaborative learning activities and detected no violation of the linearity assumption. Tests for univariate normality (Shapiro-Wilk's tests) and multi-variate normality (Mardia's tests), however, indicated that the item responses were significantly non-normal. This is to be expected as Likert-scale (i.e., ordinal) data by its very nature does not conform to a normal distribution (Beaujean, 2014; Finch & French, 2015; Gana & Broc, 2019). This provides further support for the use of PLS-SEM.

Of particular importance for PLS-SEM, outlier analyses were conducted on data for both individual and collaborative learning sections separately. Outlier analyses entailed a combination of Guttman errors (Djouvas et al., 2006; Zijlstra et al., 2007) and Tukey's adjusted boxplots for non-normal distributions (Vanderviere & Hubert, 2004). Ten outlying response patterns were identified in the individual learning section of the questionnaire and three were identified in the collaborative learning section. Upon closer inspection, several outlying participants in the individual learning section included response patterns which were variably more extreme than their peers. However, these responses were deemed to represent real subgroups of the population and were therefore retained to increase statistical power. Two of the three outlying responders in the collaborative learning section consistently used extreme response options (e.g., rating "Always" for the first 41 of 61 questions). All three participants were deemed to be aberrant responders and therefore

removed. In summary, the ten outlying participants for individual study were retained for the analysis, while the three aberrant responders for group study were removed.

Following guidance from Hair et al. (2017), the validity and reliability of the measurement model and questionnaire were then assessed separately for individual and collaborative learning activities. The measurement model represents the relationships between the latent constructs (e.g., Acoustical Fit, Decisional Control, and Academic Stress) and the indicators (i.e., questionnaire items). First, indicator reliability was assessed by inspecting each loading with its corresponding construct. Loadings represent the amount of variance in an item that is explained by the corresponding construct. Hair et al. propose that indicators with loadings < 0.70 should be removed if their removal does not hinder content validity, while all indicators with loadings < 0.40 should be removed regardless.²⁰ A single indicator was removed on each subscale (e.g., Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, Vigour, and Quantity and Quality of Work) where appropriate, with each iteration of the measurement models for both individual ($n = 5$ iterations) and collaborative ($n = 3$ iterations) learning activities, respectively.

With each iteration of the measurement models, the average variance extracted (AVE), cross-loadings, Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio of correlations, and bootstrapped confidence intervals were assessed. The AVE represents the extent to which a construct explains the variance in its indicators. Cross-loadings represent associations between items and their non-corresponding constructs. The HTMT is an estimate of the true correlation between constructs assuming they were perfectly measured. For convergent validity to be established, indicator loadings should ideally be > 0.70 and the AVE must be > 0.50 .²¹ For the establishment of discriminant validity, the loading between an item and its corresponding construct must be greater than its cross-loading with any other construct in the model, HTMT correlations must be < 0.90 (conservative) or 0.95 (liberal) thresholds, and the HTMT bootstrapped confidence intervals must differ significantly from (i.e., not include) a value of 1 (Hair et al., 2017).²² Finally, internal consistency reliability was assessed using

²⁰ Loadings for newly developed social science scales often fall between 0.60 and 0.70; the removal of indicator loadings between 0.40 and 0.70 is therefore at the discretion of the researcher (Hair et al., 2017).

²¹ Convergent validity is the extent to which a measurement item correlates positively with other items that assess the same construct (Hair et al., 2017).

²² Discriminant validity is the degree to which a latent construct is distinct from other constructs in the model (Hair et al., 2017).

Dillon-Goldstein's Rho (composite reliability) and Cronbach's α ; ideal scores for each should fall between 0.70 and 0.95.²³

Upon on the final iterations of both the individual and collaborative learning measurement models (iterations 5 and 3, respectively), the structural relations of the model were assessed, that is, the relationships between latent constructs. Firstly, the R^2 adjusted. values were examined. R^2 adj. represents the amount of variance in the latent outcome variables that is explained by their predictors; values are adjusted for the number of predictors included in the model. Hair et al. (2017) propose the following thresholds for R^2 adj.: 0.25 (weak), 0.50 (moderate), and 0.75 (substantial).

Then, the significance and direction of both the direct and indirect (mediation) path estimates were assessed. As PLS-SEM does not rely on distributional assumptions, the significance of the parameter estimates were obtained using bootstrapping resampling techniques set at $N = 5000$ (cf. Hair et al., 2017). A path is significant when the confidence interval differs significantly from (i.e., does not contain) zero. Confidence intervals for significant paths which were rounded up or down to zero were considered significant and are indicated by " < 0.00 " or " > 0.00 ". Finally, the f^2 effect sizes were inspected to determine the relative impact of the predictors on the outcomes (Hair et al., 2017). As per Hair et al. (2017), the following thresholds for f^2 were adopted: 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35, representing small, moderate, and large effects, respectively (Cohen, 1988). Effect sizes < 0.02 indicate that no effect is present (Cohen, 1988; Hair et al., 2017).

Inferential analyses were conducted in RStudio (RStudio Team, 2019) using the SEMinR package (Ray et al., 2019). Raw data for individual and collaborative learning activities are available in Appendices H and I, respectively. RStudio coding scripts for inferential analyses are accessible in Appendix J. Inferential results for both models, with and without outliers, are accessible in Appendix K. The subsequent (results) section will present the model evaluation process for individual learning activities and then collaborative learning activities. To recap, analyses for both were conducted separately.

²³ Unlike Cronbach's α , composite reliability does not assume equal loadings between indicators and constructs (Hair et al., 2017).

6.3. Results

6.3.1. Individual learning activities

This subsection will evaluate the model for individual learning in the academic library spaces. First, evaluations of the measurement models are presented to address Aim 1. Then, the evaluation of the structural model is presented to address Aim 2 and Hypotheses 1-7.

Aim 1. Evaluation of the measurement models

In the individual learning activities section of the questionnaire (Section 2), the first scale aimed to measure students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment when using their academic library spaces for individual learning activities. Four subscales sought to assess perceptions of Person-Environment Fit, including, Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, and Privacy Fit. A fifth subscale measured students' perceptions of Decisional Control. The second scale sought to measure learning and psychological outcomes when using the academic libraries for individual learning. The outcomes assessed included self-reported Academic Stress Response (manifested through both Affective Stress and Behavioural Stress); Engagement in learning activities (manifested through Vigour and Dedication); and Quantity and Quality of Work produced. As such, in the first iteration of the measurement model, it was assumed that there would be 10 reliable and valid dimensions, representing each of the subscales outlined above. Five iterations of the measurement model were run. Each iteration aimed to improve the validity and reliability of the questionnaire and measurement model, upon which, the subsequent analysis of structural relations was based. Evaluations of each iteration are outlined below.

Individual learning iteration one. In the first iteration, the following four items had indicator loadings < 0.70 and were removed to improve indicator reliability: "I felt like yelling at peers" (Affective Stress), "I procrastinated on assignments" (Behavioural Stress), "I continued for a very long time when I was studying" (Vigour), and "I found my studies challenging" (Dedication). Furthermore, the item "being distracted by window views to outside" (Ambient Fit) loaded below 0.70 and the corresponding subscale had an AVE value marginally below the 0.50 threshold. As a result, this item was removed to increase both indicator reliability and convergent validity for the subscale. In addition, the item "I had to make few changes to my work" (Quantity and Quality of Work) was below the 0.70 threshold and all cross-loadings were higher for non-corresponding constructs. This

item was removed to improve indicator reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. Finally, the item “too few people in the space” (Privacy Fit) loaded < 0.70 on its corresponding construct. Further, the HTMT correlation and corresponding CIs inferred a lack of discrimination between the Acoustical Fit and Privacy Fit subscales. Consequently, this item was removed to improve indicator reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity between the Acoustical Fit and Privacy Fit sub-dimensions.

Individual learning iteration 2. In the second iteration, one item was removed on the basis that its indicator loading was < 0.70 : “I felt lazy when it came to University work” (Behavioural Stress). Further, the item “I made many mistakes” (Quantity and Quality of Work) was below the 0.70 threshold and had five cross-loadings which were higher for non-corresponding constructs. Hence, the item was removed to improve indicator reliability, convergent, and discriminant validity. Moreover, the AVE value for Ambient Fit increased above the recommended threshold of 0.50 for convergent validity. However, the HTMT correlation and corresponding CIs continued to indicate a lack of discrimination between Acoustical Fit and Privacy Fit. As such, following guidance from Hair et al. (2017) and Henseler et al. (2015), the items for the two constructs were merged into a single dimension called Acoustical and Privacy Fit. This merger of items was conceptually justified because both the Acoustical Fit and Privacy Fit subscales contained items pertaining to input and output from others, such as, “noise/sounds from other people moving around”, “noise/sounds from other people talking”, “people looking at what I am doing”, and “interruptions”. Thus, it is reasonable to assume high correlations between scores on similar items.

Individual study iteration 3. On the third iteration, a further two items were removed on the basis of indicator loadings < 0.70 in order to improve indicator reliability and therefore convergent validity: “I had trouble remembering my notes” (Behavioural Stress) and “my work outcome was creative” (Quantity and Quality of Work). Furthermore, all constructs met the required criteria for discriminant validity: cross-loadings for all items were smaller than the loadings with their associated primary constructs, HTMT correlations were < 0.90 , and the bootstrapped HTMT CIs were significantly different from 1.

Individual study iteration 4. In the fourth iteration, the following item was removed from the Quantity and Quality of Work produced subscale: “my work was of a high quality”. The item was

removed on the basis that its loading was < 0.70 and all other items pertaining to quantity of work had been removed in previous iterations. This is conceptually justified as it is feasible that students struggle to judge the quality of work produced while studying alone (e.g., relative to working on a shared project with peers).

Individual study iteration 5. The fifth and final iteration indicated that the validity and reliability of the measurement model were acceptable. Although several items throughout each iteration contained indicator loadings < 0.70 threshold, these were retained on the basis that their exclusion would reduce the content validity of the measurement model and questionnaire. Indeed, Hair et al. (2017) note that new social science scales often contain items with loadings between 0.60 and 0.70; in addition, items with loadings between 0.40 and 0.70 should be retained if their removal would hinder the content validity of the scale (Hair et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2015). Moreover, AVE values for each subscale were above the recommended threshold. As such, convergent validity was deemed acceptable. Further, assessment of cross-loadings revealed that all items loaded highest on their primary sub-dimensions, an assessment of the HTMT correlations revealed no correlations > 0.90 threshold, and an inspection of the HTMT CIs indicated that all HTMT correlations were significantly different from 1.0. As such, discriminant validity was established. Internal consistency reliability (Dillon-Goldstein’s Rho and Cronbach’s α) for the final iteration was good (above the minimum and below maximum thresholds). In summary, the individual learning section of the USLLSE Questionnaire the USLSE measurement model had good overall psychometric properties. Indicator loadings, internal consistency metrics, and AVE values are presented in Table 16. Cross loadings and HTMT criteria are available in Appendix K.

Table 16.

Final measurement model (iteration 5) results for individual learning activities

Constructs and associated indicators	Indicator loadings	Cronbach’s α	Composite reliability	AVE
Spatial and Ergonomic Fit		0.87	0.91	0.62
Crowding	0.69			
Work surface size	0.72			
Furniture comfort	0.69			

Furniture arrangement	0.85			
Size of space	0.87			
Seating position	0.87			
Acoustical and Privacy Fit		0.90	0.92	0.63
Interruptions	0.82			
People looking at what I am doing	0.65			
Seeing other people moving	0.86			
Architectural privacy	0.84			
Noise from other people talking	0.79			
Noise from equipment	0.74			
Background noise level	0.84			
Too few people in the space	Removed for iteration 2			
Ambient Fit		0.81	0.86	0.52
Being unable to access window views to outside	0.51			
Temperature	0.66			
Air quality	0.84			
Artificial lighting	0.78			
Natural lighting	0.77			

Use of colour	0.72			
Being distracted by window views to outside	Removed for iteration 2			
Decisional Control		0.93	0.95	0.75
Ability to find spaces suitable for planned activities in library	0.85			
Ability to find space suitable for unplanned activities in library	0.88			
Ability to choose the types of spaces one wants	0.89			
Ability to choose from a range of alternatives if preferred space in the library is unavailable	0.83			
Ability to find spaces suitable for planned activities on wider campus	0.88			
Ability to find spaces suitable for unplanned activities on	0.87			
Affective Stress		0.88	0.92	0.74
Work built up so much that I felt like crying	0.88			
Felt emotional	0.90			
Emotions stopped me from studying	0.82			
Felt emotionally drained by university	0.83			
Felt like yelling at peers	Removed for iteration 2			
Behavioural Stress		0.87	0.91	0.72
Distracted in the library	0.90			

Unable to study	0.79			
Trouble concentrating	0.93			
Avoided studying	0.76			
Trouble remembering notes	Removed for iteration 4			
Procrastinated in the library	Removed for iteration 2			
Felt lazy	Removed for iteration 3			
Vigour (Engagement)		0.87	0.92	0.79
Felt mentally strong when studying	0.87			
Felt bursting with energy when studying	0.88			
Felt strong and vigorous when studying	0.91			
Continued for a long time	Removed for iteration 2			
Dedication (Engagement)		0.93	0.95	0.82
Found studies to be full of meaning and purpose	0.91			
Inspired by studies	0.93			
Enthusiastic about studies	0.92			
Proud of studies	0.86			
Studies were challenging	Removed for iteration 2			

Quantity of Work		0.91	0.94	0.75
I was productive	0.81			
Completed tasks I set out to do	0.89			
Completed most tasks I set out to do	0.87			
Completed high quantity of work	0.87			
Accomplished a great deal	0.88			
Made few changes to my work	Removed for iteration 2			
My work was of high quality	Removed for iteration 5			
I made many mistakes	Removed for iteration 3			
My work outcome was creative	Removed for iteration 4			

Note. $N = 418$.

Aim 2. Evaluation of the structural model results

The evaluation of the structural relationships between environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes for individual learning activities, was based on measurement model iteration 5. Of the 23 direct relationships, 10 were significant. Eight of the 15 indirect relationships (mediation effects) were significant. The results of the structural model analysis for individual learning activities are presented below. Standardised path coefficients and R^2 adj. values (i.e., variance explained) are presented in Figure 4.

Model fit assessment (R^2 adj.). In combination, perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical and Privacy, and Ambient Fit explained approximately 48% of the variance in perceptions of Decisional Control when using the academic library spaces for individual learning. In combination, perceptions

of Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical and Privacy, Ambient Fit, and Decisional Control explained approximately 16% of the variance in Affective Stress 49% of the variance in Behavioural Stress, 8% of the variance in Vigour, 5% of the variance in Dedication, and 16% of the variance in the Quantity of Work produced when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities.

Hypothesis 1. Direct associations between Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control. Congruent with Hypothesis 1, students' perceptions of both Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Acoustical and Privacy Fit, significantly and negatively predicted their perceptions of Decisional Control ($f^2 = 0.32$, 95% CI [-0.75, -0.54], $f^2 = 0.02$, 95% CI [-0.23, -0.01]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Spatial and Ergonomic Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control when using the academic library for individual learning activities. Effect sizes were moderate and small, respectively. The association between perceptions of Ambient Fit and Decisional Control when using the academic library spaces for individual learning tasks, however, was non-significant and no effect was present ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.05, 0.16]). Thus, Hypothesis 1 was partially supported.

Hypothesis 2. Direct associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Academic Stress. As anticipated, students' perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit significantly and positively predicted both Affective Stress ($f^2 = 0.02$, 95% CI [0.05, 0.31]) and Behavioural Stress ($f^2 = 0.21$, 95% CI [0.35, 0.53]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with less frequent Affective Stress and Behavioural Stress responses, when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities. Effect sizes were small and moderate, respectively. Congruent with predictions of the USLSE Model, students' perceptions of Decisional Control significantly and negatively predicted their Behavioural Stress responses ($f^2 = 0.07$, 95% CI [-0.37, -0.16]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with less frequent Behavioural Stress when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities. The effect size was small. As anticipated, students' perceptions of Ambient Fit significantly and positively predicted Affective Stress ($f^2 = 0.01$, 95% CI [0.01, 0.30]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Ambient Fit were associated with less frequent Affective Stress responses. Inspection of the effect size, however, indicated no detectable effect. No other significant associations or detectable effects were present. Specifically, there were no significant associations or detectable effects between students' perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Affective stress ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.06, 0.29]), Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Behavioural Stress ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.07,

0.21]), Ambient Fit and Behavioural Stress ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.06, 0.16]), nor Decisional Control and Affective Stress ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.16, 0.10]). Hypothesis 2 was, therefore, partially accepted.

Hypothesis 3. Direct associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Engagement. As hypothesised, students' perceptions of Decisional Control significantly and positively predicted Engagement, as manifested through both Vigour ($f^2 = 0.04$, 95% CI [0.13, 0.40]) and Dedication ($f^2 = 0.03$, 95% CI [0.07, 0.38]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with more frequent experiences of Vigour and Dedication, when using the academic libraries for individual learning activities. The effect sizes were small. There were, however, no other significant effects. Specifically, there were no significant associations or detectable effects between students' perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic fit and Vigour ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.21, 0.17]) nor Dedication ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.23, 0.17]); Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Vigour ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.23, 0.04]) nor Dedication ($f^2 = 0.02$, 95% CI [-0.14, 0.12]); and Ambient Fit and Vigour ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.07, 0.22]) nor Dedication ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.13, 0.18]). Consequently, Hypothesis 3 was only partially accepted.

Hypothesis 4. Direct associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Quantity of Work. As hypothesised, perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit significantly and negatively predicted Quantity of Work produced ($f^2 = 0.03$, 95% CI [-0.32, -0.08]) and perceptions of Decisional Control significantly and positively predicted Quantity of Work produced ($f^2 = 0.04$, 95% CI [0.12, 0.40]). That is, more frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Decisional Control were associated with greater Quantity of Work when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities. There were no other significant relationships nor detectable effects between Learning Space Perceptions and Quantity of Work produced when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities. Specifically, there were no significant associations nor detectable effects between students' perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.27, 0.08]) nor Ambient Fit ($f^2 = 0.01$, 95% CI [-0.04, 0.25]) and Quantity of Work. Hypothesis 4 was, therefore, accepted only in part.

Hypothesis 5. Indirect associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Academic Stress Responses. As predicted, there was a significant and positive indirect relationship between perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Behavioural Stress; the relationship was fully

mediated by perceptions of Decisional Control (95% CI [0.10, 0.25]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were, in turn, associated with less frequent Behavioural Stress responses when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities. As hypothesised, there was also a significant and positive indirect relationship between perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Behavioural Stress; perceptions of Decisional Control partially mediated this relationship (95% CI [> 0.00 , 0.07]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were, in turn, associated with more frequent Behavioural Stress responses when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities. However, incongruent with the predictions of the USLSE Model, the indirect relationships between perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Affective Stress (95% CI [-0.06, 0.11]), Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Affective Stress (95% CI [-0.02, 0.02]), Ambient Fit and Affective Stress (95% CI [-0.02, 0.01]), and Ambient Fit and Behavioural Stress (95% CI [-0.05, 0.01]), were non-significant. Consequently, Hypothesis 5 was only partially accepted.

Hypothesis 6. Indirect associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Engagement. Congruent with predictions, there was a significant and negative indirect relationship between perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and both Vigour and Dedication. More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control fully mediated the relationships between perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and both Vigour and Dedication (95% CI [-0.27, -0.08]; 95% CI [-0.26, -0.05]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were, in turn, associated with both increased Vigour and Dedication when using the academic libraries for individual study activities. In addition, as hypothesised, there was a significant and negative indirect relationship between perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit and both Vigour and Dedication; perceptions of Decisional Control fully mediated the associations between perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit and both Vigour and Dedication (95% CI [-0.07, < 0.00]; 95% CI [-0.07, < 0.00]). More frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. In turn, this was associated with more frequent experiences of Vigour and Dedication when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities. There were no indirect effects of Ambient Appraisals on Vigour (95% CI [-0.01, 0.05] nor Dedication (95% CI [-0.01, 0.04])). Partial support was, therefore, found for hypothesis 6.

Hypothesis 7. Indirect associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Quantity of Work. As predicted, there was a significant and negative relationship between perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Quantity of Work produced; perceptions of Decisional Control fully mediated the relationship between perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Quantity of Work produced (95% CI [-0.27, -0.08]). More frequent perceptions of Spatial Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. In turn, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with (more frequent) greater Quantity of Work produced when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities. In addition, as expected, there was a significant and negative indirect relationship between perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Quantity of Work produced; perceptions of Decisional Control partially mediated the relationship between Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Quantity of Work produced (95% CI [-0.07, < 0.00]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. In turn, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with (more frequent) increased Quantity of Work when using the academic libraries for individual learning activities. However, there was no indirect effect of Ambient Appraisals on Quantity of Work produced (95% CI [-0.01, 0.05]). Hypothesis 7 was, therefore, partially supported.

Figure 4.

Structural equation model depicting the relationships between students' environmental perceptions, learning and psychological outcomes when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities

Only significant mediation effects are reported here:

Spatial and Ergonomic Fit → Decisional Control → Behavioural Stress ($\beta = 0.03$), Vigour ($\beta = -0.03$), Dedication ($\beta = -0.03$), and Quantity of Work ($\beta = -0.03$).

Acoustical and Privacy Fit → Decisional Control → Behavioural Stress ($\beta = 0.17$), Vigour ($\beta = -0.17$), Dedication ($\beta = -0.15$), and Quantity of Work ($\beta = -0.17$).

6.3.2. Collaborative learning activities

This subsection will evaluate the model for collaborative learning in the academic library spaces. First, evaluations of the measurement models are presented to address Aim 3. Following this, the evaluation of the structural model is presented to address Aim 4 and hypotheses 8-14.

Aim 3. Evaluation of the measurement models

In the collaborative learning activities section of the questionnaire (Section 3), the first scale was created to measure students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment when using their academic libraries for collaborative learning activities. This scale included four subscales which aimed to assess perceptions of Person-Environment Fit, including, Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, and Privacy Fit. A fifth subscale aimed to assess students' perceptions of Decisional Control. The second scale was created to measure students' learning and psychological outcomes when using the academic libraries for collaborative learning activities, including, self-reported Academic Stress Response (manifested through both Affective Stress and Behavioural Stress); Collaborative Engagement in learning activities (manifested through Collaborative Vigour and Collaborative Dedication); and Quantity and Quality of Work produced.

As such, in the first iteration of the measurement model, it was assumed that there would be 10 reliable and valid dimensions, representing each of the subscales outlined above. Three iterations of the measurement model were run. Each iteration aimed to improve the validity and reliability of the questionnaire and measurement model, upon which, the subsequent analysis of structural relations was based. Evaluations of each iteration are outlined below.

Collaborative learning iteration 1. Following iteration one, the item "my group made many mistakes" (Quantity and Quality of Work) was removed on the basis that its indicator loading was < 0.40 and it cross-loaded higher on two non-primary sub-constructs (Affective Stress and Collective Dedication). A further item, "hard work was an effort for my group" (Collective Vigour), was removed on the basis that its loading was < 0.40 , it loaded higher on five non-primary sub-constructs (Affective Stress, Behavioural Stress, Dedication, Quantity and Quality of Work, and Ambient Fit), and the AVE value for collective vigour was below the minimum threshold of 0.50. In addition, the item "I procrastinated on assignments" was removed on the basis that it loaded < 0.70 . Finally, the loading for the item "too few people in the space" (Privacy Fit) was below the 0.70 threshold on its

corresponding sub-construct; further, the HTMT correlation between Privacy Fit and Acoustical Fit was above the 0.90 threshold. In an attempt to improve indicator reliability (convergent validity) and reduce this HTMT correlation, the indicator was removed.

Collaborative learning iteration 2. At the second iteration, the item “my group had to make few changes to our work” (Quantity and Quality of Work) was removed as its loading was below the minimum threshold of 0.40. A further two items were removed to improve indicator reliability and convergent validity, on the basis that their primary indicator loadings were below 0.70 and they were not deemed essential for the content validity of the instrument: “I felt lazy when it came to university work” (Behavioural Stress) and “my group felt very resilient during the task” (Collective Vigour). Finally, the HTMT correlation between the sub-constructs Acoustical Fit and Privacy Fit remained > 0.90 . Thus, as with individual learning activities, the items for both subscales were merged into a single subscale named Acoustical and Privacy Fit.

Collaborative learning iteration 3. Upon the third and final iteration, the psychometric properties of the measurement model and questionnaire were deemed acceptable. As with individual study, several items with loadings > 0.40 but < 0.70 were retained throughout each iteration on the basis that their exclusion would reduce the content validity of the questionnaire (cf. Hair et al., 2017). AVE values for each subscale were above the recommended threshold. As such, convergent validity was deemed acceptable. Further, assessment of cross-loadings revealed that all items loaded highest on their primary sub-dimension, an assessment of the HTMT correlations revealed no correlations < 0.90 threshold, and an inspection of the HTMT CIs indicated that all HTMT correlations were significantly different from 1.0. As such, discriminant validity was established. Internal consistency reliability (Dillon-Goldstein’s Rho and Cronbach’s α) for the final iteration was good (above the minimum and below maximum thresholds). In summary, the collaborative learning section of the USLLSE Questionnaire and the USLSE measurement model had good overall psychometric properties. Indicator loadings, internal consistency metrics, and AVE values are presented in Table 17. Cross-loadings and HTMT criteria are available in Appendix K.

Table 17.*Final measurement model (iteration 3) results for collaborative learning activities*

Constructs and associated indicators	Indicator loadings	Cronbach's α	Composite reliability	AVE
Spatial and Ergonomic Fit		0.88	0.91	0.63
Crowding	0.69			
Furniture comfort	0.70			
Size of space	0.85			
Work surface size	0.83			
Furniture arrangement	0.86			
Seating position	0.82			
Acoustical and Privacy Fit		0.93	0.94	0.67
Speech privacy	0.76			
Interruptions	0.83			
People looking at what I am doing	0.74			
Seeing other people moving	0.83			
Architectural privacy	0.87			
Noise from other people talking	0.86			
Noise from equipment	0.78			
Background noise level	0.87			
Too few people	Removed for iteration 2			

Ambient Fit		0.89	0.92	0.61
Being distracted by window views to outside	0.64			
Being unable to access window views to outside	0.69			
Temperature	0.74			
Air quality	0.85			
Artificial lighting	0.82			
Natural lighting	0.83			
Use of colour	0.77			
Decisional Control		0.93	0.94	0.74
Ability to find spaces suitable for planned activities in library	0.82			
Ability to find space suitable for unplanned activities in library	0.86			
Ability to choose the types of spaces one wants	0.89			
Ability to choose from a range of alternatives if preferred space in the library is unavailable	0.84			
Ability to find spaces suitable for planned activities on wider campus	0.87			
Ability to find spaces suitable for unplanned activities on wider campus	0.88			
Affective Stress		0.89	0.92	0.71
Felt like crying	0.89			
Felt emotional	0.89			

Emotions stopped me from studying	0.85			
Felt emotionally drained	0.84			
Felt like yelling at peers	0.71			
Behavioural Stress		0.89	0.92	0.70
Distracted in the library	0.88			
Unable to study	0.85			
Trouble concentrating	0.92			
Avoided studying	0.76			
Trouble remembering notes	0.74			
Procrastinated in the library	Removed for iteration 2			
Felt lazy	Removed for iteration 3			
Collective Vigour (Engagement)		0.85	0.89	0.62
Group felt full of energy	0.81			
Group continued working for long periods	0.82			
Group kept working even when things did not go well	0.78			
Group felt strong and vigorous	0.81			
Group had energy left for other activities when task was finishes	0.69			
Hard work was an effort	Removed for iteration 2			

Group felt resilient	Removed for iteration 3			
Collective Dedication (Engagement)		0.89	0.93	0.76
Group involved in task	0.85			
Group enthusiastic about task	0.90			
Group liked doing task	0.89			
Group felt motivated to do good job	0.84			
Work Quantity and Quality		0.93	0.95	0.71
Group was productive	0.82			
Group completed tasks set out to do	0.83			
Group completed most tasks set out to do	0.81			
Group completed high quantity of work	0.89			
Group accomplished a great deal	0.90			
Group work was of high quality	0.85			
Group work outcome was creative	0.81			
Made many mistakes	Removed for iteration 2			
Group had to make few changes to work	Removed for iteration 3			

Note. $N = 307$.

Aim 4. Evaluation of the structural model

The evaluation of the structural relationships between environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes for collaborative learning activities, was based on measurement model iteration 3. Of the 23 direct relationships, 10 were significant in the expected direction and one in

the unexpected direction. Eight of the 15 indirect relationships were significant, four of which were significant in the expected direction. The results of the structural model analysis for collaborative learning activities are presented below. Standardised path coefficients and R^2 adj. values (i.e., variance explained) are presented in Figure 5.

Model fit assessment (R^2 adj.). In combination, perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical and Privacy, and Ambient Fit explained approximately 29% of the variance in perceptions of Decisional Control. In combination, students' perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical and Privacy Fit, Ambient Fit, and Decisional Control explained 20% of the variance in Affective Stress, 34% of the variance in Behavioural Stress, 16% of the variance in Vigour, 10% of the variance in Dedication, and 7% of the variance in Quantity and Quality of work produced when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities.

Hypothesis 8. Direct associations between Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control. In line with Hypothesis 8, students' perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit significantly and negatively predicted their perceptions of Decisional Control ($f^2 = 0.20$, 95% CI [-0.74, -0.46]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control, when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning. The effect size was moderate. Counter to the predictions of the USLSE Model, perceptions of Ambient Fit significantly and positively predicted perceptions of Decisional Control ($f^2 = 0.04$, CI 95% [0.10, 0.37]). This indicated that more frequent perceptions of Ambient Fit were associated with less frequent perceptions of Decisional Control when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning. The effect was small. The association between students' perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Decisional Control when using the academic libraries for collaborative learning was non-significant and no effect was present ($f^2 = 0.01$, 95% CI [-0.26, 0.02]). Hypothesis 8 was, therefore, only partially accepted.

Hypothesis 9. Direct associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Academic Stress Responses. As hypothesised, students' perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit significantly and positively predicted both Affective Stress ($f^2 = 0.04$, 95% CI [0.13, 0.40]) and Behavioural Stress ($f^2 = 0.11$, 95% CI [0.25, 0.49]); Ambient Fit significantly and positively predicted both Affective Stress ($f^2 = 0.03$, 95% CI [0.10, 0.42]) and Behavioural Stress ($f^2 = 0.04$, 95% CI [0.11, 0.37]), and perceptions

of Decisional Control significantly and negatively predicted Behavioural Stress ($f^2 = 0.02$, 95% CI [-0.23, -0.02]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with less frequent Affective and Behavioural Stress responses, more frequent perceptions of Ambient Fit were associated with less frequent Affective and Behavioural Stress, and more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with less frequent Behavioural Stress when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities. All effects were small. However, there were no significant associations or detectable effects between perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Affective Stress ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.16, 0.19]), perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Behavioural Stress ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.18, 0.15]), and perceptions of Decisional Control and Affective Stress ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.04, 0.18]). Hypothesis 9 was, therefore, partially accepted.

Hypothesis 10. Direct Associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Engagement. As hypothesised, perceptions of Decisional Control significantly and positively predicted Collective Vigour ($f^2 = 0.09$, 95% CI [0.21, 0.46]) and Collective Dedication ($f^2 = 0.07$, 95% CI [0.17, 0.43]). This indicated that more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with more frequent experiences of both Collective Vigour and Collective Dedication when using the academic libraries for collaborative learning. Further, perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit significantly and negatively predicted collective vigour, in line with predictions ($f^2 = 0.02$, 95% CI [-0.33, -0.01]). More frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with more frequent experiences of Collective Vigour, when using the academic libraries for collaborative learning activities. All effects were small. However, there were no further significant associations between learning space perceptions and Engagement. Specifically, there were no associations or detectable effects between Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Collective Vigour ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.21, 0.13]) nor Collective Dedication ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.16, 0.22]); Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Collective Dedication ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.24, 0.07]); and Ambient Fit and Collective Vigour ($f^2 = 0.01$, 95% CI [-0.00, 0.29]) nor Collective Dedication ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.16, 0.15]). Hypothesis 10 was partially accepted.

Hypothesis 11. Direct associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Work Quantity and Work Quality. As predicted, students' perceptions of Decisional Control significantly and positively predicted Work Quantity and Quality ($f^2 = 0.03$, 95% CI [0.09, 0.34]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with (a more frequent) increase in

Quantity and Quality of Work produced when using the academic libraries for collaborative learning activities. However, there were no further significant associations or detectable effects between Learning Space Perceptions and Work Quantity and Quality for collaborative learning activities. Specifically, there were no associations or detectable effects between Spatial Fit and Quantity and Quality of Work Produced ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.10, 0.25]); Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Quantity and Quality of Work produced ($f^2 = 0.01$, 95% CI [-0.28, 0.01]); Ambient Appraisals and Quantity and Quality of Work produced ($f^2 = 0.00$, 95% CI [-0.25, 0.06]). As a result, Hypothesis 11 was only partially accepted.

Hypothesis 12. Indirect associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Academic Stress Responses. As predicted, there was a significant and positive indirect relationship between perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Behavioural Stress; perceptions of Decisional Control partially mediated this association (95% CI [0.01, 0.15]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were, in turn, associated with less frequent Behavioural Stress when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning. Contrary to predictions, there was also a significant and negative indirect relationship between perceptions of Ambient Fit and Behavioural Stress; perceptions of Decisional Control fully mediated the relationship between Ambient Fit and Behavioural Stress (95% CI [-0.06, <0.00]). More frequent perceptions of Ambient Fit were associated with less frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. In turn, less frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with more frequent Behavioural Stress when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning. Counter to predictions, there were no further significant indirect relationships. In particular, there were no significant indirect effects of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit on Affective Stress (95% CI [-0.11, 0.03]); Acoustical and Privacy Fit on Affective Stress (95% CI [-0.03, 0.01]) nor Behavioural Stress (95% CI [<0.00, 0.04]); and Ambient Fit on Affective Stress (95% CI [-0.01, 0.05]) via Decisional Control. Hypothesis 12 was, therefore, partially accepted.

Hypothesis 13. Indirect Associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Engagement. As anticipated, there was a significant and negative indirect relationship between perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and both Collective Vigour and Collective Dedication; perceptions of Decisional Control fully mediated these relationships (95% CI [-0.30, -0.12]; 95% CI [-0.28, -0.10]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit were associated

with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. In turn, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with more frequent experiences of both Collective Vigour and Collective Dedication when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities. Incongruent with predictions, however, there was a significant but positive indirect relationship between perceptions of Ambient Appraisals and both Collective Vigour and Collective Dedication; perceptions of Decisional Control significantly and fully mediated these associations (95% CI [0.03, 0.14]; 95% CI [0.02, 0.13]). Specifically, more frequent (i.e., positive) perceptions of Ambient Fit were associated with less frequent (i.e., negative) perceptions of Decisional Control. In turn, less frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with less frequent experiences of Collective Vigour and Collective Dedication, when using the academic libraries for collaborative learning tasks. Further, there was no indirect relationship between students' perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Collective Vigour (95% CI [-0.10, 0.01]) nor Collective Dedication (95% CI [-0.09, >0.00]). As such, Hypothesis 13 was partially accepted.

Hypothesis 14. Indirect associations between Person-Environment Fit, Decisional Control, and Quantity and Quality of Work. As predicted, there was a significant and negative indirect relationship between perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Work Quantity; perceptions of Decisional Control fully mediated the relationship between perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Work Quantity (95% CI [-0.22, -0.05]). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Spatial Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. In turn, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with (more frequent) increased Quantity and Quality of Work produced when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning. Also, in contrast with predictions, there was a significant and negative indirect relationship between perceptions of Ambient Fit and Work Quantity and Quality; Decisional Control fully mediated the relationship between Ambient Fit and Work Quantity and Quality (95% CI [0.01, 0.10]). Contrary to predictions the effect was positive rather than negative. Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Ambient Fit were associated with less frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. Less frequent (more negative) perceptions of Decisional Control, in turn, were associated with a (more frequent) decrease in Quantity and Quality Work produced, when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning. Finally, incongruent with the hypothesis, there was no significant indirect effect of Acoustical and Ambient Fit on Quantity and Quality of Work produced via Decisional Control when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning (95% CI [-0.07, >0.00]). Therefore, Hypothesis 14 was only partially supported.

Figure 5.

Structural equation model depicting the relationships between students' environmental perceptions, learning and psychological outcomes when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities

Only significant mediation effects are reported here:

Spatial and Ergonomic Fit → Decisional Control → Behavioural Stress ($\beta = 0.07$), Vigour ($\beta = -0.20$), Dedication ($\beta = -0.18$), and Work Quantity ($\beta = -0.13$).

Ambient Fit → Decisional Control → Behavioural Stress ($\beta = -0.03$), Vigour ($\beta = 0.08$), Dedication ($\beta = 0.07$), and Work Quantity ($\beta = 0.05$).

6.4. Chapter Discussion

6.4.1. Overview

Based on the USLSE Model (cf. Study 1), this study used a quantitative questionnaire approach to explore students' learning space experiences when using their academic library spaces for both individual and collaborative learning activities. Specifically, this study aimed to explore (i) the psychometric properties of the USLLSE Questionnaire and (ii) the associations between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes. This section will outline and discuss the findings in light of previous research and theory and move on to consider the limitations, strengths, and conclusions of the study.

6.4.2. Measurement model findings for individual learning and collaborative learning

Upon the final iterations, construct validity and internal consistency reliability for both individual and collaborative sections of the USLLSE Questionnaire were acceptable. The findings revealed that as with classroom and informal learning spaces (e.g., Scannell et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2013), students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their academic library spaces can be measured in a psychometrically robust (i.e., valid and reliable) way. Specifically, this study extends previous work by demonstrating that students' perceptions of the physical environment in their campus learning spaces can be measured in terms of the both the functionality and frequency of Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control, using a robust approach.

Comparing the psychometric results for both individual and collaborative learning activities, loadings between several items and their corresponding constructs were noticeably below the desirable threshold for individual but not collaborative learning activities. These included "People looking at what I am doing" (Acoustical and Privacy Fit), "being unable to access window views to outside" (Ambient Fit), and "temperature" (Ambient Fit). Indeed, one item "Being distracted by window views to outside" (Ambient Fit) was removed for the individual learning model as it was below the minimum threshold of 0.40.

One explanation for these findings is that these environmental characteristics are less salient when engaging in individual relative to collaborative learning. Specifically, it is possible that perceptions of Person-Environment Fit are more salient when a greater number of students place different

demands on the same environmental characteristics. Indeed, as noted in Chapter 2 and Chapter 4 (Study 1), students may place different demands on their environment as a function of personal characteristics (e.g., Beckers et al., 2016a; Wilson & Cotgrove, 2016; Yang et al., 2013). Alternatively, it is plausible that these findings stem from other between group differences, such as, situational factors (e.g., different types of space) (Baepler et al., 2014). Future research may address these findings, for example, by incorporating a commensurate scale which measures both the degree of fit and the perceived importance of each environmental variable for individual and collaborative learning activities. Such an approach is adopted in wider person-environment fit research (e.g., person-organisation fit; cf. Edwards, 1994, 2008; Kristoff, 1996), however, it would require fine balancing with issues such as respondent burden and participant dropout.

While it is difficult to compare factor analytic findings for new instruments with factor analytic findings pertaining to previous instruments, the findings are somewhat in line with previous factor analyses of learning space perception instruments. For instance, Scannell et al. (2016) found that students discriminated between perceptions of different acoustical characteristics (e.g., people-related, non-people-related, and reverberation) and other (non-acoustical) ambient characteristics, including, temperature, air quality, and lighting. While students who completed the questionnaire by Yang et al. (2013) did not discriminate between perceptions of acoustics and other ambient factors (temperature, air quality, and daylight), it is plausible that this stemmed from the inclusion of only a single item representing the acoustical environment. That said, the students who completed Yang et al.'s questionnaire did discriminate between perceptions of Spatial and Ambient Attributes, in line with our findings. While perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit were considered separately within the USLSE Model, the Model noted interrelationships between perceptions of Privacy Fit with and perceptions of Acoustical Fit. Specifically, in line with Altman's (1975) conceptualisation, Privacy Fit within the USLSE Model referred to input from and output to others; as noted in Study 1, input from others may include noise from other people talking (acoustical privacy). One item which measured Acoustical Fit attended to this issue: "noise from other people talking". Thus, merging the items for both constructs into a single construct called Acoustical and Privacy Fit was conceptually justified.

6.4.3. Predicting learning and psychological outcomes

Hypothesis 1. Predictors of Decisional Control (Individual Learning)

In considering Hypothesis 1, the Person-Environment Fit variables most strongly associated with Decisional Control when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities were

Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Acoustical and Privacy Fit, with moderate and small effects, respectively. Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control.

These findings are in line with previous work, including, the USLSE Model (Study 1), person-environment transaction theories, previous qualitative research on students' learning space experiences, and quantitative work on distractions in open-plan offices. Specifically, this body of previous work suggests that a greater fit between the environment and users' needs is associated with increased controllability (e.g., choice of suitable settings) (Evans & Stecker, 2004; Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Lazarus & Cohen, 1977; Lee & Brand, 2005, 2010; Proshansky et al., 1970; Sommer, 1966).

Hypothesis 2. Predictors of Affective and Behavioural Stress (Individual Learning)

In review of Hypothesis 2, the only environmental perception variables associated with Affective Stress (e.g., emotional distress) when using the University Campus libraries for individual learning activities were Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Ambient Fit. While the former had a moderate effect, for the latter the effect was statistically non-meaningful (i.e., < 0.02). The environmental perception variables most strongly associated with Behavioural Stress (concentration, distraction, and avoidance) were Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Decisional Control, with small and moderate effects respectively. More frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with less frequent Affective and Behavioural Stress Responses. Furthermore, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with less frequent Behavioural Stress responses.

These associations are supportive of the USLSE Model (Study 1) and other qualitative studies which suggest that better fit between the environment and students' needs can decrease negative cognitive-affective outcomes, such as, frustration and concentration deficits among students (Granito & Santana, 2016; Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017; Van Horne et al., 2014; Melhuish, 2010; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017; Van Horne et al., 2014). Further, the findings compliment previous quantitative studies in experimental settings and informal learning spaces which have demonstrated relationships between objective environmental conditions and cognitive-affective outcomes, such as, mood and environment-related well-being (Marchand et al., 2014; Scannell et al., 2016). Finally, these findings are supportive of person-environment transaction

theories which suggest that negative perceptions of the environment, including, perceptions of one's ability to cope with the environment (e.g., through Decisional Control) may lead to increased stress responses (Lazarus and Cohen, 1977). Overall, these findings extend prior work by highlighting that students' Academic Stress Responses when using academic library spaces for individual learning activities may be lowered by increasing:

- Perceptions of fit between individual learning activities and their acoustical and privacy needs; and
- Students perceived ability to choose task appropriate settings for individual learning activities.

Hypothesis 3. Predictors of Engagement (Individual Learning)

Reflecting on Hypothesis 3, only perceptions of Decisional Control when using the academic libraries for individual learning activities was directly associated with Engagement (small effects). As predicted by the USLSE Model, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with increased Vigour (mental strength and energy) and Dedication (motivation, enthusiasm, and involvement). These relationships are also supportive of the previous qualitative and quantitative research which suggests that characteristics of the physical environment may impact upon students' engagement in learning tasks (Granito & Santana, 2016; Matthews et al., 2009, 2011; Van Horne et al., 2014). In addition, the findings extend prior research by demonstrating that students' Engagement in individual learning activities may be increased by improving their perceived ability to choose settings which they believe to be congruent with their activities.

Hypothesis 4. Quantity of Work Produced (Individual Learning)

Turning to Hypothesis 4, perceptions of Decisional Control and perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit had the strongest associations with the Quantity of Work produced when using the academic libraries for individual learning activities (small effects). Consistent with predictions, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control and more frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with increased Quantity of Work produced. These findings are in line with the USLSE Model (Study 1) and previous research which has highlighted the benefits of perceived environmental control, including, (i) over noise for university students' cognitive task performance and (ii) over the workplace for self-reported job performance (Evans & Stecker, 2004; Lee & Brand, 2010; Sherrod et al., 1977). Further, the findings extend previous work by suggesting that students'

productivity (i.e., amount of work completed) when engaging in individual learning tasks in academic library spaces may be increased by improving:

- Perceptions of fit between individual learning activities and their acoustical and privacy needs; and
- Perceived ability to choose learning activity appropriate settings.

Hypotheses 5-7. Indirect effects via Decisional Control

The findings presented thus far have predominantly suggested that increasing students' perceptions of Decisional Control over the academic library for individual learning activities may have learning and psychological benefits, including, reduced Behavioural Stress, increased Engagement (Vigour and Dedication), and increased Quantity of Work produced. Exploring the Person-Environment Fit constructs which predict Decisional Control as well as the Learning and Psychological Outcomes which are predicted via Decisional Control (mediation effects), would provide a clearer insight into the specific 'student needs' that designers should consider when attempting to improve students' choice of spaces and perceived choice of spaces.

Consistent with Hypotheses 5-7, eight of the 15 indirect relationships between Person-Environment Fit and the Learning and Psychological Outcomes, via Decisional Control, were significant when using the academic library spaces for individual learning. Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Acoustical and Privacy Fit, were significantly associated with less frequent Behavioural Stress, more frequent Engagement in Learning Activities (Vigour and Dedication), and increased Quantity of Work produced, through more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control.

These mediation effects provide insight into students' needs that designers should take into account when improving students' choice of spaces for individual study. Of note, the findings suggest that designers should consult students about their Spatial and Ergonomic and Acoustical and Privacy needs when designing a variety of settings for individual learning activities within academic libraries. This is in line with the USLSE Model (Study 1) and previous work, which highlights that students strive to choose spaces for individual learning activities, which best meet their Acoustical, Privacy, Spatial, and Ergonomic needs (e.g., Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Hunter & Cox, 2014; Sommer, 1966).

Hypothesis 8. Predictors of Decisional Control (Collaborative Learning)

Turning to Hypothesis 8, the Person-Environment Fit variables most strongly associated with Decisional Control when using the academic libraries for collaborative learning activities were Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Ambient Fit, with moderate and small effect sizes, respectively. As anticipated, more frequent Spatial and Ergonomic Fit was associated with more frequent Decisional Control. This association is in line with previous work, including, the findings from Study 1 (USLSE Model) and other studies which suggest that greater fit is associated with increased environmental control, including, choice of appropriate settings (Evans & Stecker, 2004; Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Lazarus & Cohen, 1977; Lee & Brand, 2005, 2010; Proshansky et al., 1970; Sommer, 1966). Further, this finding is consistent with the model for individual learning activities. Divergent from predictions and prior work, however, more frequent Ambient Fit was associated with less frequent Decisional Control. Explanations for this unexpected finding are discussed in subsequent subsections.

Hypothesis 9. Predictors of Affective and Behavioural Stress (Collaborative Learning)

In relation to Hypothesis 9, the environmental perception variables most strongly associated with Affective Stress (e.g., emotional distress) when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities were Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Ambient Fit, both with small effect sizes. Moreover, the environmental perception variables which most strongly predicted variance in Behavioural Stress (concentration, distraction, and avoidance) were Decisional Control, Acoustical and Privacy Fit, and Ambient Fit. Again, both effects were small. Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Ambient Fit were associated with less frequent Affective and Behavioural Stress responses. Furthermore, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with less frequent Behavioural Stress responses.

Such findings are congruent with previous research. First, these findings support the predictions of the USLSE Model and other qualitative research which suggests that better fit between the environment and university students' needs can reduce frustration, increase relaxation, and improve concentration (Granito & Santana, 2016; Harrop & Turpin, 2013; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017; Melhuish, 2010; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017; Van Horne et al., 2014). Further, such findings compliment previous quantitative research which has demonstrated associations between objective environmental conditions (noise, temperature, and lighting) and students' self-reported mood and environment-related well-being (Marchand et al., 2014; Scannell et al., 2016). Finally, the findings support environmental stress theory which suggests that more positive perceptions of the

environment, including perceptions of one's ability to cope (e.g., via decisional control), may lead to reduced stress responses (Lazarus and Cohen, 1977).

Overall, the findings presented here extend previous work by highlighting that students' Academic Stress Responses when using academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities could be improved by increasing:

- Students' perceived fit between collaborative learning activities and their acoustical, privacy, and ambient needs; and
- Students' perceived ability to choose appropriate settings for collaborative learning activities.

Hypothesis 10. Predictors of Collective Engagement (Collaborative Learning)

With regards to Hypothesis 9, Collective Vigour was most strongly predicted by perceptions of Decisional Control, and Acoustical and Privacy Fit, while Collective Dedication was only predicted by Decisional Control (small effects). Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with increased Collective Vigour and Collective Dedication, while more frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with increased Collective Dedication.

Indeed, these findings are in line with the USLSE Model (Study 1) and previous qualitative studies which highlight that environmental characteristics may be associated with students' Engagement in Learning Activities (Granito & Santana, 2016; Matthews et al., 2011; Van Horne et al., 2014). Findings pertaining to Decisional Control in particular, are in line the work of Matthews et al. (2009, 2011) who found that students who choose to study in spaces which are congruent with collaborative learning (social learning spaces) have higher engagement in social learning activities than students who choose to study in spaces which are incongruent with collaborative learning (at home). Overall, the findings extend previous literature by highlighting that students' Collective Engagement (e.g., when working on group assessments) in the academic library could be increased by improving both:

- Students' perceptions of fit between collaborative learning activities and their acoustical and privacy needs; and
- Students' perceived ability to choose learning activity appropriate settings.

Hypothesis 11. Predictors of Quality and Quantity of Work (Collaborative Learning)

In review of Hypothesis 11, the only direct predictor of Quantity and Quality of Work produced when using the academic libraries for collaborative learning, was Decisional Control. More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with increased Quantity and Quality of Work produced when engaging in collaborative learning. This finding is in line with the USLSE Model (Study 1) and prior studies which have highlighted the benefits of environmental control for students' cognitive task performance and workers' job performance (Evans & Stecker, 2004; Lee & Brand, 2010; Sherrod et al., 1977). The findings extend prior work by suggesting that the Quantity and Quality of Work produced by students when using academic libraries for collaborative learning activities, may be increased by improving their perceived ability to choose task-congruent settings for collaborative activities.

Hypothesis 12-14. Indirect associations via Decisional Control (collaborative learning)

As with individual learning activities, the findings from Hypotheses 9-11 suggest that increased Decisional Control may have positive effects for students' Behavioural Stress, Engagement, and Quantity and Quality of Work produced when engaging in collaborative learning activities. Turning to Hypotheses 12-14, four of the 15 indirect relationships between Person-Environment Fit perceptions and the Learning and Psychological Outcomes, via Decisional Control are supportive of this conclusion. As expected, more frequent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit were significantly associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control, which in turn was significantly associated with less frequent Behavioural Stress Responses, increased Collaborative Vigour and Dedication, and increased Quantity and Quality of Work produced. These findings suggest that designers should account for students' Spatial and Ergonomic needs when designing a variety of settings for collaborative learning activities in academic libraries.

However, a further four indirect associations between Person-Environment Fit perceptions and the Learning and Psychological Outcomes were incongruent with predictions and therefore contradicted the conclusion that increased Decisional Control may be beneficial. Interestingly, more frequent perceptions of Ambient Fit were associated with more frequent Behavioural Stress Responses, less frequent Collective Vigour and Collective Dedication, and decreased Quantity and Quality of Work produced, via less frequent Decisional Control.

One explanation for the unexpected direction of the second effect is that environmental control in the present study focused on students' ability to choose learning activity congruent settings. As mentioned in the subsequent subsection, the amount of variance explained in Decisional Control by the Person-Environment Fit variables was appreciably greater for individual in comparison to collaborative learning activities. One explanation for this is that it may be more difficult for students to find spaces which meet the needs of several people (group members) than it is to find a suitable space for one specific individual. Following this logic, it is possible that variables pertaining to students' perceptions of alternative types of control may have influenced these findings. For example, students may be better able to cope with their ambient needs when working as a group via simple behavioural mechanisms, such as, putting on or removing a jumper, opening and closing blinds, and/or opening and closing windows. Further, the questionnaire did not measure the degree to which participants exercised environmental control. While perceived control may be as important as exercising control, Gibson (1966, 1969) highlighted the importance of considering individuals as active rather than passive agents in their environments.

Future research may attempt to incorporate such variables. However, as noted in Study 1, it may be difficult to assess the full range of behavioural options available for students to exert control over environmental demands.

Structural model comparisons (individual and collaborative learning)

Overall, relationships between environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes were stronger for individual learning activities than collaborative learning activities. Upon closer inspection of the R^2_{adj} values, the Person-Environment Fit variables explained noticeably greater variance in perceptions of Decisional Control for individual relative to collaborative learning activities. Further, both perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control explained greater variance in Behavioural Stress and Quantity (and Quality) of Work for individual relative to collaborative learning activities. However, the environmental perception variables explained greater variance in Affective Stress, (Collective) Vigour (Engagement) and (Collective) Dedication (Engagement) for collaborative relative to individual learning activities. There are several possible explanations for these discrepancies.

Considering Decisional Control, as discussed earlier, it may be easier for one individual to find spaces which meet their requirements for individual learning activities. In contrast, it may be more difficult to find a space which meets the requirements of all group members when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning. Such an assumption is supported by previous research which has found differences in students' environmental perceptions and choices as a function of personal characteristics, including, personality and personal preferences (Beckers et al., 2016a, 2016b; Wilson & Cotgrove, 2016).

Turning to the learning and psychological outcomes, however, there were inconsistencies in the amount of variance explained by the environmental perception constructs when comparing individual and collaborative activities. It is challenging to decipher why these differences occurred.

One explanation is that the effects of the environment become less salient for some outcomes when working in a group, such as, Behavioural Stress and Quantity (and Quality) of Work produced. It is possible that when students work collaboratively in the academic library spaces, the social support provided from working with peers may interact with the relationships between environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes. For instance, students may be better able to cope with some, but not all, of the negative effects of environmental demands when engaging in collaborative learning because collaborative learning by its very nature may increase opportunities to seek peer support. Supporting this conclusion, is a body of previous research and theoretical works which suggest that increased social support is generally beneficial for students' performance and abilities to cope with stress (Dupont et al., 2015; Dwyer & Cummings, 2001; Xerri et al., 2017).

In contrast, it is also possible that the effects of some environmental characteristics on other outcomes, such as, Engagement in Learning Activities (Vigour and Dedication) and Affective Stress become more salient when working as a group. Indeed, previous research suggests that the increased opportunities for collaboration within classrooms which are designed to facilitate collaborative learning, may increase the likelihood of students' becoming distracted and disengaged as a consequence non-learning task-related discussion (Walker & Baepler, 2018).

These suggestions are tentative as the findings may also stem from differences in the situational and personal characteristics of the participants who completed both individual and collaborative learning activities. Future research is therefore needed to understand (i) whether learning activities (e.g., individual versus collaborative) interact with the relationships between environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes and (ii) why such interactions may occur.

6.4.5. Limitations

There were several limitations and strengths of this quantitative investigation.

First, the author attempted to address limitations regarding the ratio of sample size to the number of parameters estimated by using PLS-SEM. However, the study did not meet the minimum sample size recommended by G*Power calculations for detecting small effects (cf. recommendations by Hair et al., 2017). Indeed, most of the effects detected were small and the analysis may have had too few participants to detect further small effects. That said, the study did meet the minimum sample requirements set out by Barclay et al. (1995) and Cohen (1992). In addition, the author believes that the use of PLS-SEM compared to CB-SEM would have helped to minimise such limitations (cf. Hair et al., 2016).

Secondly, students were recruited from a single university which recruits a larger number of students from non-traditional backgrounds (e.g., deprived communities, FE colleges, and adult returners to education) than other HEIs in Scotland. The extent to which the findings are applicable to HEIs with fewer non-traditional students is therefore unknown. That said, the data is collected from students who used academic library spaces from three campuses in very different geographical locations.

Thirdly, as with all studies of this type, there is a risk of recall bias. For example, some students may have recalled experiences in which they perceived the physical and/or socio-physical environment as particularly incongruent with their needs, rather than those perceived as having a more limited impact.

Fourthly, the data is cross-sectional and therefore causality cannot be determined. For example, it is possible that students who are more stressed (e.g., due to workload) may view their campus learning spaces in a more negative manner. Likewise, it is possible that students who are more engaged view their campus learning spaces in a more positive manner.

Finally, as with all quantitative research of this type, the author cannot account for any spurious effects that may stem from individual or situational differences. These could include variables, such as, personality (e.g., locus of control), age, and gender. As mentioned previously, this may also be a consequence of the definition for environmental control, focusing on perceptions of decisional control.

Despite the limitations, the study has several significant strengths. Firstly, both the study design (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink, 2010a, 2010b) and analyses (Hair et al., 2017) followed best practice guidance. Specifically, unlike previous studies of this type (e.g., Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016), the model constructs measured, relationships assessed, and the questionnaire underpinning the study are driven by:

- The users of campus learning spaces (students and instructors);
- Previous research; and
- Established person-environment transaction theories.

The constructs (predictors and outcomes) investigated in this study are of far greater relevance to students' learning space experiences than those investigated in previous research. This means that the USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire have far greater content validity than those developed in prior research.

Secondly, related to issues above, the study has far more rigorous conceptual underpinnings than previous research of this type. By focusing on both the dynamic nature and functionality of learning space perceptions and associated outcomes, the ecological validity of the underpinning model and subsequent findings are also enhanced (cf. Gibson, 1978; Heft, 2001). A related strength is that the USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire had good overall psychometric properties with regards to construct (convergent and discriminant) validity and internal consistency reliability (Dillon Goldstein's Rho and Cronbach's α). Further, unlike previous research, psychometric assessment and

reporting followed best practice guidance (cf. Hair et al., 2017). In summary it is postulated that the use of a rigorous methodology has led to far more reliable and valid results than reported in previous studies of this type.

Thirdly, to the best of the author's knowledge, Study 3 is the first to investigate associations between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes, in academic library spaces. As implied above, the study also extends previous research by investigating environmental characteristics (Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical and Privacy Fit, Ambient Fit, and Decisional Control) and learning and psychological outcomes (Academic Stress, Engagement and Work Quantity [and Quality]) in relation to both individual and collaborative learning activities. While not all hypotheses were fully accepted, the author has suggested several plausible explanations for these findings and model modifications which may serve as a useful starting point for future research.

6.4.6. Chapter conclusions

There were two main findings in the present study. First, the psychometric analyses demonstrated that students' learning space experiences in their academic library spaces can be measured in a valid and reliable manner. Specifically, upon the final iterations of the measurement model analyses, construct validity and internal consistency reliability for both the individual and collaborative sections of the USLLSE Questionnaire were acceptable. This supports the assumptions of the USLSE Model.

Secondly, the study found significant associations between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes in their academic library spaces. Overall, these findings supported the USLSE Model, demonstrating that more positive perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment were associated with better outcomes, including, reduced Affective and Behavioural Stress, increased Engagement (Vigour and Dedication), and increased Quantity and/or Quality of Work produced when using the academic library spaces for individual and collaborative learning activities.

While some findings suggest that the opposite may occur, these pertain only to Ambient Fit when engaging in individual learning activities and may stem from the availability of other control mechanisms (behavioural control). Therefore, these few contradictory findings should be interpreted with caution. Overall, these findings support the USLSE Model.

It is worth noting that the USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire underpinning this study have far better content validity and stronger conceptual underpinnings than previous research on university students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes, in their campus learning spaces. Related to this point, the study followed best practice guidance in PLS-SEM construct validity and reliability assessment (Hair et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2015). Thus, the inferential findings from Study 3 are more valid and reliable than those in previous research of this type. It is in (i) addressing the limitations of previous research of this type and (ii) extending previous research of this type to academic library spaces, that this study makes an original contribution to knowledge.

In the next Chapter (7), General Discussion and Conclusions, the author will reflect upon the findings from Studies 1-3 in relation to the overall thesis aims as well as implications for previous research, person-environment transaction theories, practice, and future research.

7. CHAPTER SEVEN

GENERAL DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

7.1. Chapter Introduction

This final chapter begins by illustrating how the research conducted as part of this PhD addressed the overall aims of the thesis. The chapter moves on to discuss the original contribution to knowledge, including, empirical and theoretical, methodological, and practical implications of the research. Subsequently, the limitations and strengths of the overall thesis are presented. Recommendations for future research are discussed, before the thesis is summarised and concluded.

7.2. Addressing the overall aims of the thesis

To recap, previous research on students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and the associated learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces, suffers from several methodological and conceptual flaws. These flaws include insufficient content validity, a lack of established theoretical underpinnings, and insufficient construct validity. Overall, this thesis sought to address the limitations of previous work. The following subsections illustrate how the findings from Studies 1 (focus groups), 2 (systematic review), and 3 (quantitative questionnaire) contributed to the overall aims of this project.

- **Aim 1. Understand how HE students perceive (conceptualise) the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces**

Overview of the empirical and theoretical literature

As discussed in Chapter 2, *Overview of the Empirical and Theoretical Literature*, all person-environment transactions involve an element of perception. Within Chapter 2, the author was driven to review several person-environment transaction theories, including, behaviour settings theory (Proshansky et al., 1970), affordance theory (Barker, 1968; Costall, 1995; Gibson, 1979; Heft, 2001; Prieske et al., 2015; Wicker, 1987; Withagen et al., 2012; Withagen & Wermeeskerken, 2010), control

theories (Averill, 1973; Proshansky et al., 1970), environmental stress theory (Lazarus & Cohen, 1977), and person-environment fit theory (Michelson, 1976). Each of these theories, in part, address how individuals perceive their physical and socio-physical environments to meet their needs (i.e., person-environment fit).

The review of person-environment transaction theories in Chapter 2 served as an initial theoretical base for understanding how students perceive or conceptualise the environment in their campus learning spaces. Accordingly, the theoretical review can be considered as an initial attempt to address research Aim 1. However, it was unclear whether these person-environment transaction theories were relevant to university students' learning space experiences, including, perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces. That is to say, do students conceptualise the environment in their campus learning spaces as threatening, challenging, harmful, benign/irrelevant, congruent/incongruent, in a dynamic manner, and/or in terms of its functional opportunities (e.g., cf. Barker, 1966; Gibson, 1978; Heft, 2001; Lazarus & Cohen, 1977; Michelson, 1976)? Therefore, qualitative Study 1 (focus groups) aimed, in part, to understand the utility of the abovementioned person-environment transaction theories in explaining students' learning space experiences.

Qualitative Study 1

The findings from Study 1 (focus groups) suggested that when using their campus spaces for learning and teaching activities, students perceive their environment in terms of the discrepancy or fit between (i) their needs for a particular learning activity (the ideal learning space) and (ii) the demands of the environment (their experience of campus learning spaces).²⁴ Related to this, the findings from Study 1 suggested that students also perceived the environment in their campus learning spaces in terms of the ability to choose settings that are congruent with learning activities, including, suitable alternatives. In addition, the focus group findings suggested that students' perceptions of the environment vary over time and with circumstances (e.g., learning tasks, transition into final year, and personal preferences). While it was not a direct intention to understand how instructors perceive learning spaces, the analysis of instructor data was supportive of these findings. The USLSE Model was developed based on the qualitative findings and their

²⁴ Learning activities could be conceptualised as either individual or collaborative. Individual learning activities included, for example, lecture instruction and self-directed individual learning out with class. Collaborative learning activities included, for instance, class discussion and group learning within and out with class.

empirical and theoretical interpretation which, in part, explained how students perceive the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces.

The proposition that students perceive the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces in terms of the fit between their needs for a learning activity and the demands of the environment is in line with ecological theories (Barker, 1968; Costall, 1995; Gibson, 1979; Heft, 2001; Wicker, 1987) and Michelson's (1976) person-environment which propose that individuals perceive environments and objects within environments in terms of their functions (e.g., individual and collaborative learning). The finding that students perceive choice over environmentally congruent settings for their learning activities is in line with Averill's (1973) conceptualisation of Decisional Control. Specifically, Decisional Control refers to one's ability to choose settings which meet their needs or from a range of options e.g., suitable alternatives (Averill, 1973; Gatersleben & Griffin, 2016; Haghnia & Imani, 2016). Finally, the finding that environmental perceptions are variable over time and as a function of circumstances is in line with each of the aforementioned person-environment transaction theories.

Qualitative Study 2

Study 2 (systematic review of the measurement instruments) found that six (of 136 identified) questionnaires met psychometric quality appraisal criteria for inclusion, i.e., attempted to address content validity, construct validity, and internal consistency reliability. However, none of these six instruments consistently addressed the issues identified in the USLSE Model, including, frequency of perceived Person-Environment Fit between students' needs for their learning activities and the demands of the environment within their learning spaces nor their perceptions of Decisional Control. By way of illustration, Castilla et al. (2017) included items which assessed students' affective impressions of their physical classroom environment e.g., as warm versus cold, while Yang et al. (2013) included items which measured students' 'satisfaction with' and 'perceived impact of' environmental characteristics on performance. Furthermore, it was also unclear whether and to what extent established theories underpinned the conceptualisations of students' physical and socio-physical environments. In summary, within the six instruments, researchers appeared to conceptualise students' environmental perceptions in an ad hoc manner.

Quantitative Study 3

Guided by the findings and their interpretation from Study 1 (i.e., the USLSE Model), a new and robust quantitative questionnaire was created to assess students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their academic library learning spaces. As such, the so-called USLLSE Questionnaire has superior content validity and conceptual underpinnings than previous instruments. True to the USLSE Model, the questionnaire assessed perceptions of fit between students' learning activities and the demands of their environment (i.e., functionality), perceptions of Decisional Control, and the perceived frequency with which students' needs were met (i.e., dynamic nature) when engaging in individual and/or collaborative learning in their academic library spaces. Interpretation of the PLS-SEM measurement model analyses revealed that both the individual and collaborative sections of the questionnaire had good overall psychometric properties, including, both construct validity (convergent and discriminant) and internal consistency reliability for a new questionnaire. Thus, the quantitative findings on a larger and more representative sample were in line with the qualitative findings and USLSE Model. Specifically, using a robust (valid and reliable) methodological approach, the findings suggest that students perceive/conceptualise the environment in their campus learning spaces with regards to:

- The degree of fit between their needs for a learning activity and the demands of the environment;
 - Their ability to choose their preferred settings for a particular learning activity and alternatives when their preferred settings do not meet their needs;
 - The functionality of the physical environment for different learning activities (individual and collaborative); and
 - The dynamic nature of person-environment transactions (i.e., variation in circumstances over time).
-
- **Aim 2. Understand the relevance of different (i) physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics and (ii) learning and psychological consequences to students' learning space experiences**

Environmental Characteristics

Reflecting on the second aim, the analysis of students' and instructors' discussions in Study 1 suggested that five groups of environmental variables were relevant to students' learning space experiences, in line with previous qualitative and quantitative research. These included: Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, and Decisional Control.

Spatial and Ergonomic Fit concerned students' and instructors' perceptions of the physical and social density, furniture arrangement and seating position, desk size, and furniture comfort within campus spaces used for learning and teaching activities. Acoustical Fit reflected perceptions of qualitative acoustical characteristics and included the noise level, noise from people talking, and noise from equipment (e.g., radios and ventilation systems) within a space. Ambient Fit considered the relevance of environmental characteristics, including, temperature and air quality/ventilation, natural and artificial lighting, and aesthetic variables (window views to outside spaces and the use of colour) to students' learning space experiences.

Perceptions of Privacy Fit addressed the importance of input from others, including, interruptions to learning tasks by peers (task privacy), noise from other people talking (acoustical privacy), and seeing other people moving (visual privacy). Output to others included being observed by others (visual privacy) and concerns about disturbing others (speech privacy). The degree to which students wanted to be surrounded by others and architectural privacy were also evident in the discussions. Finally, perceptions of Choice (Decisional Control) concerned students' and instructors' abilities to choose learning activity congruent spaces or choose suitable alternatives (e.g., when their preferred space did not meet their needs). Within the latter two concerns, Privacy Fit and Decisional Control, several issues became evident from the focus group discussions.

First, Privacy Fit appeared to be less of a concern to students' learning space experiences within classroom settings relative to out-of-class settings. Secondly, students' opportunities for exercising Decisional Control over settings used for learning activities out with class appeared to be greater compared with settings used for scheduled classes. Specifically, Decisional Control over classroom spaces appeared to rest with instructors and campus services (e.g., room booking services and protocols). That is not to say that concerns of privacy and decisional control are not relevant to students' in-class learning space experiences. Rather, with respect to the participants in the Study 1, Privacy Fit and Decisional Control appeared to be of greater relevance to students' learning experiences out with scheduled classes.

Indeed, the measurement model findings in Study 3 predominantly provided quantitative support for the relevance of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, and Decisional

Control with specific reference to academic library spaces. It appears to be the case that the student participants did not discriminate between perceptions of Acoustical Fit and perceptions of Privacy Fit. As such, the corresponding items for both constructs were merged to create a new construct which represented both Acoustical and Privacy Fit. This new construct was conceptually justified because both scales included items which pertained to input from other people, including, noise from other people talking (Acoustical Fit), interruptions (Privacy Fit), and seeing other people moving (Privacy Fit).

One item concerning students' perceptions of "distractions from window views to outside" was removed from the individual learning activities scale to improve validity and reliability, but not from the collaborative learning activities scale. It is possible that this issue is more relevant to students' learning space experiences when they are working in a group rather than individually. Specifically, it may be the case that students are more likely to become distracted by events that are happening outside when they are working their peers. However, given the nature of the study design (i.e., the inability to investigate statistical differences between the two models), one must be cautious about drawing such conclusions.

Another item, "too few people in the space", was removed from both the individual and collaborative learning activities scales. Specifically, this item sought to assess participants' need to be surrounded by others (Privacy Fit). It is possible that this issue is less important to students' learning space experiences than initially assumed. Alternatively, the item may have measured a separate dimension of privacy, such as, the need for interaction/communication (e.g., cf. Beckers et al., 2016a).

Learning and Psychological Outcomes

The focus group findings (Study 1) also highlighted three learning and psychological consequences of the environment. First, the most prominent consequence was that of students' Engagement in Learning Activities (individual and collaborative). This included students' involvement or motivation to involve themselves in a learning activity as well as their ability to concentrate on a learning activity without becoming distracted.

Secondly, Cognitive-Affective Consequences were based on students' and instructors' discussions of the positive and negative psychological consequences which appear to occur as a consequence of using spaces in which the environment is congruent or incongruent with learning activities. Positive consequences were discerned from discussions of 'rest', relaxation, stress relief, and 'happy spaces'. Negative cognitive-affective consequences were discerned from discussions of annoyance, frustration, comfort, and discomfort. Thirdly, Quantity and Quality of work was evidenced by students' discussions of the quantity of work produced and both students' and instructors' discussions of learning task quality (e.g., creativity and performance).

The relevance of these Learning and Psychological Outcomes was also assessed, in part, by the quantitative study (Study 3). Several measures developed and used in previous studies were adapted to measure students' self-reported Academic Stress Responses (Cognitive-Affective outcomes), Engagement (Vigour and Dedication), and Quantity and Quality of Work in relation to both individual and collaborative learning activities. The analysis predominantly supported the relevance of these outcomes, with measurement model interpretation demonstrating good overall psychometric properties. That said, items pertaining to Quality of Work were removed from the individual learning activities component of the questionnaire due to psychometric reasons; this was justified as it is possible that students may have difficulty evaluating their own performance when engaging in individual learning relative to that of their group members when engaging in collaborative learning activities.²⁵

Environmental Characteristics and Learning and Psychological Outcomes

The structural model analyses (Study 3) also demonstrated the relevance of both the environmental characteristics and learning and psychological outcomes discussed above, for students' learning space experiences. To varying degrees, each of the learning and psychological Outcomes (Academic Stress, Engagement, and Quantity and/or Quality of Work produced) were significantly predicted (directly or indirectly) by at least one of the four environmental perception constructs (Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical and Privacy Fit, Ambient Fit, and/or Decisional Control).

²⁵ Indeed, students in a study by Kurunsaari et al. (2015) noted that it was more difficult to evaluate their own skills than those of their course peers.

Summary

In summary, based on Studies 1 and 3, four key environmental characteristics were found to be important to students' learning space experiences for individual and collaborative learning activities: (i) Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, (ii) Acoustical and Privacy Fit, (iii) Ambient Fit, and (iv) Decisional Control. In addition, three learning and psychological outcomes were relevant to students' campus learning space experiences for individual and collaborative learning: (i) Cognitive-Affective Outcomes (e.g., Academic Stress), (ii) Engagement in Learning Activities (e.g., dedication and vigour), and (iii) Quantity and/or Quality of Work produced when using campus spaces for learning activities. As discussed in previous chapters, these findings are in line with prior empirical and theoretical works. This is elaborated in Subsection 7.3.1.

- Aim 3. Develop a new and robust 'learning space experience' questionnaire to measure students' perceptions of the most relevant physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics in their campus learning spaces

Previous research on the relationships between students' perceptions of the environment and learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces (e.g., Belojević et al., 1992; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016) suffer from a number of methodological and conceptual flaws. First, it is unclear how relevant the environmental characteristics and outcome variables assessed in previous research are to students' learning space experiences. Specifically, the constructs assessed are typically chosen on an ad hoc basis by researchers. The content validity of these variables and their corresponding questionnaires is therefore limited. Secondly, the constructs assessed in previous research and their corresponding questionnaires lack sufficient conceptual and theoretical underpinnings. Thirdly, the construct validity and internal consistency reliability of the constructs assessed, and their corresponding questionnaires is rarely investigated. Where construct validity is assessed, analytical procedures are poor and/or lack transparency (e.g., poor reporting) (e.g., see Castilla et al., 2017; Choi et al., 2014a; Scannell et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2013). Each of these limitations can hinder the reliability and validity of subsequent findings based on inferential statistical analyses (Elf et al., 2016; Francis et al., 2016; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014).²⁶

²⁶ See Chapters 2 (Overview of the Empirical and Theoretical Literature) and Chapter 5 (Study 2, systematic review) for more information.

To address the limitations of previous research, a new quantitative questionnaire was developed which measured students' learning space experiences. To ensure greater rigour than previous instruments, the questionnaire followed best practice guidance for new scale development (cf. Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink, 2010a, 2010b) and for PLS-SEM psychometric analysis (Hair et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2015).

To enhance content validity, focus groups were conducted with the users of the campus learning spaces (students and instructors) at the target university in order to understand students' learning space experiences. An RTA of the focus group data revealed physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics and learning and psychological outcomes which were relevant to students' learning space experiences. The focus group data was discussed in light of previous research and theory and was then used to construct a thematic model, the USLSE Model. The model explains the relationships between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces.

The USLSE Model is driven by both data from students and instructors, previous research, and established person-environment transaction theories. The model constructs, therefore, have superior content validity and conceptual underpinnings compared with the constructs assessed in previous studies.

To ensure high content validity of the subsequent questionnaire, the USLSE Model was then used to inform the development of the USLLSE Questionnaire which sought to assess students' perceptions of relevant environmental characteristics and outcomes in their campus library spaces. To further ensure content validity, the questionnaire was subject to revisions following feedback from a small sample of postgraduate students, an environmental psychologist, and a university Vice Principal for Learning and Teaching.

To investigate the construct validity and reliability of the USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire, data was collected from students across three campus library spaces at a Scottish, multi-campus and multi-geographic, HEI. 418 students provided useable responses for the section of the questionnaire pertaining to individual learning activities, while 307 provided useable responses for the section on

collaborative learning activities. Psychometric analyses using PLS-SEM revealed that the USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire had good overall psychometric properties, including, construct validity (convergent and discriminant) and internal consistency reliability (Dillon-Goldstein's Rho and Cronbach's α). Psychometric analyses were conducted and reported following best practice guidance for PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2015) and were therefore more robust and transparent than psychometric analyses of questionnaires used in previous quantitative research to assess students' learning space experiences

In summary, the USLLSE Questionnaire was developed, based on rich qualitative data from students and instructors and the interpretation of said qualitative data based on previous research and established person-environment transaction theories. The new questionnaire was subjected to further content validity checks. Psychometric analyses based on data from large samples of students across three academic library spaces demonstrated that the USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire had good overall psychometric properties. By following such rigorous procedures, the questionnaire developed in this thesis is therefore more robust (has greater validity and reliability) than those developed in previous research (e.g., Belojević et al., 1992; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016).

- **Aim 4. Explore how students' perceptions of relevant environmental characteristics are statistically associated with key learning and psychological outcomes**

To reiterate, quantitative Study 3 investigated the structural relationships proposed between the constructs in the USLSE Model (developed in Study 1). Specifically, Study 3 explored the statistical associations between students' perceptions of the environment and learning and psychological outcomes when using academic library spaces for individual and collaborative learning activities, respectively. To maximise the validity and reliability of the analyses, the structural relationships between the constructs proposed in the USLSE Model were investigated using the final iterations of the measurement models for individual learning activities (iteration 5) and collaborative learning activities (iteration 3).

Individual learning activities

The SEM analysis for students' learning space experiences when using the academic library spaces for individual learning activities, revealed that 10 of the 23 direct relationships were significant in the

anticipated direction. However, for one of these relationships, no detectable effect was present (Ambient Fit to Affective Stress). The learning and psychological outcomes most strongly associated with their respective combinations of predictors were, in order of greatest variance explained, Decisional Control, Behavioural Stress, Affective Stress, Quantity of Work produced, Vigour (Engagement), and Dedication (Engagement).

In particular, more frequent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit and Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control; more frequent perceptions of Acoustical and Privacy Fit were associated with less frequent Affective Stress; more frequent Acoustical and Privacy Fit and Decisional Control were associated with less frequent Behavioural Stress; more frequent Decisional Control was associated with increased Vigour and Dedication (Engagement); and more frequent Decisional Control and Acoustical and Privacy fit were associated with increased Work Quantity. In addition, eight of the 15 indirect effects were significant in the direction predicted by the USLSE Model for individual learning activities. Specifically, more frequent perceptions Acoustical and Privacy Fit and more frequent Spatial and Ergonomic Fit were significantly associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. In turn, more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were associated with less frequent Behavioural Stress, more frequent Vigour and Dedication, and increased Quantity of Work produced.

Collaborative learning activities

The PLS-SEM analysis for students' learning space experiences when using academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities, revealed that 10 of the 23 direct relationships were significant in direction predicted by the USLSE Model, while one was significant in the unexpected direction. In order of greatest variance explained, the outcome variables most strongly associated with their respective combinations of predictors were Behavioural Stress, Decisional Control, Collective Vigour (Engagement), Collective Dedication (Engagement), and Quantity and Quality of Work produced.

Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control; more frequent Acoustical and Privacy Fit and more frequent Ambient Fit were associated with reduced Affective Stress; more frequent Decisional Control, Acoustical and Privacy Fit, and Ambient Fit were associated with more frequent Behavioural Stress Responses; more frequent Decisional Control and Acoustical and Ambient Fit were associated

with more frequent experiences of Vigour (Engagement); more frequent Decisional Control was associated with more frequent experiences of Dedication (Engagement); and more frequent Decisional Control was associated with increased Quantity and Quality of Work produced. Incongruent with predictions, more frequent perceptions of Ambient Fit were associated with less frequent perceptions of Decisional Control when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning.

Of the 15 indirect relationships via Decisional Control, eight were significant, and four in the direction that was predicted by the USLSE Model. As hypothesised, more frequent perceptions of Spatial and Ergonomic Fit were associated with more frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. More frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were, in turn, significantly associated with less frequent Behavioural Stress, more frequent Collective Vigour and Collective Dedication (Engagement), and increased Quantity and Quality of Work produced. Incongruent with predictions of the USLSE Model, however, more frequent perceptions of Ambient Fit were significantly associated with less frequent perceptions of Decisional Control. In turn, less frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were significantly associated with more frequent experiences of Behavioural Stress, less frequent Collective Vigour and Collective Dedication (Engagement), and decreased Quantity and Quality of Work produced.

Summary

Across the two models, 20 of the 21 significant direct effects suggested that more positive perceptions of the environment (Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical and Privacy Fit, Ambient Fit, and Decisional Control) may have beneficial consequences for the learning and psychological outcomes assessed (Decisional Control, Academic Stress, Engagement, and Quantity and/or Quality of Work) when using the academic library spaces for learning. Only one of the 21 significant direct effects suggested that more positive perceptions of Person-Environment (Ambient) Fit were associated with more negative psychological consequences, specifically, more negative perceptions of Decisional Control.

Across both the individual and collaborative learning models, 12 of the 16 significant indirect effects suggested that more positive perceptions of the environment may be beneficial for students' learning and psychological outcomes when using the academic library spaces for learning. Only four

of the 16 significant indirect effects were significant in the unexpected direction, specifically, when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning.

In summary, the 32 significant associations suggest that more positive perceptions of the environment may be beneficial for learning and psychological outcomes when using the academic library spaces for individual and collaborative learning. The implications of these findings are discussed in the subsequent section. Specifically, in the subsequent subsections, the author reflects on his original contribution to knowledge, including, empirical and theoretical contributions, methodological implications, and practical implications.

7.3. Contributions to knowledge

7.3.1. Empirical and theoretical contributions

The research conducted within this thesis extends previous research and contributes to theorisation on students' learning space experiences. In the subsequent subsections the author demonstrates this original contribution in relation to previous research and the person-environment transaction theories presented in Chapter 2. The author also reflects upon methodological and practical contributions.

Previous research on objective environmental conditions and the associated learning and psychological outcomes

As discussed in Chapter 2, the relationships between objective environmental conditions and learning and psychological outcomes is well documented. This includes the impact of classroom design (active learning versus traditional) on students' environmental perceptions, engagement in student-centred versus traditional pedagogical practices and use of 21st century workplace skills (e.g., problem solving and collaborative learning), concept learning and course performance (Brooks, 2011, 2012; Baepler et al., 2014; Beichner, 2007; Dori et al., 2003; Dori & Belcher, 2005; Whiteside et al., 2010). Further, studies from environmental psychology have shown the impact of single and multiple objective environmental characteristics (e.g., noise, temperature, lighting, colour, window views, and/or density) on students' academic performance, participation in class activities, cognitive task performance and productivity, and cognitive-affective outcomes such as mood and class or course evaluations (Benfield et al., 2015; Collins-Eiland et al., 1986; Marchand et al., 2014; Salamé & Baddeley, 1987; Stone, 2001).

The findings from qualitative Study 1 both support and extend previous findings to demonstrate that students and instructors recognise the relevance of objective environmental conditions for students' learning and psychological outcomes. Further, the quantitative findings demonstrate that more positive perceptions of the environment are associated with reduced stress, increased engagement, and increased quantity and/or quality of work produced when using the academic libraries for individual and collaborative learning. Specifically, these findings highlight the importance of (i) investigating students' subjective experiences of their campus learning spaces in their own right (ii), studying the statistical relationships between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes, and (iii) considering the relationships between objective environmental conditions, students' perceptions of these conditions, and learning and psychological outcomes.

As mentioned previously, environmental conditions are one of several situational characteristics which may explain students' learning space perceptions (cf. Baepler et al., 2014; Marchand et al., 2014). Therefore, it is possible that environmental perceptions play a mediating role in explaining the relationships between objective environmental conditions, other situational and personal characteristics, and learning and psychological outcomes. This would align with environmental stress theory, which proposes that a primary and secondary appraisal process explains, in part, the relationships between environmental conditions, personal and situational circumstances, and experiences of stress and stress-related outcomes (cf. Lazarus & Cohen, 1977).

Previous qualitative research on learning space experiences

A body of qualitative findings from US and English HEIs has shown that students and instructors are able to articulate the role of the physical and socio-physical environment for students' learning and psychological experiences (Granito & Santana, 2016; Hunter & Cox, 2014; Matthews et al., 2011; Van Horne et al., 2014). Study 1 extends previous qualitative findings to students and instructors in at a Scottish, multi-campus and multi-geographic, HEI. By comparing the qualitative analysis from Study 1 with previous quantitative and qualitative findings as well as investigating the utility of person-environment transaction theories, Study 1 extends previous qualitative work by proposing a new learning space experience model. This USLSE Model describes:

- How students perceive or conceptualise the physical environment (i.e., in terms of person-environment fit and decisional control);

- The relevant physical and socio-physical environmental characteristics and learning and psychological outcomes to students' learning space experiences; and
- The associations between students' perceptions of the environment and their learning and psychological outcomes in campus learning spaces.

Additionally, Study 3 has validated previous qualitative findings from Study 1 and other qualitative studies (Granito and Santana, 2016; Hunter and Cox, 2014; Matthews et al., 2011; Van Horne et al., 2014) by demonstrating that environmental characteristics identified as important to students and instructors are statistically associated with relevant learning and psychological outcomes, on a larger and more representative sample.

Previous research on associations between students' environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes

A much smaller body of research has investigated the relationships between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and the associated learning and psychological outcomes in their campus learning spaces. These outcomes include different types of learning space perceptions, students' class and course evaluations, cognitive task performance, and academic performance (e.g., Belojević et al., 1992; Castilla et al., 2017; Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016). However, these studies have several conceptual and methodological flaws. Indeed, findings from the systematic review (Study 2) support this conclusion. Only one study which met quality appraisal criteria for inclusion investigated the relationships between students' physical and socio-physical environmental preferences and their preferred study spaces (Beckers et al., 2016a). While this study was valuable, a more nuanced investigation revealed flaws such as insufficiencies in underpinning conceptualisations, construct validity analyses, and reliability analyses (cf. Study 2, systematic review).

The significant associations identified in Study 3 support prior work (e.g., Belojević et al., 1992; Choi et al., 2014a; Hoque & Weil, 2016) by demonstrating that, generally, more positive perceptions of the environment are associated with better learning and psychological outcomes in campus learning spaces. Moreover, Study 3 extends these findings in several ways. First, Study 3 was based the findings from the qualitative data that was collected in study 1, interpretation of findings in relation to previous research, and established theory, i.e., the USLSE Model. Specifically, the USLSE Model

was used to inform the environmental characteristics and outcomes that were investigated in Study 3 and the corresponding USLLSE Questionnaire used to assess these constructs. Unlike the aforementioned studies, the findings in Study 3 are therefore based on constructs and measurement scales which (i) are more relevant to students' learning space experiences (i.e., have greater content validity) and (ii) have superior conceptual underpinnings.

Further, data collected from a representative sample of students who used three different academic libraries was employed to assess construct validity and internal consistency of the USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire. Following best practice guidance on PLS-SEM analysis and reporting (cf. Hair et al., 2017), Study 3 found that the USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire had good overall psychometric properties, including, construct validity (convergent and discriminant) and internal consistency reliability (Dillon-Goldstein's Rho and Cronbach's α). Using this framework as a basis, the inferential findings in Study 3, therefore, have far greater validity and reliability than those in previous studies of this type.²⁷

Previous research on students' learning space perceptions and the associated learning and psychological outcomes have predominantly focused on classroom spaces. To the best of the author's knowledge, only one study (Beckers et al. 2016a) investigated HE students' privacy, interaction, autonomy/control, ambient, spatial, and ICT needs and the associations with study space preferences for individual and collaborative learning ("quiet, closed" versus "busy, open spaces"). However, a nuanced evaluation of this study revealed methodological and conceptual flaws, including, insufficient psychometric analyses and conceptual underpinnings (Study 2). As such, to the best of the author's knowledge, Study 3 is the first study to investigate the statistical associations between students' perceptions of the environment and learning and psychological outcomes within the context of campus learning spaces used for learning out with class, specifically, academic library spaces.

Study 3 also extends previous research, by demonstrating that the outcome variables associated with students' learning space perceptions extend beyond those that have previously been selected by researchers on an ad hoc basis (i.e., academic achievement, class evaluations, and course

²⁷ As noted in previous chapters, poor validity and reliability can bias parameter estimates in inferential analyses (Francis et al., 2016).

evaluations). These include learning and psychological outcomes that are of relevance to students' learning space experience (Study 1; Granito & Santana, 2016; Hunter & Cox, 2014; Rands & Gansemer-Topf, 2017; Van Horne et al., 2014). The outcomes include students' Academic Stress Responses, Engagement in Learning Activities, and Quantity and/or Quality of Work produced, when using their academic library spaces for individual and collaborative learning activities (Study 3)

Finally, Study 3 raised a number of interesting questions. First, one direct effect and four indirect effects in the collaborative learning model were significant in the opposite direction than was anticipated. Specifically, more frequent perceptions of Ambient Fit were associated with more frequent Behavioural Stress Responses, less frequent Collective Vigour and Collective Dedication, and decreased Quantity and Quality of Work produced, via less frequent Decisional Control.

An explanation for the unexpected direction of these effects is the focussed definition of environmental control, which assessed students' perceptions of their ability to choose settings that were congruent with learning activities. As discussed, the amount of variance explained in Decisional Control by the Person-Environment Fit variables was noticeably greater for individual in comparison to collaborative learning activities. Following this logic, it may be more difficult for students to find spaces which meet the needs of several people (group members) than it is to find a suitable space for one specific individual. Therefore, variables pertaining to students' perceptions of alternative types of control could have influenced these findings. For instance, students may be better able to cope with their ambient needs when working as a group via simple behavioural mechanisms, such as, putting on or removing a jumper, opening and closing blinds, and/or opening and closing windows. Additionally, the questionnaire did not measure the extent to which participants exercised environmental control. Perceived control may be as important as exercising control (Averill, 1973; Haghnia & Imani, 2016; Proshansky et al., 1970). Nevertheless, Gibson (1978) highlighted the importance of considering individuals as active rather than passive agents in their environments.

Secondly, overall, the relationships between environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes were stronger for individual learning than collaborative learning activities. Upon closer inspection, the Person-Environment Fit variables explained noticeably greater variance in perceptions of Decisional Control for individual as opposed to collaborative learning activities. As noted above, a reasonable explanation for this finding is that it may be easier for one individual to

find spaces which meet their requirements for individual learning activities. In contrast, it may be more difficult to find a space which meets the requirements of all group members when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning. Such an assumption is supported by previous research which has found differences in students' environmental perceptions and choices as a function of personal characteristics, including, personality and personal preferences (Beckers et al., 2016a; Wilson & Cotgrove, 2016).

Turning to the learning and psychological outcomes, however, there were inconsistencies in the amount of variance explained by the environmental perception constructs when comparing individual and collaborative activities. In particular, the environmental perception variables explained greater variance in Affective Stress, (Collective) Vigour (Engagement), and (Collective) Dedication (Engagement) for collaborative relative to individual learning activities. It is difficult to determine why these differences may be present.

As outlined in Study 3, it is possible that the effects of the environment are less salient for some outcomes when working in a group, including, Behavioural Stress and Quantity (and Quality) of Work produced. Specifically, when students work collaboratively in the academic library spaces, the social support inherent in collaborative learning with peers may interact with the relationships between environmental perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes. For instance, students may be better able to cope with some, but not all, of the negative effects of environmental demands when engaging in collaborative learning because collaborative learning by its very nature increases opportunities to seek peer support. Supporting this conclusion, is a body of research which suggest that increased social support is generally beneficial for students' performance and ability to cope with stress (Dupont et al., 2015; Dwyer & Cummings, 2001; Xerri et al., 2017).

In contrast, it is also possible that the effects of some environmental characteristics on other outcomes, such as, Engagement in Learning Activities (Vigour and Dedication) and Affective Stress become more salient when working as a group. Indeed, previous research suggests that the increased opportunities for collaboration within classrooms which are designed to facilitate collaborative learning, may increase the likelihood of students' becoming distracted and disengaged as a consequence non-learning activity-related discussion (Walker & Baepler, 2018).

However, these suggestions are tentative as the findings may also stem from differences between the participant groups who completed both individual and collaborative learning sections of the questionnaire (e.g., differences in students' personal and situational characteristics).

Theoretical contribution

The work presented within this thesis has several theoretical contributions. The USLSE Model (Study 1) provides insight into how students conceptualise the environment in their campus learning spaces. The Model suggests that students perceive their physical environment in terms of the fit between their needs for a specific learning activity (i.e., ideal environmental conditions) and the demands of the physical environment (i.e., their experience of the settings used). This included Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical Fit, Ambient Fit, Privacy Fit, and Decisional Control. The notion that students perceive their physical environment in terms of "fit" is in line with Michelson's (1976) construct of mental congruence or perceived person-environment fit, the degree to which one believes the environment fits their needs. As mentioned previously, Michelson's construct can be considered as a meta-theory which encompasses each of the person-environment transaction theories discussed in Chapter 2; therefore, this finding is supportive of person-environment transaction theories more generally. Furthermore, the idea that students strive to choose suitable spaces and/or suitable alternatives (e.g., when their preferred space is incongruent) compliments Averill's (1973) construct of Decisional Control. To reiterate, Decisional Control refers to one's ability or perceived ability to choose appropriate settings (Averill, 1973; Gatersleben & Griffin, 2016; Haghnia & Imani, 2016).

Key to both perceptions of Person-Environment Fit and Decisional Control in the USLSE Model was the notion that, when using campus spaces for learning and teaching activities, students and instructors conceptualise the environment in terms of the degree to which it meets their requirements for their learning and teaching activities (i.e., individual or collaborative). This is in line with the notion that the environment is perceived in terms of the functional opportunities or the possibilities for action that an environment provides or constrains (Barker, 1968; Costall, 1995; Gibson, 1979; Heft, 2001; Michelson, 1976; Wicker, 1987). As noted by ecological theorists (Gibson, 1979; Heft, 2001), perceived functionality of the environment represents a far more ecologically valid approach to understanding environmental perceptions than traditional form-based or descriptive approaches.

In addition, it was apparent from the students' and instructors' discussions (Study 1) that perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and the learning and psychological consequences of the environment were dynamic. That is, learning space perceptions vary as a function of situational and personal characteristics. Again, this finding is supportive of the person-environment transaction theories discussed in Chapter 2, which suggest (explicitly or implicitly) that perceptions of the environment and associated consequences vary over time and as a function of circumstances (Barker, 1968; Costall, 1995; Gibson, 1979; Heft, 2001; Lazarus & Cohen, 1977; Proshansky et al., 1970; Wicker, 1987).

The quantitative findings (Study 3) also support the qualitative theoretical findings of Study 1 and the person-environment transaction theories discussed above. Specifically, the constructs in USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire had good overall psychometric properties. This suggests that when using their academic library spaces for both individual and collaborative learning activities, students' learning space perceptions can be measured both in a valid and reliable way in terms of:

1. The degree of fit between their needs and the demands of the environment;
2. Their ability to choose their preferred settings for a particular task and alternatives when their preferred settings do not meet their needs;
3. The functionality of the physical environment for different learning activities (individual and collaborative); and
4. The dynamic nature of person-environment transactions (i.e., variation in circumstances over time).

Further theoretical implications from both Studies 1 and 3 concern the notion that, irrespective of objective environmental conditions, students' perceptions of environmental demands may have positive and negative learning and psychological implications. This is in line with Michelson's (1976) comparison of mental congruence or perceived person-environment fit to a "self-fulfilling prophecy". That is, if an individual perceives poor fit between their needs for a specific activity and the demands of the environment, then the individual is less likely to engage in said activity (Michelson, 1976).

Similarly, theories of environmental control purport that learned helplessness can ensue when people experience a loss of (perceived environmental control), whereby people give up attempting to regain environmental control, regardless of whether objective control can be regained. This has been evidenced in previous studies which have shown a lack of task engagement, affect-related consequences (including depression), and lowered cognitive task performance when participants are exposed to uncontrollable environmental stressors in quasi-experimental and laboratory settings (Evans & Stecker, 2004; Sherrod et al., 1977).

Likewise, Lazarus and Cohen (1977) propose that negative primary and secondary appraisals (e.g., threat and poor coping appraisals) are associated with increased stress and stress-related outcomes. Indeed, the students and instructors in Study 1 articulated that those environmental characteristics which they perceived negatively (e.g., incongruent furniture arrangements and/or uncomfortable temperature) could have negative consequences for students' learning experiences, including, Cognitive-Affective consequences (annoyance and frustration), decreased Engagement in Learning Activities, and reduced Quantity and Quality of Work produced when using campus spaces for learning and teaching activities.

Overall, the significant associations identified in Study 3 are also supportive of this assumption. There were, however, some exceptions to this. Interestingly, students' with more frequent perceptions of Ambient Fit had less frequent perceptions of Decisional Control when using their academic library spaces for collaborative learning activities. Less frequent perceptions of Decisional Control were, in turn, associated with more frequent Behavioural Stress Responses, less frequent Collective Engagement (Vigour and Dedication), and decreased Quantity and Quality of Work produced when using the academic library spaces for collaborative learning. As mentioned previously, Ambient Fit is concerned with students' perceptions of temperature, air quality/ventilation, natural and artificial lighting, window views to outside, and use of colour. One explanation for these findings is that it is difficult for students to choose and utilise spaces which meet the ambient needs of all students within their group. As such, students may engage in much simpler behavioural mechanisms to exert control over their environment, such as, putting on or removing a jumper, switching lights on or off, and/or opening and closing blinds. Future research should strive to assess students' perceptions of behavioural control.

Overall, the qualitative findings from Study 1 together with the significant associations from Study 3 support the use of person-environment transaction theories as a potential underpinning for future research on students' learning space perceptions and the associated learning and psychological outcomes.

7.3.2. Methodological contributions

The research conducted within this thesis is based on best practice guidance for research design, including the development of robust questionnaires. The rigorous mixed methodological approach adopted in this thesis may be used in future research to measure students' experiences of other campus spaces, for example, in classroom, social, and extracurricular spaces.

First, a broad review of the literature could be useful in serving as both an empirical and theoretical base for the subsequent empirical studies. Secondly, the collection of qualitative data to identify constructs which are relevant to students' experiences, can help to develop a useful framework for (i) enhancing the content validity of the constructs assessed and their corresponding measurement instruments and (ii) investigating the utility of established theoretical frameworks (e.g., person-environment transaction theories) identified in the broader literature review. This qualitative data may then be used to develop a thematic model which is driven by users' experiences, previous research, and established (person-environment transaction) theoretical frameworks. This model could, for example, explain students' experiences of campus spaces used for extra-curricular and social activities.

The resulting model can then be used as part of a framework for evaluation and research design in subsequent stages. Overall, such an approach can help to enhance content validity and provide a strong conceptual basis for subsequent research (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink, 2010a, 2010b). Further, the use of systematic review methodologies can be beneficial in investigating the suitability of existing instruments, for example, by evaluating their psychometric properties and conceptual underpinnings. Finally, by drawing on various prior stages, researchers can identify constructs and create corresponding measurement instruments (e.g., questionnaires) which are relevant to students' experiences of campus spaces. Data collected from larger and more representative samples can then be used for psychometric analyses which follow best practice guidance for both analytic procedures and reporting (e.g., Hair et al., 2017;

Kline, 2016; Study 2, present thesis; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014). Researchers may then use such rigorous instruments to measure students' perceptions of a space for research purposes, such as, exploring associations between perceptions of the environment and outcomes or between group differences. Furthermore, such instruments may be used to robustly evaluate the suitability of existing and new learning spaces.

7.3.3. Practical implications

The work conducted within this PhD proposes significant practical implications and contributions. First, the systematic review (Study 2) raises concerns about the validity and reliability of previous instruments used to assess students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning spaces. That said, the USLLSE Questionnaire provides an alternative instrument developed using best practice guidance (cf. Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink, 2010a, 2010b). Thus, relative to previous instruments, the USLLSE Questionnaire has been constructed using a more transparent, valid, and reliable approach than the instruments used in previous research. In addition, the instrument has good overall psychometric properties. This instrument is therefore a useful tool for collecting more robust data, for example, in the post-occupancy evaluation of academic library learning spaces. This data can be used to gain insight into students' needs for Spatial and Ergonomic Fit, Acoustical and Privacy Fit, Ambient Fit, and Decisional Control to inform key considerations in the design of new and renovation of existing library learning spaces.

Furthermore, while future research is required to assess the stability of construct validity and reliability over time, the questionnaire provides a viably reliable and valid measure for assessing changes in students' learning space experiences as a function of library space renovations and pre- and post-transitions to new academic libraries. While the instrument may need to be adapted to measure students' experiences of classrooms and informal learning spaces (e.g., non-classroom and non-library spaces like cafeterias, social spaces, and lounges), the USLSE Model, USLLSE Questionnaire, and mixed methodological framework, provide a useful basis for valid and reliable adaptation.

A second contribution to practice is that the research in this thesis largely supports the 'user-centred' approach to HE learning space design (Aronoff, 2016; Cleveland & Fisher, 2014; Harrop &

Turpin, 2013; Lippincott, 2009; Somerville and Collins, 2008; Tavaniemi et al., 2015; Zhang & Maddison, 2016). The qualitative analysis of students' and instructors' discussions in Study 1, alongside previous qualitative work, demonstrate that students and instructors articulate the relevance of environmental characteristics to students' learning space experiences. Moreover, the findings show that students and instructors articulate the consequences of the physical and socio-physical environment in their campus learning space experiences. The quantitative data from Study 3 predominantly supports these findings and demonstrates that more positive perceptions of Person-Environment Fit are associated with more positive outcomes with respect to students' Academic Stress Responses, Engagement in Learning Activities, and Quantity and/or Quality of Work produced when engaging in both individual and collaborative learning within their academic library spaces. In other words, to construct university learning spaces that benefit students, these findings suggest that students should be consulted in order to incorporate their preferences (e.g., environmental needs and demands) into renovated and new learning spaces.

Thirdly, several practical considerations stem from both the qualitative and quantitative findings. Specifically, the USLSE Model (Study 1) identified five key requirements for students in HE learning spaces: Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical and Privacy, Ambient, and Decisional Control needs. In Study 3, each of the aforementioned perception constructs were found to be significantly associated (directly and/or indirectly) with key learning and psychological outcomes when using the academic library spaces for individual and collaborative learning activities, including, Affective Stress, Behavioural Stress, Vigour (Engagement), Dedication (Engagement), and Quantity and/or Quality of Work produced. As mentioned above, it is proposed that students should be consulted in the learning space design process. Here, it is proposed that those involved in the design of new and evaluation of existing HE campus learning spaces should consult students about the specific requirements and learning and psychological consequences outlined above.

Fourthly, the direct and indirect relationships pertaining to Decisional Control are also worthy of consideration. To re-emphasise, in the USLSE Model, Decisional Control represents a students' ability to choose a suitable space (e.g., their preferred space) and/or an alternative space (e.g., when their preferred space does not meet their needs). The finding that more positive perceptions of Decisional Control are generally associated with more positive learning and psychological outcomes when using academic library spaces for individual and collaborative learning activities, suggests that designers

should maximise students' ability to choose appropriate settings for both learning activities, i.e., build in flexibility. This includes enhancing students' ability to select suitable alternative spaces.

Connected to this, the significant indirect or mediation effects via Decisional Control, particularly those indirect effects which were present in the anticipated direction, provide specific insight into students' requirements for a variety of spaces. Specifically, the findings highlight the importance of consulting students about their Spatial and Ergonomic needs when designing different spaces for both individual and collaborative learning activities, including, physical and social density, furniture arrangement and seating location, work surface size, and furniture comfort. Additionally, the findings emphasise the significance of consulting students about their Acoustical and Privacy Needs (e.g., noise level, noise from others talking, noise from equipment, architectural privacy, learning task privacy or interruptions, and visual privacy) when designing a variety of settings from which students can choose the most appropriate space for individual learning activities.

One way of enhancing students' ability to choose learning activity appropriate spaces would be to provide a variety of settings which meet different spatial and ergonomic and acoustical and privacy needs. To re-emphasise, as stated by Sommer (1966):

The ideal library would not be one with all individual study rooms or all open areas but, instead, would contain a diversity of spaces that would meet the needs of introverts and extroverts, lone studiers and group studiers, browsers and day-long researchers ... It is a serious mistake to assume that all people have the same spatial needs (p. 246).

However, the author recognises provision of spaces which meet a wide variety of students' needs may have significant financial implications. An additional approach could involve increasing students' knowledge of the different spaces which are available to them. For example, several students in Study 1 noted that they use spaces which other students are not aware of, for both individual and collaborative learning, out with class. This included 'hidden' atrium spaces, bookable art studios, and empty classroom spaces. By ensuring that students are aware of the different spaces that might meet their needs for individual and collaborative learning out with class, Decisional Control may be enhanced.

7.4. Limitations and Strengths

As with all research, the work conducted in this thesis had limitations and strengths. Study specific limitations and strengths were considered within their corresponding chapters. This section therefore considers the overall limitations and strengths of the approach adopted in this thesis.

The first limitation concerns the methodological limitations of the mixed methods design. It is possible that the variables identified in the USLSE Model and measured using the USLLSE Questionnaire were only of relevance to the students and instructors who participated in the focus groups (cf. Almeida, 2018). This, in turn, may have biased the findings in subsequent studies.

Secondly, the data for both Studies 1 and 3 were collected from students at a single Scottish HEI. Thus, the findings could be specific to a particular population of students. As mentioned in the previous chapter, the target university recruits a larger number of students from non-traditional backgrounds (e.g., deprived communities, FE colleges, and adult returners to education) than other HEIs in Scotland. The extent to which the findings are applicable to HEIs with fewer participants from non-traditional backgrounds is therefore unknown.

A third limitation is that all of the data collected in Studies 1 and 3 were self-report. Thus, there is a risk of recall bias. For example, in both Studies 1 and 3, it is possible that some students may have recalled experiences in which they perceived the environment as particularly incongruent with their needs, rather than those situations perceived as having a lesser impact. Consequently, these strong experiences may have influenced participants' responses. Related to this, several theorists propose that many person-environment transactions are unconscious cognitive processes (e.g., Choi et al., 2014b; Lazarus & Cohen, 1977).

Nevertheless, the research in this thesis has numerous strengths. First, to minimise the limitations of the mixed methods approach, outlined above, the USLSE Model was developed based on relevant empirical and theoretical literature in addition to the data from students and instructors. Thus, the qualitative thematic findings were generalisable to previous qualitative research, prior quantitative research, and established person-environment transaction theories.

Secondly, while data was collected from students at a single HEI, the data pertains to academic library spaces from three campuses in different geographical locations. Thirdly, despite the limitations of self-report methods (focus groups and questionnaire), students and instructors may react differently to the same environmental characteristics (cf. Chapter 2). Thus, providing students (and instructors) with the opportunity to 'give their voice' about their learning space experiences is exceptionally important for both research and practice.

Additional strengths relate to the mixed methodological approach adopted in the thesis. Specifically, in order to address the insufficient content validity and conceptual underpinnings which have plagued previous research, the author followed best practice guidance on exploratory quantitative research and questionnaire design (cf. Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Francis et al., 2016; Mokkink, 2010a, 2010b). Unlike previous research of this type (e.g., Choi et al., 2014a; Hill & Epps, 2010; Hoque & Weil, 2016), the model constructs measured, relationships assessed, and the questionnaire underpinning the study are driven by:

- The users of campus learning spaces (students and instructors);
- Previous research; and
- Established person-environment transaction theories.

Thus, the constructs (predictors and outcomes) investigated in this PhD are of far greater relevance to students' learning space experiences than those investigated in previous research. This means that the constructs in the USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire have far greater content validity than those in prior research.

An associated strength is that the overall research in this thesis is based on a far more rigorous conceptual framework than previous works. In addition to drawing on students' and instructors' experiences, the thesis draws on relevant empirical work and established person-environment transaction theories. By addressing both the dynamic nature and functionality of learning space perceptions and associated outcomes, the ecological validity of the underpinning model and subsequent findings are also enhanced (cf. Gibson, 1978; Heft, 2001).

In addition, the author followed best practice guidance for RTA (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2012, 2017) and PLS-SEM analysis, including, psychometric (validity and reliability) and structural analyses (Hair

et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2015). By doing so, (i) the transparency and generalisability of the qualitative findings (to theory and previous research) and (ii) the validity and reliability of the quantitative findings are enhanced (cf. Braun & Clarke, 2020; Francis et al., 2016). In short, the use of a rigorous mixed methodology and analysis has led to far more valid and reliable findings and conclusions than reported in previous studies of this type.

Finally, as mentioned in Chapters 1 and 2, policymakers are often quantitatively biased. One reason for this is that the data and findings from larger and more representative samples are more generalisable to the population from which the sample was drawn, than qualitative data and findings with typically smaller samples (cf. Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). In addition, quantitative data can be used more easily to infer the presence or absence of statistical associations between constructs (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). The USLSE Model was based on qualitative data analysis and interpretation. By combining this rich qualitative data analysis and interpretation (Study 1) with subsequent quantitative research on a larger sample (Study 3), the research conducted in this thesis may be better received and utilised by quantitatively biased audiences (e.g., policymakers) (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Doherty & Chen, 2016).

7.5. Directions for Future Research

Research on students' learning space perceptions and the associated learning and psychological outcomes warrants further investigation. First, it would be valuable to conduct further psychometric analyses on the USLLSE Questionnaire. Specifically, this could include further examination of construct validity and reliability on large samples across different HEIs (cross-population equivalence). Further, it would be worthwhile to assess construct validity and reliability longitudinally. Despite empirical and theoretical variations in students' perceptions over time and as a function of circumstances, it would be useful to determine whether the constructs identified and reliability of the tool remain stable over time (cf. Francis et al., 2016; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2014).

Secondly, it would be interesting to assess the content validity of the USLSE Model and USLLSE Questionnaire for other campus learning spaces, including different classroom types (e.g., large- and small-scale instructional and active learning classrooms) and informal learning spaces (e.g., study lounges, canteens and cafeterias, and atria). Following the methodological approach adopted within this study, this could involve using qualitative approaches to establish content validity, drawing on

previous empirical and theoretical works to inform strong conceptual underpinnings, and using subsequent quantitative research on larger samples to investigate construct validity and internal consistency reliability.

Thirdly, by incorporating students' personal characteristics (e.g., personality, age, gender, environmental preferences) and situational characteristics (e.g., objective environmental conditions, study year, and discipline), it may be possible to identify subgroups and conditions under which environmental perceptions and outcomes are stronger or weaker. Such an approach could be used to investigate whether environmental perceptions mediate the relationships between objective environmental conditions and learning and psychological outcomes (see Subsection 7.3.1.).

Fourthly, it would be interesting to broaden the definition of environmental control. This could involve assessing perceptions of behavioural control, that is, actions to exert control over environmental variables (Gatersleben & Griffin, 2016). Examples include closing blinds to prevent glare, adding or removing jumpers, and using earphones to prevent acoustical distractions from others. Furthermore, it may be useful to measure the degree to which participants exercise environmental control as well as perceive environmental control. However, given the wide range of behavioural options available to students, it may be difficult to balance additional questions required to assess behavioural and exercised control, with respondent burden and dropout.

Fifthly, it may be useful to develop research which incorporates the role of social support and distractions when working with others on collaborative learning activities. Understanding the circumstances under which studying with others may reduce or enhance the relationships between learning space perceptions and learning and psychological outcomes, would help to further inform the design of spaces which are compatible with both individual and collaborative learning activities. As discussed in Chapter 6, future research may address these findings by incorporating a commensurate scale which measures both the degree of fit and the perceived importance of each environmental variable for individual and collaborative learning activities. Such an approach is adopted in wider person-environment fit research (e.g., person-organisation fit; cf. Edwards, 1994, 2008; Kristoff, 1996), however, it would require fine balancing with issues such as respondent burden and participant dropout.

Finally, the success of classroom spaces is dependent on whether the environment meets the needs of instructors. It would therefore be valuable for future research to investigate more fully instructors' experiences in university learning spaces. This may, for example, involve an assessment of relationships between instructors' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment in classrooms with different designs (e.g., active learning versus traditional) and the ability to engage in different types of learning and teaching activities.

7.6. Thesis Conclusions

The research conducted in this thesis has contributed to the literature on HE students' learning space experiences by (i) demonstrating how students perceive the physical and socio-physical environment in their HE campus learning spaces; (ii) identifying the relevant environmental characteristics and learning and psychological outcomes to students' learning space experiences; (iii) developing a new and robust (psychometrically tested) 'learning space experience' questionnaire; and (iv) using this tool to investigate the relationships between students' perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment and learning and psychological outcomes in their academic library spaces.

The research has exemplified the value of adopting a rigorous mixed methodological approach, beginning with qualitative research, and drawing on established empirical and theoretical literature to inform subsequent quantitative research and instrument design. Ultimately, by adopting such an approach, future research can improve the validity and reliability of quantitative findings on students' experiences of campus spaces.

Overall, the findings from the research in this thesis have complimented and extended previous research. Based on the qualitative data analysis (Study 1), previous empirical research, and established person-environment transaction theories, the belated development of the USLSE Model and proposed modifications based on the quantitative Study 3 (e.g., expanding the definition of perceived environmental control and incorporating exercised control) presents a superior conceptual basis for future research.

The quantitative findings demonstrated that more positive perceptions of the physical and socio-physical environment are predominantly associated with better learning and psychological outcomes (e.g., reduced stress, increased engagement, and increased quantity and/or quality of work) when using academic library spaces for both individual and collaborative learning activities. This supports the need to 'give students a voice' in the design of new and evaluation of existing learning spaces. Specifically, the qualitative and quantitative findings highlight the value of consulting students about their Spatial and Ergonomic, Acoustical and Privacy, Ambient, and Decisional Control needs for individual and collaborative learning. Additionally, designers should consult students about the potential consequences of the environment, including, Engagement in Learning Activities, Cognitive-Affective Consequences (e.g., Academic Stress), and Quantity and Quality of Work produced when using campus learning spaces for individual and collaborative learning activities.

Overall, the findings from this thesis highlight the importance of the physical and socio-physical environment to students' learning space experiences. Therefore, those involved in future research and the design of new and evaluation of existing learning spaces should aim to comprehensively consider and incorporate students' learning space experiences.

8.0. References

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